

Host genetics shapes crypt niche colonisation by keystone gut bacteria, influencing metabolic health

Fusing cost-effective quantitative genetics with systems biology to decode host-microbiota functional wiring

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In appreciation

The opportunity to finish a doctoral project is a genuine privilege that very few people have. In many places, it can be a dream that may never come true, due to a profound lack of investment and essential conditions that allow predoctoral students to afford a life with minimal dignity while dedicating their time to such an admirable work. In my case, the privilege of being here today, sharing this knowledge about one of the most fascinating research fields, was having people around me who believed in this dream and provided the support I needed in many different aspects. I am eternally grateful to all of you.

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contribution to the conversion of initial codes into a robust pipeline that has continued to grow since then.

Third, I would like to thank all the incredible scientists who composed my Thesis Advisory Committee, my two thesis reviewers, and the other members of my tribunal for dedicating their time to contribute to the consolidation of this research. Some of them have become important mentors to me along the way. At the same time, I am grateful to all friends I have met over the last years at conferences that, at a certain point, have also become my mentors, always helping me with scientific guidance and making me remember that there are many incredible and passionate scientists around the world willing to build a community in which I feel very welcomed.

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Lastly, I would like to acknowledge that Science is something that not only grows through a perpetual collaborative construction, but on a personal level, its main fuel has always been the inspiring people behind it. In 1947, an immigrant like me, Johanna Döbereiner, arrived in Brazil, and there, she revolutionised the agricultural field by consolidating the application of biological nitrogen fixation in soybeans and other plants. Her work enabled the entire country to reduce its consumption of nitrogen-based fertilisers, increasing productivity and significantly reducing the environmental costs associated with the industrial production of such products. Since then, many scientists have continued her research on the contribution of commensal bacteria to their hosts. Now, I am very happy to present this work, hoping that one day I can also be part of this fantastic inspirational chain.

Abstract in English

A “polygenic-first” design for causal inference was adopted to study the caecal microbiome of HS rats, combining shallow-shotgun metagenomics with linear-mixed models to map host polygenic effects on multi-level microbiome traits. A reproducible, shallow shotgun-optimised pipeline yielded better results for detecting such effects than 16S, with heritable signals concentrating in *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, their shared guild, and β -diversity. Then, genome-resolved enrichments suggested potential adaptations to the crypt niche, leading to a hypothesis-driven selection of host genes. A cross-validated set of sentinel SNPs for these candidate genes explained genus-level polygenic effects and served as instruments in mediation and Mendelian randomisation analyses, contributing to a structural equation model that linked keystone bacteria, community structure, and host metabolism. The effects of these genera on fasting glucose levels had opposite signs and were balanced by indirect effects routed through community traits, suggesting that genotype-aware, niche-engineering interventions could better modulate glycaemia and other health-related traits.

Abstract in Spanish

Se adoptó un diseño “*polygenic-first*” para inferencia causal del microbioma cecal en ratas HS, combinando metagenómica *shallow-shotgun* y modelos lineales mixtos para identificar efectos poligénicos del hospedador sobre rasgos del microbioma. Un *pipeline* reproducible optimizado para *shallow-shotgun* superó a 16S en la detección de estos efectos, destacando *Bacteroides* y *Prevotella*, su gremio compartido y la β -diversidad. Enriquecimientos genómicos sugirieron adaptaciones al nicho de las criptas y motivaron la selección de genes candidatos del hospedador. Un conjunto de SNP centinelas, mediante validación cruzada, explicó efectos poligénicos a nivel de género y sirvió como instrumento en mediación y aleatorización Mendeliana, dando lugar a un modelo de ecuaciones estructurales que vinculó bacterias clave, estructura comunitaria y metabolismo. Los efectos directos de estos géneros sobre la glucosa en ayunas fueron de signo opuesto y se compensaron por efectos indirectos mediados por rasgos comunitarios, apoyando intervenciones de ingeniería de nicho guiadas por genotipo.

Preface

This thesis was conducted between October 2021 and October 2025 at the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG) under the supervision of Dr Amelie Baud (CRG/UPF) as a requirement of the PhD program in Biomedicine of the Department of Medicine and Life Sciences at Universitat Pompeu Fabra.

It is divided into eight chapters: Chapter 1 (Introduction), Chapter 2 (Hypotheses and Objectives), Chapters 3-7, each containing its own Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion sections; and Chapter 8 (Final Remarks).

The research presented here was initially funded by a postdoctoral grant from the La Caixa Foundation, granted to Dr Baud. During this research, only bioinformatics activities were performed, with all data being collected and shared in advance by Dr Baud, in collaboration with the National Institute for Drug Abuse Center of Excellence for Genetics, Genomics, and Epigenetics of Substance Use Disorders in Outbred Rats (NIDA) and the Center for Microbiome Innovation. The current research uses a subset of the caecal metagenomic database prepared by Dr. Baud, focusing on samples that were sequenced with both 16S and shallow shotgun methods. Although the study reported in this thesis did not encompass all these previous steps, the main information about them was included in the material to place the research within its broader context and facilitate the interpretation and discussion of its results.

Additionally, the PhD student presented results at multiple international events, including the Applied Hologenomics Conference, the EMBO | EMBL Symposium: The Human Microbiome, the Barcelona Debates on the Gut Microbiome (twice), the 2022 BIST Conference, and the 20th Annual Meeting of the Complex Trait Community | Rat Genome & Models. Furthermore, he attended the online course Introduction to Microbiomics (Campinas, Brazil) and the international course of Computational Metagenomics (Advanced) in Wageningen (the Netherlands), along with a two-week internship at the EMBL | EBI with the Mgnify team, to learn and start the development of an HS rat gut bacterial genome catalogue.

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List of abbreviations

AMP	Antimicrobial peptides
ANI	Average nucleotide identity
ARI	Adjusted Rand Index
ASV	Amplicon sequence variant
ATP	Adenosine triphosphate
BH	Benjamini-Hochberg
BMI	Body mass index
BSEM	Bayesian structured equation model
CAZymes	Carbohydrate-active enzymes
CCF	Commensal colonisation factors
CFI	Comparative Fit Index
CLR	Centred log-ratio
COG	Cluster of an orthologous group
CPS	Capsular polysaccharide
CPU	Central processing unit
CRG	Centre for Genomic Regulation
CS	Chondroitin sulphate
DBCV	Density-Based Clustering Validation index
DCS	Deep crypt secretory cells
ddGBS	Double-digest genotyping-by-sequencing
df	Degrees of freedom
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic acid
EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
EC	Enzyme Commission number (with four levels: EC4, EC3, EC2 and EC1)
ECM	Extracellular matrix
ENOG	eggNOG ortholog group
ERAD	Endoplasmic reticulum associated degradation
F:B	Firmicutes-Bacteroidota ratios
FDR	False Discovery Rate
FISH	Fluorescence in situ hybridisation
FMT	Faecal microbiota transplantation
GAG	Glycosaminoglycan
GDS	Genomic Data Structure
GF	Germ-free
GLS	Generalized Least Squares
GPCR	G-protein-coupled receptor

GREML	Genome-based restricted maximum likelihood
GRM	Genetic relatedness matrix
GTDB	Genome taxonomy database
GWAS	Genome-wide association studies
HDBSCAN	Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
HIF	Hypoxia-Inducible Factor
HMP	Human Microbiome Project
HPC	High-performance computing cluster
HS	Heterogeneous Stock
HWE	Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium
IACUC	Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees
IBD	Inflammatory bowel disease
IFGP	IBM Functional Genomics Platform
IgA	Immunoglobulin A
IL	Interleukin
ILC	Innate lymphoid cell
ILR	Isometric log-ratio
KDO	3-deoxy-D-manno-oct-2-ulosonic acid
KEGG	Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes
KO	KEGG Ortholog
LD	Linkage disequilibrium
LMM	Linear mixed models
LOCO	Leave-one-chromosome-out
logFC	log ₂ Fold Change
LPS	Lipopolysaccharides
LRT	Likelihood-ratio test
MAC	Minor allele count
MAF	Minor allele frequency
MAG	Metagenome-assembled genome
MAMP	Microbe-associated molecular patterns
MANOVA	Multivariate analysis of variance
MGBC	Mouse Gastrointestinal Bacteria Catalogue
ML	Maximum likelihood
MLR	Maximum likelihood ratio
MME	Multivariate molecular ecology
MR	Mendelian randomisation
NCBI	National center for Biotechnology Information

NIDA	National Institute for Drug Abuse
NIH	National Institute of Health
NLPR	NOD-like receptor-pyrimin-containing proteins
NO	Nitric oxide
NOD	Nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-containing proteins
OGU	Operational Genomic Unit
OTU	Operational Taxonomic Unit
PC	Principal component
PCA	Principal component analysis
PCo	Principal coordinate
PCo1/PCo2	First and second principal coordinates
PCoA	Principal coordinate analysis
PCR	Polymerase chain reaction
PEP	Positive edge percentage
PERMANOVA	Permutational multivariate analysis of variance
PGLS	Phylogenetic Generalized Least Squares
PLP	Pyridoxal 5'-Fosphate
PPP	Posterior predictive <i>p</i> -value
PRR	Pattern recognition receptors
PUL	Polysaccharide utilisation locus
QIIME	Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology
QMP	Quantitative microbiome profiling
QS50	Quality Score 50
QTL	Quantitative trait loci
REML	Restricted maximum likelihood
RMSEA	Root Mean Square Error of Approximation
ROS	Reactive oxygen species
RPMA	Reads-per-mega-amino-acids
SD	Sprague-Dawley
SE	Standard error
SEM	Structured equation model
SGBP	Surface glycan-binding lipoproteins
SNP	Single-nucleotide polymorphism
SCFA	Short-chain fatty acid
SOR	Superoxide reductase
SPF	Specific pathogen-free
SrcF	Small-RNA colonisation factor
SRM	Sparse relationship matrices
SRMR	Standardized Root Mean Square Residual

SSU	Small subunit
Sus	Starch utilisation system
SV	Structural Variant
T6SS	Type VI secretion systems
TCA	Tricarboxylic acid cycle
TLI	Tucker-Lewis Index
TLR	Toll-like receptor
UMAP	Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection
WHO	World Health Organization
WoL	Web of Life

CHAPTER 1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The biomedical importance of the gut microbiome

The gastrointestinal tract of mammals is composed of a diverse community of living microorganisms, including archaea, bacteria, fungi, viruses, and protists, referred to as the gut microbiota. Their collective genomes, structural elements and metabolic products represent the functional potential of the microbiota in the context of the environment they interact with, being generally defined as the gut microbiome¹. However, given that bacterial species account for more than 70% of the mammalian gut microbiota², studies commonly refer to them as ultimately being the “gut microbiota” and their functional potential, the “gut microbiome”.

Although the colon of an average 70 kg man contains approximately the same number of bacterial cells as human cells in the body ($\sim 3.8 \times 10^{13}$), the gut microbiota comprises thousands of diverse species with their unique genomes. Hence, the total number of exclusive microbial genes far exceeds those from host cells^{3,4}, and the resulting functional expansion makes it an essential component of host physiological homeostasis. For instance, these bacteria contribute to dietary fibre fermentation, releasing short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) as byproducts, which are important regulators of intestinal cell metabolism⁵. Additionally, immune system maturation, pathogen exclusion and even neuroendocrine signalling have already been documented as other contributions from the gut microbiome to the host, becoming a central focus of contemporary biomedicine⁶⁻⁹.

This functional integration has been formally conceptualised through the “holobiont” paradigm, which frames the host and its commensal microbiota as a unified entity governed by co-evolved interdependence^{3,10}. Thus, due to this operative aspect of the gut microbiome, methods that can map its different elements have contributed to what is currently known about them. The so-called “omics” sciences (e.g., metagenomics, metatranscriptomics, metaproteomics, and metabolomics) have been extensively deployed over the years, providing a systemic view of how hosts and their commensals are interconnected.

Among these discoveries, one of the most studied phenomena is the connection between chronic diseases and gut dysbiosis (i.e., imbalances in gut microbiome composition that make it diverge from more “typical” structures⁷). Case-control and population studies have associated reproducible dysbiotic signatures with chronic diseases such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, cardiometabolic disorders, and neurodegeneration for years, positioning faecal microbiome profiles as promising non-invasive biomarkers for patient stratification^{7-9,11-14}. For example, reduced *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and elevated *Escherichia coli* levels have been shown to be highly correlated with inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) markers¹².

However, while such correlations between microbial taxa and disease are extensively documented, causal paths remain elusive due to confounding environmental variables and the challenge of distinguishing microbial drivers from disease-induced reversal influence¹⁵. Many studies have already demonstrated that most reported correlations do not always accurately reflect actual causal relationships, making the gap between correlation and causation a significant obstacle to clinical applications¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Furthermore, factors influencing the colonisation and maintenance of gut bacterial communities still need to be better clarified, so that when such causal paths are detected and validated, precise clinical interventions can be designed effectively¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

1.2 How host genetics shape the gut microbiome

Considering the principle that host genetic variants are not defined by any environmental factor, being inherited at birth, mapping host loci with a strong influence on gut bacteria can enable causal inference frameworks, such as quantitative trait loci (QTL)-based mediation analysis or Mendelian randomisation (MR). These methods have as their primary objective to test whether specific gut commensals are responsible for causal paths leading to complex disease pathways¹⁴⁻¹⁶ (further discussed in Chapter 7), which places the detection of host genetic effects as a vital step for microbiome-centred precise medicine.

Several approaches can be used to identify gut bacteria affected by host genetic effects. On one hand, it can be estimated from the perspective of aggregate genetic effects (i.e., heritability tests), by assessing the extent to which bacterial relative abundances vary across hosts, according to their genetic relatedness to each other. On the other hand, the additive effects of specific QTLs on the same bacterial variances can also be estimated in genome-wide association studies (GWAS), which is the approach currently deployed to identify genetic variants that can be used as instruments in causal inference analyses. While metagenomic studies with twins or inbred and hybrid animals have contributed considerably to the detection of such effects²⁰⁻²⁴, population-based studies have become more attractive, as they enable the use of genetically unique individuals on a larger scale^{14,25-31}. However, so far, few study-wise significant host genetic effects have been reported and validated across multiple studies and hosts. The main consistent ones comprehend the association between the lactase gene (*LCT*) and *Bifidobacteria*, as well as the associations between the genes responsible for the secretion of blood antigen groups (*ABO* and *FUT2*) and *Faecalibacterium* and *Collinsella*^{21,26,27,29}.

Because large cohorts are required in these epidemiological studies to ensure good statistical power^{32,33}, the adoption of deep shotgun sequencing (>20 million pairs of reads³⁴⁻³⁶) as a metagenomic approach for microbiome profiling is very restrictive, given its high costs (further discussed in Chapter 4). For this reason, most researchers have worked with the 16S ribosomal subunit marker gene (i.e. metataxonomics), as it has variable regions that are relatively consistent with bacterial phylogeny, allowing the construction of low-cost taxonomic profiles³⁷. However, this method has limitations, such as low resolution at the species level, the presence of multiple copies of this gene in some bacteria, and amplification biases³⁷⁻⁴⁰, which may contribute to the limited observation of strong host genetic effects on microbial taxa. Therefore, shallow shotgun sequencing (0.5-1 million pairs of reads) has emerged as an alternative, due to the increasing evidence that it is both able to recover similar results as ultra-deep shotgun data for the main microbiome measures used in differential abundance analyses⁴¹ and also provide similar sensitivity (or recall rate) and higher precision compared to 16S data when profiling known mock microbiomes⁴² (further discussed in Chapters 4 and 5).

Although shallow shotgun sequencing seems very promising, no studies have yet employed this approach to detect host genetic effects on the gut microbiome, to our current knowledge. One of the main requirements imposed by this method is the use of bacterial genome catalogues as a proxy to map metagenomic sequences, assigning them to specific taxa and then building profiles based on their counts. This happens because shallow shotgun metagenomic data does not generate enough sequences for a *de novo* genome assembly to be used as part of a self-reference database^{41,43}. For this reason, over the last years, many host-specific or broad bacterial catalogues have been built. One of the largest and most phylogenetically consistent catalogues used in multiple studies is the Genome Taxonomy Database (GTDB), which, in its R207 release, already contained more than 65,000 bacterial and archaeal clusters of same-species genomes^{44,45} (further described in Chapter 4).

Many studies have already demonstrated how QTLs associated with gut bacteria can be used as anchors to define causal pathways linking these commensals with host traits⁴⁶. A notable example is a study that identified a genetic locus associated with *Akkermansia muciniphila*, which indirectly modulates the host's anti-inflammatory response to lipopolysaccharides (LPS) through the bacterium's metabolic activity, specifically, the production of immunomodulatory ornithine lipids. The discovery was validated both in vitro and in vivo, confirming a causal chain from the host gene to the bacterium and then from the bacterium to the host phenotype⁴⁷.

Nevertheless, causal inference requires stringent assumptions, such as instrumental relevance (i.e., the effect size of the variant, also known as the exposure, on the microbiome trait defined as the mediator), independence from confounders, and the absence of horizontal pleiotropy, which means the concomitant existence of direct and indirect effects on the target outcome^{46,48-50}. In particular, controlling for confounders is a significant challenge when working with humans, primarily due to dietary plasticity, which reduces the likelihood of identifying new, robust, and validated QTLs⁴⁸. Consequently, controlled genetically heterogeneous laboratory rat panels have been advocated to combine human-like polygenicity with environmental standardisation for a more sensitive detection of host genetic effects on microbiome-associated traits. A population of

animal models with characteristics that make them very suitable for this task is the Heterogeneous Stock (HS) of rats⁵¹⁻⁵³ (further discussed in Chapter 3).

1.3 The gut microbiome as a complex trait

From the perspective of Quantitative Genetics, gut microbiome traits, including taxon relative abundances, α -diversity and β -diversity, exhibit characteristics of host-complex traits: they are polygenic, being influenced by numerous small-effect host alleles, and demonstrate moderate heritability^{54,55}. Population studies with genetically diverse humans and wild baboons have estimated the heritability of gut bacterial taxa to be as high as 20%. However, these effects are often cohort-specific due to environmental heterogeneity, with a strong influence of cohabitation effects^{25,56}. This scarcity of replicable host genetic effects undermines GWAS results, which require large populations to achieve statistical power, either due to the necessity of mapping loci with minor effects in the population or because of the statistical multiple-testing penalty^{32,33}. For example, a GWAS of microbial α -diversity (Shannon index) in 9,015 people identified only the well-reported *ABO* locus as a robust hit, underscoring the challenge of detecting variants with significantly small effects²⁶. Thus, despite the importance of identifying host genetic loci for causal inference analysis, GWAS tends to be a limited approach, given the highly polygenic architecture of these microbiome traits^{7,55}.

At the same time, heritability analysis, which usually involves the detection of single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP)-based aggregate host genetic effects, provides a feasible path to genetic insights. Power calculators indicate that ~3,000 unrelated individuals are already sufficient to detect a significant heritability of 30% (p -value < 0.05), whereas a GWAS seeking to pinpoint the median SNP effect on the same trait would require over 100,000 participants to overcome the Bonferroni correction for multiple testing⁵⁷⁻⁵⁹. The empirical contrast is striking when considering height as an example of a human complex trait: Genome-based Restricted Maximum Likelihood (GREML), a measure of the significance of polygenic effects, recovered 45% of phenotypic variance associated with aggregate genetic effects by studying only 3,925 adults⁶⁰, while the

first meta-analysis that showed up to 10% of QTL-based variance, required 183,727 samples and 180 genome-wide significant loci⁶¹. In this case, studying the characteristics of gut microbiome traits with significant heritability values as opposed to looking agnostically for individual host loci affecting them could be an alternative starting point to unveil host-bacteria interactions (further discussed in Chapters 5 and 6).

1.4 The gut microbiome as an ecosystem

Beyond being a host trait, the gut microbiome is also a complex ecosystem governed by ecological principles such as cross-feeding hierarchies, successional dynamics, and competition⁶²⁻⁶⁴. This forces us to look away from taxa-driven host-microbiota interactions and focus more on the functional aspects of the microbiome. For instance, a study involving patients with IBD and faecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) revealed that, independently of the taxonomy assigned to them, slow-growing bacteria with bigger genomes and more metabolic independence (due to the presence of complete pathways for the biosynthesis of vital metabolites) were enriched in more stressful environments (i.e. inflamed guts), being also the best-performing colonisers. At the same time, healthy patients presented more fast-growing bacteria with small genomes and incomplete metabolic pathways, probably due to the diversification of interactions, niches, and metabolites they can find in homeostatic environments⁶⁵.

By combining this perspective with the detection of host genetic effects, studies that used deep shotgun data to create functional profiles of microbiomes by directly mapping and counting bacterial genes, or even their structural variants (SVs), have obtained more substantial heritability values^{25,26}. This is important because bacteria can engage in various types of horizontal gene transfer (HGT) events, which enable advantageous fitness functions that transcend taxonomic limits and spread throughout the community^{66,67}. For example, studies have demonstrated that SVs of many genes, such as promoter inversions⁶⁸, explain the high functional diversity among strains of the same species⁶⁹ and, consequently, influence the detection of host genetic effects on the gut microbiome²⁶ (further discussed in Chapter 5). However, this gene-centric approach has

been criticised, as it tends to ignore the fact that the same gene in a different organism can lead to distinct functional outcomes, at the same time that their carriers might be under different selective forces, or simply have different growth rates, which will tweak the signal of the effects on them^{70,71}. Moreover, when shotgun sequencing is not sufficiently deep for contig assembly and is based on short reads (i.e., sequences with 150 bp), they may map parts of inactive genes or pseudogenes, which can interfere with a functional-based interpretation of host-microbiome interactions^{72,73}.

For being an ecosystem with functional units interacting with each other and their environment, system-level patterns can emerge. Therefore, many researchers in the field argue that a reliable alternative to the real definition of microbiome functional units should be co-abundance clusters. These clusters represent guilds of bacteria that co-occur in the same spaces, interacting with each other on a local scale^{70,74,75}, which could be defined as the first level of an ecosystem-based microbiome trait. Beyond that, like any other biota, bacterial communities are ultimately governed by the equilibrium between global functional diversity and redundancy, which is determined by the selective forces that affect them, resulting in community homeostasis and resilience. If this balance is disturbed for any reason, the microbiota no longer presents its resilience and enters a state of dysbiosis⁷⁶⁻⁷⁸. This state is often characterised by reduced α -diversity and usually accompanies metabolic and inflammatory diseases, highlighting the value of community-level diversity metrics in clinical studies. In the omics sciences, bringing such concepts to the characterisation of metagenomic-based microbiome profiles has been defined as multivariate molecular ecology (MME), contributing with an important point of view in biomedical-focused studies⁷⁹⁻⁸¹ (further discussed in Chapters 4-7).

Taking all of this into consideration, it is possible to deduce that while environmental factors are known to have the most significant influence on gut microbiome composition^{25,56,82}, a combination of host-to-bacteria and bacteria-to-bacteria interactions seems to play an essential role in the establishment and maintenance of gut microbial assemblies^{62,83}. By conferring a relatively stable structure to community composition, such interactions might actually constrain environmental effects^{14,18,64,84-87}. For example, recent studies have shown that gut commensals most affected by host genes tend to

behave as keystone species, presenting elevated connectivity with other community members⁸⁸⁻⁹⁰, and being possible drivers of stable microbiome compositions commonly defined as enterotypes^{91,92}. For this reason, the identification and characterisation of such pivotal bacteria may help us understand the requirements for successful microbiome interventions to prevent diseases and improve health (further explored in Chapter 5).

1.5 A fresh framework to comprehend host-microbiome interactions

Building on these insights, the current work proposes a hypothesis-driven framework that begins with the detection of microbiome traits significantly affected by polygenic signals, rather than single-locus hits, to unravel host-microbiome-health relationships. The first step is to assess whether the multi-cohort approach adopted in this project to study the caecal microbiome of a population of HS rats can lead to population structure problems (Chapter 3). The second is to employ shallow shotgun metagenomics to define the taxonomic and functional profiles of the caecal samples, characterise them and identify multi-level traits with significant associations (Chapter 4). The third is to estimate heritability values for every microbial taxon, gene-based function, guilds, α - and β -diversity measurements, and prioritise those with a significant polygenic signal (Chapter 5). The fourth involves mapping the functions enriched in the genomes of highly heritable taxa to infer which host-derived ecological niches they possibly exploit and selecting host genes and their respective single-nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) to be used as candidate instruments for causal inference analysis (Chapter 6). In the last step, variants whose additive effects have significant correlations with species heritability values within the same genus will be selected to assess how these bacteria mediate shifts in community guilds, β -diversity and host metabolic phenotypes (Chapter 7), finishing with the construction of a structural equation model (SEM) representing the influence chain from heritable keystone bacteria to community structure and, ultimately, to disease-related phenotypes, using the body mass index (BMI) and fasting blood glucose levels as proof-of-concepts (Chapter 7). This strategy relaxes GWAS sample size requirements and moves microbiome research closer to actionable, mechanistic insights.

CHAPTER 2. HYPOTHESES AND OBJECTIVES

2.1 Hypothesis 1: HS rats show minimal cross-cohort stratification

The population of Heterogeneous Stock (HS) rats has no substantial cross-cohort stratification within studies, avoiding possible biases derived from population structure artefacts in multi-cohort datasets.

Objective 1: To validate the genetic homogeneity of HS rats between the two cohorts studied (Chapter 3).

2.2 Hypothesis 2: Shallow shotgun can detect associations between taxa, functions and community features

Shallow shotgun metagenomic sequencing data from HS rat caecal samples can quantify the relative abundance of bacterial taxa and their associated functions, along with other microbiome features, such as co-abundance guilds, enterotypes, α - and β -diversity, therefore revealing significant associations between these traits.

Objective 2: To develop an optimised pipeline that takes raw shallow shotgun data as input for microbiome profiling and characterisation. Then, characterise the HS rat caecal microbiome based on the taxonomic and functional profiles, deriving other microbiome features (e.g., co-abundance guilds, enterotypes, α - and β -diversity) to test convergent patterns and elaborate a first hypothesis on how the rat caecal microbiome is structured (Chapter 4).

2.3 Hypothesis 3: Shallow shotgun improves heritability detection compared to 16S

Shallow shotgun data can reveal a greater number of bacterial taxa with significant SNP heritability (also defined as host polygenic effects or aggregate host genetic effects) and yield higher heritability estimates than 16S-based profiling.

Objective 3: To assess whether shallow shotgun data can improve the detection of significant heritable taxa and heritability estimates compared to 16S data generated from the same caecal samples (Chapter 5).

2.4 Hypothesis 4: Host genetic effects extend to functions, guilds and community diversity

By quantifying bacterial functions from shallow shotgun-based gene-centric profiles, it is possible to identify host genetic effects that go beyond taxonomic boundaries. Moreover, by considering that the microbiome's functional structure can also emerge from the interaction between different bacteria within the microbiota, it was also hypothesised that host genetic effects can be detected in community-level measurements, such as the relative abundances of species co-abundance guilds, α - and β -diversity.

Objective 4: To apply gene-centric derived functional profiles, species guild relative abundances, and species-based α - and β -diversity values as non-taxonomic microbiome traits for heritability analyses (Chapter 5).

2.5 Hypothesis 5: Heritable microbiome traits are genetically correlated

Multi-level microbiome traits affected by host genetic effects share genetic correlations.

Objective 5: To test whether microbiome traits with significant heritability values covary to some extent under the influence of host polygenic effects (Chapter 6).

2.6 Hypothesis 6: High- h^2 species share niche-adaptation functions

Within a genus, bacterial species with higher heritability values share specific functions that represent niche-adaptations.

Objective 6: To select the bacterial genera with the highest proportion of heritable species and/or the highest median heritability values, annotate the functions present in their genomes and identify which are enriched in those species with higher and lower heritability values. Then, evaluate whether the patterns behind such host genetic effects converge with the original hypothesis about the mechanisms underlying the microbiome structure (Chapter 6).

2.7 Hypothesis 7: Candidate host genes capture polygenic control missed by GWAS

A hypothesis-driven list of candidate genes can reveal additive effects associated with host polygenic control of the caecal microbiota that are usually not detected by agnostic GWAS.

Objective 7: To elaborate a hypothesis on the host genes responsible for the establishment and stability of gut niches and identify SNPs within these genes that exert additive effects associated with the heritability values of bacterial species (Chapter 6).

2.8 Hypothesis 8: Heritable genera mediate host genetic effects

Genera with highly heritable species are not only favoured by the environmental conditions exerted by the same host genetic makeup that shapes community-level microbiome traits (e.g., co-abundance guilds, α - and β -diversity, etc.) but also shape them. Thus, they can mediate host genetic effects on BMI and fasting blood glucose levels both directly and indirectly (by affecting the rest of the microbial community).

Objective 8: To assess whether the selected genera mediate the effects of heritability-associated host variants on community-level traits and validate causal paths. Then, assess how heritable bacteria can both directly and indirectly influence host BMI and fasting blood glucose levels through their impact on the rest of the microbial community (Chapter 7).

CHAPTER 3. HARNESSING HS RATS TO REVEAL HOST POLYGENIC EFFECTS

3.1 Introduction

a) Why rats? The case for the animal model

The utilisation of laboratory rodent models is pivotal for biomedical research targeting the gut microbiome. These models can be manipulated in controlled environments, with the standardisation of diet, strains, kinship or cohousing conditions, thereby reducing confounding variables that are typically present in human studies⁹³. This facilitates the exploration of microbiome dynamics and the assessment of potential microbiome-based FMT interventions, such as dietary manipulation, antibiotics and FMT⁹⁴. Furthermore, strict conditions that allow the obtainment of animals with known microbiotas by design, the so-called gnotobiotic animals, make them even more relevant for experimentation. Germ-free (GF) rodents, for example, are model animals devoid of all detectable bacteria, viruses, fungi, and parasites, maintained within sterile flexible-film isolators using rigorous protocols involving peracetic acid sterilisation, autoclaved supplies, and caesarean rederivation, along with in vitro fertilisation to prevent microbial colonisation. Another group of gnotobiotic animals harbours intentionally introduced, fully defined microbial communities, thus enabling controlled studies of host-microbe interactions⁹⁵⁻⁹⁷. Specific pathogen-free (SPF) rodents, for example, represent a subset of conventional animals bred to exclude designated pathogens (e.g., *Clostridium piliforme* or *Salmonella* spp.). However, they retain undefined commensal microbiota and exhibit significant physiological deviations from wild-type rodents, including immune dysregulation and metabolic alterations^{98,99}. Humanised gnotobiotic rodents can also be generated through the FMT of human donor material into GF hosts, creating chimeric models that recapitulate human microbial ecosystems for translational studies¹⁰⁰.

The manipulation of different animal model groups has been instrumental in driving significant advances in microbiome research. For instance, some of the most well-known experiments investigating

the possible causal link between the gut microbiota and host non-communicable traits involved transplanting microbial communities from obese patients to GF rodents, revealing that those animals tended to become obese, replicating the phenotype of the human donors, or presenting symptoms of common comorbidities associated with obesity, such as glucose intolerance¹⁰¹⁻¹⁰³. However, these experiments have their limitations. For example, maintenance protocols involve specialised infrastructure: GF colonies require negative-pressure isolators with double-barrier containment, sterile air filtration, and meticulous hand-rearing of neonates using artificial milk formulas during the lactation period. SPF facilities employ strict exclusion lists and health monitoring, but face challenges in standardising microbiota across vendors. At the same time, humanised models require careful donor screening (considering geography, diet, and ethnicity) and optimised colonisation conditions to maintain human-derived taxa in murine systems⁹⁵⁻¹⁰⁰.

While both mice (*Mus musculus*) and rats (*Rattus norvegicus*) are commonly used as primary rodent models, debates persist regarding their respective suitability. Comparative studies have yielded conflicting results: for example, one study reported that the UniFrac distance between human and mouse microbiomes was lower than that between humans and rats¹⁰⁴. In contrast, another study revealed an opposite trend for the exact measurement, using different mouse and rat strains¹⁰⁵. In addition, the age of the rats also affects how similar or dissimilar their microbiomes are compared to those of humans, making these comparisons even more debatable¹⁰⁶. Moreover, while few studies have revealed that mice share a higher proportion of bacterial taxa with humans^{104,106}, rats tend to exhibit greater overlap at the functional level¹⁰⁷. These discrepancies suggest that mere taxonomic comparisons may not be sufficient to define the most suitable model for translational microbiome research. Evaluating the engraftment efficiency of human gut bacteria in germ-free or SPF animals could be an alternative approach. Studies have consistently demonstrated that rats yield better results than mice, thereby serving as a suitable model for translatable preclinical trials¹⁰².

b) Bioinformatics strategy

Although experimental approaches using gnotobiotic or knockout animals have been adopted over the years, the reduction of animal experimentation based on pre-validated targeted investigations has also been stimulated^{50,108}. Additionally, much criticism involves this kind of experimentation, as it imposes artificial conditions on the animals that could be detrimental to translational studies^{50,109}. Advances in high-throughput sequencing technologies have facilitated the collection of vast amounts of genomic, metagenomic, and metataxonomic data, enabling researchers to explore the complex relationships between hosts and their commensal gut bacteria *in silico* before experimentation¹¹⁰. For instance, by identifying candidate host genes and microbial taxa of interest, researchers can then prioritise specific conditions for validation in controlled settings, such as GF or humanised animal models⁵⁰. This pre-filtering process not only aims to enhance the efficiency of experimental studies but also to reduce the ethical and logistical burdens associated with *in vivo* research.

Bioinformatic tools can facilitate numerous microbiome analyses, including the assessment of microbial diversity, functional capabilities, and community dynamics, thereby providing a comprehensive framework for understanding host-microbiome interactions without imposing artificial conditions on the animals. Techniques such as differential abundance analysis, network modelling, and machine learning algorithms contribute to the elucidation of complex patterns, the identification of predictive markers within the data^{7,9}, and even the causal paths connecting gut bacteria with host health traits.

By serving as a bridge between observational studies and experimental validation, these approaches accelerate the translation of microbiome research into clinical and therapeutic advancements. However, this demands a population of laboratory animals that consistently complies with essential requirements in quantitative genetics, such as phenotypic variability, pairwise genetic diversity, and genetic homogeneity across cohorts, to avoid population structure biases and enable the analysis of comparable multi-cohort datasets.

c) The advantages of HS rats

Heterogeneous Stock (HS) rats, developed by interbreeding eight inbred strains (ACI/N, BN/SsN, BUF/N, F344/N, M520/N, MR/N, WKY/N, and WN/N), represent a genetically diverse outbred population maintained through random mating over numerous generations^{52,111,112}. This genetic diversity mirrors that of human populations, making HS rats an excellent model for dissecting the genetic basis of complex traits, including those related to psychiatric and metabolic diseases^{53,113,114}. The extensive recombination in HS rats enables high-resolution mapping of QTLs, which have facilitated the identification of genetic variants that influence phenotypes such as body weight, adiposity, and fasting glucose levels¹¹⁵. Compared to other outbred laboratory rats, such as the Sprague-Dawley (SD), HS rats offer several advantages, including higher phenotypic variability and rotational mating schemes to minimise inbreeding drift and ensure genetic homogeneity within studies⁵³. In contrast, although widely used, SD rats exhibit significant genetic variability between different vendors and colonies, resulting in inconsistent experimental outcomes^{116,117}.

In the context of gut microbiome research, the genetic heterogeneity of HS rats also enables the detection of host polygenic effects on the microbiome composition. For instance, a recent study that utilised HS rats from multiple cohorts identified consistent aggregate host genetic effects on bacterial taxa mapped by 16S-based profiling, which reinforces the benefits of working with this population⁵¹.

d) The importance of the caecum

The general adoption of “gut microbiota” as an abstract concept can make comparisons between studies difficult, as it can refer to either the bacteria mapped from faecal DNA or directly from different parts of the gastrointestinal tract. Even the latter might constrain comparability between studies, as bacterial colonisation across the gastrointestinal tract results in the establishment of multiple distinct microbiotas^{118,119}. While faecal sampling dominates microbiome studies, as it does not require invasive methods or the sacrifice of hosts, the caecum, a specialised fermentative chamber in rodents and other mammals, emerges as a better option for detecting host genetic effects on microbial communities of model animals¹¹⁸⁻¹²⁰.

The caecum, along with the colon, is the gastrointestinal region with the highest density and diversity of gut bacteria, and the primary fermentation centre, which leads to a large production of SCFAs^{119,121}. A good example of the main dissimilarities between caecal and rectal metabolomic profiles (with the latter typically being very similar to faecal samples) was performed with the capybara (*Hydrochoerus hydrochaeris*), the largest living rodent species¹²². This study showed significant differences in the caecal and rectal concentrations of the main SCFAs usually researched in the microbiome field: acetate $\approx 74.8 \pm 22.2 \mu\text{M}$ vs $30.4 \pm 22.8 \mu\text{M}$, propionate $\approx 31.0 \pm 6.7 \mu\text{M}$ vs $16.0 \pm 12.8 \mu\text{M}$, and butyrate $\approx 23.3 \pm 5.6 \mu\text{M}$ vs $8.35 \pm 12.8 \mu\text{M}$, respectively, which reinforced the caecum as a relevant active metabolic centre.

Furthermore, the caecum has been described as containing the microbiome most susceptible to environmental changes in laboratory rodents, making it a valuable source of biomarkers¹²³. It includes an ample anoxic luminal space and an epithelial lining covered by a thin mucus layer, permitting more direct microbe-host interactions than the colon, which has a bilayer mucus with an inner sterile stratum and an outer loose layer that allows colonisation¹²⁴⁻¹²⁶. Furthermore, as seen throughout the rest of the gastrointestinal tract, the caecum's epithelial lining features invaginations denoted as crypts, where epithelial stem cells are protected at the bottom by a mucus layer filling the entire cavity¹²⁷. This structure facilitates immune surveillance and the exchange of metabolites between host cells and the commensal bacteria that can colonise it (Figure 1).

Figure 1: General representation of the rodent caecum, highlighting its position in the gastrointestinal tract (top illustration) and the structure of its epithelial lining (bottom illustration), where invaginations denominated crypts protect stem-cells from luminal stressors with the protection of a single mucus layer. While most bacteria are found in the lumen, few are capable of adhering to the mucus (dark red bacteria in the first crypt), and some are even capable of developing biofilms on it (as represented in the last crypt). However, few bacterial groups can penetrate the mucus layer, coming into closer proximity to epithelium cells and exchanging molecules with the host, such as SCAFs or microbe-associated molecular patterns (MAMPs), which may trigger immune reactions (as represented in the central crypt by red circles). In exchange, host cells can increase mucus production or respond with antimicrobial peptides (AMPs), cytokines, immunoglobulins or reactive oxygen species (ROS)^{128,129} (as represented in the central crypt by purple circles). Created in BioRender.com¹³⁰.

Humans also have a short caecum located next to the proximal colon and connected to a small vermiform structure absent in rodents: the appendix. The appendix was hypothesised to be a remnant of the caecum, and the organ has recently been shown to have evolved under multiple environmental factors beyond diet, probably acting as a repository for beneficial bacteria, replenishing the gut microbiota after disturbances^{94,131}. All these elements support the use of rodent caecum samples as a reliable proxy for translational research. Therefore, the present study focused on the rat caecal microbiota as

its target “gut microbiota”. This way, the likelihood of mapping bacterial species that are mucus- or lumen-associated would increase, in contrast to faecal microbiotas, which tend to be more represented by luminal microorganisms¹²³.

e) Detecting polygenic signals in pooled cohorts

Although estimating heritability typically requires less statistical power than pinpointing individual variants in GWAS, securing a sufficiently large cohort is still essential to minimise sampling error and deliver stable, trustworthy estimates. One of the main strategies adopted for this is to combine datasets from multiple cohorts into a larger dataset and then account for the confounding effects inherent in this combination. A high-impact example involved a study performed by the MiBioGen consortium, which analysed the faecal microbiome of more than 18,000 people, pooling data from 24 different studies¹³². This enabled the discovery of 31 significant loci, including many that were previously invisible in single-study analyses.

Yet, the very heterogeneity that grants generalisability introduces severe batch and cohort artefacts arising from divergent extraction protocols, sequencing platforms, and population structure, which can overwhelm actual host-gene effects if left unchecked¹³³. A very illustrative example of the importance of these effects was reported during the validation of the Mouse Gastrointestinal Bacteria Catalogue (MGBC), which used a dataset of mouse gut metagenomes pooled from 75 different studies¹³⁴. In this research, a permutational multivariate analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) was performed to assess the effects of different metadata factors on the variances of bacterial relative abundances, after profiling all these metagenomes with the catalogue. The results showed that the study to which the metagenome belonged was the factor with the most considerable effect, explaining 40% of the variance observed, followed by the institutes that realised the studies, with an effect size of 38%. Such effects were far stronger than those obtained by factors such as strain (11%), genotype (5%), and sex (2%), reinforcing the importance of considering them when adopting a pooled dataset.

The current best-practice solution for this problem is therefore a two-step harmonisation pipeline that involves inverse rank normalisation to stabilise variance¹³⁵, followed by linear regression of explicit confounders (e.g., cohort, batch, age and sex) so that the resulting residuals behave as pseudo-relative abundances suitable for pooled modelling¹³⁵ (further discussed in Chapter 4). While this method aims to minimise both experimental and biological confounders in the detection of host genetic effects, it is still imperative to identify whether pooling different cohorts of the same population is at risk of creating biases due to population structure (i.e. systematic ancestry differences that shift allele frequencies between subgroups). As discussed before, one of the main advantages of the HS rat population is that the rotational mating applied to them tends to minimise inbreeding drift, ensuring genetic homogeneity within cohorts. Therefore, in this chapter, the primary objective is to validate the absence of significant population structure effects in a dataset comprising two cohorts of HS rats (MI and NY) using their genomic data (Objective 1).

3.2 Methods

a) Experimental design and sampling

In a collaboration with NIDA and the Center for Microbiome Innovation, caecal metagenomic and metataxonomic data were obtained from two cohorts of HS rats: one maintained at the University at Buffalo (the NY cohort) in an SPF facility with conventional cages (i.e. non-ventilated), and the other at the University of Michigan (the MI cohort) in a non-SPF facility also with the same type of cages. These cohorts had a balanced proportion of males and females and corresponded to animals born at the Medical College of Wisconsin, where they were kept in an SPF facility with ventilated cages. They were then shipped to their corresponding phenotyping centres at 3-6 weeks of age (after weaning), where they were exposed to different doses of cocaine and subjected to behavioural tests to be phenotyped for drug addiction and metabolism-associated traits. All animals received an *ad libitum* chow diet and were fasted overnight (17 ± 2 hours) before their sacrifice, with MI animals being fed the LabDiet Picolab Laboratory Rodent Diet Irradiated and NY animals being fed the Envigo Teklad

18% Protein Rodent Diet, which both maintained similar proportions of calories from protein (24-29% of kcal), fat (14-18% of kcal) and carbohydrates (57.5-58% of kcal)^{136,137}. Both are grain-based chow diets with typical proportions of neutral detergent fibre (~15-17%), not being considered 'high-fibre' diets¹³⁸. Individuals from the same sex were randomly housed either in pairs (NY) or trios (MI), ensuring that siblings would not cohabit the same cage to avoid confounding between maternal effects (shared dams) and cohousing effects (shared cages). Fasting blood glucose levels were measured with the Contour Next EZ system (Bayer, Elkhart, Indiana)¹³⁹, and all animals were subjected to phenobarbital anaesthesia for measurements such as body length (from the nose to the tail tip) and weight, followed by decapitation. In MI, euthanasia happened to animals at 11-14 weeks of age, while in NY, rats were sacrificed at 27-30 weeks of age. At this point, their caeca and spleens were removed for DNA extraction. All procedures were performed after approval by the corresponding Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees (IACUC). Further details about them can be found in the original studies that generated the phenotypic, genomic and metagenomic data^{51,113,115}.

b) Host genotyping workflow

Host DNA was extracted and purified from spleen tissues using the Agencourt DNAdvance Kit (Beckman Coulter Life Sciences, Indianapolis, IN)¹¹¹. Then, a low-coverage double-digest genotyping-by-sequencing (ddGBS) library was prepared using 1 µg of DNA and PstI/NlaIII barcoded adapters. Sequencing was performed using the Illumina HiSeq 4000 (Illumina, San Diego, CA, USA)¹⁴⁰ with 100-bp single-end reads, being demultiplexed with `fastx_toolkit v0.0.14`¹⁴¹, trimmed with `cutadapt v4.4`¹⁴² and `bbDuk v38.94`¹⁴³, aligned to the reference rat genome assembly `mRatBN7.2`¹⁴⁴ with `bwa-mem v0.7.17`¹⁴⁵, with subsequent variant calling¹¹¹. Then, genotype imputation was performed based on the reference haplotype panel of the HS population founder strains using `STITCH v1.6.6`^{51,146}, and the SNPs were pruned based on their linkage disequilibrium (LD) rates¹¹⁵ using `PLINK v1.90b6.2`¹⁴⁷, which resulted in a final dataset with 4,880,609 autosomal SNPs⁵¹. This panel was used to build a genetic relatedness matrix (GRM) for downstream heritability estimation. A GRM is simply a table of pair-wise genetic similarities. For each SNP, the allele dosage

value $x \in \{0,1,2\}$ is first centred on its expected frequency $2p$ and scaled by the standard deviation $\sqrt{2p(1-p)}$, giving the standardised score $w = (x - 2p)/\sqrt{2p(1-p)}$. In simple terms, this standardising score is based on the number of copies of a certain allele the mapped SNPs have, adjusted for the frequency of that allele in the population. As a result, the diagonal of the matrix is ≈ 1 (the relatedness of the individual with itself), and only inbreeding or sampling noise makes it deviate. The genetic relatedness between two individuals is then the average product of their w -scores over all SNPs. This weighting scheme naturally assigns greater influence to matches at rare alleles, given that sharing an allele that is rare in the population is a stronger signal of recent common ancestry than sharing a common allele¹⁴⁸. The GRM was stored in an HDF5 file¹⁴⁹ to enable fast, hierarchical access to the table both in R and Python scripts. HDF5 is a hierarchical, binary format for large heterogeneous datasets, and the same file containing the GRM also stored the matrices of the SNP-based genotypes per chromosome (only the autosomes: 1-20) and was used subsequently for the inclusion of the microbiome phenotype matrix (as further described in Chapter 5).

c) Caecal metagenomics workflow

In order to generate the raw data used by the pipeline, each caecum was extracted by cutting the gastrointestinal tract between the ileum and the caecum, and between the caecum and the colon. All caeca had their luminal content emptied, and the remaining tissue was placed in a sterile jar for storage at -80°C for subsequent DNA extraction⁵¹. For this final step, frozen caeca were partially thawed in ice and cut transversely. Approximately 100 μl of residual luminal content from their apical side was scooped and placed in a 1.5 ml tube for storage in dry ice before the total DNA could be obtained and purified, immediately after (Figure 2). Further details about all procedures deployed can be found in recent studies that used the same samples^{51,113,115}.

Figure 2: General scheme of caecum collection. **A)** The caecum was cut in its two openings, one to the ileum and the other to the colon. **B)** Then, its luminal content was removed. **C)** The remaining tissue was stored in a -80°C freezer until DNA extraction. **D)** Frozen caeca were partially thawed in ice and had their apical parts separated from the rest. **E)** The remaining luminal content in this part of the caecum was scooped and kept in a small tube for DNA extraction. Generated with ChatGPT (o4-mini)¹⁵⁰ and BioRender.com¹³⁰.

Total caecal DNA was extracted and purified with the MoBio PowerSoil® DNA Isolation Kit (QIAGEN, Germantown, US)¹⁵¹. For 16S sequencing, the V4 region of the 16S small subunit (SSU) rRNA was amplified using the same protocol adopted by the Earth Microbiome Project¹⁵² with 5-10% PhiX added to each library. The libraries were then processed in eleven batches with Illumina MiSeq¹⁵³, generating FASTQ files with 150bp paired-end reads and obtaining an average sample depth of 20,842 pairs of reads (minimum: 6,624 and maximum: 34,495)⁵¹. For shallow shotgun data, libraries were prepared using the HyperPlus library prep kit (KAPA Biosciences)¹⁵⁴ and then sequenced with Illumina HiSeq 2500¹⁵⁵, generating 150-bp paired-end reads with a target of 1 million pairs of reads per sample, which resulted in an average sample depth of 902,683 pairs of reads (minimum: 20,124 and maximum: 5,506,276). After sequencing, all FASTQ files were uploaded to Qiita¹⁵⁶ (Study #11479), where demultiplexing was performed using Qiime¹⁵⁷. This resulted in 1,041 samples with shallow shotgun data and 4,422 with 16S data.

d) Population structure checks

From the 1,041 samples present in the pooled metagenomic dataset, only 858 remained after quality filtering steps were implemented for the analysis of the whole shallow shotgun metagenomic data (i.e., not involving comparisons with 16S data), with the additional removal of two more samples from hosts that lacked complete genotyping information. This resulted in 467 samples from MI and 389 from NY (further details are provided in Chapter 4).

Using a custom R script, the existence of a cohort-based significant population structure was assessed through a multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) and PERMANOVA, obtaining the top significant principal components (PCs) of the GRM eigen decomposition. Firstly, to ensure that the GRM conformed to the assumptions of kernel-Principal Component Analysis (PCA), it was verified whether the matrix was already mean-centred by checking that: (i) row and column means were numerically zero, (ii) the constant vector was in the null-space (iii), a second application of the centring operator left the matrix unchanged, and (iv) the mean off-diagonal element was equal to zero with the precision threshold of $1e-10^{158}$. If any of these tests failed, the matrix would be re-centred before downstream analyses. Secondly, the centred GRM eigenvalues were compared, using the Tracy-Widom test with Bonferroni correction, which identified statistically significant axes of genetic variation beyond random matrix theory expectations¹⁵⁹. By using the RMTstat v0.3.1 package¹⁶⁰, this test provided the number of PCs to be subjected to MANOVA using Pillai's trace statistic test for the identification of systematic differences between study cohorts. As a final validation, PERMANOVA (999 permutations) was also employed, using the Euclidean distance to provide a non-parametric assessment of cohort-based population structure effect, with *vegan* v2.6.10¹⁶¹. Finally, population structure was visualised through a scatterplot of the top two significant PCs, with cohorts indicated by different colours, using *ggplot2* v3.5.2¹⁶².

3.3 Results

As expected, no significant differences were detected between the genetic distances of animals from different cohorts, with p -values of 0.74 for MANOVA and 0.75 for PERMANOVA, indicating that they consisted of two groups of individuals with no genetic heterogeneity driven by their division into different studies (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Principal component analysis (PCA) of the genetic distance between the subgroup of animals used in shallow shotgun microbiome profiling. The dot colours represent samples from the MI (blue) or NY cohorts (orange). The p -value on the top-right side of the plot represents an approximate discrete Monte-Carlo p -value for 999 permutations of the PERMANOVA test, performed to assess whether grouping HS rats from these different cohorts would result in significant population structure issues.

3.4 Discussion, limitations and conclusion

Eigenvalue decomposition has been widely used and improved since its first proposal in 2006 to detect genetic population stratification in datasets¹⁶⁴⁻¹⁶⁷. With the adoption of the Tracy-Widom test, only significant PCs are considered for statistical tests, allowing a rapid

and reproducible screening of population structure biases. With the application of these tools, it was possible to verify that the selected multi-cohort dataset of HS rats was suitable for posterior heritability tests. Nevertheless, the current study only assessed the population structure between two cohorts, which does not necessarily mean that all cohorts of HS rats will present the same results. Thus, the inclusion of such analysis should be considered in all multi-cohort studies to detect and mitigate any bias that genetic drifts between cohorts may cause to the detection of host genetic effects. Additionally, working with a pooled dataset still demands a pipeline that evaluates the dimension of the impact of cohorts and other potential confounders on the variance of microbiome traits, even when population structure does not seem to be a problem.

CHAPTER 4. A REPRODUCIBLE PIPELINE FOR SHALLOW-SHOTGUN DATA

4.1 Introduction

a) Shallow shotgun: pros and cons

In Chapter 1, the benefits of using shallow shotgun sequencing were briefly listed, positioning it as an intermediate, cost-effective alternative to both 16S and deep shotgun sequencing. To exemplify how the costs between these three methods compare to each other, a quotation for sequencing 1,000 samples at the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG) was solicited, revealing that even though the cost per unit tends to be reduced when the target number of pairs of reads are higher (1.98 euros for 20 millions pairs of reads and 3.29 euros for 960 thousand pairs of reads), deep shotgun ends being 199% more expensive than 16S, while shallow is only 37% more expensive (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S1). This slight increase in costs comes with the advantages of no amplification biases, resolution at the species level, less sparse datasets, and technical reproducibility^{37,38,41,42,168-171}.

Amplification biases in 16S sequencing occur for two reasons associated with the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification of hypervariable regions (e.g., V3-V4): i) Primer mismatches due to variable GC content and the generation of chimeric reads, which lead to inconsistent detection of taxa and contribute to inflated false zeros (non-detection despite presence); ii) Differences in 16S rRNA gene copies across species, skewing abundance estimates in a way that low-copy-number taxa appear artificially sparse, while high-copy-number taxa are overrepresented^{37,167,168,171}. For instance, in a colorectal cancer study, 58% of the total species mapped by shotgun sequencing were undetected in the 16S data from the same samples¹⁶⁸.

Regarding taxonomic resolution, by targeting only a short and conserved region of the bacterial genome, 16S data often lack sufficient variability to distinguish between closely related species. Unlike metagenomic profiling, which directly assigns bacterial genomes to the obtained reads, corresponding to specific strains or

species, metataxonomics operates with either operational taxonomic units (OTUs) or amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) as the lowest taxonomic resolution. An ASV is the exact DNA sequence that algorithms such as DADA2¹⁷² or Deblur¹⁷³ infer to be truly present in a sample after “denoising” 16S rRNA gene data, i.e., statistically modelling and removing the errors introduced by PCR and sequencing, so that even single-nucleotide differences are retained. In contrast, OTUs group reads into clusters at an arbitrary similarity cutoff (commonly 97%), which can merge distinct organisms, and vary from study to study, making results harder to compare¹⁷⁴. Because ASVs are defined by their precise sequences rather than by a threshold, they are consistent and reproducible across datasets, enabling finer ecological and taxonomic resolution, simplifying chimaera detection, and generally showing higher sensitivity and specificity than traditional OTU clustering. Nevertheless, widely used 16S reference databases, such as SILVA¹⁷⁵, often group multiple species under identical sequences, whereas shotgun sequencing leverages whole-genome databases for finer discrimination¹⁷⁶. This issue was also exemplified in the same colorectal cancer study cited before, which showed that while samples from patients were enriched with *Bacteroides fragilis*, *Bacteroides ovatus* was more associated with control samples when deep shotgun sequencing was applied. However, when the same samples were sequenced with 16S metabarcoding, neither of these biomarkers was detected as significant, due to their ambiguous classification as the same taxonomic trait: “*Bacteroides fragilis* / *koreensis* / *kribbi* / *ovatus* / *xylanisolvans*”¹⁶⁸.

In another study, a comparison between 16S and shallow shotgun data, using daily and weekly faecal samples with technical replicates from the same five individuals, revealed that shallow shotgun was significantly less influenced by technical variability (at both DNA extraction and library preparation stages)¹⁷⁰. All of these criteria back up the results of comparisons between 16S and shallow shotgun data, which showed that the latter is also more accurate in profiling mock microbiomes, in addition to its capacity to reproduce similar results to those obtained with ultra-deep shotgun sequencing.^{41,42}

Additionally, since 16S sequencing only maps one specific region of the bacterial genome, the whole functional profiling of the microbiome must be inferred based on genomic reference catalogues

that link 16S sequences to functionally annotated reference genomes, which includes the employment of widely used tools such as PICRUST¹⁷⁷. However, due to the low taxonomic resolution, this inference tends to be less accurate than directly mapping many bacterial genes simultaneously, as done by shallow shotgun data. In multivariate analyses, for example, such as the measurements of α - and β -diversity, shallow shotgun-based functional profiling has yielded more accurate results than 16S^{41,170}.

However, while shallow shotgun shows more advantages than 16S, it suffers from limitations when compared to deep shotgun data. The first is that there is a depth limit to which shallow shotgun can still replicate the results of deep shotgun, which is around 500,000 pairs of reads⁴¹. It is essential to note that this threshold only accounts for the number of reads obtained immediately after sequencing (also referred to as raw reads), disregarding the fact that during various steps of metagenomic data processing, this number tends to decrease. Depending on the sampling and sequencing steps, quality filters such as trimming and the removal of host reads normally do not impose a considerable reduction in sample depth. However, the choice of the reference catalogue used to assign reads to bacterial taxa or functions can significantly impact the number of reads that proceed to the following steps. This can happen due to low mapping ratios, the discard of multi-mappers (i.e., sequences that equally map to two different taxa or genes, leading to ambiguous counts) and the removal of taxa with very low relative abundances (usually with a threshold of 0.01%), which is a necessary step to reduce the risk of mapping false positives.

Moreover, gold standard practices in microbiome profiling dictate that the avoidance of count biases caused by bacterial genome sizes must also be accounted for, as bacteria with larger genomes will have more reads mapped to them, which will be misinterpreted as higher relative abundances¹⁷⁸. Due to this inherent bias in shotgun profiling, the approach of focusing on multiple species-specific marker genes, rather than whole genomes, is typically employed when deep shotgun sequencing is adopted, by tools such as MetaPhlAn^{179,180}. However, due to the lower coverage of shallow shotgun data, this method is not recommended, as it yields extremely low mapping ratios¹⁸⁰.

b) Reference genome catalogues matter

In the microbiome field, either bacterial gene or genome catalogues can be used as references to map sequences from metagenomic data. On one hand, gene catalogues are recommended for microbiome functional profiling only, as they commonly rely on a sequence clustering step to provide a non-redundant database^{107,181,182}. On the other hand, genome catalogues can be used for both functional and taxonomic profiling. Such catalogues can be obtained by sequencing isolated genomes from cultivated bacteria or by assembling the reads from deep shotgun metagenomic data into contigs and then binning these contigs into metagenome-assembled genomes (MAGs)^{134,184-186}. Because most gut bacteria are strictly anaerobic (i.e., not tolerant to oxygen, normally due to the absence of ROS-detoxifying enzymes such as superoxide dismutase), they cannot be easily cultivated¹. This requires anaerobic chambers¹⁸⁶ or specific culture media with reducing agents that can maintain an oxygen-free environment¹⁸⁷, thereby allowing their survival. Consequently, such complexity has made MAG-based catalogues the main source of bacterial reference genomes for microbiome profiling.

Along with sequencing, assembling and binning, the main steps of the construction of a MAG catalogue include the selection of high-quality genomes based on completeness (i.e., the proportion of known multiple broad bacterial marker genes that are present in the bin) and contamination (i.e., the proportion of the same marker genes that are duplicated in the bin). The normal thresholds selected for this are 50% for completeness and 5% for contamination, which is also combined into a final quality indicator named the quality score 50 (QS50), defined by the formula: completeness - (5 × contamination). Then, tools such as GUNC¹⁸⁸ identify and remove chimeric bins, and the final dataset of bins is dereplicated to define genome clusters associated with unique species. This dereplication is done by adopting an average nucleotide identity (ANI) of 95% or higher. Furthermore, the genome with the best quality scores within the cluster is considered the representative species genome, resulting in lean catalogues that contain only one genome assigned to a unique species. The final steps involve the taxonomic and functional annotation of these MAGs, making the catalogue ready for use as a reference¹⁸⁹. It is essential to highlight that while a minimum sample

depth of 20 million pairs of reads is already acceptable to be used for the construction of a MAG catalogue with short reads³⁴⁻³⁶, the adoption of metagenome sequencing with long reads has become the gold standard practice, as it enables the obtainment of complete MAGs^{72,73,190}.

When the pipeline for this project was developed, only two annotated rat gut microbiome gene catalogues had been identified: one based on faecal and another on milk samples of SD rats^{107,191}. Because these catalogues involved a sequence clustering step to provide a non-redundant database, microbial taxonomic classification based on them could lead to spurious results, as discussed before¹⁸². Thus, GTDB R207 was chosen as the reference catalogue to be used by the pipeline, as it is a well-recognised broad catalogue based on bacterial genomes rather than genes, all obtained from the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) repositories^{44,45}. Additionally, this database is also widely adopted as the gold standard for phylogenetically accurate taxonomic annotation of new catalogues¹⁸⁹.

Nevertheless, it is worth noting that two bacterial genome catalogues have been recently identified as references for the gut microbiome of rodents (mainly wild animals), including MAGs obtained from the metagenomes of rat guts^{192,193}. Moreover, a specific MAG catalogue is also being developed by the Social and Host-Microbiome Systems lab, led by Dr. Baud at CRG, in collaboration with the European Bioinformatics Institute (EBI), based on deep shotgun sequencing (~50 million pairs of short reads) of faecal and caecal samples from HS rats.

c) Taxonomy and cross-study comparability

Significant reclassifications of bacterial lineages have been done very recently, with GTDB already in its R226 release (2025)¹⁹⁴. Despite these developments, the present study adopts the bacterial and archaeal taxonomic framework established by GTDB in April 2022, the release 207 (R207)⁴⁴, as it was the bacterial genome catalogue used to profile the HS rats' caecal microbiota with shallow shotgun data, aiming for comparisons with Greengenes2-based 16S taxonomically annotated profiles, a catalogue that uses the same

nomenclature as GTDB R207¹⁹⁵ (Chapter 5). GTDB R207 provides a standardised, phylogenetically consistent system that enhances comparability across genomic and ecological studies. In the current research, the formerly known phylum Firmicutes (recently renamed Bacillota and Bacillota A in subsequent updates of the catalogue^{196,197}) retains the GTDB R207 designation, with its subgroup Firmicutes A representing the most functionally and numerically significant phylum lineage. As evidenced by GTDB R207 statistics⁴⁴, Firmicutes A encompasses 8,243 species clusters, surpassing all other Firmicutes subgroups, and includes the class Clostridia, a pivotal taxon in mammalian gut ecosystems due to its high abundance and roles in fibre fermentation, SCFA production, and immune modulation¹⁹⁸. Because of this relevance, the present research considers other studies' references to Firmicutes, Bacillota or Bacillota A as corresponding to GTDB R207's Firmicutes A. Similarly, the phylum formerly known as Bacteroidetes is treated here as Bacteroidota, aligning with GTDB R207's nomenclature, which documents 8,588 species clusters within this group⁴⁴.

Notably, this release also precedes major reclassifications of the genus *Prevotella*, which subsequent studies have split into new genera (e.g., *Segatella*, *Hoylesella*, *Leyella*, and *Palleniella*) based on genomic divergence and functional distinctions¹⁹⁹. For instance, *Prevotella copri*, a prevalent human gut commensal implicated in enterotype dynamics and host health, was reclassified as *Segatella copri* in 2022¹⁹⁹. However, GTDB R207 retains the original *Prevotella* designation, as these changes were validated after its cutoff date⁴⁴. Furthermore, previous studies used to separate *Prevotella* and *Bacteroides* into two different families: Prevotellaceae and Bacteroidaceae²⁰⁰. However, according to the taxonomy adopted by GTDB R207 (and the subsequent ones), both genera now belong to the Bacteroidaceae family.

All species included in the GTDB R207 catalogue used in this research correspond to genomes selected as the representative species of genome clusters, which are identified by either GenBank or RefSeq accession numbers^{44,45}. This allows them to be recognised by the genome assembly they represent in the NCBI repositories, independently of the taxonomy assigned to it. Therefore, by disclaiming the taxonomy adopted in the current study, it grounds its investigations within a stable, widely referenced taxonomic

framework, avoiding ambiguities arising from transitional nomenclature and acknowledging the intention to make it comparable to past and future studies.

d) Functional profiling

While healthy individuals tend to exhibit high inter-individual variation in the relative abundances of common faecal bacterial groups (even at the phylum level), functional profiles consistently display homogeneous distributions of standard biological processes, such as the biosynthesis of many cell-structuring molecules^{25,76,201}. The current understanding about this phenomenon is that this pattern reflects the high functional redundancy observed in diverse homeostatic guts. In other words, while groups of taxonomically distinct bacteria can vary across individuals, they tend to share similar functions, maintaining a condition that could be defined as “healthy”. At the same time, studies have shown that when samples from stool and biopsies of patients with different degrees of gut inflammatory conditions are analysed (e.g., IBD, Crohn’s disease, or ulcerative colitis), the relative abundances of specific bacterial functions differ, facilitating their stratification. This suggests that focusing on functions rather than taxa may be an interesting approach to distinguish healthy and unhealthy hosts^{201,202}.

In general, to profile bacterial functions present in metagenomic data, it is typically assumed that “function” refers to the activity performed by a translatable gene (i.e., genes coding for short peptides or proteins). Such functionality could be assigned to the particular activity in which the corresponding protein engages, such as the catalytic role of an enzyme in a specific biochemical reaction, or even according to the higher biological processes in which these proteins are involved, such as aerobic respiration or vitamin biosynthesis. Due to this, functional profiling is identified as being gene-centric, with both gene, protein and genome reference catalogues being applied for homology-based profiling. Furthermore, if new genes with no homologs are found, they can also be analysed based on a motif-based approach in order to unveil their possible roles⁷¹.

The motif-based profiling involves the deployment of protein catalogues and predictive models to identify domains (i.e., distinct,

independently folding units within a protein, often with specific functions such as catalysis, binding, or structural roles) and classify new sequences according to their similarity to known protein families. Meanwhile, homology-based profiling is defined by mapping metagenomic sequences (with or without assembling the reads) to reference gene or protein catalogues, such as the broad UniProt database²⁰⁴ (in this case, by translating all possible six open reading frames from the DNA reads²⁰⁵). These protein-based profiles can then be collapsed into different functional hierarchies. First, protein sequences from various organisms that perform the same function due to a shared ancestor can be grouped into orthologous groups, including Enzyme Commission numbers (ECs)²⁰⁶, Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) Orthologs (KOs)²⁰⁷, or Clusters of Orthologous Groups (COGs)^{208,209}. Additionally, the counts obtained for orthologous groups can be collapsed into groups of proteins with very specific functions, such as carbohydrate-active enzymes (CAZymes), or to their corresponding metabolic reactions, modules or pathways, using tools such as the KEGG mappers²⁰⁷ or HUMAnN¹⁸⁰. Higher functional classification approaches also include MetaCyc²¹⁰ reactions and pathways, as well as Gene Ontologies (GO)²¹¹.

HUMAnN is part of the bioBakery pipeline, which employs a tiered search strategy: first aligning reads to species-specific pangenomes (i.e., the full collection of genes found across every strain of a species), then resolving unclassified reads via translated search against comprehensive databases (i.e., UniProt's non-redundant catalogues such as UniRef90), and finally quantifying metabolic pathway abundances through MetaCyc annotations²¹⁰. However, this and similar pipelines are typically oriented toward high-coverage sequencing methods (i.e., deep shotgun metagenomics). Therefore, emerging tools optimised for shallow shotgun data, such as Woltka²¹², address these gaps by coupling the partial direct mapping of bacterial genes with gene imputation based on their positions in the respective mapped bacterial genomes, using the Web of Life (WoL) database as a reference. Therefore, Woltka integrates taxonomic and functional profiling in the same workflow, acting as an intermediate approach between PICRUSt (used for 16S-based profiling) and HUMAnN. However, even though it enhances resolution for shallow-shotgun data, this pipeline remains constrained by the fact that all optimisations are designed for the use

of WoL as a database, which is limited in terms of the number and diversity of species representative genomes²¹².

Alternatively, large functional databases focused on microorganisms have been proven to be a more effective approach. For example, the IBM Functional Genomics Platform (IFGP), previously known as the OMXWare database²¹³, compiles over 11.9 million bacterial and viral protein domain sequences with curated EC annotations, allowing metagenomic reads to be mapped to these domains and regrouped into the EC-based four-level hierarchy using a profiler named PRROMenade^{214,215}. Similar to phylogenetically consistent taxonomic profiling, this approach enables a coherent, multi-rank functional outline in a single analytical step. A recent benchmarking study, which analysed functional profiles of 880 metagenomic datasets collected for the Earth Microbiome Project, revealed that, compared to Woltka, PRROMenade mapped functions across diverse environments more efficiently²¹⁷.

e) Species guilds as a proxy for functional wiring

Beyond individual bacteria or bacterial genes, researchers are increasingly examining clusters of co-occurring species (or species guilds) as proxies for emergent community functional groups^{70,74,75,218}. In ecology, non-random species co-abundance patterns indicate underlying interactions and shared niches²¹⁹. Similarly, gut bacteria often form clusters of taxa that consistently co-vary across many hosts, which can be identified via clustering analyses of the species relative abundances. This reveals sets of organisms that likely cooperate in the gut ecosystem, reflecting community-level processes that almost no single species can carry out alone, such as full fibre degradation or mucin utilisation^{62,64,220}. For instance, one recent large-scale analysis defined what was denominated as human enterosignatures: five reproducible guilds of co-occurring gut genera, each dominated by a different core taxon (*Bacteroides*, *Prevotella*, a consortium of Firmicutes, *Bifidobacterium*, or *Escherichia*) in different proportions across samples²¹⁸. This method has already been deployed, for example, to detect host genetic effects on pig gut microbiome guilds, making it an approach suitable for multiple hosts²²¹.

Notably, co-abundance clusters tend to recur across diverse human populations, suggesting that microbiomes converge on a limited number of assemblages²¹⁸. Studies have shown that changes in bacterial guilds can correspond to changes in community outputs. For example, a guild associated with fibre fermentation may flourish on a plant-rich diet and contribute to higher butyrate levels. Likewise, disturbances to the microbiome (e.g., antibiotics, diet shifts, etc.) often perturb entire guilds in concert, rather than just individual species⁷⁰. Additionally, by measuring co-abundance guild dynamics, scientists capture emergent properties, such as community stability, resilience, and functional redundancy, which connect this concept to principles of network analysis and community diversity metrics⁷⁴.

Many methods can be applied for the delimitation of co-abundant clusters. However, when dealing with sparse and compositional abundance matrices typical of microbiome studies, it is crucial to consider that linear methods, such as PCA, may often distort the reduction of these highly dimensional datasets, affecting both local and global neighbourhood topology, and being less efficient in detecting noise. Due to that, non-linear techniques such as the Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection (UMAP) have become popular in microbiome studies for non-linear dimensionality reduction^{222,223}. Comparative tutorials have shown that UMAP better maintains density information than PCA, an essential prerequisite for subsequent density-based clustering²²⁵⁻²²⁷. Tools such as the Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN) then leverage these density cues to identify clusters of variable size and shape, while automatically labelling noise and outliers, thereby reducing false guild assignments^{227,228}. This synergy has been adopted in microbiome-specific toolkits such as MicNet, which first embeds low-rank taxon tables, including 16S-based amplicon sequence variants (ASVs), using UMAP and then groups them with HDBSCAN into ecologically coherent modules²²⁹. In a marine benchmark, MicNet resolved 49 guilds while relegating 553 rare ASVs to noise, highlighting its ability to separate core guilds from background taxa²²⁹.

Nevertheless, it is essential to consider that such approach requires fine-tuning of parameters followed by validation to ensure that the obtained clusters are intrinsically well-separated in the density space and remain consistent under data perturbation. For the first

requirement, defining a threshold for a Density-Based Clustering Validation index (DBCVI) can be a good validation step to move parameters such as the number of neighbours, the minimum distance or the epsilon (i.e., how finely HDBSCAN cuts the condensed cluster tree after UMAP has placed the points based on a minimum embedding distance)^{230,231}. For the second requirement, bootstrapping the data (i.e., resampling 80-90 % of samples without replacement 20-30 times) and defining a threshold for the Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) will then assess whether the parameters used result in clusters re-appearing in most resamples, being a sign of reproducibility²³².

In practice, network analyses of the gut microbiome have revealed that specific modules of co-occurring species correlate with host phenotypes or outcomes. In IBD and obesity, for example, particular species sub-networks were found to be disrupted, and their alteration was linked to disease-specific metabolic changes²³³. Overall, accounting for gut microbiome guilds is an approach that complements traditional taxon-based analyses by highlighting interactions that drive the community operation mode. As a consequence, they ultimately reflect the behaviour of the whole microbial assembly^{74,218}. It has been shown, for example, that the enterosignature-based guild approach replicates patterns also observed through the identification of enterotypes²¹⁸, another widely adopted concept in the microbiome field to define communities with different compositions.

f) Enterotypes

While co-abundance guilds represent how microbiome traits (e.g., bacterial species, ASVs, or genes) coexist in a manner that suggests modular ecological teamwork, enterotypes represent how different hosts can be stratified based on the overall structure of their commensal community²³⁴. An interesting aspect of enterotypes is that they represent recurrent microbiome configurations across populations. For example, in humans, three enterotypes have been consistently identified: one dominated by *Bacteroides*, one dominated by *Prevotella* and another dominated by a diverse group of Firmicutes (or sometimes characterised specifically as a *Ruminococcus*-dominated group)^{234,235}. While the Firmicutes

enterotype tends to be present in almost every human population, there is a clear division between populations that present the *Prevotella* or the *Bacteroidetes* enterotypes, with the former being associated with the so-called “agrarian” or “non-Western” societies and the latter with “industrial” or “Western” societies, reflecting diet-driven patterns (i.e., fibre-rich diets vs protein/fat-rich diets, respectively)²³⁶.

At the same time, enterotypes are also valuable for patient stratification, with the *Bacteroides* enterotype being generally associated with gut inflammation and high body weight^{237,238} and the Firmicutes enterotype sometimes serving as a biomarker for certain metabolic diseases²³⁹. A study has shown that in extreme cases, such as those involving patients with colorectal cancer, an *Escherichia*-associated enterotype can also be detected, revealing a gut microbiome community in a state of grave dysbiosis²⁴⁰.

However, in other well-studied mammals, such as farm pigs, only two enterotypes are observed, with the one often associated with higher *Prevotella* abundances being typically linked with improved growth performance^{91,222,242-244}. A recent study has shown that these enterotypes can be selected among farm pigs by interbreeding animals based on high or low abundances of the corresponding dominant bacteria. This reveals not only the possible role of host genetic effects in defining these two community states but also suggests that specific bacteria might be responsible for mediating it⁹¹. The same two-enterotype pattern has also been observed in inbred laboratory mice, with one type being more linked to inflammation and the other to a healthier gut²⁴⁴.

Curiously, while traditional reports of human microbiomes have shown the existence of the three aforementioned enterotypes, new studies suggest an overlap between the *Bacteroides* and Firmicutes/*Ruminococcus* groups²³⁸. At the same time, others are already working with the idea of two human enterotypes, also defining them as health- or inflammation-associated, after accounting for known confounders, such as age, lifestyle or medication use²³⁹. This represents a significant shift in the human enterotype paradigm, as it aligns not only with patterns found in other mammals but also with the two alternative stable states model proposed in 2020, which demonstrated through experiments with SPF Fischer 344 male rats

that, under identical environmental conditions, a combination of host and gut microbiome factors results in two alternative stable community compositions²⁴⁵.

The main methods employed for the multivariate partitioning of samples into distinct enterotypes are PCA, Dirichlet multinomial mixtures (DMM), the partitioning around medoids (PAM) algorithm with the Jensen-Shannon distance and k -means based on the Euclidean distance^{234,239,246}. While these methods result in a clear separation of samples into relatively discrete and highly dense stable regions in the multivariate microbial profile space, critics highlight that, in fact, enterotypes often form a continuous distribution^{226,247,248}. For this reason, combining a method that adopts the same distance measure for both enterotype delimitation and β -diversity estimation could benefit from the linear aspect of β -diversity principal coordinates and address enterotypes as extremes of the same continuum.

g) Diversity analysis

Running a diversity analysis is the simplest way to reduce the complexity of multivariate microbiome profiles and answer two fundamental questions: i) To what extent are the communities of different groups of samples significantly dissimilar? and ii) How complex are the microbial assemblies within each sample? To answer the first question, β -diversity is the measure utilised (also known as sample dissimilarity or sample distance), while the estimation of within-sample α -diversity addresses the second question⁷⁹.

Diversity measures tend to be one of the topics in microbiome studies that most generates confusion and difficulties in terms of comparability, as researchers can adopt different metrics for them^{79,249}. This is important because they are extensively used to associate the gut microbiome with health and disease. For example, it is well known that dysbiotic communities are characterised by low α -diversity values (richness and evenness) and can be easily distinguished from communities of healthy hosts by β -diversity estimation^{7,251-254}. These bacterial assemblies are characterised by many imbalanced features that can occur at either the taxonomic level, such as the extreme Firmicutes A : Bacteroidota (F:B) ratio

seen in obese patients⁹, or at the functional level, with reduced concentrations of SCFAs and an increased presence of highly immunogenic LPS²⁵⁰. Due to several experimental studies and clinical cases, the mechanisms behind diversity biomarkers and health conditions, ranging from gastric to psychiatric diseases, are now better understood²⁵⁰. Furthermore, the factors that often provoke dysbiosis are also well acknowledged and include the excessive use of antibiotics, poor diets and even environmental intoxication by pesticides or heavy metals²⁵³.

The primary explanation for the connection between α -diversity, dysbiosis, and health lies in two factors: (i) more diverse communities have higher resilience, which makes them less prone to enter a dysbiotic state after external disturbances; and ii) more functional efficiency, due to the presence of many taxa performing the same functions⁷⁷. In the second case, accommodating a higher number of different species (or even strains) that perform similar functions reduces the number of necessary connections they must make to achieve functional completeness for many biological processes^{76,77}. This results in patterns already observed by other studies: an increase in less metabolically independent, fast-growing bacteria with smaller genomes grouped into local guilds⁶⁵.

While most studies refer to α -diversity as being exclusively the Shannon evenness index, the current research follows the guidelines suggested by a recent methodological review, which classifies multiple α -diversity measures based on two axes²⁴⁹. The first one defines the Hill number, which, in simple terms, refers to the degree of complexity aimed for (e.g., “ $q = 0$ ” for richness, “ $q = 1$ ”, for evenness and “ $q = 2$ ” for the probability of randomly picking two traits that are not the same)²⁵⁴. On one hand, richness refers to the number of unique microbiome taxa, being a binary measurement (present or absent); on the other hand, the others combine richness with relative abundances, accounting for dominant taxa as a factor that reduces diversity. The second axis determines whether the focus is on neutral or phylogenetic diversity. The latter involves assigning weights to the estimations based on the phylogenetic relatedness of the traits. Therefore, given these two axes, six possible α -diversity measurements can be estimated^{249,254}. This is particularly important, given that the phylogenetic diversity $q = 2$ (also known as Rao’s quadratic index) exhibits temporal fluctuations that better reflect

those of functional diversity, compared to other α -diversity metrics²⁵⁵, but is barely included in microbiome characterisation.

Furthermore, whilst most studies deal with the effects of sample depth on α -diversity estimation by standardising them through rarefaction, working with shallow shotgun demands the avoidance of losing reads. In this case, the rarefaction and extrapolation method is a good alternative, as it standardises α -diversity values across samples with different depths through the estimation of their asymptotic values²⁵⁵⁻²⁵⁷. This elegant solution addresses the restrictive condition in which α -diversity cannot be defined based on log-ratios, a necessary transformation step for compositional data, such as microbiome profiles^{249,257} (further discussed in the next section). Similarly, β -diversity can be calculated in different ways, depending on the study's focus: whether it should be neutral or phylogenetic; whether it includes relative abundances or just the presence or absence of traits; and whether the compositional nature of the data will be accounted for^{249,258}.

h) Compositionality and fixed effects removal

High-throughput metagenomic sequencing leads to read-count matrices whose entries describe the proportional contribution of each taxon to a fixed sample size, confining the data to the simplex (i.e., the specific geometric space where data points are constrained to sum to 100%, creating dependencies between them)²⁵⁷. This happens because metagenome sequencing is limited by the number of reads it can generate. Thus, every read count assigned to a bacterial taxon or gene necessarily represents a count not computed for the others, making it a non-quantitative method. Treating these constrained counts with total-sum scaling or rarefaction assumes an arbitrary total of 100% that may never be achieved. It can then induce spurious correlations or false differences between samples, which are pitfalls identified a long time ago and now widely acknowledged as statistically problematic²⁶⁰⁻²⁶³.

The current gold standard for quantifying microbiome traits from metagenomes is the quantitative microbiome profiling (QMP), which combines sequencing with absolute cell or DNA load quantification to measure accurate abundances and eliminate compositional

artefacts²⁶³. This approach consistently outperforms purely computational fixes across diversity estimation, co-abundance clustering and network analysis^{264,265}. Yet, because absolute counts remain expensive or impossible for many archived datasets, the log-ratio transformation from compositional data analysis provides a pragmatic bridge²⁶⁰.

Nevertheless, there is no single solution for the adoption of log-ratios, and different types of microbiome analyses require distinct approaches. To quantify the compositional relative abundances of individual microbiome features (i.e., taxa or functions), the centred log-ratio (CLR) transformation is the recommended approach, as it renders every value scale-invariant and symmetric, allowing robust differential-abundance modelling and longitudinal trajectories while preserving sub-compositional coherence²⁶⁰. Between-sample multivariate distance measures (β -diversity) and the definition of enterotypes require the deployment of isometric log-ratios (ILR) instead. This happens because by mapping the composition to orthonormal coordinates in Euclidean space, ILR supports distance metrics without the singular covariance matrix that hinders CLR²⁵⁸. Furthermore, at the same time that phylogenetic α -diversity metrics, such as Rao's quadratic index, have become an interesting approach for a more refined within-sample community analysis²⁵⁵, the inclusion of phylogenetic-based weights into ILR transformation for between-sample estimations has also shown great value, compared to other methods^{258,266}.

In contrast, α -diversity estimation operates on non-negative frequencies. Because their algorithms cannot accept the negative values introduced by log-ratios and already summarise each sample independently, they are calculated directly on raw or proportionally normalised counts, optionally after rarefaction, but without any log-ratio step, which makes the asymptotic approach commented before the best solution to the problem²⁴⁹. Crucially, ignoring the compositional nature of the data can lead to distorted biological inferences. An important example for the present research comes from a study that reported inflated estimates of microbial heritability due to the adoption of simple proportional relative abundances of individual taxa²⁶⁷.

In addition, by focusing on the detection of host genetic effects on gut microbiome traits, a second step is necessary after treating the data with adequate transformation methods: removing the effects of known biological and experimental confounders, also referred to as fixed effects. This is an important step, given the considerable well-reported impact already identified for many of these factors, such as the study (or cohort), the institutions where the studies were conducted, host sex and age, sequencing batch and others¹³⁴. A method commonly applied for this is to run an inverse rank-based normalisation of the values, turning them into parametric variables that can be used to fit such fixed effects in a linear regression and obtain the residual values as “clean” pseudo-relative abundances¹³⁵. Thus, every further measure necessary to characterise the gut microbiome (e.g., co-abundance, centrality, diversity, etc.) must use these final values to avoid biases imposed by the compositional nature of the data and the effects of known confounders.

i) Network analysis

In the field of multivariate molecular ecology⁷⁹, to which gut microbiome studies belong, the conceptual framework that delves deeper into the dynamics behind co-abundance guilds, enterotypes, and diversity is network analysis^{268,269}. Through the network theory perspective, it is possible to model the interaction between species or biological functions as graphs, where nodes represent each of them, edges represent their correlations with one another, and edge weights represent the strength of such correlations. Then, the position of individual nodes, coupled with the topology of the entire graph, generates new metrics that allow the identification of novel relevant information about the orchestration of the gut microbiome and its components²⁷⁰.

Firstly, from the perspective of individual nodes, centrality values can reveal not only who they interact with more closely, as similarly shown in co-abundance analysis, but also how relevant the node is to both local guilds (also termed as network modules) and the entire community. The number of edges established by a node is referred to as its degree centrality, a metric that suggests how central a node is in a particular ecological process. For instance, primary fibre or mucin degraders are usually identified as central nodes in local cross-

feeding chains^{64,220}. Complementarily, closeness centrality measures the proximity of a node to all other nodes, indicating a broader influence within the community, a characteristic often observed in bacteria that systemically affect the host's immunoregulation. During an experimental study with SPF wild mice, for example, it was observed that when *Prevotella intestinalis* colonises their gut, it triggers physiological changes that result in the reduction of interleukin-18 (IL-18), leading to exacerbated mucosal inflammation and associated dysbiosis, characterised by a significant decrease in the F:B ratio²⁷¹. In addition to these two metrics, betweenness centrality measures how often a node acts as a bridge between two other nodes that are not directly connected, which can also represent a connection between different guilds. Meanwhile, eigenvector centrality defines the position of a node in the network hierarchy as more influential if it has more connections with other relevant central nodes^{229,272}.

Although bacterial species can be defined as network or module hubs based on their centrality values, they may not achieve ecological relevance to be considered keystone species if many other nodes around them perform similar functions. For this reason, network analyses of gut microbiomes have recently replaced degree and closeness centralities by betweenness and eigenvector centralities to identify such relevant species. This occurs because healthy gut microbiomes tend to be highly modular, with many redundant nodes per module. In this case, only the removal of species with high betweenness and eigenvector centralities would result in network destabilisation, leading to dysbiosis^{92,274-276}.

Despite this, when the research focus is on detecting host genetic effects on the gut microbiome, degree centrality still seems to be an essential measure. A multi-cohort study with cows has shown, for example, that rumen-associated bacteria with significant heritability values exhibit a higher degree centrality than the non-heritable ones⁸⁸. This suggests that host genetics may have strong links with bacteria that play central roles on a local level, which likely narrows the type of host-bacterial interactions contributing to heritability values. As a consequence, the connection between degree centrality and heritability emphasises the importance of incorporating co-abundance guilds as a microbiome trait likely affected by host polygenic effects.

Secondly, the characterisation of emerging patterns associated with the network itself is crucial for understanding how such interactions, which can be represented by either positive or negative edges, collectively define the final community assembly. This characterisation is mainly represented by measures associated with the topological aspect of the network (e.g., random, scale-free, small-world-like, etc.). These indicators are primarily: density (the proportion of existing edges with respect to all possible edges), modularity (whether there are more edges within modules than between them), transitivity (the average probability that two nodes sharing an edge with a third node are also connected) and the average shortest path length (the average minimum number of edges that connect two nodes)^{229,272}. Based on these, algorithms can determine whether the network presents a random (or Poisson) distribution of edges, a power-law distribution where few hubs concentrate the edges (scale-free topology), or a power-law distribution with short path lengths for most nodes, but with a relevant degree of modularity (small-world-like topology)²²⁹. High transitivity and modularity characterise a specific type of small-world-like topology usually described as a cliquish topology, which contains highly dense modules with redundant nodes. This is a very common topology found in gut microbiomes of healthy individuals and represents, in ecological terms, a community with an elevated degree of niche compartmentalisation²⁷⁶. Another highly indicative measure of this kind of topology is the positive edge percentage (PEP), which tends to be higher in more modular networks, due to increased cooperation between nodes within guilds^{277,278}. On this analytical level, network examinations can be used to demonstrate whether different enterotypes detected in a population under standardised conditions (as done for the identification of alternative stable states in SPF Fischer 344 rats²⁴⁵) exhibit characteristics that can differentiate them.

j) Comparing profiling pipelines

Taking all necessary steps to profile a microbiome from raw metagenomic data and then characterise it based on the principles discussed previously involves the complex orchestration of many bioinformatics processes and tools. While some efforts have been made to define standardised pipelines for microbiome studies,

targeting reproducibility and comparability²⁸⁰⁻²⁸² is still challenging, given the combination of many particularities of a microbiome study, starting with the sequencing method adopted.

For amplicon sequencing data (16S rRNA gene), the go-to pipeline has long been the Quantitative Insights Into Microbial Ecology (QIIME). Its successor, QIIME 2, provides a suite of modules for various steps, including quality control (via DADA2¹⁷² or Deblur¹⁷³ denoising), clustering or exact sequence variant calling, taxonomic assignment using reference databases such as Greengenes^{195,282} or SILVA¹⁷⁵, along with diversity estimation, and visualisation. It is designed to be user-friendly and reproducible. For example, QIIME 2 automatically tracks metadata and parameters through analyses, ensuring that results can be traced and replicated²⁸³. The QIIME 2 platform is also interactive and extensible, supporting plugins for new algorithms and facilitating integration with visualisation tools. Another associated resource, Qiita¹⁵⁶, serves as a web-based microbiome analysis platform and repository, which integrates pipelines like QIIME and allows researchers to reuse standardised workflows on large, public datasets. Qiita emphasises consistent processing to enable meta-analyses across studies, a crucial feature given that results can vary with different bioinformatic handling. However, both QIIME 2 and Qiita have historically focused on metataxonomics (16S/18S amplicons) and have only recently added extensions for whole-shotgun data, including tools such as SHOGUN²⁸⁴ and Woltka²¹².

Shotgun metagenomics requires additional steps and has inspired the development of dedicated pipelines. The bioBakery suite, for example, is a leading pipeline for shotgun microbiome profiling in benchmark studies²⁸⁵. The bioBakery 3, released in 2021 and widely used in numerous studies, integrates enhanced methods for taxonomic profiling (MetaPhlAn 3), functional profiling (HUMAnN 3), and even strain-level analysis (StrainPhlAn)¹⁸⁰. MetaPhlAn 3 utilises an expanded set of clade-specific marker genes to accurately profile microbes at the species level, whereas HUMAnN 3 maps reads first to known species pangenomes and then to protein databases (UniRef²⁰⁴) to quantify gene families and pathways, yielding more accurate and comprehensive profiles compared to earlier approaches. The associated workflows also include utilities for normalisation and statistical analysis, and are

distributed individually as reproducible workflows (i.e., with the creation of environments, such as Docker containers²⁸⁶) to facilitate adoption. Many large-scale projects, including human disease-microbiome studies, now employ bioBakery for its balance between accuracy and efficiency²⁸⁷. However, as discussed earlier, by focusing on marker genes for taxonomic profiling, the MetaPhlAn workflow is not suitable for shallow shotgun data, as it can result in very low mapping ratios.

An alternative approach, motivated by the rise of shallow shotgun sequencing, is the SHOGUN workflow. SHOGUN was developed to profile short-read shotgun data in a modular, scalable, and fast manner, catering to situations where per-sample sequencing depth is limited^{41,284}. It produces both taxonomic profiles and gene-family abundance profiles in one pass, outputting standardised tables that can be directly used for downstream analysis and is built with a plugin system for QIIME 2 and Qiita. A recent evolution of SHOGUN's methodology is Woltka, a pipeline designed for phylogeny-aware analysis of shotgun data, using the Web of Life (WoL) as a reference catalogue²⁸⁸. Instead of clustering reads by predefined taxonomic ranks, Woltka can assign reads to Operational Genomic Units (OGUs), which are essentially species representative genomes that can then be collapsed into higher taxonomic ranks. This fine-grained approach enhances resolution, particularly for shallow shotgun data, as it avoids prematurely grouping reads into broader species groups, as many taxonomic classifiers do, based on the common ancestor approach²¹². By anchoring reads to specific genome contexts, Woltka also enables functional imputation: once reads are mapped to a reference genome, one can infer the presence of gene pathways, even if only a few reads directly align to them. In effect, it marries the taxonomic placement with a gene catalogue, similarly to what PICRUSt do for 16S-based functional profiling, but using actual shotgun reads and a genome tree.

All of this reflects a broader trend of pipelining microbiome analysis, which involves consolidating all steps from raw reads to interpretable outputs in an automated and shareable manner. The benefit is not only the convenience but also reproducibility, with the entire pipeline being version-controlled and shared, reducing lab-to-lab variability in bioinformatics processing. However, it is vital to highlight that each study can result in a combination of factors and circumstances

that restrain methodological options and standardisation. In the previous sections, the advantages and limitations of various approaches have been highlighted, considering the purposes and conditions specified by the current experimental design, which reveals that there is no single solution that fits all. Factors such as the sequencing method, the adoption of a multi-cohort dataset, the specificity of the host under investigation, and the representativeness of available reference catalogues for the target microbiome require optimisations that not all standardised pipelines can deliver.

For instance, even though Woltka was designed for shallow shotgun data, its primary limitation is the use of DNA-to-DNA aligners to map reads to the WoL database, which may result in very low mapping ratios. The reasoning behind this is that such a lean DNA database (containing only 10,575 reference genomes²⁸⁸) reduces the chances of many sequences being mapped for not meeting the required tight thresholds for this kind of alignment, even when parameters are set for high sensitivity. This is a risk that cannot be ignored when the objective is to profile metagenomic data from hosts whose microbiomes are still not so well-characterised. Additionally, dropping multimappers, dividing their counts equally, or assigning them to the lowest common ancestor, which are the options offered by the pipeline, can either reduce the mapping ratio or bias the final counts²⁹⁰⁻²⁹³. On top of that, log-ratio transformations are not included as options to address the compositional nature of the data and no sample filtering is performed based on the final sample depths after removing low-abundant taxa^{291,292}. For this reason, the current project proposes the development of a new pipeline that incorporates the best practices described previously, in order to leverage the use of shallow shotgun data for HS rats' caeca.

k) The advantages of Nextflow

Nextflow is both a workflow engine and a domain-specific language based on Groovy^{293,294} that enables scalable and reproducible pipelines through containerised modules (which means that all software dependencies can be encapsulated into a downloadable environment and used without a tool-by-tool installation). In addition, it allows parallel execution across either high-performance computing (HPC) clusters or cloud platforms²⁹³,

parametrisation (soft coding with parameters defined once in separate files), and resilience (by allowing jobs to be resumed after failures). At the same time, Nextflow pipelines are plain-text scripts and can therefore be version-controlled with Git²⁹⁵.

Some initiatives have leveraged these advantages and promoted reusable, peer-reviewed pipelines, such as the nf-core²⁹⁶. By defining guidelines and sharing best practices, this global community offers curated, high-quality open-source Nextflow pipelines for many bioinformatics analyses. Emerging pipelines for microbiome profiling and characterisation, such as the nf-core/ampliseq, have already been incorporated into the platform, with the intention of unifying 16S and shotgun processing to reduce field fragmentation²⁹⁷. Furthermore, the CRG's Bioinformatics Unit also offers a repository named BioNextflow, which features several workflows commonly adopted in bioinformatics that can be easily integrated into pipelines for microbiome analyses²⁹⁸.

Taking into consideration that none of the current pipelines reunite all of the optimal conditions described to process the shallow shotgun data of HS rats caeca, the primary objectives in this chapter are: to develop a suite of Nextflow pipelines including a first step that processes raw shallow shotgun data, maps and profiles bacterial taxa and functions, and a second step that then characterises these profiles in order to identify their main properties (Objective 2). The pipeline of the second step also includes heritability tests as a final stage and a harmonisation module for comparisons between 16S and shallow shotgun data, but both will be further detailed in Chapter 5.

4.2 Methods

The suite of Nextflow pipelines, named “HERMES-WIRE” (**HER**itable **MicrobiomE** Structure - **W**orkflow for **I**nterpreting host-microbiome **R**elationships & **E**ffects), was divided into four steps. The first two steps (Figure 4) will be described in this chapter and in Chapter 5, while the remaining steps will be described in Chapters 6 and 7. Step 1 begins pre-processing the raw shallow shotgun data and concludes with the first version of the count table, either for taxonomic or functional profiles. Then, Step 2 starts processing this count table (i.e., sample and feature filtering, log-ratio

transformation, etc.) and concludes with heritability tests. Apart from the heritability tests, which will be further detailed in Chapter 5, all the other tasks performed for each step will be described in this Methods section, highlighting the main optimisations that were implemented according to the considerations exposed in the Introduction. Additionally, separate analyses that were executed outside the pipeline will also be described. The main libraries/packages used for custom R and Python scripts will be highlighted in the following sections; however, the complete list can be accessed either in the headers of each script or in the Dockerfiles built for the containers used, which are available on <https://github.com/Baud-lab/hermes-wire>. All plots generated in R that were not associated with specific packages, such as *heatmap*²⁹⁹ or *NetCoMi*²⁷², used *ggplot2* v3.4.4³⁰⁰ and *ggsignif* v0.6.4³⁰¹ (when *p*-values were included for Wilcoxon rank-sum tests comparing boxplots).

Figure 4: Overall scheme of the two-step pipelines developed for the taxonomic and functional profiling of shallow shotgun data, followed by host polygenic effects analysis.

a) Read pre-processing

For the shallow shotgun dataset, reads with poor quality and those contaminated with adapter sequences were trimmed from the paired raw FASTQ files using Trimmomatic v0.32 with default

parameters³⁰². Then, the remaining reads were aligned to the mRatBN7.2 rat reference genome¹⁴⁴, using Bowtie2 v2.4.4³⁰³, and new FASTQ files with no host-associated reads were created using Samtools v1.10, also with default parameters³⁰⁴. A quality check was performed and reported for both raw and trimmed files using FastQC v0.11.9³⁰⁵ and MultiQC v1.10.1³⁰⁶.

b) Taxonomic profiling

To ensure high mapping ratios, DNA-to-protein alignment was employed as a strategy to enhance sensitivity (or recall) to novel sequences. This choice was made considering that amino acid chains tend to present lower variability compared with nucleotide sequences, due to the degenerate nature of the genetic code (i.e., amino acids being coded by different nucleotide codons)³⁰⁷. Thus, all protein FASTA files associated with the 65,703 GTDB 207 genomes^{44,45} defined as representative species had their sequence names replaced by the corresponding genome accession numbers. SeqKit v2.2.0³⁰⁸ was then used to estimate the size of each genome in terms of the total number of amino acids in the corresponding FASTA files. All these databases were concatenated into a final protein catalogue, which was subsequently converted into an index for posterior alignment with the metagenomic data. These steps were created using custom Bash scripts and have not yet been included in the pipeline, even though they are available on the suite's GitHub repository (<https://github.com/Baud-lab/hermes-wire>).

The alignment was performed with Kaiju v1.9.2^{205,309}, using default options, as it has demonstrated a good balance of recall and precision when compared with other commonly used profilers³¹⁰. However, instead of adopting the standard command “kaiju”, the option used was “kaijux”, as it promotes DNA-to-protein alignment without taxonomic classification. This way, the resulting output files reported the direct assignment of genome accession numbers to the reads, following the same OGU principles adopted by Woltka²¹².

Additionally, because many multimappers were observed (i.e., reads with ambiguous genome assignments that shared the same top score), these counts were redistributed to the respective genomes proportionally to the number of read counts obtained by the same

genomes in non-ambiguous alignments, adapting the method employed by the profiler Metalign²⁹⁰ (Figure 5). After this correction, the final counts were scaled (or normalised) as reads-per-mega-amino-acids (RPMA), a recommended approach to minimise the alignment biases caused by genome sizes, when profiling cannot rely on marker genes^{178,307}. This data treatment was performed using custom Python³¹¹ scripts, and all parameters adopted are listed in Annexe II, Supplementary Code S1.

Figure 5: Redistribution of counts for multimappers. A multimapper is a read that received the same top alignment score (S) for two or more genomes. Step 1 of the count redistribution involves counting the number of times the same genomes were assigned to a read uniquely (i.e., no multimappers) and then summing the total counts. Step 2 consists of defining the proportion of unique counts for each genome, relative to the total counts involving only these selected genomes. Finally, the read with an ambiguous assignment will have its count (initially equal to 1) proportionally split between the genomes it mapped (Step 3).

c) Functional profiling

Two tools were considered for shallow shotgun functional profiling: HUMAnN v3.0^{180,312} and PRROMenade^{216,313}. The former is a workflow that utilises DIAMOND³¹⁴ to perform a DNA-to-protein alignment, using the Uniref90 protein catalogue²⁰⁴. Then, it regroups the assigned protein families into MetaCyc reactions and pathways²¹⁰, KOs, ECs, COGs, GOs or CAZymes, resulting in the count tables to be processed in Step 2. The latter is a profiler that utilises IFGP, a catalogue of proteins containing EC annotation²¹³. When aligned to the short reads, it creates EC profiles across all four EC hierarchical levels^{206,216}.

While the IFGP comprises 11.9 million EC-annotated bacterial or viral protein domains²¹⁴⁻²¹⁷, the Uniref90 database contains 109 million proteins from organisms across many different taxonomic domains, with only 4.35% of them being EC-annotated³¹⁵. This results in ~5 million sequences, with only a fraction of them likely belonging to bacteria. Thus, in order to increase the mapping ratio and reduce sparsity, PRROMenade/IFGP was adopted for the shallow shotgun-based functional profiling. Furthermore, it has been reported that among all protein domains in the IFGP catalogue, the median length is 283 amino acids per domain, with the 25th percentile at 167 amino acids²¹⁶. This is consistent with the narrow length distribution of protein domains reported by other studies³¹⁶, compared with the more than 100-fold variation observed for full protein sequences³¹⁷. Therefore, count scaling by domain length was not included in the pipeline, following the precedent of previous studies that used PRROMenade, given the expected ephemeral effects of domain sizes on profiling accuracy^{214,216,318}.

Using the same approach as for species in taxonomic profiling, level 4 EC profiles (EC4) were considered those belonging to the lowest functional rank, while levels 1, 2 and 3 were included as higher-rank classifications. However, unlike taxonomic profiles, which have a direct one-to-one assignment per rank for each OGU, unresolved EC4 functions were counted for higher ranks but not included in EC4 profiles. As a result, four count tables were generated in this step, each containing different read counts. Additionally, the same count redistribution for multimappers, which was applied to Kaiju/GTDB, was deployed for PRROMenade/IFGP. All parameters used are listed in Annexe II, Supplementary Code S1.

d) Matrix processing

Since taxonomic profiles from Step 1 generated only one count table, while functional profiles generated four, two different R scripts were created to handle the matrix processing tasks. Therefore, while taxonomic and functional profiles could be completed simultaneously in Step 1, their analyses were set to be performed one at a time in Step 2, according to the parameter chosen by the user (Annexe II, Supplementary Code S2).

The count matrices were first submitted to sample filtering, based on a list of samples marked as having inconsistent metadata or being probably swapped, according to an adapted version of a protocol published in 2021 for the identification of sample mix-ups and mixtures³¹⁹ (such analysis was performed outside the pipeline). Subsequently, feature filtering was performed, excluding those with an average relative abundance per sample of less than 0.01%, to reduce the presence of false positives. This filtering step was included only for taxonomic profiling, as it is already performed in HERMES-WIRE's Step 1 for functional profiling, where PRROMenade collapses protein domain counts into ECs. Additionally, considering the higher sparsity in gene-centric matrices, not including this filtering step also aimed to minimise the risk of losing low-abundant, relevant functions, which outweighs the risk of mapping false positives. Furthermore, mapping protein domains instead of specific taxa or large proteins provides a broader scope for read counting sensitivity, as many different proteins are expected to map to the same domain.

To proceed with the taxonomic profiling, new matrices were created by collapsing the counts of OGU's into taxonomic ranks (i.e., species, genus, family, order, class, and phylum). However, as pointed out earlier, given the sequential reduction in sample depth across the pipeline due to trimming, the removal of host reads, alignment, and taxa filtering, all samples with fewer than 30,000 reads were discarded after this to avoid spurious results due to low depths. The threshold was defined based on the visual observation of a scatter plot showing the stabilisation of the asymptotic richness (estimated with the package *iNEXT.3D v1.0.1*²⁵⁵) with increasing sample depths (total reads). For EC functional profiles, no threshold was established, as samples were selected solely based on the final sample selection obtained during taxonomic profiling for comparability (Annexe II, Supplementary Code S2).

As the final filtering step, features detected in fewer than 50% of the samples were excluded to retain sufficient phenotypic variance and thereby improve statistical power in the heritability tests. All final matrices were submitted to both CLR transformation, with the inclusion of an offset value of 0.00001 to avoid zeroes, and ILR transformation, using an offset value of 1. The destiny of each

transformed table through the pipeline depended on whether features were compared across samples (e.g., individual features, guilds and networks) or whether whole communities were compared between samples (e.g., β -diversity and enterotypes), respectively. For α -diversity estimation, non-transformed counts were used (Figure 6). Then, as the final profile processing step, all matrices underwent inverse rank normalisation, and the fixed effects of rat sex, sequencing batch, and cohort were regressed out from them (also referred to here as “residualisation”). With this, only the residual values were used for all subsequent analyses, thereby reducing the impact of known covariates.

Figure 6: General scheme of how the final filtered tables (i.e., after the removal of low-prevalent features) would be processed to reduce biases associated with the compositionality of the data and the influence of fixed effects (rat sex, sequencing batch and cohort). Furthermore, the scheme also illustrates that the results of different steps were crossed in separate analyses to assess convergent patterns. PhILR-based data transformation takes hierarchical trees, such as phylogenetic trees, into consideration, refining distance measurements, while one of the α -diversity metrics (Rao’s quadratic index) also incorporates the same trees.

Until this step, a Woltka’s taxonomic count table was also generated within Qiita (Study #11479, Artefact #192967, file “none.biom”), once all FASTQ files used in this project were stored on the platform

and incorporated into its available standard pipeline, which includes Woltka v1.0.4. It is essential to note that while HERMES-WIRE utilises the mRatBN7.2 rat reference genome¹⁴⁴ to remove host reads, the Qiita pipeline uses an older version (Rnor_6.0³²⁰). However, this did not change much the number of available reads, with HERMES-WIRE providing a mean number of 396,350 non-host pairs of reads (minimum = 41,441 and maximum = 4,431,012), while Qiita resulted in a mean number of 375,604 (minimum = 43,342 and maximum = 4,551,272). However, the resulting mapping ratios obtained after the alignments with the respective catalogues were very different: Woltka/WoL resulted in a mapping ratio ~6 times smaller than Kaiju/GTDB. Therefore, Woltka/WoL was not adopted by HERMES-WIRE. It is also imperative to highlight that the resulting count tables generated by both methods included the total number of read counts, whereas all previous counting steps considered pairs of reads. This way, the estimation of mapping ratios involved dividing the final counts by two, including EC profiling.

The results of the alignments were compared using a custom R script, along with a comparative analysis of the isolation sources of each genome mapped by both methods (i.e. GTDB with Kaiju in HERMES-WIRE and WoL with Woltka in Qiita). This second comparison utilised only the same 858 samples as those used in the posterior taxonomic analyses performed by HERMES-WIRE after all sample filtering steps. Consequently, this comparison only included OGU's with mean relative abundances higher than 0.01%. In addition, a Python³¹¹ code was developed to fetch NCBI's BioSample metadata information for each genome accession number, using Biopython v1.85³²¹, and then classify their isolation sources according to the host (or environment) and the tissue (if associated with a host). Such classification was performed based on a custom-made, non-exhaustive dictionary of words (Annexe I, Supplementary Tables S2 and S3), given the lack of standardisation adopted over the last years for metadata submission to NCBI³²². This second analysis aimed to evaluate whether both databases could provide genome references that somehow reflected the bacterial species present in the caeca of HS rats. The two comparisons were conducted outside of the pipeline, but their results are also reported in the Results section.

e) Guild-based profiling

The definition of co-abundance clusters was performed with a custom Python script based on the MicNet toolbox²²⁹, considering only the residual pseudo-relative abundances of the matrix with species counts. Guilds were defined by combining the use of UMAP-learn v0.5.1^{222,223,225} (Cosine distance) and HDBSCAN v0.8.33^{227,228} (Euclidean distance). The same script allowed fine-tuning of the numeric parameters to ensure DBCV > 0.5 and ARI > 0.6 (all adopted parameters are listed in Annexe II, Supplementary Code S2). For bootstrapping, 90% of the samples were resampled without replacement 20 times. Then, a custom R script was used to collapse the species raw read counts (after relative abundance filtering) into guild counts. Following the CLR transformation and the removal of fixed effects, guild residual tables were added to the final taxonomic matrix, with guilds being treated as another microbiome trait, alongside individual taxa, α - and β -diversity values. Species that were not assigned to any cluster were classified as “noise”.

f) Enterotype definition

The population was stratified according to enterotypes using the species residual tables, which had been previously transformed with PhILR v1.20.1 to account for both compositionality and phylogeny²⁵⁸. Then, a custom R script that included the packages factextra v1.0.7³²³ and cluster v2.1.3³²⁴ was deployed to define and assign enterotypes to the samples. First, the optimal number of enterotypes (k) was estimated using the silhouette method, with the Euclidean distance as the default³²⁵. The resulting k value was then used to perform sample enterotype stratification based on k -means clustering, an approach that has been recently adopted for the definition of healthy and unhealthy enterotypes in a longitudinal study with humans²³⁹.

g) Diversity measurements

Following the proposal to create a distance vector that reflects the actual continuous nature of sample distribution into enterotypes, raw count tables were ILR-transformed after the filtering steps, using an R script that contained the package PhILR v1.20.1s²⁵⁸. Then, the data were rank-normalised and residualised for the estimation of

Euclidean distances using the stats package v4.2.1³²⁶ (Figure 6). The first two PCos were extracted using the package ape v5.7.1³²⁷, and the dispersion from the centroid was calculated with the package vegan v2.6.4¹⁶¹. These three measures were then used as the β -diversity features for posterior analyses such as heritability tests. HERMES-WIRE allows the inclusion of non-phylogenetic β -diversity estimation after ILR transformation by including the option “TD” (taxonomic diversity), instead of “PD” (phylogenetic diversity) in the parameters file (field: “diversity_parameter_type”), which are the same options used for α -diversity. However, the TD-based approach was not considered for posterior analyses, given that PhILR was used to define enterotypes, as recommended in recent benchmarking studies²⁶⁶. Instead of a phylogenetic tree, a functional hierarchical tree was created for EC4 functions, taking into consideration the EC hierarchical structure at four levels, using the same custom R script with packages stats v4.1.3³²⁶ and ape v5.7.1³²⁷.

For α -diversity, not only were the asymptotic richness ($q = 0$) and the Shannon index ($q = 1$) estimated, but also the phylogenetic diversity $q = 2$ (Rao’s quadratic index). This choice preserves comparability with other studies, which mostly use the former two metrics for α -diversity analysis, while also incorporating the Rao’s quadratic index as a way to account for phylogenetic relationships between the taxa mapped for each sample. This diversity measure not only tends to reflect functional diversity better, as previously reported in a longitudinal ecological study with fish²⁵⁵, but also has the potential to reveal more profound differences in terms of microbial community states³²⁸, such as considerable variations in F:B ratios. Thus, a custom R script with the package iNEXT.3D v1.0.1²⁵⁵ was used to estimate these three asymptotic α -diversity measures, and the resulting values were rank-normalised and residualised to remove fixed effects (Figure 6).

The final values for both α - and β -diversity were added to the final taxonomic or functional tables, being treated as other microbiome traits. ANOVA and PERMANOVA tests were performed on α - and β -diversity values before and after the removal of fixed effects to assess the significance of known biological and experimental covariates (rat sex, batch and cohort), along with enterotypes. ANOVA was performed using the package stats v4.2.1³²⁶, based on

inverse rank-normalised α -diversity values, while PERMANOVA tests were performed using `vegan` v2.6.4.¹⁶¹

h) Network mapping

Species and EC4 count tables with pseudo-relative abundances were processed using a custom R script with packages `NetCoMi` v1.1.0²⁷², `igraph` v1.4.1³²⁹, and `WGCNA` v1.71³³⁰, along with the assigned guilds and enterotypes for network analyses. Given the need to incorporate such tables in order to ensure that fixed effects did not affect the measurements, options such as `SparCC` or `SPIEC-EASI`^{272,331,332}, commonly used to build networks by taking raw counts and performing CLR-transformation before measuring correlations, could not be used. Thus, the biweight mid-correlation (or “bicolor”)³³³ was the chosen method, keeping the linear interpretability of a Pearson coefficient, while replacing the mean and standard deviation with median-based biweights, which sharply down-weight the few heavy-tailed or zero-inflated entries that can persist after preprocessing. This method has been shown to improve module detection in gene co-expression analysis benchmarks³³³ and is also recommended by `NetCoMi` as an option when CLR-transformation is not going to be applied by the tool²⁷².

First, bicor estimations were performed for the full dataset and all centrality values per feature were calculated (e.g., degree, closeness, betweenness and eigenvector). Then, modules within the network were identified, along with the definition of global and local hubs (i.e., considering the entire network or only the subnetwork of each module), using betweenness and eigenvector centrality values. Later, the same estimations for hub definitions were done for the pre-defined guilds instead of modules. It is crucial to highlight that for these local estimations, the bicor network was built in a weighted manner, preserving the true strength and sign of each association according to the correlation tests, which is essential for edge lengths in plots, strength-sensitive centralities, and module-finding algorithms that rely on the full weighted adjacency matrix (i.e., the square matrix that encodes the finite graph)^{272,330}.

By contrast, classic global-topology measures (e.g., average path length, modularity, transitivity) were defined for binary (or

unweighted) graphs, where edges were represented as either present (1) or absent (0). Dropping the weights after thresholding yields results that remain comparable across datasets and are free from weight-scale artefacts³³⁴, which both NetCoMi and WGCNA recommend^{272,330}.

Second, the entire matrix was divided into two matrices according to the species-based enterotype partitioning, even when the network analysis involved EC4 orthologs. This way, patterns associated with both taxonomic and functional network profiles could be compared between the two exact enterotypes. Therefore, a new network analysis was performed using the two matrices instead of one, with the comparison between them being included through the function “netCompare”. This approach also respected the rule of using weighted-based results for local comparisons and unweighted-based results for topological comparisons. For all networks, internal modules were defined with the option “cluster_walktrap”, which uses edge weights as transition probabilities. This means that community boundaries are defined by the strength of association, not just the presence of edges. In all functional plots, nodes were coloured according to their assigned module. However, for taxonomic plots, nodes were coloured according to the guild to which they belonged.

i) Linking functions and guilds across enterotypes

As a final evaluation, by considering the hypothesis that species guilds are assembled based on ecologically relevant functional wiring, correlation matrices between guilds and EC4 profiles were built for the total dataset and then for subsets of samples partitioned according to their enterotypes. Once the residual matrices generally retained aspects of a normal distribution, even after fitting fixed effects, the Pearson correlation was the chosen method. Then, heatmaps were generated to verify grouping patterns that could reveal associations between different guilds and types of functions, based on the wald.D2 clustering method. Only correlations with $p_{adj} < 0.05$, based on Benjamini-Hochberg (BH) False Discovery Rate (FDR), and $\rho > |0.40|$ were kept (in order to keep the number of functions up to the top 50), and the whole analysis was done separately from the pipeline, using an R script with packages WGCNA v1.73³³⁰ and pheatmap v1.0.12²⁹⁹. EC4s were manually classified into higher-

level pathways according to KEGG²⁰⁷ and MetaCyc²¹⁰ to facilitate their interpretation. A Mantel test for dissimilarity matrices (999 permutations) was performed using the package `vegan` v2.6.10^{161,335} to assess whether the correlation matrices were significantly similar between the two enterotypes. The definition of the bioprocesses used for higher-level functional annotation of EC4s was done based on literature review.

4.3 Results

a) A new solution for shallow shotgun data of less-represented hosts

The HERMES-WIRE suite of Nextflow pipelines was developed and shared in a GitHub repository (<https://github.com/Baud-lab/hermes-wire>), integrating the necessary steps required for microbiome taxonomic and functional characterisation based on shallow shotgun data (Figure 4). The suite was divided into four parts, with the first containing the pre-processing steps of trimming, quality control, removal of host reads, and assignment of bacterial traits through alignment with reference catalogues (taxon-based or EC-based). The second part involves the steps of data filtering, transformation and residualisation; definition of co-abundant guilds, enterotypes, and diversity values, along with network analyses; and estimation of host genetic effects. Such division was intended not only to split the entire computational allocation into two distinct moments, given the high number of steps and parallelisation involved, but also to allow the user to carefully analyse the results of the alignments before defining the parameters of the second part.

The pipelines developed are highly modular and soft-coded, allowing users to choose whether they want to perform a taxonomic or functional analysis and include (or not) the definition of guilds, enterotypes, diversity measures, networks, and heritability. Additionally, Step 2 also offers the option to harmonise samples and features with a second dataset, so comparisons between 16S and shallow shotgun-based profiles can be performed. Furthermore, many parameters can be set from the beginning, such as filtering and significance thresholds, taxonomic and functional ranks, whether the analysis will involve a dataset with pooled cohorts or not, and types

of diversity measurements, allowing the easy comparison of results obtained under different conditions. The parameters defined for each analysis of this chapter are listed in Annexe II, Supplementary Codes S1 and S2. The details about the harmonisation and heritability tests modules will be further explored in Chapter 5.

b) Read trimming, host-read depletion and profiling

In Step 1, although trimming was not a stage with a considerable reduction in reads, the subsequent alignment with host reads revealed that only an average of 45.75% of them did not correspond to rat sequences, indicating considerable contamination of host DNA. Additionally, just over 30% of these reads mapped to GTDB R207, even with all optimisations to ensure high sensitivity (Figure 7A). In Step 2, only 18 of the 1,041 samples were removed during the first sample filtering step, including two pairs identified as swaps. Then, with the abundance filter, of the 58,917 OGU_s mapped by Kaiju/GTDB, only 1,199 remained, which did not significantly affect the scaled read counts, suggesting that very few reads were wrongly assigned to genomes that did not reflect what was present in the HS rat caecum (Figure 7A).

The rarefaction curve plotting the number of expected species (asymptotic α -diversity $q = 0$) with increasing sample depths (total reads) reached an asymptote at roughly 30,000 reads per sample, placing this as the threshold to be used for the removal of reads that were too shallow, being possibly detrimental for posterior analyses (Figure 7B). This filtering step retained 858 samples, which were then used in all subsequent measurements. After collapsing the reads to the higher ranks and filtering low-prevalent taxa, the final numbers of taxa mapped per rank were: 1,190 species, 228 genera, 61 families, 35 orders, 16 classes and 14 phyla.

Figure 7: Sample depth reduction throughout the pipeline (considering only the OGU profile). **A)** Distribution of the number of thousands of pairs of reads per sample in different steps of the pipeline, along with the corresponding filtering rates. It is crucial to note that the mapped reads correspond to the values obtained after scaling read counts by the genome size (total amino acids). **B)** Rarefaction curve of the asymptotic number of species per sample depth (total number of reads) after the removal of low-abundance OGUs. The vertical red line indicates the threshold used to filter out too-shallow samples, and the smaller curve is a zoom-in of the larger one.

By considering only the final 858 samples, the comparison between Kaiju/GTDB and Woltka/WoL mapping ratios revealed that the former was, on average, around 6 times higher than the latter (33.1% against 5.4%, respectively) (Figure 8A). At the same time, for the 1,199 species mapped by Kaiju/GTDB after the relative abundance filtering step, 57% of them did not have their isolation sources mapped (characterised as “undefined”), while 88% of the 421 species mapped by Woltka/WoL received the same classification. Nevertheless, by comparing only those with identifiable isolation sources, it was possible to see that species mapped with Kaiju/GTDB were highly represented by bacteria associated with rodents as hosts (Figure 8B) and the gut as a host tissue (Figure 8C). In contrast, Woltka/WoL-mapped species were more biased towards human samples. The same comparison, with a detailed classification of the isolation source based on the combination of host and tissue, is presented in Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S1.

Figure 8: Comparisons between Kaiju/GTDB and Woltka/WoL species mapping. **A)** Histograms of mapping ratios per sample. **B)** Number of mapped species with known associated hosts. **C)** Number of mapped species with known associated host tissue. All comparisons involve the same 858 samples after filtering out species with low relative abundances (< 0.01%).

In terms of functional profiling, PRROMenade/IFGP presented a considerably higher mapping ratio compared to Kaiju/GTDB (using the 1,023 samples retained after removing the 18 with poor metadata information quality or swaps) (Figure 9A). Given that the same 858 samples used for taxonomic profiling were also considered for the functional-based workflow, the EC4 rarefaction curve also showed

that the selected samples encompassed a stable number of functions (Figure 9B). After filtering out low-prevalence ECs, the final profiles per rank yielded 1,005 EC4, 155 EC3, 55 EC2, and 7 EC1 functions.

Figure 9: Sample depth reduction throughout the pipeline (considering only the EC4 profile). **A)** Distribution of the number of thousands of pairs of reads per sample in different steps of the pipeline, along with the corresponding filtering rates. The mapped reads correspond to the raw read counts, unadjusted for protein domain size. Furthermore, unlike the taxonomic mapping, no abundance filter was applied. **B)** Rarefaction curve of the asymptotic number of EC4s per sample depth (total number of reads) after the selection of the 858 samples used for taxonomic profiling. The vertical red line indicates the minimum sample depth obtained by this dataset (76,960.68 reads), and the smaller curve is a zoom-in of the larger one.

c) Taxonomic and functional characterisation

Although using relative abundances (i.e., proportional counts per sample) is not recommended for statistical analyses involving compositional data, it remains helpful for qualitative observations on how bacterial taxa and functions are distributed within a dataset. Thus, the mean relative abundances of bacterial phyla and EC1 functions were calculated based on non-transformed counts after all filtering steps to assess high-level patterns, both for the whole dataset (Figure 10) and for subsets representing the different fixed effects and enterotypes (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S2).

Figure 10: Stacked bar plots containing the mean relative abundances of bacterial phyla (A) and EC1 protein domains (B) after all feature and sample filtering steps.

Overall, the results showed that nearly 80% of the reads were mapped to bacterial genomes belonging to the phylum Firmicutes A (53%) or Bacteroidota (26%), which corresponded perfectly with the proportions of the classes Clostridia and Bacteroidia, respectively. The most abundant families were Oscillospiraceae (22.2%) and Lachnospiraceae (21.4%), both belonging to the class Clostridia, followed by the families Muribaculaceae (15.1%) and Bacteroidaceae (9.6%), both belonging to the class Bacteroidia. However, at the genus level, *Helicobacter D*, a genus belonging to the phylum Campylobacterota, had the highest relative abundance (7.2%), followed by *Prevotella* (7%), while *Bacteroides*, a remarkably prevalent Bacteroidaceae genus in the gut of mammals, presented a very low mean relative abundance (0.33%). Despite these proportions, the ranking of the top five genera with the highest number of mapped species consisted of the Muribaculaceae *CAG-485* in the first place (with 81 species), followed by *Prevotella* (56 species), *CAG-873* (another Muribaculaceae, with 52 species), *UBA3282* (a Lachnospiraceae, with 51 species) and *Acetatifactor* (also a Lachnospiraceae with 51 species).

Additionally, by considering the differences between the two main phyla (Firmicutes A and Bacteroidota) in the different subgroups of samples represented by the fixed effects batch, sex and cohort, it was

noticeable that even though Firmicutes A tended to be always the most dominant phylum, in some conditions the F:B ratios were reduced. For example, males presented a slight decrease in F:B, compared to females, while MI showed a more balanced F:B, compared to NY, which had an extremely high proportion of Firmicutes A (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S2).

Regarding the relative abundances of bacterial functions, at the EC1 level, most of them belonged to transferases (40%) and ligases (17%). Looking at the figures for the lowest functional rank (EC4), it was possible to note that highly abundant functions represented bacterial housekeeping genes (i.e., genes encoding enzymes indispensable for essential cellular processes), such as DNA polymerases, peptidoglycan glycosyltransferases and glutaminyl-tRNA synthases, which are fundamental for DNA replication, cell-wall synthesis and protein translation, respectively. Furthermore, in contrast to the taxonomic profiles, these proportions tended to be relatively constant across the same subsets based on rat sex, sequencing batches, and cohorts (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S2).

d) Co-abundance guilds

The UMAP-HDBSCAN clustering of bacterial species defined 12 guilds and grouped as “noise” the species that were not included in any of them (DBCV=0.504, ARI=0.61) (Figure 11A). The clusters were then renamed as “guilds”, and their mean relative abundances were estimated in the same way as done for phyla and EC1-level functions (Figure 11B and Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S3).

Figure 11: Definition of guilds. **A)** Two-dimensional UMAP embedding of high-dimensional samples, coloured by HDBSCAN cluster assignment (Euclidean metric). Points sharing a colour/label belong to the same density-based cluster (0-11), with points labelled as “-1” being classified by HDBSCAN as “noise” because they did not belong to any cluster. Axes represent abstract manifold coordinates and do not carry interpretable units or variance percentages. **B)** Stacked bar plot containing the mean relative abundances of bacterial species guilds.

Although only one guild was entirely composed of species from the same genus (Table 1), the guilds tended to reflect assemblies in which species would be phylogenetically close, even when coming from different genera. Guild 7, dominated by Lachnospiraceae, was the guild with the highest number of species and the highest relative abundance, comprising 98% of all Lachnospiraceae species. Guild 11 was the second most abundant, being mainly represented by other families from phylum Firmicutes A, even though it did not contain more species than Guild 1, which occupied the third position in terms of relative abundance. Together with Guilds 3 and 0, their collective relative abundances represented almost 84% of the whole community. Curiously, Guild 0 (which reunited all Campylobacterota species) was only 2pp below Guild 3 (dominated by Bacteroidaceae) in terms of relative abundance, even though it comprised 81% fewer species (Table 1).

Table 1: Characterisation of the guilds: mean relative abundances (%), number of species and the dominant bacterial group:

Guild	Mean relative abundance (%)	Number of species	Dominant group
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Guild 0	8.84	19	Campylobacterota (mostly <i>Helicobacter</i>)
Guild 1	18.84	264	Muribaculaceae (Bacteroidota)
Guild 2	2.80	73	Firmicutes A
Guild 3	10.75	101	Bacteroidaceae (Bacteroidota): All <i>Prevotella</i> and most <i>Bacteroides</i>
Guild 4	1.61	17	Ruminococcaceae (Firmicutes A)
Guild 5	1.95	42	Firmicutes A and Firmicutes
Guild 6	2.13	30	Actinobacteria, Firmicutes and Firmicutes A
Guild 7	25.00	360	Lachnospiraceae (Firmicutes A)
Guild 8	0.72	15	<i>Acetatifactor</i> (Firmicutes A)
Guild 9	3.05	24	Oscillospiraceae (Firmicutes A)
Guild 10	3.82	27	Oscillospiraceae (Firmicutes A)
Guild 11	20.48	149	Oscillospiraceae and Ruminococcaceae (Firmicutes A)

e) Enterotypes and diversity

Two optimal clusters were identified using the silhouette method, resulting in $k = 2$ (Figure 12A). Then, the samples were clustered according to their distances to each centroid (Figure 12B), with 414 samples belonging to Enterotype 1 (Ent1) and 444 samples belonging to Enterotype 2 (Ent2). This relatively balanced distribution was also seen between sexes and cohorts (Figure 12C). Moreover, while the top twenty most abundant EC4 functions barely changed their mean relative abundances between the two enterotypes ($< 0.02\text{pp}$) (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S4), considerable changes were detected among bacterial genera. The most noticeable of them was the substantial drop in the mean relative abundances of *Prevotella* between Enterotypes 1 and 2 ($\sim 5\text{pp}$), followed by a decrease of *Helicobacter D* ($\sim 2\text{pp}$), while few Firmicutes A, such as *Acetatifactor*, *Romboutsia* and *UBA3282* had slight increases ($\sim 1\text{pp}$, $\sim 0.9\text{pp}$ and $\sim 0.7\text{pp}$, respectively) (Figure 12D). These taxonomic changes were also reflected in guild mean relative abundances, with Guild 3 decreasing $\sim 7\text{pp}$ and Guild 0 decreasing $\sim 3\text{pp}$ while Guild 7 elevated $\sim 4\text{pp}$ (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S4). Interestingly, although Guild 1 was mainly represented by Muribaculaceae species, its mean relative abundance increased by $\sim 3\text{pp}$ between Enterotypes 1 and 2, in an opposite direction to that of the Bacteroidaceae-dominated Guild 3. Moreover, although on the genus level the changes in *Prevotella* relative abundances between Ent1 and Ent2

were expressive, the mean relative abundance of the phylum Bacteroidota as a whole was only slightly reduced in Ent2, with a proportional increase in Firmicutes A. In contrast, for EC1-level functions, no apparent changes were noticed (Figure 12E).

Figure 12: Characterisation of the species-based enterotypes. **A)** Silhouette plot highlighting the optimal number of clusters (k) according to the data. **B)** PCA ordination of samples coloured by k -means-derived enterotypes (Enterotype 1 samples are represented by red circles, while blue triangles represent Enterotype 2 samples). Convex hulls indicate cluster boundaries. **C)** Number of samples belonging to each enterotype per cohort (MI and NY) and per rat sex (M=Males, F=Females). **D)** Mean relative abundance (%) of the top 20 most abundant genera per enterotype. Each bar is identified with the colour of the respective phylum the genus belongs to. **E)** Mean relative abundances (proportions) of phyla and EC1-level functions per enterotype.

Before estimating β -diversity with the residualised data, Aitchison distances were calculated immediately after running PhILR on the filtered count table to assess the extent to which the fixed effects affected the relative abundances of both species and EC4 functions. PCoA plots and PERMANOVA tests (999 permutations) were performed for each covariate individually (Figure 13 for species and Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S5 for EC4 functions), revealing that sex, batch, and cohort had significant effects on PhILR-based β -diversity. Cohort was the most critical factor, resulting in an R^2 value of 0.17 for species-based β -diversity and 0.16 for EC4-based β -diversity. Therefore, by applying inverse rank normalisation and then removing these fixed effects through linear regression, they were no longer detected, with the separation of samples by enterotypes being the only sample clustering method that yielded significant PERMANOVA results in both cases (Figure 13D). By working with species-based tables containing pseudo-relative abundances and ordinating their multivariate distances in principal coordinates, it was easy to identify that the first PCo (PCo1) was the coordinate that could be used as a likely continuous metric to display the enterotypes in a linear vector (Figure 13D). This was confirmed by a Wilcoxon rank-sum test, which revealed that the separation of enterotypes based on PCo1 reached significance ($p = 1.79e-139$), with Ent1-like samples represented mainly by negative values and Ent2-like samples by positive values (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S6). It is also important to highlight that by running the Pearson correlation test between all species' pseudo-relative abundances and β -diversity PCo1, *Prevotella* was the only genus with more than 10 species that presented significant correlations (after Bonferroni correction: $p_{adj} < 0.05$) for all species.

Figure 13: PCoA plots for species-based between-sample multivariate distances (β -diversity) before and after the removal of fixed effects from the data (left and right charts, respectively). Each pair of plots identifies the samples according to different characteristics: **A)** PCoA plots with samples separated by animal sex (F = Female and M = Male), with females represented by dark green points and males by light green points. **B)** PCoA plots with samples separated by sequencing batch with multiple colours. **C)** PCoA plots with samples separated by the cohort the sample came from (MI or NY). **D)** PCoA plots with samples separated by the enterotypes detected in the current study (Enterotype 1 as dark red points and Enterotype 2 as orange points). Note that before fitting the known biological and experimental covariates, identifying samples by cohort results in clear separation along the first PCo axis (Figure 13C). In contrast, the same occurs with enterotype-identified samples after fitting the fixed effects (Figure 13D). PERMANOVA p -values are highlighted in small boxes within the plots (Approximate discrete Monte-Carlo p -values for 999 permutations on the top-right side of each plot).

Regarding α -diversity values, three asymptotic measurements were obtained: richness, the Shannon index (or evenness) and the Rao's quadratic index, with the latter representing a hierarchical-aware measure (i.e., phylogenetic). An ANOVA test was performed individually for each of them, comparing differences across all covariates (i.e., the fixed effects: sex, batch and cohort; along with enterotype), both before and after fitting fixed effects for functional (EC4) and taxonomic (species) profiles. As also seen in the β -diversity PERMANOVA tests, the cohort (hereafter referred to as "Study") had the greatest influence on all α -diversity values compared to the other covariates. In this case, the Rao's quadratic

index was the metric with the highest significance level for taxonomic profiles (p -value = $6.94e-45$), while the Shannon index yielded a higher significance level for functional profiles (p -value = $1.98e-14$) (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S4). As expected, no impacts on any α -diversity measures were detected for sex, batch, or study after fitting (p -values = 1).

For the two enterotypes, the α -diversity estimates based on residuals revealed the same pattern, with the Rao's quadratic index yielding the highest significance level for taxonomic profiles (p -value = $3.66e-06$), while the Shannon index had the lowest p -value for functional profiles (p -value = $1.95e-05$) (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S4). Thus, by comparing all α -diversity measures, focusing on study (with fixed effects) and enterotype (without fixed effects), it was possible to identify concordant and discordant patterns (Figure 14).

A)

B)

Figure 14: Boxplots comparing different α -diversity metrics for functional and taxonomic profiles per cohort and enterotype. All comparisons between studies used α -diversity values obtained from data with fixed effects, whereas comparisons between enterotypes used the same data after removing fixed effects. **A)** Functional and taxonomic richness (neutral $q = 0$) per cohort (dark and light blue boxes on the left) and per enterotype (dark red and orange boxes on the right). **B)** Functional and taxonomic Shannon indices (neutral $q = 1$) per cohort (left) and enterotype (right). **C)** Functional and taxonomic Rao's quadratic indices (hierarchical $q = 2$) per cohort (left) and enterotype (right). All p -values were obtained after Wilcoxon rank-sum tests.

In comparisons between cohorts, MI showed the highest species richness (number of different species), with the abundant species tending to be more phylogenetically distant than in NY (Rao's quadratic index), even though neutral species evenness (Shannon index) was lower. In contrast, NY had the highest functional diversity values for all metrics. Similarly, Ent1 showed higher taxonomic richness and phylogenetic breadth, yet its dominant species were so skewed that the Shannon index was lower than that of Ent2. However, unlike the cohort comparisons, Ent1 also had a functionally richer and more even community, but with the core functional protein activities conserved between both enterotypes (Figure 14).

f) Network centrality values and topologies

Firstly, the entire network and its topological properties were analysed, considering the bicor for all 1,190 species and 1,005 EC4 functions across the 858 samples, using the same parameters. The

results for the main network measurements are summarised in Table 2 and are reflected in Figure 15, with the species network being more modular and far less dense than the EC4 network. The taxonomic sub-networks of each co-abundance guild defined by the UMAP-HDBSCAN analysis were also demarcated, along with the sub-networks representing the functional modules assigned by NetCoMi (Annexe III, Supplementary Figures S7 and S8).

Table 2: Comparison of the key network properties between the taxonomic network (species) and the functional network (EC4 functions)

Property	Taxonomic Network	Functional Network	Interpretation
Density	29.60%	91.10%	Functional network almost fully connected
Negative edges	6.00%	0.00%	Competition apparent only at species level
Transitivity	0.757	0.971	Functional co-occurrences form dense triangles
Modularity	0.371	~0	Taxa cluster into modules; functions do not
Communities	13	25	Taxa form clear big modules; functions split into many weak ones
Average path length	1.85	1.09	Information diffuses faster functionally
Hub dominance	0.177	0.107	Influential nodes more evenly distributed in functions
Median edge strength $ r $	0.4	0.73	Stronger overall correlations among functions
Topology classification	Cliquish structure	Cliquish structure	Both networks densely interconnected, especially functionally

Figure 15: Graphical representation of the species (A) and the EC4 (B) networks. Every circle characterises a node (species or EC4 function), and

the lines connecting them symbolise their edges. Green edges denote positive correlations, while red edges represent negative correlations. Furthermore, edge lengths vary with edge weight, approximating nodes when the weight is greater. Edges were included only when correlations exceeded 10%. Node sizes are defined by their eigenvector centrality values, and while the node colours in the taxonomic network correspond to the co-abundance guild to which the node belongs (according to the UMAP-HDBSCAN analysis), the node colours in the functional network represent the network modules assigned to them by NetCoMi. The plots for the sub-networks corresponding to each species guild and EC4 module are presented in Annexe III, Supplementary Figures S7 and S8, which use the same colours as in (A) and (B), respectively.

By mapping the guilds on Figure 15A based on the colours assigned to them (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S7 and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S5), it is possible to note that Guilds 1 and 3 (crimson red and bright leaf green nodes on the lower-right side) are tightly connected as a bigger cluster by positive edges (30% of all nodes and 34% of all edges in the network), while Guilds 7, 8, 9, 10 and 11 (magenta, light violet, indigo, mustard and yellow nodes on the upper-left side) are also clustered by positive edges (48% of all nodes and 62% of all edges in the network), with many negative correlations connecting it with Guilds 1 and 3. On the very upper left side, Guild 4 (spring-mint green) is positively linked to the largest cluster, whereas on the upper right side, Guild 2 (lime green) shows both positive and negative correlations with the two dominant groups, with stronger negative links to the one on the left. Guilds 5 and 6 (sky blue and cornflower blue nodes on the very lower-central side) look diffusely connected by positive edges to the two contrasting groups, along with guild 0 (teal nodes), which seems to be more central in the network, although closer to the largest assembly. Regarding EC4 modules, Module 1 (crimson red) reunited more than 90% of the nodes (805) and 99.6% of the edges (304,731), followed by Module 2, consisting of ~6% of the nodes (50), Module 0 with only 13 nodes and seven modules containing only two nodes each (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S8). Due to this highly dense structure, the subdivision of the EC4 network into modules was deemed irrelevant for subsequent global analyses and for centrality analyses of individual functions.

In the species network, Guild 8 had the highest median species eigenvector, degree and closeness centrality values (0.05, 604 and

1,704, respectively), however, by adopting betweenness and eigenvector as the criteria to identify keystone hubs in the network, 110 species were mapped, with ~55.4% of them belonging to Guild 7, followed by Guild 11 (~24%), both dominated by Firmicutes A. The guilds obtained results that reflected patterns observed for their dominant taxa, with the Acutalibacteraceae family (mostly Guild 8) also having the highest median species eigenvector, degree, and closeness centrality values (0.05, 575.5, and 1,589, respectively). Interestingly, species belonging to the phylum Desulfobacterota I, which had a high number of species classified as ‘noise’ (i.e., not assigned to any cluster), showed the highest median betweenness and closeness centrality scores and ranked second only to Firmicutes A species in degree and eigenvector centralities. This pattern suggests that, rather than forming a cohesive guild of their own, Desulfobacterota I species primarily act as connectors, bridging multiple guilds within the network.

Secondly, comparisons between the taxonomic and functional networks of the two identified enterotypes were also performed to verify whether network properties could reveal more details about their differences. Overall, at the species level, the two enterotypes displayed a moderately different organisation of their motifs (i.e., small, repeatedly occurring wiring patterns of just a few nodes and edges that appear more often than expected by chance and serve as a fundamental structural building block of the network). The graphlet-correlation distance, which indicates the dissimilarity in the organisation of motifs between two networks, was 1.19, and Ent1 contained six extra disconnected components (i.e., a maximal set of nodes in which every one of them can reach every other via at least one path, completely disconnected from all nodes outside the set). Apart from this fragmentation, their global topology changed only marginally; the average dissimilarity remained identical, and the differences in path length, edge density, and natural connectivity amounted to roughly 1% of their absolute scale. Ent1 was slightly denser, more clustered and more modular; yet, the way nodes assembled into communities remained strikingly alike, with the Louvain partitions reaching an adjusted Rand index of 0.82 ($p < 0.001$). A larger share of edges in Ent1 was positive (+7.6 pp), consistent with its slight rise in clustering. By focusing on centrality values for individual nodes, overlap was heterogeneous: eigenvector and betweenness hubs were broadly shared, whereas high-degree

nodes overlapped only weakly, with closeness “bottlenecks” being essentially enterotype-specific (Table 3 and Annexe III Supplementary Figure S9).

By contrast, the functional networks built from EC4 enzyme categories were almost superimposable. Their graphlet-correlation distance was only 0.23, and although Ent1 showed three additional components, the shifts in density, clustering, and robustness were an order of magnitude smaller than in the taxonomic view. Community structure was virtually identical: modularity differed by only 0.0004, and the partitions agreed with an ARI of 0.75 ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, the balance of positive versus negative edges was effectively unchanged. Most central functional nodes were shared: closeness hubs overlapped almost perfectly ($J = 0.92, p < 0.001$), and betweenness hubs overlapped to a lesser but still significant extent, while the identities of degree and eigenvector hubs diverged completely (Table 3 and Annexe III Supplementary Figure S9).

Taken together, these observations suggest that enterotype differences are more pronounced at the taxonomic level than at the functional level. Species assemblages rewire motifs, fragmentation, and certain classes of key nodes, whereas the underlying enzyme-function interaction backbone remains highly conserved, with divergence primarily confined to which enzymes occupy the most connected or influential positions.

Table 3: Comparisons of the primary metrics between Ent1 and Ent2 networks for taxonomic and functional profiles.

Profile	Metric	Value	Significance	Interpretation
	Graphlet Correlation Distance (GCD)	1.19	n/a	The two networks differ moderately in motif structure (GCD \approx 1.19).
Taxonomic (bacterial species)	Difference in the number of components	6.00	n/a	Ent1 contains six more disconnected components than Ent2.
	Difference in average dissimilarity	0.00	n/a	Average pairwise dissimilarity is identical in both networks.
	Difference in average path length	0.07	n/a	Paths in Ent1 are \sim 0.07 steps longer on average.

	Difference in density	0.01	n/a	Ent1 is slightly denser (+0.009).
	Difference in vertex connectivity	0.00	n/a	Vertex connectivity is identical.
	Difference in edge connectivity	0.00	n/a	Edge connectivity is identical.
	Difference in natural connectivity	0.01	n/a	Ent1 is marginally more robust.
	Difference in Positive Edge Proportion	7.56	n/a	Ent1's edges are ~7.6 pp more often positive.
	Difference in clustering coefficient	0.02	n/a	Ent1 is slightly more clustered (+0.017).
	Difference in modularity	0.05	n/a	Communities in Ent1 are moderately more modular.
	Adjusted Rand index of community partitions	0.82	Yes (p < 0.001)	Community structure is highly congruent between networks (ARI ≈ 0.82).
	Jaccard overlap of top degree nodes	0.37	No (p > 0.05)	Roughly one-third of high-degree nodes are shared between networks.
	Jaccard overlap of top betweenness nodes	0.40	Yes (p = 0.004)	Key betweenness hubs are moderately conserved.
	Jaccard overlap of top closeness nodes	0.15	Yes (p < 0.001, lower than random)	Central bottlenecks differ strongly between networks.
	Jaccard overlap of top eigenvector nodes	0.62	Yes (p < 0.001)	Influential nodes are largely shared (J ≈ 0.62).
	Jaccard overlap of top hub scores	0.00	No (p > 0.05)	No hub nodes are shared between the networks.
Functional (bacterial EC4 functions)	Graphlet Correlation Distance (GCD)	0.23	n/a	Motif structure is very similar (GCD ≈ 0.23).
	Difference in the number of components	3.00	n/a	Ent1 contains three more disconnected fragments than Ent2.
	Difference in average dissimilarity	0.00	n/a	Average pairwise dissimilarity is identical in both networks.
	Difference in average path length	0.01	n/a	Paths in Ent1 are ~0.013 steps longer on average.
	Difference in density	0.00	n/a	Ent1 is marginally denser (+0.003).

Difference in vertex connectivity	0.00	n/a	Vertex connectivity is identical.
Difference in edge connectivity	0.00	n/a	Edge connectivity is identical.
Difference in natural connectivity	0.01	n/a	Ent1 is marginally more robust.
Difference in Positive Edge Proportion	0.00	n/a	Positive edges are virtually identical (+0.08 pp).
Difference in clustering coefficient	0.01	n/a	Ent1 is slightly more clustered (+0.007).
Difference in modularity	0.00	n/a	Community modularity is virtually identical (+0.0004).
Adjusted Rand index of community partitions	0.75	Yes ($p < 0.001$)	Community structure is strongly congruent between networks (ARI ≈ 0.75).
Jaccard overlap of top degree nodes	0.00	No ($p > 0.05$)	High-degree nodes are entirely distinct between networks.
Jaccard overlap of top betweenness nodes	0.44	Yes ($p = 0.0013$)	Key betweenness hubs are moderately conserved.
Jaccard overlap of top closeness nodes	0.92	Yes ($p < 0.001$)	Nearly all central bottlenecks are shared between networks.
Jaccard overlap of top eigenvector nodes	0.00	No ($p > 0.05$)	Influential eigenvector hubs are completely different.
Jaccard overlap of top hub scores	0.00	No ($p > 0.05$)	No hub nodes are shared between the networks.

g) Functional aggregation of guilds

From the 1,005 EC4 functions mapped, only 33 remained after the filters applied (Pearson correlation $padj < 0.05$ and $\rho > |0.40|$), resulting in a range from -0.490 to +0.585 ρ values (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S6), resulting in the heatmap shown in Figure 16A.

Figure 16: Heatmaps of Pearson correlations between EC4 functions and the pseudo-relative abundances of guilds. **A)** Heatmap for the correlations across all 858 samples, with EC4 functions being filtered based on correlation p -value < 0.05 and $\rho > |0.40|$, resulting in 33 remaining

functions. **B)** Comparisons of the same correlations when only samples assigned to Ent1 or Ent2 were selected. The dendrograms were defined based on the wald.D2 clustering method.

Most EC4s fall into distinct functional groups, defined here as “Bioprocesses”: cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis, cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis, amino acid & polyamine metabolism, carbohydrate metabolism & storage, redox balance, SCFA & organic acids metabolism, and nucleotide metabolism. Two EC4 entries required curation: the generic “ATPase” EC4 3.6.1.3 is now a deleted umbrella entry with activities redistributed mainly to EC 5.6 (motor proteins) and EC 7 (translocases); and KDO-8-phosphate synthase is correctly annotated as EC4 2.5.1.55 (formerly EC4 4.1.2.16), in line with IUBMB/IntEnz and KEGG/Expasy records (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S6).

Notably, many lipopolysaccharide (LPS) core biosynthesis enzymes were present: KDO-8-P synthase produces 3-deoxy-D-manno-octulosonate for Gram-negative LPS inner core, and ADP-heptose epimerase, in combination with phosphoheptose isomerase, generates L-glycero-D-manno-heptose, also for the LPS core. In contrast, heptose-7-P kinase is involved in S-layer glycan assembly in Gram-positives. At the same time, many cofactor biosynthesis enzymes appeared: MenB, 1,4-dihydroxy-2-naphthoyl-CoA synthase in the menaquinone (vitamin K₂) pathway, UbiA, 4-hydroxybenzoate polyprenyltransferase in ubiquinone (coenzyme Q) biosynthesis, QueC, 7-cyano-7-deazaguanine synthase in queuosine-tRNA modification, and PdxJ, pyridoxine-5'-phosphate synthase in vitamin B₆ biosynthesis. The presence of both quinone pathways suggests the existence of strictly anaerobic (menaquinone-using) and facultative aerobic (ubiquinone-using) microbes in the community. Enzymes like cytochrome c nitrite reductase, NrfA and cytochrome c nitrate reductase, NapA, indicate anaerobic respiration using nitrite and nitrate, respectively, which are typically traits of facultative anaerobes that can respire alternative electron acceptors in the gut. Moreover, multiple amino acid catabolic enzymes were also mapped: urocanase and formiminoglutamate transferase are consecutive steps in histidine degradation; arginine decarboxylase produces agmatine (entry point for polyamine biosynthesis and an acid resistance route); and asparaginase releases

aspartate from asparagine. Two polyamine-related enzymes, carboxynorspermidine decarboxylase and S-adenosylhomocysteine/5'-methylthioadenosine nucleosidase, are noteworthy. The former is essential in *Vibrio* biofilm spermidine production³³⁶, and the latter participates in the methionine salvage cycle and quorum signalling (cleaving S-adenosylhomocysteine and 5'-methylthioadenosine), linking to competitive and communicative fitness³³⁷. Key carbohydrate-utilisation enzymes appeared, such as α -amylase for starch/glycogen breakdown, and glycogen synthase for polymer synthesis and storage in stressful conditions³³⁸. Moreover, inositol-3-phosphate synthase, which is part of myo-inositol biosynthesis and is rare in bacteria, was also present, possibly indicating the presence of Actinobacteriota species in the positively associated guilds³³⁹. Central carbon flow was represented by glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase in glycolysis and 6-phosphogluconolactonase in the pentose phosphate pathway. Finally, 2-oxoglutarate synthase, a ferredoxin-dependent TCA variant enzyme replacing α -ketoglutarate dehydrogenase in obligate anaerobes, reflected an anaerobic TCA shunt³⁴⁰ (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S6).

While Guilds 0, 1, 3, 5, and 6 showed positive correlations with most enzymes associated with the synthesis of Gram-negative cell wall structures, such as LPS, along with the propionate pathway, cofactor/vitamin biosynthesis, amino acid and polyamine metabolism, Guilds 7, 8, 10, and 11 had negative correlations for all of those. Furthermore, Guilds 7 and 8 had mild positive correlations for the generic ATP-based motility or membrane transport systems (EC4 3.6.1.3, with $\rho = 0.06$ and 0.11 , respectively), which was the function with the strongest negative values for Guilds 1 and 3 ($\rho = -0.20$ and -0.37 , respectively). Guilds 2, 4 and 9 occupied an intermediate position with generally weak absolute correlations, compared to the other two guild clusters (Figure 16A). Additionally, within these three major clusters, internal differences for specific EC4s highlighted guild-specific characteristics. For instance, although Guilds 1 and 3 were closer to each other than the rest of the guilds due to shared high correlations with glycogen synthase and dolichol-P-mannosyltransferase, Guild 1 showed a uniquely high correlation with oxalyl-CoA decarboxylase, which was far higher than Guild 3 ($\rho \sim 0.45$ vs 0.10). The same happened with Guild 0, which differed from the Guilds 1, 3, 5, and 6 due to a very high

positive correlation with cytochrome c nitrite and nitrate reductases, as seen in Figure 16A.

Nevertheless, these correlations did not remain the same across enterotypes. Overall, even though the Mantel test (999 permutations) revealed that both guild and EC4 clustering distances were significantly similar between enterotypes (p -value = 0.003 and 0.001, respectively), the functional landscape observed for all samples became either sharper or flatter depending on the enterotype. For the aggregate composed of guilds 0, 1, 3, 5 and 6 (Figure 16A) the average absolute difference between Ent1 _{ρ} and Ent2 _{ρ} ($|\Delta\rho|$) was the highest (0.092, Table 4), being driven by higher positive correlations in Ent1 to EC4 2.1.2.5 (Glutamate formimidoyltransferase), EC4 4.2.1.49 (Urocanate hydratase), and EC4 2.5.1.55 (KDO synthase), together with weaker links to the carbohydrate-associated pair: EC4 3.2.1.1 (α -amylase) and EC4 2.4.1.11 (Glycogen synthase). This means that in Ent1, these guilds were more closely associated with amino acid degradation and LPS-core sugar functions, while being less engaged in starch metabolism. On the contrary, for guilds 7, 8, 10 and 11, the mean $|\Delta\rho|$ was lower (0.074) and dominated by stronger positives to EC4 3.2.1.1, EC4 4.1.1.8 and EC4 3.6.1.3 (i.e., functions associated with carbon metabolism, and ATP consumption for motility or membrane transport). At the same time, this group experienced a relaxation of their negative association with the LPS-core trio (EC4 5.1.3.20, EC4 5.3.1.28, EC4 2.5.1.55), seen in Ent1. Guilds 2, 4 and 9 showed the smallest overall change ($|\Delta\rho| \sim 0.072$) with weak positive values, confirming the pattern identified in the complete data for having almost neutral correlations with the selected functions in both enterotypes. At the individual level, the greatest positive differences were observed in EC4 2.1.2.5 in guild 0 (+0.163), EC4 2.7.1.158 (*Myo*-inositol pentakisphosphate 2-kinase) in guild 1 (+0.101), EC4 4.1.1.8 (Oxalyl-CoA decarboxylase) in guilds 10 and 11 (+0.264 / +0.260, respectively), and EC4 3.1.5.1 (*L*-asparaginase) in guild 3 (+0.205). The most substantial negative shifts included EC4 2.7.1.168 (*D*-glycero- α -*D*-manno-heptose-7-phosphate kinase) in guild 0 (-0.039) and EC4 4.2.1.100 (Cyclohexa-1,5-dienecarbonyl-CoA hydratase) in six different guilds, with the most considerable of them (-0.138) being with guild 11 (Annexe 1, Supplementary Table S7). These results suggest that, rather than a significant whole-community reconfiguration, the functional

properties underlying the enterotype differences may lie in conditions that affect more specific subgroups of gut bacteria.

Table 4: Average absolute, positive and negative $\Delta\rho$ values (Ent1 - Ent2) for the three guild aggregates. Guilds were previously aggregated based on wald.D2 clustering, defined from their correlations with 33 EC4 functions.

Guild aggregate members	Avg. $ \Delta\rho $ across 33 EC4s	Avg. positive $\Delta\rho$ (Ent1 > Ent2)	Avg. negative $\Delta\rho$ (Ent1 < Ent2)
Guilds 0, 1, 3, 5 and 6	0.092	0.074	-0.108
Guilds 7, 8, 10 and 11	0.074	0.078	-0.052
Guilds 2, 4 and 9	0.072	0.083	-0.034

4.4 Discussion, limitations and conclusion

The results showed that the pipelines optimised for shallow shotgun data were able to profile and characterise the caecal microbiome of heterogeneous stock (HS) rats with a resolution and ecological nuance previously attainable only with far deeper sequencing³⁴¹. By integrating protein catalogues, applying stringent filtering, and explicitly removing batch, sex, and cohort effects, the study uncovered two community configurations: one *Prevotella*-rich and one *Prevotella*-poor, which differ in taxonomy, diversity, and network architecture, although they overlap in functional potential. These findings refine current models of gut ecosystem stability, highlight the value of guild-level analyses, and lay the groundwork for investigating host genetic influences on microbiome structure.

a) Profiling HS rat caecal microbiomes with shallow shotgun data

The leading aspect researchers must be aware of when working with shallow shotgun data is that even though targeting 1 million pairs of reads seems a safe minimum threshold, given that previous studies revealed that only 0.5 million was already enough to replicate profiles obtained with ultradeep shotgun data⁴¹, many factors contribute to the reduction of the depth through the profiling pipeline. Firstly, the sequencing step itself does not generate FASTQ files with all raw reads orbiting the target depth. With the HS rat caecal metagenomic shallow data, for example, an average sample depth of 902,683 pairs

of reads was achieved, and 57% of them reached lower values, with a minimum depth of 20,124 pairs of reads, far below the safe threshold of 0.5 million. Then, by removing host genome-associated reads, an average of more than half of the reads were stripped away, which was not expected, based on the range of 5-16% reported by the current literature³⁴²⁻³⁴⁴. This should serve as a warning about using defrost empty caecum samples. Although it was designed to allow the identification of more mucus-associated species than just extracting DNA from the luminal content, the method came with the trade-off of high host contamination.

On top of that, even with the expectation of a high mapping ratio by aligning the remaining reads to the broad GTDB R207 catalogue using a DNA-to-protein approach, only roughly a third of all sequences were mapped. This was six times more than the Web of Life database could recover under its recommended parameters (Figure 8A), which may have occurred because GTDB R207 contained a richer representation of rodent-adapted and gut-adapted species representative genomes (Figures 8B and 8C). It is important to highlight that even though many of these genomes might be first classified as belonging to a certain environment, it does not necessarily mean that they are only found there. The MicrobeAtlas is a web tool that displays, for example, the different isolation sources where certain bacteria were identified, with many species being found in both environmental and host-associated samples^{345,346}. However, even though the high proportion of non-mapped reads reinforced the importance of working with host-specific reference catalogues¹³⁴, by plotting the asymptotic richness per increasing depths, it was possible to notice a safe threshold around 30,000 pairs of reads (after the removal of low-abundant taxa), from which the estimated number of GTDB R207 mapped species tended to stabilise around 1,200 (Figure 7B). Therefore, instead of using raw reads as a reference for the accepted minimum depth, it was fundamental to map all steps in which reads could be lost (Figure 7A) and impose a sample depth-based removal after all previous filtering steps were done, to reduce the illusion that a minimum limit for raw data was enough to avoid biases due to sample depth.

On one hand, despite the low mapping ratio with GTDB R207, the predominance of Firmicutes A and Bacteroidota (Figure 10A) matched earlier caecal taxonomic profiles in laboratory rats,

suggesting that the pipeline retrieved biologically plausible profiles³⁴⁷. On the other hand, using PRROMenade against the IFGP catalogue pushed functional mapping to very high values, reaching an average of more than 90% of reads mapped per sample (Figure 8A). The asymptotic EC4 rarefaction curve levelled well below the one-million-read mark, indicating that the most prevalent enzymes were detected by the profiler (Figure 8B). This was an important result, reinforced by the fact that even the least abundant EC4 function (4.2.1.159, with 0.013% of mean relative abundances across 858 samples) was present in more than 50% of the samples, while ~72% of the mapped functions were detected in all samples.

Because read counts were normalised for genome size across taxonomic profiles and then residualised to remove sex, batch, and cohort effects, downstream statistics were less confounded, making the further characterisation of the microbiome more interpretable from the perspectives of host-to-bacteria and bacteria-to-bacteria relationships. Log-ratio transformations and inverse rank normalisation, followed by linear regression on the fixed effects, effectively erased visible clustering by such technical or biological covariates, with only the enterotype partition remaining significant in terms of α - and β -diversity (Figure 13 and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S4). These steps satisfy recent recommendations that microbiome pipelines should provide the proper count matrix for each kind of analysis (Figure 6)^{249,260,348}.

The pipeline's two-part architecture (Figure 4) proved advantageous as well. Users can pause after the alignment stage, as one would with SHOGUN or Woltka, to inspect mapping statistics and then iterate on parameters for diversity calculations, guild extraction or network building. This flexibility will be essential when the forthcoming HS rat MAG collection becomes available, as incorporating a rodent-specific catalogue should further increase mapping ratios and reduce false positives, allowing future refinements, including the implementation of approaches that promote better specificity, such as DNA-to-DNA profiling.

b) Two worlds, same functions: ecological insights

To dissect the community organisation beyond individual taxa, clusters of co-occurring species representing ecological guilds were defined via UMAP dimensionality reduction and HDBSCAN clustering^{222,227,229} (Figure 11 and Table 1). This analysis revealed 12 guilds, and the guild structure recapitulated known phylogenetic and ecological groupings, resulting in a pattern that aligns with current frameworks for how microbiome assemblies are phylogenetically constrained. For example, one of the largest guilds (Guild 7) was overwhelmingly composed of Lachnospiraceae (Firmicutes A) and accounted for roughly a quarter of the community. Another guild (Guild 3) was dominated by Bacteroidaceae (which, under the GTDB R207 taxonomy, includes *Prevotella* and *Bacteroides* species), while Guild 1 consisted mainly of Muribaculaceae, a family of Bacteroidota commonly found in rodents³⁴⁹. These clustering patterns suggest that taxa within each guild likely occupy similar niches and thus flourish or wane together due to shared phylogenetically based functional redundancy. This phenomenon is broadly documented across many microbiotas and has recently been described as “phylo-niches”³⁵⁰.

Additionally, two enterotypes were revealed: Ent1 was characterised by the high relative abundance of *Prevotella* species, whereas Ent2 was dominated by Firmicutes A families, such as Lachnospiraceae and Oscillospiraceae (Figure 12B). Similar dichotomies (one *Prevotella*-rich, one Firmicutes-rich) have been reported in SPF Fischer 344 rats, pigs, mice and human populations, suggesting the existence of common alternative stable states in mammalian guts^{91,222,240,242-244}. In particular, a study based on three generations of 8,208 Dutch individuals showed that the same bi-model clustering was associated with differences in the relative abundances of *Prevotella copri*²⁵. However, such community-based sample partitioning does not represent rigid, discrete categories, but rather extremes on a continuum of community variation^{226,247,248}. This was evidenced by the phylogenetically aware β -diversity PCo1, which served as a quantitative “enterotype axis” capturing the continuum between these states (Figure 12D and Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S6).

The three α -diversity metrics added depth to this picture. Ent1 harboured significantly more species and Rao’s quadratic diversity, even though its Shannon evenness was lower (Figure 14), indicating

that a *Prevotella* bloom can coexist with a wide phylogenetic breadth. Therefore, the result cautions against relying on evenness-heavy indices alone and supports calls for phylogeny-weighted metrics when assessing gut microbiome diversity states. Functionally, however, the two enterotypes were almost indistinguishable (Figures 12E, 14C and Annexe III Supplementary Figure S4). Transferases and ligases dominated both EC1 profiles, and the top twenty EC4 enzymes differed their relative abundances across enterotypes by less than 0.02pp. This striking functional redundancy mirrored decades of work showing that gut communities buffer pathway loss by recruiting alternative taxa that perform similar biological tasks^{3,76,77,351}. In ecological terms, Ent2 is far from being a “functional desert” compared to Ent1, but rather a taxonomic rearrangement that preserves the operative core.

This observation was consonant with the network analysis, as comparisons between species and EC4 network properties shed light on how that redundancy is organised. While the species network was sparse and highly modular (Table 2 and Figure 15), splitting into connected sub-networks that could be easily assigned to UMAP-HDBSCAN-defined guilds (Figures 11, 15, and Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S7; and Tables 1 and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S5), the functional network was almost entirely connected (Table 2 and Figure 15). Interestingly, two species mega-clusters were detected, aligning closely with slow-growing, less-motile Gram-negative Bacteroidota (Guilds 1 and 3) and fast-growing, more-motile Gram-positive Firmicutes (Guilds 7-11) (Table 1 and Figure 15), a pattern that has been recently demonstrated for mice caecal bacterial networks as well³⁵². This reveals that, at either the guild or network levels, phylogenetically close bacteria tend to co-occur more tightly across hosts. That pattern was reproduced by the heatmap clustering guilds based on their correlations with EC4 functions (Figure 16A). Guilds dominated by Muribaculaceae and Bacteroidaceae species (Guilds 1 and 3, respectively) grouped with other co-abundant clusters that correlated positively to functional signatures of amino-acid and polyamine metabolism, cofactor/vitamin biosynthesis and anaerobic respiration (Figure 16 and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S6). Conversely, the guilds dominated by Firmicutes A that collapsed into the largest network mega-cluster (Table 1 and Figure 15) correlated negatively with such functions but positively with a function normally linked

with ATP consumption for motility and transmembrane transport (Figure 16A and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S6).

Together, the network analysis and correlations between guilds and functions suggest a form of niche compartmentalisation, separating two core phylogenetically-coherent groups associated with distinct functions that, along with existing literature findings, support the hypothesis of a caecal microbiota organisation into a mucus- and a lumen-associated phylo-niches³⁵⁰, with the mucus being dominated by Bacteroidota species and the lumen by Firmicutes A. From a metabolic point of view, for example, it is well documented that Bacteroidota species, such as those belonging to Guild 3 (mainly *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*), possess multiple gene clusters designated as polysaccharide utilisation loci (PULs)^{353,354}. These clusters follow a common structure termed the “Sus-like paradigm”³⁵⁵, which consists of a modular blueprint containing surface glycan-binding lipoproteins, including SusD (Starch utilisation system D) to capture the polymer and decompose it into oligosaccharides; a SusD-associated TonB transporter named SusC, that imports such oligomers; and periplasmic CAZymes that finish depolymerisation before the remaining monosaccharides enter the bacterial central metabolism³⁵⁵. Some of these PULs will then help these bacterial groups degrade and consume either plant glycans (e.g., starch, fibres) or host glycans (e.g., mucins, glycosaminoglycans)^{353,354}.

Although other phylogenetically distant bacteria, such as many Gram-positive Firmicutes A, are also capable of degrading the O-glycans present in the mucus layer through other strategies³⁵⁶, Bacteroidota-specific PULs are known for being transcriptionally regulated in a very refined way, including the commensal colonisation factors (CCF) present in *Bacteroides* and the Small-RNA colonisation factor (SrcF) detected in *Segatella copri* (previously known as *Prevotella copri*)^{357,358}. Additionally, such PULs contain M60-like peptidases and sulfatases, which are important for initiating the serial depolymerisation of O-glycans and are not prevalent in other groups, such as Firmicutes A³⁵⁵. For instance, the genome of *Bacteroides thetaiotaomicron* encodes more sulfatases than of *Akkermansia muciniphila*³⁵⁹, a well-known mucin degrader in humans and commonly cited as a possible new-generation probiotic³⁶⁰.

However, the colonisation of the mucus layer not only involves the ability to degrade mucins but also to attach to them and then cope with the specific physiological conditions imposed by proximity to the epithelial lining (Figure 1). This environment tends to be more hypoxic (i.e., with very low levels of oxygen, but still higher than the anoxic luminal space), less rich in essential vitamins from diet, and implies a higher contact with different host defence systems against bacteria, such as AMPs, ROS, immunoglobulins, and immune system cells^{78,118,119,126,361-365}. Due to that, the positive correlations found in the current investigation between Bacteroidota-associated guilds and EC4 functions linked with Gram-negative cell-surface structural biosynthesis and cofactor/vitamin biosynthesis (Figure 16A and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S6) are reasonably consistent with this hypothesis and mirror the heatmap defined in a 2018 study with pigs that mapped luminal and mucosal bacteria and correlated them with KEGG Pathways³⁶⁶. In this study, 16S-mapped OTUs had stronger positive correlations with energy metabolism, replication and repair pathways in the lumen, suggesting reduced growth in the mucus layer.

Additionally, although HGT is very common among gut bacteria, leading to the transmission of adaptive functions across different taxa, studies have shown that most HGT events actually occur between phylogenetically closely related species^{67,367}. This way, instead of reducing the importance of phylogenetic relationships in ecological dynamics, HGT acts as an additional mechanism to the vertical transmission of genes by cell duplication, reinforcing the differential niche colonisation by distinct evolutionary branches. For instance, some of the referred functions associated with mucus colonisation, such as mucin-degrading CAZymes (or even whole PULs) and the biosynthesis of polysaccharide capsules, tend to be found in mobile genetic elements (MGEs), and their transmission can be stimulated by host physiological changes, such as inflammatory responses^{67,367}, strengthening the functional convergence between co-abundant phylogenetically-close bacteria.

All this converging evidence could explain why, despite some overlap, Bacteroidota and Firmicutes A species appear as opposing network clusters in the caeca of HS rats. A clear indication of the dichotomy between mucosal and luminal colonisation by such phyla

involved the combination of mouse caecal bacteria quantification with 3D imaging of the mucus layer, revealing that Bacteroidota species were more abundant in the interior of mucin-rich crypts, whereas Firmicutes A mostly inhabited the crypt luminal end¹²⁴.

The Bacteroidota/Firmicutes A phylo-niche compartmentalisation hypothesis also provides a conceptual framework for developing an explanation for the differences between enterotypes. Even though both enterotypes shared the same core structure of their species networks (Table 3 and Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S9), Ent1 displayed higher modularity and more positive intra-guild correlations than Ent2, implying stronger niche compartmentalisation. Then, by comparing the heatmaps of the correlations between all guilds and the same EC4 profiles across Ent1 and Ent2 samples (Figure 16B and Annexe 1, Supplementary Table S7), it was possible to notice that the hypothesized mucus/crypt-associated guilds (e.g. Guilds 0, 1, 3, 5 and 6) were more tightly linked to cell-surface remodelling and anaerobic respiration functions in Ent1, while the hypothesized lumen-associated guilds (e.g. Guilds 7-11) had stronger correlations with carbohydrate metabolism and energy consumption, once again, suggesting that in Ent1 their separation into different niches was more accentuated. Nevertheless, the fact that the first group had the largest average absolute difference across all correlations ($|\Delta\rho|$: Ent1 - Ent2), as seen in Table 4, suggests that the mucus/crypt niche might be the one primarily driving the differences between enterotypes, with Ent1 showing greater stability. Therefore, the reduction in the relative abundances of bacteria that depend on this niche (such as *Prevotella*) can be functionally compensated for by other groups that are more functionally versatile, thereby maintaining core functions necessary for a homeostatic gut community to thrive. Thus, the “decoupling” effect between guilds and functions from Ent1 to Ent2 can be a result of their replacement by other taxa capable of performing similar functions.

c) Limitations and conclusion

Several caveats temper these interpretations. For instance, shallow shotgun sequencing still limits strain-level resolution, and an average of almost 70% of reads remained unmapped, a gap that can be filled

by the forthcoming caecal and faecal HS rats-associated MAG catalogue. At the same time, working with compositional data, instead of estimating absolute abundances through QMP, can be managed with the right mathematical techniques; however, it is still not as accurate as the quantitative approach. Furthermore, correlation networks cannot prove direct interactions themselves and should be validated experimentally. The data also lacked temporal depth; whether these rats switch enterotypes or maintain them in the long term is unknown. Lastly, while a few parameters were defined based on refinements, targeting the achievement of quality indicators, such as the parameters adopted for the definition of species guilds, many other parameters, such as few filtering thresholds, were defined based on the default of corresponding tools, benchmarks or, in the case of the last sample filtering step, based on the visual analysis of rarefaction plots. This is something that could also be better explored in the future, in order to improve the pipeline.

However, even with these limitations, the current research was able to offer a fresh lens on the rat gut microbiome, leveraging multiple consolidated approaches to integrate the information provided by them into further analytical layers. This resulted in the detection of convergent patterns, which, once put into perspective with the current scientific literature, led to the development of a theoretical framework centred on the concept of mucosal vs luminal niche compartmentalisation as a driver of functionally and phylogenetically consistent modular assembly. By coupling a low-cost, highly informative sequencing method with modular bioinformatics pipelines, the study revealed how distinct taxonomic assemblies can be associated with shared metabolic repertoires through finely tuned guild structures and network architectures. The logical next question addressed in Chapter 5 is to what extent host genotypes nudge this balance: does genetic variation push rats' caecal communities toward enterotype partitioning, favouring specific taxa and guilds, even though the core functions remain relatively stable? Answering these questions will provide a more comprehensive map of the host genotype-to-bacterial function relationships within the gut ecosystem.

CHAPTER 5. SHALLOW SHOTGUN IMPROVES THE DETECTION OF HOST POLYGENIC EFFECTS

5.1 Introduction

a) Does the sequencing method matter?

As previously discussed in Chapters 1 and 4, 16S sequencing yields rapid, low-cost genus-level inventories but suffers from region-specific primer bias, intragenomic copy number variation, and limited species resolution. Therefore, the resulting amplicon-based profiles tend to be characteristically sparse, displaying lower observed richness and inflating β -diversity distances, compared with shotgun metagenomes^{168,368}. By contrast, the denser abundance matrix produced by shotgun data lowers sparsity, increases effective sample size for rare taxa, and improves the stability of α -diversity estimates¹⁶⁸. Such discrepancies cascade into higher-order descriptors: co-abundance networks inferred from highly sparse datasets, for example, are prone to spurious negative correlations arising from compositional constraints, and enterotype assignments can flip when the underlying dissimilarity metric is recalculated from shotgun reads^{257,272,369}. Due to its affordability, 16S data have dominated Quantitative Genetics studies of the gut microbiome, and, to our knowledge, no publication has reported heritability estimates derived from shallow shotgun data in any species. This leaves open the question of whether improved resolution in shallow shotgun data can reveal stronger host genetic effects.

b) Genetic relatedness and heritability

Heritability, the proportion of phenotypic variance attributable to aggregate genetic differences within a population, can be estimated without pedigree information by modelling phenotypic covariance as a linear function of genome-wide SNP similarity estimated from a GRM^{370,371}. Linear mixed models (LMMs), also known as “variance component models”, implement this framework efficiently by appending random-effect terms to known fixed effects, allowing the model to account for stochastic heterogeneity across multiple

equivalent levels. In this framework, fixed effects capture deterministic shifts of substantive interest (e.g., animal sex, cohorts), whereas random effects are assumed to follow independent Gaussian distributions, with their variances quantifying unexplained heterogeneity across groups. For instance, shared dams and cages across the HS rats studied in the current research can be treated as random effects, given that the model's concern is the overall influence of cohousing and maternal seeding rather than the particular contribution of any single cage or dam compared to the others³⁷². Thus, the model used to explain phenotypic variance is:

$$V_p = Var(X\beta) + \sum_{k=1}^K \sigma_{u_k}^2 + \sigma_e^2$$

Where V_p is the vector representing the observed values of a trait, $Var(X\beta)$ is the systematic variance due to fixed effects (with X being the matrix that encodes factors whose exact coefficients are being taken into account, and β being the vector with those coefficients), $\sum_{k=1}^K \sigma_{u_k}^2$ is the sum of random-effect variance components (with u_k representing each one of those k components), and σ_e^2 is the residual variance (which represents anything not explicit by the model, also termed as noise or the error rate).

In these models, the maximum likelihood (ML) fitting is performed, with V_p corresponding to the dependent variable, while each one of the selected components is treated as an independent variable that will be included or zeroed to generate the “full” and the “null” models used for the likelihood-ratio test (LRT). The result of this test is an LRT statistic value given by $\Lambda = 2(\ell_1 - \ell_0)$, with ℓ_1 and ℓ_0 being the maximised log-likelihood estimates for the full and the null models, respectively. This will then be converted into a p -value that returns the probability of observing an extreme improvement in the full model if the component effect truly contributed with no variance.

However, conventional ML fitting is downward-biased from ignoring the loss of degrees of freedom when estimating fixed effects, which is exacerbated by small or unbalanced samples. Therefore, LMMs are typically fitted using restricted ML (REML)³⁷³. This refinement yields nearly unbiased estimates, even in complex

designs, by first removing the fixed-effect contribution (using residuals) and maximising the likelihood of the reduced data. Because fixed effects are no longer estimated within the likelihood, the degrees of freedom correction largely eliminates downward bias and yields variance component estimates closer to the true population values. This is particularly important when random effects, such as additive genetics, are the components of scientific interest³⁷⁴.

As described in Chapter 3, the definition of GRMs assumes additive effects for all SNPs, with the genotypes being defined as 2, 1 or 0 (“2” being the presence of two copies of the allele that contributes additively to phenotype variance, “1” being the presence of only one copy of such allele and “0” being its total absence). For that reason, it is said that the covariance obtained from the GRM inherits this property by design, in a way that the final estimation of heritability values only corresponds to the host polygenic additive effects on the phenotype (no dominance or epistasis). Due to this characteristic, this metric is also referred to as narrow-sense heritability (or simply h^2)^{370,371}.

Thus, including the additive genetic effects, dams and cages as the random effects that are usually modelled when estimating host polygenic effects on gut bacteria^{25,51}, the final model used for the estimation of h^2 on gut microbiome traits can be described as:

$$\widehat{h_{\text{REML}}^2} = \frac{\widehat{\sigma_a^2}}{\widehat{\sigma_a^2} + \widehat{\sigma_m^2} + \widehat{\sigma_c^2} + \widehat{\sigma_e^2}}$$

Where $\widehat{h_{\text{REML}}^2}$ is the REML-based narrow-heritability value, representing the fraction of total phenotypic variance explained by additive host genetics ($\widehat{\sigma_a^2}$). The total phenotypic variance is given by summing the variances of additive effects ($\widehat{\sigma_a^2}$), maternal effects ($\widehat{\sigma_m^2}$), cohousing effects ($\widehat{\sigma_c^2}$) and noise ($\widehat{\sigma_e^2}$). The hats symbolise that these are all data-based estimates, not real population values. Specifically, the REML algorithm models vector a as a normal distribution $a \sim N(0, \sigma_A^2 A)$, where A is the GRM whose elements record pairwise SNP similarities after centring and allele frequency scaling. The fitted multiplier $\widehat{\sigma_a^2}$, therefore, measures how strongly

those genome-wide similarities translate into phenotypic resemblance^{148,373}.

Estimating host-genetic contributions to microbiome variation has become routine thanks to a mature ecosystem of LMM software. Its canonical implementation comprises GCTA/GREML¹⁴⁸, a C++ package that efficiently performs single-trait REML across cohorts of hundreds of thousands of individuals, offering variance partitioning and genetic correlation options that remain a reference in the field. GEMMMA extends the same framework with Bayesian sparse LMMs and multivariate REML while retaining fast exact inference on the central processing unit (CPU), making it popular for studies that analyse dozens of correlated microbial traits at once³⁷⁵. Additionally, BOLT-LMM and its REML companion BOLT-REML are other LMM tools that approximate the likelihood with conjugate gradients and leave-one-chromosome-out (LOCO) tricks, so they scale to full biobank datasets in hours rather than days, albeit with fewer options for arbitrary random-effect structures³⁷⁶. Additionally, pyLMM/FaST-LMM is another alternative that provides Python bindings for the same spectral algorithms and remains useful for rapid exploratory work or teaching³⁷⁷. LDAK-GBAT broadens the menu by letting users impose customised SNP-weighting schemes and delivers summary-statistic heritability estimation alongside REML on individual-level data³⁷⁸. In terms of cloud-native pipelines, the Hail framework exposes a kinship-based LMM for heritability and GWAS that integrates seamlessly with distributed genotype data structures, though its LMM module is no longer actively developed in Hail v0.2³⁷⁹.

Among these options, LIMIX occupies a niche as a flexible, multi-trait engine built in Python with highly optimised C++ back-ends. It can handle any number of user-supplied covariance matrices, exploits Kronecker-product algebra to accelerate repeated-measures or spatial designs, and fits gradient-based REML, which remains numerically stable for thousands of traits. Benchmarks show that LIMIX matches GCTA's speed for single-trait REML while running roughly ten-times faster for multi-trait analyses, and its Pandas-like API makes it easy to embed in microbial-heritability workflows where individual taxa are treated as traits³⁸⁰.

c) What is known about gut microbiome heritability?

Twin and population studies converge on the view that most human gut taxa (i.e. faecal bacteria) exhibit low but measurable heritability, typically $h^2 < 0.20$, with a long tail of more heritable clades that often belong to the Firmicutes A and Actinobacteria phyla^{33,89}. However, in other animals, such as cows, along with Firmicutes A, Bacteroidota species are also detected as heritable, while in poultry, Proteobacteria is the additional phylum with heritable species²⁷. These phylogenetic differences across diverse hosts are also observed in current studies, which have shown that, despite the almost ubiquitous distribution of Clostridiales (Firmicutes A), due to their high horizontal transfer rates, other gut bacteria tend to coevolve and cospeciate tightly with their hosts³⁸¹⁻³⁸³. This pattern underscores the importance of the genetic association between host and gut commensal bacteria in shaping their evolution³⁸⁴, which reinforces the current paradigm that places the holobiont (host cells and commensals) as a unit of selection¹⁰. A longitudinal investigation of a wild population of baboons revealed, for example, that even under the modulation of seasonal dietary changes, h^2 values estimated for faecal bacteria tend to be significant for almost all taxa, with a phylogenetic component included (i.e., phylogenetically closer bacteria had more similar h^2). This emphasises the idea that host genetics imposes a persistent baseline signal, while diet and other environmental factors modulate the expressivity of that signal through short periods of time⁵⁶.

Beyond genetic effects on microbiome taxonomic features, on one hand, gene-centric functional features, such as CAZyme repertoires, vitamin biosynthesis or secondary metabolite gene clusters, have achieved h^2 values comparable to those of host-encoded complex traits^{25,33}. A recent study mapping microbial structural variation to ABO and FUT2 host loci, for example, has demonstrated that gene structural differences within the same bacterial species are also heritable²⁶. On the other hand, global diversity metrics have shown inconsistent genetic signals: α -diversity heritability rarely exceeds 0.10 and often collapses to zero after accounting for diet, whereas β -diversity axes can carry stronger host genetic components yet are sensitive to the choice of distance metric and sequencing strategy^{54,56}. Interestingly, the same longitudinal study with wild baboons discussed earlier revealed that by running PCoA decomposition of

the obtained Bray-Curtis between-sample dissimilarity (a β -diversity measurement), PCo1 was the microbiome trait with the highest h^2 (21%), while explaining 19% of the variance in the whole community⁵⁶. This mirrors the idea that host genetic control over the gut microbiome evolved as a biotic filter that shapes the interactions between commensal bacteria with each other, and with the host environment in a manner that results in ecological stability through the establishment of phylo-niches^{87,350}. This will then limit intra-individual fluctuating selection, resulting in more predictable outcomes with possible consequences for host health, such as the risk of some bacteria transitioning from commensalism to pathogenicity^{78,245,385}. Furthermore, the same theoretical framework suggests that such a deterministic mechanism will affect sub-groups within the gut community in different ways, with those under host genetic control being more relevant to the whole network⁸⁷. This assumption is in line with recent discoveries that have shown not only higher degree centrality values of heritable bacteria in the core rumen microbiome, but also their association with improved traits in cows⁸⁸.

Even though species co-abundance guilds have become important microbiome features capable of amplifying host effects through the integration of strong and weak associations across multiple taxa^{75,221}, only one study was identified using this approach to detect host genetic effects in pigs²²¹. Meanwhile, enterotypes, which have long been considered environmentally driven, have also been associated with heritable bacteria. The selective breeding of pigs for *Prevotella*-dominated versus *Ruminococcus*-dominated enterotypes⁹¹, as well as Systems Genetics analyses linking the amylase copy number to mouse enterotypes³⁵², indicate that these broad compositional states can respond to host genetic selection pressures.

Additionally, although studies that partition microbiome trait variance into additive genetics, maternal, and cohort strata have often shown that such non-genetic factors can be important confounders³⁷², a multi-generational experiment with mice demonstrated that host genetics overcomes maternal seeding effects in the long term³⁸⁶. In this experiment, researchers mixed two-cell stage embryos from C57BL/6J and BALB/c mice (i.e., two different inbred strains) and implanted them into identical hybrid recipient dams to standardise maternal microbiota. Then, they maintained genotype-separated, non-contact cage lineages for six generations under controlled

housing while profiling gut and skin microbiomes of 334 mice based on 16S data. This revealed that, in the end, the host genotype had an effect size around 0.3 on Bray-Curtis dissimilarity, while the maternal legacy had an effect size of less than 0.05, leading to the conclusion that the host genetic makeup actively shapes the gut microbiome composition after maternal seeding, instead of this being the result of stochastic mechanisms during host development³⁸⁶.

Nevertheless, a major set of unknowns concerns the architecture through which host genes act. Although several studies continue to support the polygenic nature of host genetic effects on gut microbiome traits, GWAS based on faecal samples in humans and other mammals consistently identify the same study-wide loci (LCT and ABO/FUT2) associated with the availability of sugars from diet or host glycans, with a “long tail” of minor effects remaining unknown^{26,28,29,33,387}. In 2022, a research group proposed maximising GWAS statistical power by using a panel of inbred lines derived from a natural hybrid zone of two incipient house-mouse species (targeting dense recombination and uniform environment) and mapping microbial traits taken directly from the caecal mucosal interface, not stool. This approach also involved pre-filtering microbiome traits based on a median abundance of non-zero values greater than 0.2% and a prevalence greater than 25% to reduce multiple testing. Additionally, it also modelled dominance variance components along with additive effects and, using a high-resolution SNP map, narrowed 428 significant loci for 120 taxa to tight intervals containing biologically plausible candidates. With these results, they were able to define part of the genetic architecture of host-bacteria interactions, revealing the importance of several genes, primarily those associated with G-protein-coupled receptor (GPCR) signalling and the innate immune system³⁸³. This expands the possible mechanisms behind polygenic effects on gut bacteria, pointing the way to new approaches that can advance the discovery of causal pathways linking the gut microbiome and host health.

d) A 16S baseline for host genetic effects

A recent multi-cohort study is currently the most comprehensive examination of how host genetics influences caecal communities in HS rats⁵¹. Working across four independently reared colonies (TN1,

TN2, and the same two cohorts studied in the current research: MI and NY), 3,897 animals were genotyped (the same genotyping data described in Chapter 3) and their caecal microbiomes were taxonomically profiled using high-resolution 16S amplicon sequencing data. The profiles revealed the same four most abundant families detected by the shallow shotgun data (Chapter 4), with Lachnospiraceae being the most abundant family, rather than Oscillospiraceae. Then, the study showed that a modest but pervasive layer of additive host control permeates the gut: roughly one in five ASVs carried significant SNP-based h^2 , with the polygenic signal being remarkably consistent despite marked environmental heterogeneity between cohorts. For example, the Spearman correlation of h^2 estimates involving shared taxa between MI and NY had $\rho = 0.31$ ($p_{adj} < 0.05$, after Bonferroni correction). Furthermore, it was also observed that the most heritable bacteria were not necessarily the most abundant, which indicates that the effect size of h^2 values is not a matter of how strong the signal is. Additionally, the study also shared that host polygenetic effects were, in general, comparable to maternal effects but much smaller than cage (or cohousing) effects.

To define whether the same host polygenic effects underpin microbiome variation in the four colonies, the study treated the relative abundances of each taxon in each pair of cohorts as two manifestations of the same host trait expressed in “different environments”. This approach is also termed genetic correlation, a statistic that captures the proportion of additive genetic variance shared across settings³⁸⁸. Genetic correlations require reliable genetic variance estimates; thus, the analysis was restricted to ASVs, as the lowest taxonomic rank level, focusing on those with $h^2 > 5\%$ in both cohorts. The resulting distribution of genetic correlations was strongly positive: the median correlation was ≈ 0.50 with a median standard error (SE) of 0.30, and 60% of estimates remained significant after Storey's FDR correction ($p_{adj} < 0.1$), showing that roughly half of the host-driven variance in microbial abundance was portable between husbandry environments. These values accord with classical Quantitative Genetics theory, which predicts modest genotype-by-environment interaction when genetic correlations stay well above zero³⁸⁸, and mirror observations in other mammals where host genetics explains a detectable yet secondary share of

microbiome variation^{21,25,56}. A striking outlier was an ASV assigned to genus *Anaerotruncus*, whose genetic correlation values were essentially 1 across every pair of cohorts, indicating virtually identical alleles and echoing reports that this genus closely tracks host genomic background^{389,390}. Together, these results reinforced the view that, while environmental context modulates overall community structure, the underlying polygenic architecture of many host-microbe relationships remains largely conserved across diverse laboratory environments.

In order to expand this starting knowledge about the heritability of caecal microbiome traits in HS rats, the main objectives of this chapter are: to assess whether shallow shotgun data can improve the detection of host polygenic effects on taxonomic profiles compared to 16S (Objective 3), and run heritability tests on non-taxonomic shallow shotgun-based profiles (e.g., gene-centric functions, species guilds, and species-based α - and β -diversity) (Objective 4).

5.2 Methods

a) 16S-based taxonomic profiling

Metataxonomic data (16S rRNA) were pre-processed on Qiita¹⁵⁶, with the raw FASTQ files being demultiplexed and trimmed with Qiime v1.9.1^{157,283}. All sequences ended with 150 bp, being then denoised with Deblur v2021.09¹⁷³, using Qiita default parameters for the definition of ASVs. This step also included the placement of ASVs within the Greengenes v13.8 phylogeny²⁸² using SEPP³⁹¹, in order to filter out sequences that did not belong to archaea or bacteria. The remaining ASVs were then mapped to the Greengenes2 v2022.10 database¹⁹⁵, providing the final ASV count table to be used for comparisons with shallow shotgun data. Qiime2 v2023.2.0²⁸³ was used to filter the corresponding taxonomy of all mapped ASVs from the total Greengenes2 taxonomy reference table. It is important to highlight that even though shallow shotgun and 16S taxonomic profiles were built based on different reference catalogues (a marker gene catalogue for 16S and a genome catalogue for shallow shotgun), both databases adopted the same taxonomy defined by the GTDB 207 release, which is an important feature of Greengenes2, compared to its older version¹⁹⁵. The resulting counts table was processed by

HERMES-WIRE in the same manner as the shallow shotgun profile. However, according to the rarefaction curve of asymptotic richness by sample depth, the sample filtering threshold defined for the 16S dataset was 6,000 (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S10).

Before comparing h^2 values, the number of shared taxa, their relative abundances and the sparsity (i.e., proportion of zeroes per sample) of both 16S- and shallow shotgun-based taxonomic profiles were compared with custom R scripts not included yet in the pipeline. Venn diagrams were made using `ggvenn v0.1.10`³⁹² for a visual representation of shared taxa (with sample harmonisation after filtering taxa by prevalence > 50%), and a Spearman correlation was made for the closed geometric mean of each taxon's relative abundance across samples, which was zero-replaced with an offset value of 0.00001, and estimated with `coda.base v0.5.5`³⁹³. Then, these values were transformed (using the negative \log_{10}) for the construction of scatter plots with the base R package `graphics v4.2.1`, following the steps taken in another comparison between 16S and shotgun data¹⁶⁸. Additionally, the phylogenetic β -diversity for the profiles of the shared species between the two methods was estimated using `PhILR v1.24.0`²⁵⁸, and a PERMANOVA test was performed for each to compare the resulting R^2 values of their sample partitioning by cohort.

b) Heritability estimation with HERMES-WIRE

As described in Chapter 4, HERMES-WIRE's Step 2 pipeline combines all individual and community-level traits (i.e., guilds and diversity values) in a single matrix, with each measurement appropriately transformed to account for data compositionality and residualized (no fixed effects) (Figure 6). Using a custom R script with `rhdf5 v2.38.1`³⁹⁴, the pipeline then proceeds by including this phenotype table in the same HDF5 file where the GRM was previously stored (as described in Chapter 3), along with the metadata identification of dams and cages to be used for the estimation of their random effects. This file is processed by custom Python scripts, using `h5py v3.8.0`³⁹⁵ to produce both the full and the null models (with and without additive genetic effects, respectively). Subsequently, the random effects in each model are fit with LIMIX³⁸⁰ (`limix-core v1.0.2` and `limix-lmm v0.1.2`) to provide effect sizes for all of them,

and p -values for additive effects, following LMM/REML principles. Lastly, all results are combined in their corresponding tables for full and null models, and the significance of the estimated h^2 values is defined after Storey's FDR correction ($p_{adj} < 0.1$) in a final R script. Features with significant h^2 values are considered “heritable”. This process occurs for both taxonomic and functional profiles, independently of the sequencing method used to construct the counts table in Step 1, whereas it depends on the parameters adopted by the user in Step 2 (Figure 4 and Annexe II, Supplementary Code S2).

While the full analysis of 858 samples was performed based on these steps for shallow shotgun data only, comparisons between 16S and shallow shotgun taxonomic profiles involved an additional first step to promote dataset harmonisation, ensuring that only samples containing both types of sequencing data were selected. While this would be enough for comparisons in terms of the detection of taxa with significant h^2 values, a taxon harmonisation step was also included to perform pairwise comparisons of h^2 values. The pipeline was configured in a way that the analysis would happen only based on one main counts table at a time, resulting in four runs: two for 16S data (only samples harmonised or samples and taxa harmonised with shallow shotgun data) and two for shallow shotgun data, following the same harmonisation principles (Figure 17). The parameters used for these comparisons are in Annexe II, Supplementary Code S3. It was noted that, due to the lack of dam and cage annotation for some samples, 10 of them were dropped by LIMIX.

Figure 17: Overall scheme of how heritability analyses were performed. **A)** Shallow shotgun-based functional and taxonomic count tables from the Microbiome Profiling Step 1 were used one at a time to make a full heritability panel that also included species guilds along with species and EC4-based α - and β -diversity values as non-taxonomic microbiome traits. **B)** The shallow shotgun-based taxonomic profile was also used for comparisons with the 16S-based profile, after sample harmonisation **(C)** or sample and taxon harmonisation **(D)**. Heritability tests done for 16S or shallow shotgun profiles with only the samples being harmonised were performed for the comparison of the number of heritable taxa detected by each sequencing method **(C)**, while the harmonisation of samples and taxa meant for pairwise comparisons of the h^2 values of taxa mapped by both methods **(D)**.

5.3 Results

a) Shallow shotgun sequencing is more informative

After sample harmonisation (i.e., the selection of common samples that survived the filtering steps for both 16S and shallow shotgun taxonomic profiles), 797 samples remained for the comparison (MI = 441 and NY = 356). Shallow shotgun data mapped many more exclusive species than 16S (1,154 versus 44, respectively), with an overlap of only 2.8% after prevalence filtering (Figure 18A). This trend extended to higher taxonomic ranks, up to the order level, with shallow shotgun and 16S sequencing identifying the same number of exclusive classes and phyla (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S11A). However, even though the 16S dataset mapped fewer taxa, the resulting profiles were generally far sparser than those of their shallow shotgun counterparts in all ranks (Figure 18B and Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S11B). Moreover, despite the significant positive correlation of the \log_{10} (geometric mean counts) of shared species between both methods (Spearman: $\rho = 0.534$, p -value < 0.001) (Figure 18C), when their count tables were used for phylogenetic β -diversity estimation (PhILR), a PERMANOVA test revealed that the shallow shotgun-based profile detected a stronger cohort effect size than 16S ($R^2 \sim 0.31$ and ~ 0.17 , respectively, both with p -values < 0.001). The correlations for the other ranks are shown in Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S11C.

A)

Figure 18: Comparisons between 16S- and shallow shotgun-based taxonomic profiles. **A)** Venn diagrams of genera and species mapped by shallow shotgun and 16S sequencing. **B)** Density of samples according to

their proportion of zeroes (sparsity), comparing values obtained by 16S and shallow shotgun-based genus and species profiles. The boxplots on the top right illustrate the significant differences in the proportion of zeroes between the two methods (Wilcoxon rank-sum test). C) Spearman correlation between the \log_{10} (geometric mean counts) of shared genera and species between both methods (purple dots with a diagonal purple line). Taxa mapped only by shallow shotgun data are represented by green vertical dots, and the ones mapped only by 16S data are represented by red horizontal dots.

Together, these results showed that shallow shotgun was more informative than 16S, not only because it could map more taxa but also because it provided less sparse profiles. Therefore, shallow shotgun-based profiles revealed more substantial cohort effects on phylogenetic β -diversity, which suggests it could also improve the detection of host genetic effects compared to 16S.

b) Shallow shotgun detects more and stronger host polygenic effects

To assess whether shallow shotgun could improve the detection of aggregate host genetic effects compared to 16S, two analyses were performed. Firstly, h^2 was estimated for all taxa mapped with 16S and shallow shotgun sequencing, considering the same samples ($n=797$) and all taxonomic ranks (from species to phylum). Then, the number of taxa with significant h^2 values, also termed as “heritable taxa”, was compared for both methods (Figure 17C). As shown in Figure 19A, shallow shotgun was not only able to map more taxa but also the only method capable of revealing taxa with significant h^2 values, mapping them at the family, genus, and species levels. Secondly, h^2 values estimated only for common taxa mapped by both shallow shotgun and 16S data (corresponding to 164 taxa, from species to phylum) were paired, and the overall differences between them were significant, with higher values being achieved by shallow shotgun sequencing (Figure 19B). These significant differences were also seen in all taxonomic levels, except phylum and order (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure 12)

Figure 19: Comparisons of h^2 significance and intensity between 16S- and shallow shotgun-based taxonomic profiles based on the same samples ($n = 797$). **A)** Total number of mapped taxa per sequencing method and rank after filtering by relative abundance ($> 0.01\%$) and prevalence ($> 50\%$), highlighting the number of heritable taxa (dark blue). **B)** Pairwise comparison of h^2 values between common taxa mapped by both sequencing methods (considering all ranks, from species to phylum). The p -value on the top of the boxes was defined with the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and shows significantly higher h^2 values for the shallow shotgun-based profile. Light blue lines represent h^2 values that were higher in the shallow shotgun profile, while light red lines represent h^2 values that were higher in the 16S profile.

c) Phylogeny drives host polygenic effects on gut microbiome traits

Once shallow shotgun-based taxonomic profiles yielded improved heritability values, also revealing more heritable taxa compared to 16S data, the same 858 samples used previously for characterising the HS rats' caecal microbiome (Chapter 4) were considered for a more in-depth heritability analysis. Firstly, the species profile revealed a similar pattern of variance decomposition to that seen in the previous work with a multi-cohort dataset of 16S caecal samples from HS rats⁵¹: cohousing was the random effect that explained most of the variance in bacterial species pseudo-relative abundances, presenting a very significantly higher effect size compared to additive genetic effects, while the latter also had a significantly higher effect size compared to maternal effects (Figure 20A).

Secondly, no correlation was detected between the mean relative abundances and heritability values, showing that not necessarily highly abundant taxa had higher h^2 values, which was also seen in the cited work⁵¹ (Figure 20B). For example, even though *Helicobacter D* was the genus with the highest mean relative abundance (~7.2%), while *Prevotella* was the second in the rank (with a mean relative abundance of ~6.7%), its h^2 value was ~6% (not significant after Storey's FDR correction). In contrast, *Prevotella* had a significant h^2 value of 11.6%, almost two times higher.

Thirdly, the study using HS rats' caecal 16S data showed that ASVs tended to present higher heritability values than those in the upper ranks⁵¹. However, when heritability was estimated from shallow shotgun data, this pattern was not observed for species, the lowest taxonomic rank with a direct one-to-one correspondence to the OGU profile. Interestingly, at the order level, heritability values tended to be lower than in other ranks (Figure 20C). Despite that, even after multiple-testing correction (Storey's FDR, $p_{adj} < 0.1$), three entire orders were considered heritable, with species representing the rank with the highest number of heritable taxa, followed by genus, family and order, which just tracked the increasing number of mapped taxa in lower ranks (Figure 20D).

Figure 20: Aggregate host genetic effects (h^2) on bacterial taxa. **A)** Proportion of individual taxa variance explained by the random effects included by the LMM: Maternal effects, host additive genetic effects (or h^2), and cohousing effects. **B)** Scatterplot associating species h^2 values with their mean relative abundances. Both values within the box on the top right (ρ and p -value) were estimated based on the Spearman correlation test. **C)** Comparison of the distribution of h^2 values per taxonomic rank, along with the species co-abundance guilds. **D)** Number of traits mapped by each taxonomic rank and guilds, highlighting the ones considered “heritable” (with significant h^2 values after Storey's FDR correction). **E)** Proportion of heritable species per phylum. **F)** Proportion of heritable species per family. **G)** Number of heritable and non-heritable species among the genera with at least one heritable species mapped. **H)** Comparison of species h^2 values per genus, considering only the ones with more than 10 species mapped. **I)** Comparisons of genome sizes (in number of amino acids: AAs) between

heritable and non-heritable species. The p -value was estimated based on a Wilcoxon rank-sum test. **J)** Comparisons of degree centrality between heritable and non-heritable species. The p -value was estimated based on a Wilcoxon rank-sum test. **K)** Proportion of heritable species per guild. **L)** Comparisons of species h^2 values per guild.

By analysing the taxonomic distribution of heritable species, it was noticed that, even though Firmicutes A was the most abundant phylum in the HS rat's caecal microbiota (Figure 10A), the proportion of heritable species was much higher among the Bacteroidota (Figure 20E), representing 72.7% of all heritable species mapped. Moreover, on the family level, despite being the most abundant Bacteroidota family (as reported in Chapter 4), Muribaculaceae only represented 19.2% of all heritable species, while Bacteroidaceae contained 51.5% (Figure 20F). This trend was mainly driven by the *Prevotella* genus, whose ~74% of its 57 mapped species were considered heritable (Figure 20G), including three species with significant h^2 values even after Bonferroni correction ($p_{adj} < 0.05$). The median h^2 value of *Prevotella* species was also the highest among all genera with more than 10 species, followed by *Bacteroides* (~10.3% and ~9.1%, respectively) (Figure 20H).

Complementing such results, by comparing the genome sizes (in number of amino acids due to the DNA-to-protein approach adopted in the profiling method) and the degree centralities of heritable and non-heritable species, it was also possible to observe that heritable species tended to have significantly bigger genomes and higher degree centrality values (Figures 20I-J).

Interestingly, even though the genus *Anaerotruncus* was mapped, along with four *Anaerotruncus* species, none of them were considered heritable. For the comparisons between 16S and shallow shotgun data, the genus *Anaerotruncus* was one of the genera with the highest h^2 values for 16S, while having weak signals at the genus and species levels when using shallow shotgun data, even though they were present in almost 100% of samples.

Following the same patterns observed across taxa, Guild 3, which was dominated by Bacteroidaceae species, was the only guild with significant h^2 (~10%) (Figure 20D), being also the one with the highest proportion of heritable species (Figure 20K) and the one with

the species containing the highest h^2 values (Figure 20L). Although the significance of Guild 3's h^2 value mirrors what was revealed for the main taxa present in this cluster, it was 0.45pp higher than the median h^2 value of all species that integrate it (10.05% and 9.60%, respectively), which might point to a better signal resulting from the collective interaction of those co-abundant bacteria and the host. Notably, at the community level, no α -diversity measurements had significant h^2 values; however, β -diversity PCo1 was considered heritable, with $h^2 \sim 14\%$. It is essential to highlight that this community-level microbiome trait corresponded to the PCoA axis separating the samples into two different enterotypes and was also significantly correlated (Pearson correlation; Bonferroni-corrected $p_{adj} < 0.05$) with all *Prevotella* species (as reported in Chapter 4).

Nevertheless, at the gene-centric functional level, no ECs were considered heritable at any rank, along with all α - and β -diversity measures derived from the EC4 profile. Even though three functions had p -values < 0.01 (EC4 1.1.1.271: GDP-*L*-fucose synthase, EC4 3.5.1.53: *N*-carbamoylputrescine amidase, and EC4 2.5.1.141: heme o synthase, with $h^2 \sim 11.2\%$, $\sim 10.8\%$ and $\sim 9.1\%$, respectively), after BH FDR correction, they were no longer considered significant. Curiously, EC4 1.1.1.271 was the one with the highest h^2 value, and one of the functions whose pseudo-relative abundances had significant positive correlations with the pseudo-relative abundances of assumed mucin-associated guilds, which includes Guild 3 (Figure 16A). Despite the superior mapping ratio obtained for the functional profiling (Figure 9A) and the reduced number of mapped traits after all filtering steps, compared to OGU (1,219 and 1,556, respectively, summing up mapped traits at all ranks), the EC4 profile was significantly more sparse than the OGU profile (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S12), which might have contributed with the lack of functions with significant heritability.

5.4 Discussion, limitations and conclusion

The results provided strong evidence that shallow shotgun metagenomic sequencing can enhance the detection of host polygenic effects on the gut microbiome, addressing limitations inherent to 16S rRNA gene profiling. Shallow shotgun sequencing revealed orders of magnitude more bacterial taxa than 16S (e.g. 1,188 and 78 species,

respectively, in a harmonised sample set) and produced far less sparse abundance profiles (Figure 18). These richer profiles with higher resolution translated into greater power to detect host-genetic associations: when applying identical heritability analyses, only shallow shotgun data yielded taxa with statistically significant SNP-based h^2 , even under a higher multi-testing penalty (Figure 19A). In addition, shallow shotgun data estimated increased h^2 values for most traits mapped by both methods (Figure 19B), representing a substantial improvement over 16S-based studies and a demonstration that shallow shotgun metagenomics can be successfully employed to estimate microbiome heritability. This finding is particularly important, given that 16S-based profiles have dominated the efforts in Quantitative Genetics until now^{21,32}. Consequently, the improved results obtained with shallow shotgun-based taxonomic profiles led to the investigation of a broader range of microbial traits, including functional genes and community-level metrics, which produced novel insights into how host genetics may shape the gut ecosystem.

However, while the current study offered new information that can contribute to a better theoretical framework on host-bacteria interactions, it is vital to highlight its current limitations. One assumption underpinning the heritability analysis performed was that the LMM was appropriately specified for microbiome data, restricting it to only additive genetic effects captured by a SNP-derived GRM. This additive model does not capture dominance or epistatic interactions between host alleles, which can underrepresent the full host-genetic influence. However, given the polygenic architecture of complex traits, additive variance typically accounts for the majority of heritability, serving as a good starting point, with the detection of dominance or epistasis requiring even larger sample sizes and specialised models³⁸³.

Another consideration, also pointed out in Chapter 4, is that microbial relative abundances are compositional and non-independent by nature. Even though compositional artefacts were mitigated by using appropriate data transformation, and known fixed effects were removed by residualizing the inverse rank-normalised counts, the gold standard in the field is still the quantitative approach²⁶⁴⁻²⁶⁶. Furthermore, even though fitting fixed effects does not seem to change much the parametric structure of the normalised data, which is vital for the posterior linear regressions performed by the LMM,

this still needs to be further evaluated systematically, along with the definition of the thresholds and parameters adopted in this step. Another potential issue is the treatment of zero-inflation in microbial counts. While filtering out low-prevalent traits (< 50%), coupled with log-count transformation, alleviates this, the interpretation of h^2 for very sparse traits can be tricky (heritability estimates might be biased downward for extremely zero-inflated variables due to the additional “absence/presence” variance). Encouragingly, the traits identified as heritable (such as *Prevotella* species or Guild 3) were generally those with higher prevalence values across samples, so reliable continuous variation was likely captured in those cases rather than binary presence/absence patterns.

The estimated h^2 values were mostly in the range of 5-15%, which is near the lower limit of what can be safely detected with less than 1,000 subjects⁵⁸. In addition, the relatively liberal significance threshold (Storey's FDR, $p_{adj} < 0.1$) for defining traits as “heritable” aimed to prioritise sensitivity in this exploratory context. It is still possible that a few of the taxa deemed heritable are false discoveries, and conversely, some true heritable taxa might not have reached the chosen threshold. However, the coherence of such results, with the large number of heritable *Prevotella* species, their collective association with other taxa in a heritable guild and a β -diversity axis with significant correlations with all these *Prevotella* spp. mitigates some concern about it, since this would be a remarkable coincidence for multiple false positives to all lie in the same phylogenetic group and yield a consistent ecological story. Still, future replication in independent populations would be ideal.

The multi-cohort 16S study in HS rats⁵¹ provided some important insights that connect to the results obtained. Despite using a different sequencing method and accounting for environmental heterogeneity, the study found that host-genetic effect sizes were modest (in comparison to cage effects), which aligns with current observations from shallow shotgun data. This underlined that environmental and stochastic factors dominate gut microbiome variation, even in a controlled lab setting, a point that guards against overinterpretation of h^2 values. The host's contribution, while statistically significant for specific traits, is a subtler secondary layer. This nuance is crucial, by not suggesting that the host genome rigidly determines the microbiome composition, but rather that it drives the community

within the permissive range allowed by the environment. The previously mentioned longitudinal study with baboons illustrates this well: despite seasonal diet changes, a consistent genetic signal persisted over time, acting as a stable baseline upon which diet-induced fluctuations were superimposed⁵⁶. Likewise, genetic correlations of microbial traits between disparate HS rat colonies were significantly positive (a median of 0.5), indicating that host genetic effects were consistent across different environments to an extent.

It is crucial to note that despite the significant h^2 values for the *Anaerotruncus*-associated ASV, coupled with the strong genetic correlation of its relative abundances across cohorts in the 16S-based study⁵¹, no *Anaerotruncus* species or even the whole genus were considered heritable by the same study or by the current research using shallow shotgun data. With the observation that highly heritable taxa tended to be phylogenetically close to each other, probably meaning shared functions that are essential for survival in host-specific niches, it seemed inconsistent that only one *Anaerotruncus*-associated ASV would present such outstanding results, while no other associated higher ranks would. For instance, shallow shotgun data showed that not only were most *Prevotella* species considered heritable, but also the whole genus and the Bacteroidaceae family, along with other genera and families from close branches. The closest species to *Anaerotruncus* that were considered heritable in the shallow shotgun-based profile were the Oscillospirales *RGIG8773 sp910586535*, *UMGS363 sp900768245* and *RGIG8773 sp017847885*. Thus, taking all of this into consideration, one parsimonious hypothesis that could explain such differences may lie in the approach adopted by Greengenes2 to assign taxonomy to ASVs.

Greengenes2 trains a deep learning model named DEPP³⁹⁶ on the full-length 16S rRNA sequences present in the WoL2 genome phylogeny^{397,398}, which serves as the backbone for inserting short V4 reads¹⁹⁵. Many Oscillospirales lineages, such as *RGIG8773* and *UMGS363*, were only recently split based on the expansion of MAG databases⁴⁴ and, unlike full-close genomes sequenced from isolates, MAGs generally consist of non-closed genomes without full-length 16S rRNA sequences, as they are hard to assemble³⁹⁹. Therefore, the representative species of such genera

lack full-length 16S sequences in the WoL2 backbone, and their V4 fragments are automatically placed on (and inherit the name of) the nearest labelled node^{195,400}. So, given the fact that *Anaerotruncus colihominis* (Accession number GCF_000154565) is the only Oscillospirales represented in the WoL2 16S backbone³⁹⁸, the heritable *Anaerotruncus* ASV detected in the 16S-based study likely pools reads from several closely related genera that the OGU-resolved shotgun pipeline quantifies separately, diluting the host-genetic signal in each OGU. In other words, there is a possibility that the significant heritability detected in the shallow shotgun profile for *RGIG8773* and *UMGS363* species (combined with the relative abundances of other Oscillospiraceae species present in the community) artificially resulted in the remarkable heritability of the *Anaerotruncus* ASV. If this is the case, it is very important to assess whether the heritability of these other species is also consistent across cohorts and whether it involves genetic correlations. If confirmed, even if the 16S pipeline misclassified the *Anaerotruncus* ASV as heritable, the principle that the same polygenic architecture is behind such genetic effects can be maintained as compelling evidence of deterministic mechanisms orchestrating the host control of the microbiome.

An important limitation of using shallow shotgun sequencing for the detection of host genetic effects on the gut microbiome is that while it captures genome-based taxonomic profiles very well, it may be less powerful for detecting consistent variances in the long-tail of rare functional genes, resulting in a significantly sparser profile than the species table (Annexe II, Supplementary Figure S13), despite high average mapping rates (Figure 9). In addition to that, it is also well-known that HGT and functional redundancy result in diverse taxa carrying the same specific function in different genomic configurations^{66,85,351,367}. If the hypothesis that host genetic effects are taxon-specific, meaning that a few particular phylogenetically driven gene combinations are under host selection instead of individual functions, then the simple aggregation of counts by function could blur the real signal. This interpretation cautions against a purely gene-centric view of host-microbiome interactions, echoing critiques in the literature that focusing on genes outside the context of their host organisms can be misleading⁷⁰. Furthermore, the GTDB database for taxonomy, although comprehensive (Figure 8), may not perfectly represent all species/strain variation in the HS rats'

caeca, as evidenced by the low mapping ratio obtained (Figure 7A). Thus, if a heritable commensal was a novel species without an available reference genome, it might have been under-detected or mis-assigned in the current pipeline. The upcoming availability of an HS rat-specific gut bacterial genome catalogue will further improve resolution. For now, an encouraging sign is that even with the support of a generic reference dataset, biologically plausible profiles consistent with the current literature and heritability signals for well-known genera were recovered, indicating that the reference-based approach was effective to some extent.

Ultimately, the host polygenic effects detected with shallow shotgun data exhibited a clear phylogenetic pattern, with no significant isolated functions being detected. Heritable taxa were not randomly scattered across the bacterial tree; instead, they were highly concentrated in the phylum Bacteroidota (Figure 20C), even though Firmicutes A was the most abundant phylum in the rat caecum (Figure 10A). Specifically, the Bacteroidaceae family had the highest proportion of heritable species (Figure 20F), with genus *Prevotella* standing out for presenting the highest proportion of them (Figure 20G) and considerably higher species h^2 values, compared to other genera (Figure 20H). This bias towards Bacteroidaceae in rats differs from patterns reported in human twin or population studies, where the relatively small set of heritable bacteria often includes members of Firmicutes A (mostly Clostridia, such as *Christensenella*^{20,89}) and Actinobacteria (e.g. *Bifidobacterium* spp.), with Bacteroidota being typically less represented as heritable. However, it is essential to highlight that while the current research involved caecal metagenomic data, most studies with humans have analysed stool samples. These are known to have a different microbial profile when compared to metagenomic data of colonic samples from the same individuals, forming separate clusters in β -diversity PCoA analyses, for example⁴⁰¹.

Bacteroidota species are consistently heritable when caecal, colonic and ruminal bacteria are studied in animals. For instance, in a 500-animal study that sequenced pig caecal and faecal contents separately, 67 caecal taxa had $h^2 > 0.15$, with Bacteroidota being the second-most represented phylum among those heritable OTUs across time points⁴⁰². Additionally, a multibreed analysis of chicken caecal 16S data found 15 ASVs whose variance was $\geq 20\%$ explained by

the host genetic makeup, with 8 of them belonging to *Bacteroides*⁴⁰³. These results also mirror ruminant papers⁸⁸, supporting the notion that Bacteroidota lineages can track host genetics when samples come from the place they preferentially live. Given that *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species encode a full toolkit of mucin-glycan CAZymes (e.g., GH33, GH16, GH29, GH95)^{353,354,356}, and because mucus composition is under direct host genetic control (e.g., fucosylation, sialylation, sulphation)^{359,404,405}, it provides a possible mechanistic route for Bacteroidota heritability, which might tie them to the mucosal surface of the intestinal tract, leading to their reduced presence in faecal samples. This dynamic is typically observed in studies comparing *Bacteroides* relative abundances in mucosal and faecal samples from healthy individuals⁴⁰⁶, and was also well exemplified in a study involving patients with IBD in China, which showed the inversion in their abundances in faecal and colonic samples according to the patient stratum (more *Bacteroides* in mucosal samples of healthy individuals and more *Bacteroides* in the faeces of IBD patients)⁴⁰⁷.

The fact that heritable bacteria corresponded to those with higher genome sizes (Figure 20I) connects these results with the recent discovery that species with larger genomes, and consequently more complete metabolic pathways and biosynthetic potential, are the most resilient under stressful conditions, such as IBD, and the primary colonisers in FMT⁶⁵. Given that a considerable number of *Prevotella* and *Bacteroides* species exhibited the highest h^2 values, belonging to the also heritable Guild 3, which was significantly correlated with biosynthesis functions (Figure 16A), it is plausible to assume that these taxa possess the same capabilities. Indeed, the same study reported *Bacteroides* species among the ones with high metabolic independence, and consequently, more resilient and better colonisers. This fact has been broadly pointed out by many studies, showing *Bacteroides* species as being capable of colonising the gut early in life, occupying protected niches such as the mucus-rich crypts and behaving as a reservoir to repopulate the gut and allow the colonisation of other bacteria after disturbances^{118,119,218,358}.

Furthermore, because the animals were kept in a controlled setting with a standard chow diet and homogenous laboratory environment, the aggregate host genetic effects on *Prevotella* spp. might have come through strongly due to reduced dietary effects, which are

known to be very influential to *Prevotella* abundances, a biomarker of fibre-rich diets, even though species from this genus are also able to degrade host glycans^{63,353,408,409}. The fact that *Prevotella* species showed some of the highest h^2 values of all species mapped and collectively constituted more than 40% of all heritable bacteria implies that this genus has a special relationship with host genetics in the rat caecum. The same can be said about genus *Bacteroides*, of which 40% of the 15 mapped species were considered heritable, presenting non-significant differences in terms of species h^2 values compared to *Prevotella* (Figure 20H).

The detection of significant h^2 values at the guild and community levels reinforced the idea that host genetic effects in specific phylogenetic groups can also be reflected in their placement within the microbiota network^{88,91}. This was exemplified by the fact that the only heritable guild (Guild 3) was a cluster overwhelmingly dominated by Bacteroidaceae (78% of its member species, including all *Prevotella* spp. and most *Bacteroides*). Curiously, Guild 3's h^2 value slightly exceeded the median of its constituent species, which suggests that such aggregation might amplify the host signal. Furthermore, Guild 3 was the group with the highest proportion of heritable species (Figure 20K) and contained the species with the top h^2 values (Figure 20L), so its significance was not surprising; instead, it reinforced that the host polygenic effects were concentrated on a specific phylogenetic group, the Bacteroidaceae. This result mirrors the discovery that a Bacteroidota-enriched co-occurrence core network in the rumen of cows comprehends a high number of heritable taxa⁸⁸. Curiously, the same research also revealed that heritable bacteria were the ones with significantly higher degree centrality values, a finding replicated by the current study (Figure 20J). However, to assume that being under stronger host control is the fundamental factor associated with degree centrality and not just a non-associated characteristic of the heritable phylogenetic group, it is crucial to evaluate whether heritable species within the same genus tend to be the ones with more local connections (further explored in Chapter 6).

The current findings also suggest that by affecting a large consortium of Bacteroidaceae species that co-occur in those rats, host genetic effects essentially push an individual's microbiome toward a "*Prevotella*-rich" community type versus a "*Prevotella*-poor"

alternative state. This interpretation comes from the observation that β -diversity (PCo1) was also heritable ($h^2 \sim 14\%$), being the axis that separates samples into the two major enterotypes characterised in Chapter 4. The fact that the same PCo1 is strongly associated with *Prevotella*, having significant Pearson correlations (after Bonferroni adjustment; $p_{adj} < 0.05$) with the pseudo-relative abundances of every *Prevotella* species, reinforces this connection (as reported in Chapter 4). This mirrors observations from the longitudinal study of wild baboons, where the microbiome's β -diversity primary axis of variation had the highest heritability ($\sim 21\%$) of all microbiome traits tested⁵⁶. Together, these results support a model in which host genetic differences bias the gut ecosystem toward one of two stable configurations, while concurrently affecting many members of a particular ecological guild. This emerging picture is highly consistent with the “phylo-niche” hypothesis of host-microbiome interactions³⁵⁰, adding a new layer of evidence sustaining the discussion started in Chapter 4.

From a broader perspective, such findings fit into the emerging understanding that the host genetic architecture influences the microbiome in a highly polygenic manner^{51,383}. This underscores that, as opposed to a few major effect genes, many loci of small effects underlie the host control of the microbiome, being consistent with most microbiome GWAS being limited in the identification of large numbers of genome-wide significant hits. The exceptions, such as LCT or FUT2, highlight that when associations are found, they often make biological sense by affecting nutrient availability for specific taxa²⁹, however, they still cannot explain alone the consistent observations that the host genetics affect the community as a whole, either based on significant β -diversity PCo1 h^2 values⁵⁶ or due to the fixation of enterotypes in a population by the artificial selection of heritable species⁹¹. Therefore, the current results encourage a synthesis of ecological and genetic viewpoints by suggesting that the host exerts selective pressure on specific phylogenetically driven guilds, probably by modulating multiple environmental conditions within the niche where they thrive best.

Coupling these results with the functional wiring of guilds explored in Chapter 4, it is hypothesised that a central host-driven niche could be the mucus-rich crypts. Such a targeted effect can be interpreted as the host acting as a biotic filter, modulating, for example, the

substrates available, the mucosal immunity, or even morphological conditions that promote a stable co-occurring set of commensals with the proper genetic background to adapt to them. That said, mapping the genes enriched in species with higher h^2 values within the same genera is essential to reveal which bacterial features enable them to be better adapted to such host polygenic effects, which will be further explored in Chapter 6.

CHAPTER 6. DECIPHERING HERITABLE BACTERIA TO MAP INFLUENTIAL HOST GENES

6.1 Introduction

a) Caecal niche compartmentalisation beyond mucin

Commensal bacteria do not distribute uniformly across the gut, being primarily stratified across three transversal habitats: the nutrient-rich, turbulent and competitive lumen, the adherent mucus surface, and the sheltered crypts, each governed by intersecting physical and immunological gradients^{118,119,365,410}. Along the intestine of mammals, spatial ‘rules’ emerge from local flow regimes, epithelial gene programs, and host-microbial feedback loops, generating reproducible “biogeographies” detectable with modern spatial omics and imaging^{124,411}, which makes colonisation a systems-level outcome rather than a mere consequence of mucus composition.

The lumen is nutrient-rich, containing dietary polymers (e.g. starch, fibres, etc.) and bile-modified substrates, but very unstable. Transit time, pH, and water content shift daily among individuals, altering fermentation outputs and selecting for different trophic guilds even under similar diets (e.g., saccharolysis vs. proteolysis)²³⁸. In contrast, the mucus surface is a gel habitat structured mainly by mucin O-glycans; however, the architecture is region-dependent and more penetrable in the proximal colon and caecum than in the distal colon, where the mucus tends to be separated into inner and outer layers^{412,413}. Mucus turnover is rapid, and its viscoelasticity responds to ions, pH, and microbial enzymes, making it a dynamic scaffold rather than a static wall^{126,412,414}. Deeper still, mucus-rich crypts are narrow sacs abutting epithelial stem cells. They are typically hypoxic, enriched for host-derived glycans and cell debris, bathed in secreted IgA and antimicrobial AMPs, and subject to local immune programs that vary by gut segment. This niche tends to be more temporally stable than the lumen and can maintain spatially organised “patches” of colonised vs. non-colonised crypts after perturbations^{118,119,124,125,365}. Underneath the crypt mucus layer, epithelial cells also benefit from the extra protection of the

glycocalyx, which consists of glycolipids and glycoproteins, such as glycosaminoglycans (GAGs)⁴¹⁵, including chondroitin sulphates (CS), a GAG also found in the maternal breastmilk⁴¹⁶. These GAGs are shed from the epithelial lining during the normal cellular turnover, being another adhesion site and carbon source for specific groups of mucus colonisers, such as *Bacteroides*⁴¹⁷.

Multiple other gradients jointly shape these habitats. Oxygen diffuses from the epithelium into the mucus and is rapidly consumed by host cells in aerobic respiration, creating steep redox gradients across tens to hundreds of micrometres. While most is known about the detrimental effect of small doses of oxygen to strict anaerobes due to a reduced ability to deal with the ROS formed during aerobic metabolism, many gut bacteria actually tend to be harmed by oxygen itself due to its deleterious effects on the redox activity of many key enzymes in their metabolism^{363,418,419}. This favours facultative anaerobes or obligate anaerobes that harbour oxygen-detoxifying or tolerance strategies near the hypoxic epithelium, while keeping the bulk lumen strictly anaerobic^{126,420,421}. Such segregation is, in principle, a conserved strategy across many animals. In the fruit fly (*Drosophila melanogaster*), the peritrophic matrix and Duox-derived ROS create compartmentalised, time-varying antimicrobial zones that preserve indigenous symbionts while restricting pathogens, an elegant demonstration that chemical barriers and redox micro-gradients sculpt spatial microbiotas even in simpler guts⁴²¹⁻⁴²³.

Additionally, the immune landscape imposes another gradient filter: RegIII γ and additional AMPs enforce a bacteria-free buffer over the epithelium, for example, and secretory IgA binds and agglomerates growing bacterial cells, with region-specific host epithelial cells modulating these mechanisms along the whole mucosa^{365,425,426}, which can be specific for different types of bacteria. On one hand, the leptin ZG16 can be secreted by the host, which is a globular protein attached to sulphated GAGs and mannose, binding the peptidoglycan of Gram-positive species and preventing mucus penetration through cell aggregation^{427,428}. On the other hand, another protein named RELM β , can also be secreted, targeting lipids of the outer membrane of Gram-negative species, creating pores that kill them⁴²⁹. Furthermore, inflammatory responses can also be promoted, releasing ROS, recruiting immune cells and generating inflammasomes in extreme cases, which are multiprotein complexes

in the cytoplasm of immune and non-immune cells that trigger inflammatory responses and cell death, mainly due to the presence of the proteolytic caspases^{430,431}.

All responses to bacterial MAMPs that trigger such responses by the epithelial cells correspond to the identification of such structures by pattern recognition receptors (PRRs) such as toll-like receptors (TLRs), which are transmembrane proteins that recognise MAMPs outside the cell, and nucleotide-binding oligomerisation domain-containing proteins (NODs), which are cytoplasmic proteins capable of detecting MAMPs inside the cells^{432,433}. The latter include NOD-like receptor-pyrin-containing proteins (NLPRs), which are the sensors responsible for the assembly of inflammasomes. While most epithelial cell types are capable of both detecting and responding to surrounding MAMPs, they can also communicate to each other through cytokines and chemokines, which can also reach immune cells in the stroma below the epithelial lining too¹²⁹. Together, all these physical (flow, viscosity), chemical (pH, oxygen/ROS, ions), and immunological (AMPs, IgA, inflammasomes) variables produce the observed biogeographical structure in a way that mucin composition is necessary but far from being sufficient to explain host polygenic effects alone⁷⁸.

High-resolution 3D imaging has recently shown the direct quantification of these distribution patterns in the mouse caecum. The analysis revealed that crypt colonisation occurs in clusters (with adjacent colonised crypts also being surrounded by unoccupied ones), and this spatial pattern persists even after antibiotic regimens that selectively deplete the Muribaculaceae (or Bacteroidota species in general), implying that local host context and inter-crypt dynamics stabilise the niche beyond community membership alone¹²⁴. Spatial multi-omics has further revealed segment-specific immune programs (notably in the mid colon) that adapt structural cells to local microbial cues, reinforcing the idea that cross-sectional distributions reflect coordinated host-microbe patterning rather than just passive attachment to mucus^{365,411}.

Nevertheless, contradictory findings on what taxa tend to occupy each niche in the mouse caecum expose the importance of methodological precaution in microbiome studies. For instance, a 2020 study reported that mouse caecal crypt communities were

enriched with Proteobacteria and Deferribacteres (specifically *Mucispirillum*), with Bacteroidota and Firmicutes A predominating in the lumen¹²⁵, the contrary of what posterior imaging and spatial assays revealed for mucus-adjacent niches¹²⁴. Several methodological features likely contributed, such as low-biomass sampling of crypts, requiring extensive contaminant subtraction (11.6% of exact sequence variants in environmental controls) and raising the risk of over-correction, or skewing toward lab-typical Proteobacteria; significant extraction batch effects requiring statistical control, again consistent with low-signal, high-noise samples; mechanical microdissection and pooled 16S and shotgun profiling without orthogonal spatial validation beyond targeted fluorescence in situ hybridisation (FISH) for *Mucispirillum*, which does not allow generalisation for the whole crypt community; and the study's broader focus on how multiple surgical stress factors (fasting, antibiotics and hepatectomy) collapses compartmentalization, potentially conflating baseline niche signals with perturbation responses. In contrast, the 3D-imaging workflow performed in 2022 preserved native tissue orientation, quantified crypt-resolved colonisation, and cross-validated taxa with multiplexed probes, yielding a spatially coherent pattern robust to antibiotic filtering of specific clades. Methodological spatial fidelity and biomass constraints thus plausibly explain the discrepancy¹²⁴.

Additionally, rodent caecum peculiarities help explain such biogeographies. The caecum is a fermentation chamber relatively insulated from the faecal stream, with region-dependent mucus architecture that is less stably stratified than in the distal colon and often more penetrable to bacteria^{125,412,414} (as discussed in Chapter 3). That combination: stable hypoxia, host-glycan availability, IgA and AMP exposure, and reduced mucus shear due to the flow stream, favours taxa with mucin adhesion and foraging; oxygen-detoxifying; and immune-evasion strategies, properties common in Bacteroidota (e.g., *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella*) and other mucus specialists. Therefore, the stability of caecal crypt homeostasis, and consequently better niche compartmentalisation, in rats could be the polygenic-based phenotype influencing the bacterial relative abundances toward Bacteroidota species that are capable of persistent crypt-proximal associations, while fast-growing Firmicutes A are more prevalent in the dynamic lumen, along with

mucus-surface specialists, being consistent with a multi-variable colonisation model^{412,414,434}.

b) Factors shaping the crypt niche dynamics

Crypts are the engine rooms of the intestinal lining. In mammals, the epithelial sheet is replaced in just a few days as stem cells at the crypt base divide and push new cells upward; this rapid turnover underpins barrier integrity but requires a tightly protected niche to keep stem cells safe and properly instructed. Classic and recent syntheses agree that WNT, NOTCH, EGF and BMP/TGF- β signals, delivered by epithelial and stromal partners, such as smooth muscle and fibroblasts, position stem cells at the crypt base and choreograph their differentiation, achieving whole-epithelium renewal roughly every 3-5 days⁴³⁵. Crypts themselves arise postnatally by a defined morphogenetic program: an apical constriction and hinge formation sculpt invaginations that later compartmentalise niche and non-niche territories, illustrating that crypt architecture is not incidental but a built feature that sustains niche function⁴³⁶. The crypt is resilient and plastic: when key pathways are perturbed (for example, transient NOTCH inhibition), crypt cell types remodel quickly and restore stem-cell support, emphasising a dynamic, multi-cell cooperation rather than a fixed cell roster⁴³⁷.

Specialised secretory cells at the crypt bottom help enforce microbial control while feeding stem-cell programs. In the small intestine, Paneth cells deliver AMPs (e.g., α -defensins, lysozyme) and other niche factors. They are now known to respond to IL-22 in order to mature and sustain antimicrobial and WNT outputs, linking innate cytokine cues to epithelial defence and stem-cell support⁴³⁸. However, in the caecum and colon, where Paneth cells are largely absent under homeostasis, deep crypt secretory (DCS) cells fulfil analogous roles. Reg4⁺ DCS cells sit at the crypt base, express niche-support factors, and upregulate host-defence genes such as RELM- β , positioning them as the caecal guardians of the stem-cell zone^{439,440}. These epithelial sentinels operate within a broader stromal scaffold: crypt-associated fibroblasts form “top” and “bottom” hubs that distribute WNT and BMP/TGF- β signals to maintain an axis of cell proliferation at the base and differentiation at the top⁴⁴¹. Mesenchymal stromal cells also organise immune niches

along the bottom-to-top crypt axis, positioning macrophages, dendritic cells and innate lymphoid cells (ILCs) in predictable territories that can rapidly tune epithelial programs when microbes or injury perturb homeostasis⁴⁴². The extracellular matrix (ECM) is an active component here, not a passive scaffold. Its basement membrane composition and mechanics (e.g., stiffness, topography) modulate stem-cell behaviour and help stabilise the niche's spatial signals^{443,444}.

Immune-epithelial crosstalk fortifies crypts without sterilising them. Group 3 ILCs and Th17/22 cells supply IL-22, which promotes mucin and antimicrobial peptide production, supports epithelial repair, and indirectly preserves stem-cell function; this cytokine axis is central to crypt resilience across mammals^{445,446}. The “mucosal firewall” (mucus, epithelium and lamina propria immunity) generally keeps bacteria at a distance from stem-cell zones, yet a small, adapted community can persist in large-intestinal crypts⁴⁴⁷. In rats and other rodents, the caecum is an especially instructive case: its enlarged, fermentation-oriented anatomy features deep crypts and abundant lymphoid tissue. Here, crypts can harbour a specific core microbiota whose products (notably LPS) tip epithelial programs toward differentiation and goblet-cell expansion while curbing proliferation in a TLR4-dependent manner, showing that resident crypt bacteria can help set the renewal/differentiation balance locally⁴⁴⁸. When the caecal crypt microbiota is lost (e.g., after surgical stress with fasting and antibiotics), crypt homeostasis falters and regenerative capacity drops. Then, restoring commensals repopulates crypts and rescues regeneration, underscoring that the crypt microbiota is part of niche homeostasis rather than mere bystanders¹²⁰. Human data mirror rodent patterns: laser-microdissection and imaging revealed crypt-associated communities in the colon that differ from those of overlying mucosa, highlighting that crypts are distinct, regulated habitats in multiple species⁴⁴⁹.

Pulling these threads together, crypt homeostasis emerges from the integration of form (crypt geometry and ECM), function (stem-cell signalling gradients), defence (DCS outputs, IL-22-driven programs, mucus barrier), chemical gradients (oxygen, nutrients), and ecology (resident crypt microbiota and their products). The rodent caecum accentuates these interactions: a relatively permeable mucus barrier, niche-structuring stromal hubs, and a small, adapted crypt microbiota

collectively tune renewal and defence in a way that is optimised for a fermentation-rich segment of the gut. This integrated view helps explain why caecal crypt homeostasis could potentially shift the relative abundances and network modularisation of key commensals (e.g., Bacteroidota), resulting in different enterotypes.

c) Commensal strategies to colonise caecal crypts

Deep colonisation of mucus-rich caecal crypts requires a toolset that is broader than “living on mucus”. In rodents, gut commensals face a selective gauntlet at the crypt base: host mucus is the dominant carbon reservoir; oxygen and reactive oxygen species (ROS) leak from the epithelium; antimicrobial peptides (AMPs) and IgA are abundant; and space is contested. The strains that persist there are typically those that can feed on host glycans, tolerate hypoxia and inflammatory cues, adhere to the mucosal matrix, and modulate the immune response, while excluding competitors^{450,451}.

The first divide between *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* (the genera containing species with the highest h^2 values in this study) is what they can degrade at the mucosal surface. *Bacteroides* spp. encode numerous polysaccharide utilisation loci (PULs), which are operons with SusC/SusD-based systems that bind, import, and degrade complex glycans, including many PULs specialised in mucin O-glycans (e.g., fucose, galactose, GalNAc, GlcNAc, sialic acid) and their sulphated variants. This capacity enables a diet switch: when fibre wanes, *Bacteroides* can pivot to host mucus, keeping a foothold in crypts⁴⁵¹⁻⁴⁵⁴. By contrast, *Prevotella* tends to carry PUL repertoires more tuned to hemicellulose polysaccharides (e.g., arabinoxyylan, xyloglucan, glucomannan) and pectin (e.g., arabinan and pectic galactan); systems that flourish in high-fibre, luminal contexts but generally confer less breadth for mucin glycan foraging, explaining why *Prevotella* often tracks diet more tightly^{122,454-456}. Contemporary mucin-centric reviews have reached the same conclusion at the pathway level: *Bacteroides* encode larger, more diverse mucin-degrading CAZyme arsenals (including endo-acting GH16 O-glycanases and accessory sulphatases), equipping them to use host mucus as a stable “fallback” carbon source when plant polysaccharides are scarce^{359,454,455}.

Nutritional flexibility is necessary but not sufficient, as crypts are hypoxic and prone to ROS. Nevertheless, *Bacteroides* spp. such as *Bacteroides fragilis* can be unusually aerotolerant for strict anaerobic bacteria, inducing catalase, peroxidases (AhpC/Tpx), rubrerythrin, and thioredoxin systems, and being therefore able to survive days in room air (a profile that supports residence adjacent to oxygen-leaking epithelia^{451,458}). *Prevotella* spp. are generally more oxygen-sensitive and less often catalase-positive, a trait consistent with a preference for the strictly anaerobic, fibre-rich lumen rather than the hypoxic crypt interface. Mechanisms vary by species and strain, but multiple comparative and in vivo studies converge on this ecology⁴⁵⁷.

Close to the epithelium, bacteria also face cationic AMPs. Many human-gut *Bacteroides* reduce the net negative charge of their outer membrane by dephosphorylating an important LPS component, the lipid A (via LpxF), which markedly increases tolerance to host AMPs and preserves fitness during inflammation. In *B. thetaiotaomicron*, for example, loss of *lpxF* renders strains that are AMP-sensitive and unfit during host inflammation, exactly the scenario in which crypt refugia matter most⁴⁵⁰. This AMP resilience likely aids *Bacteroides* in withstanding bursts of defensins and related peptides near deep crypt secretory cells in the caecum.

Attachment and community architecture are additional hurdles. *Bacteroides* possess surface glycan-binding lipoproteins (SusD-like “SGBPs”) and adhesins that recognise host/mucin epitopes; *B. fragilis* binds intestinal mucin directly, and *B. thetaiotaomicron* can form biofilms whose strength is regulated by capsular polysaccharides (CPS). These features promote retention within the crypt mucus and resist washout⁴⁵⁸⁻⁴⁶⁰. CPS phase variation by invertible promoters (i.e., switching among multiple capsules, through mechanisms that allow changing the direction of the respective promoters of their genes) further tunes adhesion, immune visibility, and biofilm traits, a strategy widely used by gut *Bacteroides* to adapt to local conditions⁴⁶². Far from being purely defensive, immune engagement can be an asset near the mucosa. *Bacteroides fragilis*, for example, benefits from the combination of the CCF locus (discussed in Chapter 4) to penetrate the mucus layer and stably occupy the crypt niche³⁵⁸, while IgA (typically viewed as an exclusionary antibody) facilitates aggregation and an intimate

association with the epithelial surface³⁶². Together, CCF-mediated niche entry and IgA-mediated retention provide a mechanistic basis for the often-observed crypt “safehouse” that seeds recovery after antibiotics or infection³⁵⁸.

Nevertheless, the mucus layer is also a competitive space, due to close contact between bacterial cells and phages. Bacteroidales frequently deploy Type VI secretion systems (T6SS) to intoxicate neighbouring bacteria lacking cognate immunity proteins, thereby securing territory at the mucosal edge. In *B. fragilis*, GA3-type T6SSs antagonise other Bacteroidales and shape community structure in vivo, an advantage likely magnified in the confined crypt habitat^{463,464}. Reviews of gut T6SSs underscore their role in niche occupancy and colonisation resistance, showing consistency with the observation that mucosal *Bacteroides* often carry and use such systems⁴⁶⁵.

Putting these layers together clarifies why rats on high-fibre diets can be *Prevotella*-rich in the caecal lumen (reflected by their high abundances in faeces) yet still harbour *Bacteroides*-skewed communities within crypts. *Prevotella* thrives in environments where plant glycans are abundant and strictly anaerobic conditions prevail⁴⁶⁵⁻⁴⁶⁷. Still, so far, the current knowledge about this genus says it generally lacks the combination of broad mucin catabolism, AMP resistance, oxidative stress hardiness, phase-variable surface architecture, and immune-engaging colonisation loci that favour deep crypt residence in *Bacteroides*. The connection between crypt occupation and the genetic arsenal that provides the necessary adaptations for it offers a testable explanation for *Prevotella/Bacteroides* shifts in rat caecal samples across diets and perturbations: when fibre dips or inflammation rises, crypt-resident *Bacteroides* persist and rebound, while lumen-biased *Prevotella* contracts^{362,450,457}.

However, it is imperative to stress again that most of these conclusions come from studies with humans, which tend to focus on faecal samples and face limitations in terms of diet standardisation across individuals in a population. Although *Bacteroides* often present a richer genomic “toolkit” for deep mucosal residence, *Prevotella* should not be cast as a purely luminal genus. Several *Prevotella* encode mucin-targeting CAZymes, including a

characterised mucin-desulphating glycosidase that removes sulphate caps from intestinal O-glycans, a key step that exposes underlying sugars for subsequent degradation^{353,390,469}. Beyond that, *Prevotella* can marshal microaerotolerance suited to the crypt-epithelium interface: in *P. intermedia*, for example, oxidative stress responses governed by OxyR include induction of cytochrome bd oxidase (CydA), a terminal oxidase known to enhance survival in low-O₂/ROS-rich milieus, being a trait that plausibly extends to gut-adapted *Prevotella* lineages encountering epithelial oxygen leak⁴⁶⁹⁻⁴⁷¹. In vivo, mucosal surveys consistently detected *Prevotella* among genera inhabiting the colonic surface (alongside *Bacteroides*), and older biopsy-based studies grouped “*Bacteroides-Prevotella-Porphyrromonas*” as dominant mucosa-associated taxa, underscoring that both genera can occupy mucus-proximal space rather than being strictly stool-segregated⁴⁷³. Mechanistically, *Bacteroides* may even facilitate *Prevotella*’s mucosal foothold: mucin breakdown in the gut is typically a cooperative process in which primary degraders cleave terminal sialic acid and sulphate/fucose caps and partially depolymerise glycans, generating diffusible “public goods” that secondary foragers consume⁶⁴. Experiments have shown, for example, that mucolytic bacteria enhance the growth of other species on mucin^{64,220,356,405,469,474}. Additionally, recent work illustrates how a single *Bacteroides* sialidase (NanH) promotes stable mucosal occupancy and remodels the glycan landscape in early life, a context in which released sugars can feed neighbouring bacteria and potentially ease entry of taxa such as *Prevotella* into mucus niches^{475,476}.

Immune interactions also argue against a hard exclusion: IgA binds *P. copri* as well, implying that immune “inclusion” is not restricted to *Bacteroides* and could support *Prevotella* persistence near the epithelium⁴⁷⁷. In pigs, for example, high levels of IgA are associated with the *Prevotella*-associated enterotype rather than the *Ruminococcus*-associated one⁴⁷⁸. Furthermore, genomics-based investigations have revealed that *Prevotella* also possesses PULs tuned to complex glycans and competes in vivo for overlapping niches⁴⁵⁷, while population studies caution that *Bacteroides/Prevotella* patterns reflect gradients rather than mutually exclusive “enterotypes,” consistent with co-occurrence under specific diets and host states^{479,480}. Together, these lines of evidence support a model in which *Prevotella*, though generally less equipped

than *Bacteroides* for the harsh crypt conditions, retain enzymatic, stress-response, and host-interaction capacities that can permit at least mucosal colonisation, particularly when *Bacteroides* precondition the niche and share mucin-derived resources^{218,474}.

d) A hypothesis-driven candidate-gene screen

As discussed in previous chapters, GWAS have transformed complex-trait genetics by scanning millions of variants agnostically^{481,482}; however, they pay a steep multiple-testing penalty and often require very large cohorts to reach adequate power^{33,481,483,484}. The hypothesis-driven candidate-gene approach, on the other hand, takes a different route: it narrows the search space to biologically motivated regions, genes, or variant sets, and then asks focused questions with appropriately tailored tests. The pay-off is statistical efficiency and interpretability: fewer tests, higher power per hypothesis, and results that map naturally onto mechanisms⁴⁸⁵. The cost, however, is that one can miss unexpected loci if the prior is wrong, which argues for transparent, pre-specified hypotheses and replication (Table 5).

Table 5: Methodological comparisons of the hypothesis-driven and agnostic paradigms in Quantitative Genetics.

Characteristic	Hypothesis-Driven (Candidate Gene Study)	Hypothesis-Driven (QTL Mapping)	Agnostic (GWAS)
Search Scope	Focused on a small set of pre-selected genes/SNPs.	Focused on broad chromosomal regions correlated with a trait.	Scan of millions of SNPs across the entire genome.
Statistical Power	High, due to the reduced multiple-testing burden.	High, with strong power to detect important QTLs.	Low, due to the extreme multiple-testing burden.
Resolution	High (down to the SNP level, if the hypothesis is correct).	Low, generally at the cM level, identifying a region rather than the exact gene. Does not require samples as large as GWAS but generally demands controlled mapping populations.	Very high (up to base-pair resolution), identifying specific SNPs.
Sample Size	Does not require samples as large as GWAS.	Does not require samples as large as GWAS but generally demands controlled mapping populations.	Usually requires very large samples (hundreds of thousands of individuals).
Population Type	Unrelated populations (case-control) or families.	Controlled mapping populations.	Unrelated populations (case-control) or families, with high genetic diversity.
Primary Advantage	High power to detect associations in plausible genes.	High power and ideal for traits with rare alleles or major-effect loci.	Unbiased discovery potential for novel genes and pathways.
Primary Disadvantage	A priori knowledge often incomplete, leading to replication failures when overfitting is not considered.	Limited resolution for identifying the causal gene; requires controlled mapping populations.	Heavy multiple-testing burden, resulting in low power and demanding huge samples.

A hypothesis-driven map can, for example, concentrate on host genes with immune-mucosal functions, diet-responsive pathways, or tissue-specific eQTLs pertinent to the gut (i.e., QTLs mapped using gene expression levels as a trait), and then test associations with select microbial taxa, diversity metrics, or community features using mixed models with LOCO to guard against confounding by relatedness and local LD⁴⁸⁶. LOCO is now standard in GWAS-LMM practice because it preserves well-calibrated statistics at the locus under test without sacrificing control of polygenic background elsewhere. This narrows the inferential gap between statistical signal and plausible mechanism and dovetails with downstream causal analyses.

Early hypothesis-driven scans often relied on small samples and lenient thresholds, resulting in reported signals that failed to replicate. This led to the belief that the method was flawed, resulting in more efforts being devoted to GWAS. What has changed over the years to make such an approach relevant again was not the idea of using prior biology, but the tooling and discipline surrounding it: rigorous multiple-testing control, pre-registered hypotheses, large or cross-validated cohorts, and replication in independent datasets⁴⁸⁵. When these safeguards are in place, hypothesis-driven analyses can deliver findings that are both statistically credible and biologically coherent, slotting naturally beside agnostic GWAS in the modern toolbox.

One of the main problems detected in the past was the Type I error bias that happens when the same candidate-gene dataset is used for the selection of per gene proxy SNPs per association strength (the so-called “sentinel” or “lead” SNPs, which are often the ones with the lowest p -value⁴⁸⁸), and then use the same SNPs for posterior tests, creating an overfitting issue (also known as the “winner’s curse”⁴⁸⁹). A method that has the benefit of reducing this risk involves splitting these two steps into different sample sets, one defined as the training or discovery set (for the selection of sentinel SNPs, for example) and the other as the test set (for the application of such SNPs in further analyses, such as causal inference)^{490,491}. Following this reasoning, a technique often used in machine learning training has become appealing in the field of Biological Sciences: the cross-validation method based on k -folds⁴⁹². In summary, it involves evaluating how well a machine learning model performs on new, unseen data, which is an improvement over a simple train-test split. This approach

utilises all available data for both training and validation, providing a more robust and reliable estimate of the model's performance. The process of k -fold cross-validation involves: i) dividing the entire dataset into k equal-sized subsets (or "folds"); ii) performing a loop that runs k times, with a different fold being set aside as the test set, followed by the remaining $k-1$ folds being combined into a training set; iii) making predictions on the reserved test set, based on the training set, with the performance of the model (e.g., its accuracy, or error rate) being recorded for each specific fold; and iv) averaging the performance scores from all k iterations to get a single, overall performance estimate for the whole model (i.e., "meta" values). In Quantitative Genetics, this approach can serve to identify sentinel SNPs per gene based on a certain criterion, such as the strongest additive effects on a microbiome trait in a training set, and then use them as a proxy for the region that represents the gene itself on the host genome for subsequent tests, such as MR⁴⁹¹.

In short, hypothesis-driven candidate-gene-based SNP picking is a principled, mechanism-aware counterpoint to fully agnostic GWAS. By aggregating signals within biologically defined units, leveraging strength from candidate genes, and utilising kinship-aware LMM in a k -fold cross-validation setting, this approach enhances power and interpretability. Used in conjunction with agnostic scans, it helps to convert statistical associations into testable, pathway-level explanations.

e) From heritability to a niche-colonisation hypothesis

The current study has shown that host polygenic effects on the HS rat caecal microbiome are stronger among the *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species, which is reflected in the significant heritability of Guild 3 (Chapter 5). Furthermore, β -diversity PCo1, the PCoA axis that separates samples into two enterotypes, is also heritable, with significant correlations with all *Prevotella* species, resulting in Ent1 being a *Prevotella*-enriched enterotype (Chapters 4 and 5). In addition, correlations with EC4-level functions and network analyses also suggested a certain degree of niche compartmentalisation involving groups of phylogenetically and functionally close bacteria, which tends to be more concise in Ent1 samples (Chapter 4). Collectively, these patterns led to the formulation of the hypothesis

that these two bacterial genera are capable of penetrating deeply into the mucus layer towards the epithelium, inhabiting the interior of crypts, and are therefore more susceptible to host control than to environmental influences. However, it is still not clear whether both genera interact with the host in a similar way or engage in different strategies to colonise this niche.

Then, in order to investigate the possible mechanisms behind the host genetic control of these microbiome traits, the objectives of the current chapter involve: i) To identify genetic correlations between the two genera, Guild 3 and β -diversity PCo1; ii) to map similarities and divergences of genome size, network centrality and correlations with the mapped EC4 functions between heritable and non-heritable *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species; iii) to identify within their genomes which functions are enriched in those with higher h^2 values, thereby consolidating or changing the current hypothesis; and iv) to shift the focus back to the host, gathering a hypothesis-driven group of genes with possible links to the detected polygenic effects and assess their association with host polygenic effects (Objectives 5-7).

6.2 Methods

a) Genome size, network centrality and EC4 correlations

As already reported in Chapter 4, SeqKit v2.2.0³⁰⁸ was used to count the number of amino acids in the corresponding FASTA files of each GTDB R207's representative species genome. These counts were used as estimates of genome sizes, which were compared between *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species using boxplots and the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. The same was done for the subgroups of heritable and non-heritable species within each genus. Additionally, all network centrality values (e.g., degree, betweenness, closeness and eigenvector) were measured based on the species profiles, using an R script with packages NetCoMi v1.1.0²⁷², igraph v1.4.1³²⁹, and WGCNA v1.71³³⁰, as also reported in Chapter 4. This data was then used to compare the centrality of *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* heritable and non-heritable species. In addition, Pearson correlations between the pseudo-relative abundances of the mapped EC4 functions and the pseudo-relative abundances of both genera were performed and reported following the same reasoning and structure

used in Chapter 4 for the guilds; however, in this case, the threshold used was $\rho > |0.45|$, instead of $|0.40|$, to keep selecting up to 50 EC4s. The definition of the bioprocesses and categories used for higher-level functional annotation of EC4s was done based on a literature review.

b) Functional enrichment analysis

All mapped species belonging to the genera *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* had their protein FASTA files functionally annotated by running the eggNOG-mapper v2.1.7²⁰⁹ in a bash script. Then, an R script was deployed to count functions classified as COGs, ECs, CAZymes, KOs, KEGG Modules, and KEGG pathways. However, given that the most comprehensive functional annotation by the eggNOG-mapper tended to focus on COGs and other eggNOG ortholog groups (ENOGs), this functional classification was adopted (all annotated proteins contained a COG or an ENOG assignment, while the other functional types could appear as blank in some cases). Orthology-based resources such as the eggNOG database are designed to aggregate evolutionarily consistent protein families across thousands of genomes, allowing presence/absence matrices to be constructed at the species level with broad coverage and standardised functional labels. Using these resources helps to ensure that the presence of a function reflects conserved orthology rather than superficial sequence similarity^{208,209}.

To test whether specific functional gene families present in bacterial genomes were associated with inter-species differences in host-driven heritability, a phylogenetically informed enrichment analysis was implemented using a custom R script for all 57 *Prevotella* species and all 15 *Bacteroides* species. Firstly, a filtering step was performed: when a certain function had equal counts across all bacterial genomes (according to the chosen set), it was excluded. Secondly, COGs that were present ($n1$) or absent ($n0$) in fewer than $n_{\min}(N)=\max(3, [0.10 \times N])$ species in the chosen set were also excluded as a quality control step⁴⁹³. Thirdly, h^2 values were inverse rank-normalised, better meeting the Gaussian error assumptions of linear models¹³⁵. Then, the effects of COG presence or absence on h^2 values were estimated, accounting for phylogenetic non-

independence, using the Phylogenetic Generalised Least Squares (PGLS) method⁴⁹⁴.

PGLS treats the residual covariance among species as expected under trait evolution on the phylogeny tree. Specifically, Pagel's λ was chosen to scale phylogenetic dependence: λ multiplies the off-diagonal elements of the Brownian covariance matrix (diagonals unchanged), so $\lambda \approx 0$ implies little residual phylogenetic signal and $\lambda \approx 1$ implies Brownian-like signal on the GTDB R207 tree⁴⁴. Models were fitted by maximum-likelihood (ML) using the packages nlme v3.1.168⁴⁹⁵ and ape v5.8.1,³²⁷ with λ being estimated from the data. The ML- λ fit was complemented with λ fixed at 0 and 1 to check the extent to which the sign of the association was sensitive to the assumed phylogenetic signal. For model support, ΔAIC was defined for each λ setting, treating results as well-supported when the reported model was within $\Delta\text{AIC} \leq 2$ (the difference compared to the best competitor⁴⁹⁶). Statistical evidence across many functions was controlled with BH FDR, and the associations were considered noteworthy only when $p_{adj} < 0.10$ and $\Delta\text{AIC} \leq 2$.

After the tests, a set of indicators was designed to separate effect size, statistical support, model adequacy, and phylogenetic plausibility. The primary effect estimate was the PGLS regression coefficient (β) for “presence→heritability” (the ML- λ fit), accompanied by its p -value and the corresponding BH FDR p_{adj} -value, along with the chosen ΔAIC . For interpretability, the mean raw h^2 in the presence (n1) vs. absence (n0) strata and the sample sizes in each stratum were also added. Furthermore, the regression coefficient and the $-\log_{10} p$ -value distributions for each set were summarised with volcano-style plots. The definition of the bioprocesses and categories used for higher-level functional annotation of COGs/ENOGs was done based on a literature review. All codes used in this analysis were organised as HERMES-WIRE “Step 3” Nextflow pipeline on <https://github.com/Baud-lab/hermes-wire>.

c) Selecting rat genes linked to crypt homeostasis

A non-exhaustive literature review was conducted, focusing on genes that have already been mapped in studies targeting the host genetic control of the gut microbiome or crypt morphogenesis and

homeostasis. This resulted in a list containing genes associated with crypt development and maintenance, oxygen/ROS regulation, signal transduction, mucosal barrier, immunity and inflammation, gut motility and secretion, or metabolite recognition and processing. From this first group of genes, the Rat Genome Database^{497,498} was consulted, and all their sub-units and variants were mapped, including the information about the chromosome on which they are located, along with their initial and final positions (all based on the rat genome assembly mRatBN7.2¹⁴⁴). Then, only the ones located on autosomal chromosomes (1-20) were kept, excluding, for example, *Cldn2* (a tight-junction pore-forming claudin that regulates intestinal permeability and is often associated with dysbiosis^{383,499,500}). Furthermore, a classification of the genes according to the bioprocesses listed before and the sub-groups associated with them (herein referred to as “category”) was also performed. Then, the curated list of genes and their locations was organised as an XLSX input file. The definitions of bioprocesses and categories used for higher-level functional annotation of host genes were based on a literature review.

d) Identifying rat genes associated with *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* heritability

Ultimately, the primary objective of this chapter is to determine whether host genetic variation in the curated set of rat genes is associated with polygenic control over the caecal abundances of *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species, allowing for their selection for causal inference analyses (Chapter 7). To do this rigorously, a HERMES-WIRE’s Step 4 Nextflow pipeline was built to standardise and harmonise genotypes and the pseudo-relative abundances of both genera, modelling multiple sources of dependence with LMM (using the R package GENESIS v2.39.2⁵⁰¹), and adopting *k*-fold cross-validation so that the sentinel SNPs used for discovery were never evaluated on the same samples used for further effect estimations⁵⁰². This train-and-test sample partition was the core safeguard against selection bias, while the mixed-model framework with multiple variance components absorbed relatedness and shared-environment structure (maternal and cohabiting random effects). Furthermore, as associations were carried out with LOCO GRMs, proximal contamination was also avoided, while false discovery was

controlled with BH FDR ($p_{adj} < 0.10$) afterwards. Together, these choices prioritised valid inference and out-of-sample transport of effects over optimistic in-sample fits.

The pipeline was divided into phases that start with data preparation and harmonisation, and end with causal inference analyses (Figure 21). This last step will be further discussed in Chapter 7. In the current chapter, the pipeline will be described until the point it defines which of the curated genes exert, through their sentinel SNPs, additive effects in *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species, whose effect sizes (β -values) are significantly correlated with their h^2 values, pointing out to genes likely integrating the host polygenic effects on such bacteria.

Figure 21: Overall scheme of the pipeline involving the definition of sentinel SNPs within the regions of a curated list of genes, the selection of the ones with additive effects associated with species h^2 values and their use for causal inference analyses. The genetic correlations also belong to the pipeline, running in parallel to this path, not being included in the image.

a) Data preparation

The pipeline starts building sparse relationship matrices (SRMs) that encode the shared environment, one for dams and one for cages. In each SRM, diagonal entries are equal to one, and any pair of samples that share the same dam (or cage) receives such a value, while all other pairs are zeroes. These SRMs behave like kinship-style

covariance matrices and are passed to the mixed model so that variance attributable to maternal or cohousing structure is modelled as a random effect, not wrongly assigned to the genotype. Sample IDs are harmonised across all inputs used (e.g., GRM, genotyping panel, pseudo-relative abundances, etc.), preserving a fixed order. This design leverages the ability of GENESIS to fit null models with multiple variance components supplied as user-defined covariance matrices, ensuring that LMM separates additive genetic signal from shared-environment blocks during association.

Next, the HDF5-stored genotypes are converted into a compact, analysis-ready Genomic Data Structure (GDS) file that contains only variants mapped to the candidate genes, with optional upstream/downstream windows. Such windows are usually recommended as a means to also map SNPs associated with the gene promoter region or *cis*-enhancers that may influence its transcription levels, while not necessarily being placed within the locus that limits it^{503,504}. To simplify the interpretation of the results, it was assumed that by taking SNPs within the gene sequence, it was more likely that allele dosages (0, 1 and 2) would reflect the number of functional copies of the resulting proteins. It is still not necessarily true, due to many factors, including the selection of intronic SNPs, for example. However, by reducing the number of SNPs likely affecting gene transcription levels, the complexity around an initial interpretation of the results is reduced.

Using an R script with packages `rhdf5` v2.53.24³⁹⁴, `data.table` v1.17.8⁵⁰⁵, `gdsfmt` v.1.45.1 and `SNPRelate` v1.43.0⁵⁰⁶, per-chromosome position indices are located and classified as in-gene, recording per-gene counts, and writing a combined GDS plus a `SeqArray` v1.49.4⁵⁰⁷ structure for downstream tools. GDS and `SeqArray` were chosen because they are designed for large-scale genotypes with fast, block-wise access and minimal memory overhead, which is critical for repeated folding and per-chromosome operations later in the pipeline. By retaining a lookup that links integer scan IDs to sample labels, the pipeline guarantees stable sample alignment across all subsequent steps.

Following these processes, the cohort-definition helper then establishes a single, authoritative universe of samples by intersecting IDs across the residual microbiome trait matrices, metadata, the full

GRM, both SRMs, and the GDS sample set. It writes the aligned integer scan IDs that GENESIS expects, as well as the corresponding human-readable labels. This strict intersection prevents downstream crashes and, more importantly, guarantees that every matrix (genotypes, GRMs/SRMs, residuals, covariates) refers to the same individuals in the same order.

The candidate-only GDS is then subset to the analysis cohort and exported to PLINK v1.90b6.21¹⁴⁷. Before writing, the converter performs a cohort-aware scan of each variant and keeps it only if the cohort exhibits all three additive dosages (0, 1 and 2). This is a deliberate, conservative quality control measure to ensure identifiability of an additive effect and to avoid nearly singular genotype columns that can produce unstable estimates or quasi-separation, especially once random effects are present. Additionally, it complements standard per-variant filters on MAF, minor allele count (MAC), Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium (HWE), and missingness, which are also applied before running the LMM (All parameters used are in Annexe II, Supplementary Code S4). As a result, a PLINK trio (bim, bed, and fam files) is generated with clean variation that is suitable for LD computations and the construction of LOCO GRMs⁵⁰³.

For gene-centric bookkeeping and downstream set operations, the pipeline builds a MAGMA-style gene location file⁵⁰³ from the curated XLSX input, harmonises chromosome encodings, and optionally widens intervals upstream and downstream. It tabulates the PLINK SNPs that overlap each widened interval and emits per-gene counts and summaries. Using MAGMA conventions ensures that gene intervals are defined in a way that can be reused for alternative analyses (e.g., set tests or enrichment), providing a transparent and auditable record of which SNPs were considered to be within or near each locus. With cleaned PLINK files in hand, the pipeline constructs LOCO GRMs using GCTA v1.94.1¹⁴⁸. For each chromosome, the GRM is computed from all SNPs, not just those on the focus chromosome, and the set of prefixes is indexed for easy use within R.

Although the steps above focus on data hygiene and random-effect structure, they are designed around the downstream inference strategy. The analysis employs k -fold cross-validation, ensuring that

the discovery of putative signals (training folds) is kept separate from effect estimation and validation (test folds). Cross-validation is widely recommended in modern causal/associational settings to remove bias from overfitting and to deliver approximately unbiased estimators by ensuring that any feature selection or tuning never “sees” the held-out data. Here, it directly addresses the winner’s curse that inflates effect sizes in discovery samples; by aggregating out-of-fold estimates, the pipeline produces meta β values (i.e., the estimated effects) that are less optimistic and more likely to replicate.

Finally, wherever families of hypotheses arise (e.g., when screening sentinels within a fold or when evaluating mediation paths), the pipeline controls the expected proportion of false discoveries using BH multiple-testing correction. The expected outputs of these opening steps are therefore: dam and cage SRMs aligned to the cohort; a candidate-only GDS/SeqArray genotype store with per-gene mapping summaries; a PLINK trio restricted to informative variants in the analysis cohort; a pair of authoritative sample-ID files for GENESIS; a MAGMA-compatible gene location file with overlap summaries; and a complete set of LOCO GRMs. These artefacts constitute the audited substrate on which the cross-validation sentinel selection, out-of-fold species-level β -values, phylogeny-aware PGLS correlations, and mediation/MR tests operate in later stages.

b) k -fold cross-validation

By applying the cross-validation approach with $k = 5$, a variant-microbiome association and downstream synthesis were implemented in four stages designed to preserve rigorous sample alignment and out-of-sample estimation. First, within each training fold, single-variant association analyses are performed on genus-level pseudo-relative abundances (*Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, individually) using an LMM implemented in GENESIS. An R script loads the residual matrices and, depending on whether the trait domain is “Taxa” (either of any of the two genera), Guild 3, phylogenetic α -diversity (Rao’s quadratic index) or phylogenetic β -diversity PCo1, it selects the appropriate block of per-sample residuals, then trims residual row names to the label domain used by phenotype preprocessing to ensure one-to-one matching with the metadata and covariance structures. Sample identities are harmonised

by mapping integer scan IDs to their authoritative sample labels, and the GDS is then subset to the fold, with basic per-variant quality control being applied once (missingness, MAF/MAC, and optional HWE). For each column matching the requested trait, a null model is fit with the three covariance components: the corresponding LOCO GRM and the two SRMs (shared dams and cages). There is an iteration through the chromosome's passing variants in fixed blocks, to run the score test, writing out p -values, effect estimates, and SEs. After model fitting, gene-centric sentinel variants per trait are selected, based on the minimum p -value, emitting a single record per gene/trait.

While the sentinel SNPs selected for Guild 3, α - and β -diversity are directly used in the posterior causal inference analyses, in the case of the two genera, the chosen SNPs still need to be filtered based on the associations with the corresponding species h^2 values, to guarantee that only genes with strong evidence pointing them out as participants of host polygenic effects proceed. Therefore, out-of-fold species-level effect sizes are estimated by restricting association testing to the sentinel positions in each held-out test fold. The species-level residual matrix is selected analogously to the genus step but filtered to include only species belonging to the focal genus, and the same GENESIS-LMM tests are performed. This step involves reapplying per-variant quality control within the test cohort, where the exact position matches for the fold's sentinels on each chromosome are identified, resulting in per-chromosome variant index sets. The null model is then refitted, and score tests are run only at those positions. This produces out-of-sample species-level β_a values and SEs per sentinel site, fold, and species. By using sentinels chosen in training and estimating effects exclusively in held-out samples, selection bias relative to naïve in-sample effect sizes is then reduced for the species-level association tests.

The next step involves merging the per-fold species β_a values using a fixed-effect meta-analysis at the sentinel sites after forming a per-gene consensus sentinel across folds. To build consensus, the per-fold sentinel tables are stacked, and the frequency with which each position occurrence recurs for a given gene is counted. The modal site per gene is then selected, breaking ties by the median p -value. Then, each fold's species β_a values are filtered to those consensus sites, and inverse-variance weighted meta-analytic β_a and SEs are

calculated when SEs are available; otherwise, the mean β_a is reported with “NA” for such values. As a result, two-sided p -values are obtained from the meta-analytic z -statistics, and BH FDR p_{adj} (also reported as q -values) are computed alongside a Bonferroni correction to provide both adaptive and conservative multiple-testing control. The mixed-model single-variant score test and inverse-variance fixed-effect meta-analysis are standard choices for GWAS-style studies and, paired with BH FDR control, provide interpretable error rates at the study level⁵⁰¹.

c) PGLS test between SNP effects and h^2

The meta-analytic species-level associations between SNP additive effects (the linear coefficients, or β_a values) and h^2 estimates are fitted with PGLS for each genus/gene group. To achieve this, a species-space subtree from the GTDB R207⁴⁴ phylogenetic tree is constructed, and before fitting, both β_a and h^2 are transformed (using rank-based normal scores by default), enforcing a full-case rule so that each group uses the same species set. Then, GLS models are fit with a Pagel’s λ correlation structure to account for phylogenetic non-independence, estimating λ by ML and also evaluating λ fixed at 0 and 1. For reporting, either the ML fit or the fit with the lowest AIC is selected, and BH FDR q -values are estimated, along with Bonferroni thresholds, over the tested groups. The same R packages used for the PGLS-based enrichment tests reported earlier are also employed in this analysis.

As a final step, in order to synthesise interpretable, portable inputs for downstream modelling, the significant cross-validation correlations are intersected with the curated list of putative genes, selecting the sentinel SNP per gene name, mapping those sites to GDS variant IDs, and extracting the alternate-allele dosages with SeqVarTools v1.43.0⁵⁰⁸. The stacked bar plot was built in Microsoft Excel⁵⁰⁹.

d) Genetic correlations among microbiome traits

Pairwise genetic correlations among gut-microbiome and host traits (e.g., the pseudo-relative abundances of *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella* and Guild 3, along with phylogenetic α - and β -diversity PCo1, BMI and fasting blood glucose levels) were performed using bivariate

GREML in GCTA¹⁴⁸. Conceptually, genetic correlation (r_g) measures the extent to which the same aggregate genetic effects contribute to variation in two traits, by fitting an LMM to GRM and extracting the genetic covariance standardised by the two SNP-heritability values ($r_g = \text{cov}_g / \sqrt{h_1^2 h_2^2}$). The bivariate implementation in GCTA directly estimates variance and covariance components by REML, following the principles of pleiotropy (i.e., when genetic effects occur on different traits independently)^{148,510}.

The GRM was combined with matrices encoding shared environmental structure (dam and cage SRMs), allowing for the adjustment of their variance components while estimating the additive SNP components. The resulting GCTA phenotype file was harmonised to the GRM IDs, and missing values were encoded as “-9” (GCTA’s default missing phenotype code), and only individuals present in both the GRM and phenotype file were retained for analysis. The list of pairwise trait comparisons was generated programmatically, ensuring that each requested pair was mapped to the corresponding phenotype columns. For each pair of bivariate traits and the corresponding random effect (G1, G2, or G3), GREML was performed, which, by default, models the residual (environmental) covariance between traits and estimates separate variance components per matrix (the GRM and the two SRMs). The primary outputs were, per pair, an .hsq file containing the point estimate of r_g and its SE. For hypothesis testing, a Wald z-test was performed, using $z = r_g / \text{SE}(r_g)$ and a BH FDR ($p_{adj} < 0.10$) to define statistically significant genetic correlations. The stacked bar plot was built in Microsoft Excel⁵⁰⁹.

6.3 Results

a) Heritable microbiome traits are genetically correlated

The genetic correlation tests revealed that, after filtering out the pairs that did not result in REML convergence after a maximum number of iterations, the covariances between *Bacteroides* or *Prevotella* and Guild 3 or β -diversity PCol were the only significant ones (Table 6).

Table 6: Significant genetic correlations detected for microbiome traits.

Trait 1	Trait 2	rG	rG (SE)	p-value	p _{adj}
Bacteroides	β-diversity PCo1	-0.957155	0.229142	2.95E-05	1.25E-04
Bacteroides	Guild 3	0.796592	0.167698	2.03E-06	1.15E-05
Prevotella	β-diversity PCo1	-1.000000	0.166554	1.92E-09	1.64E-08
Prevotella	Guild 3	0.969469	0.063502	1.27E-52	2.17E-51

b) How *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* differ in terms of heritability

Even though *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species did not present a significant difference in their collective h^2 values (Annexe III, Supplementary Figure S14), being both genera considered heritable with similar heritability (~12%), and belonging to the only heritable guild (Guild 3), *Prevotella* was the genus with the highest proportion of heritable species (~74% vs. 40% of *Bacteroides* species). At the same time, although host polygenic effects were significantly higher than maternal and cohousing effects for species of both genera, *Bacteroides* species exhibited significantly higher maternal effects than cohousing effects, whereas the opposite was observed for *Prevotella* species (Figure 22A).

By comparing the genome sizes of their mapped species, it was noticeable that *Bacteroides* genomes were significantly bigger; however, no significant differences were noted between the heritable and the non-heritable species within both genera (Figure 22B), indicating that for both taxa, no associations between host polygenic effects and genome sizes were detected. Nevertheless, in terms of network centrality, heritable *Prevotella* species tended to have significantly higher degree and eigenvector centrality, which was not noticed for *Bacteroides* (Figure 22C). Furthermore, while no major differences were identified for *Bacteroides*, heritable *Prevotella* species demonstrated a significantly stronger positive correlation with the phylogenetic α -diversity (Rao's quadratic index) and a negative correlation with phylogenetic β -diversity PCo1 (Figure 22D), indicating a higher link with Ent1-type communities, as expected (Figure 13D).

A)

B)

C)

Figure 22: Comparisons between characteristics of *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species. All p -values were defined based on the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. **A)** Random effects. **B)** Genome size differences between all *Bacteroides* species in comparison with all *Prevotella* species, and then the same comparison, but splitting the species within both genera into heritable and non-heritable. **C)** Degree and eigenvector centrality differences between heritable and non-heritable *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species. **D)** Differences in the Pearson correlation (ρ values) between phylogenetic α - and β -diversity values and the pseudo-relative abundances of heritable and non-heritable *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species.

In addition, when Pearson correlations were performed between the pseudo-relative abundances of EC4 functions and both genera, it was possible to notice similar patterns as seen for Guild 3 in Chapter 4 (Figure 16), but now with a better resolution of specific similarities and dissimilarities between these heritable taxa (Figure 23 and Annexe I Supplementary Table S8).

Figure 23: Heatmaps of Pearson correlations between EC4 functions and taxa (genera *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*) pseudo-relative abundances. **A)** Heatmap for the correlations across all 858 samples, with EC4 functions being filtered based on correlation p -value < 0.05 and $\rho > |0.45|$,

resulting in 24 remaining functions. **B)** Comparisons of the same correlations when only samples assigned to Ent1 or Ent2 are selected. The dendrograms were defined based on wald.D2 clustering.

After the application of filtering steps, 24 EC4-level enzyme functions were significantly correlated with *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, spanning a broad range of metabolic bioprocesses (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S8). Notably, a large subset was involved in carbohydrate metabolism, including enzymes for degrading plant cell wall polysaccharides: pectinesterase and tagaturonate reductase, which is one of the most recognised characteristics of both genera (and most Bacteroidota, in general)^{63,122,353,455}. Several energy metabolism enzymes from the TCA and electron transport chain (e.g., succinate dehydrogenase and NADH dehydrogenase) emerged, alongside SCFA pathways such as methylmalonyl-CoA mutase/epimerase, which is involved in propionate formation. Amino acid metabolism was another prominent category; for example, arginine decarboxylase (producing agmatine for polyamine biosynthesis) and tryptophanase (cleaving tryptophan into indole and other products), indicating a connection with protein fermentation and nutrient recycling. Additionally, multiple cofactor/vitamin biosynthesis enzymes, including those for pyridoxal-5'-phosphate (PLP, the active form of vitamin B₆), riboflavin (B₂), nicotinate (NAD precursor), and menaquinone (vitamin K₂) were also mapped as significantly correlated with their abundances. Finally, three enzymes were identified as being involved in cell envelope biosynthesis: two Lpx enzymes and a KDO synthase, which are involved in the synthesis of LPS; and a dolichol-phosphate mannosyltransferase, which is related to N-linked glycan assembly. In summary, the correlated functions fall into key metabolic themes, including carbohydrate metabolism and storage, amino acid and polyamine metabolism, cell envelope and biofilm biosynthesis, cofactor and vitamin biosynthesis, SCFA and organic acid metabolism, and redox balance (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S8).

As expected, *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* exhibit overall similar correlation profiles with these 24 enzyme functions, with both genera showing only positive correlations with them. The absolute correlation values were moderate to high for both (ρ ranging approximately 0.38-0.61 in *Bacteroides* and 0.37-0.58 in *Prevotella* (Figure 23A), indicating that both genera tend to co-occur with these

functional pathways. For instance, glycogen synthase was positively associated with *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* in a very similar way ($\rho \approx 0.61$ and $\rho \approx 0.58$, respectively). However, although the two profiles were highly congruent, a few quantitative differences emerged. *Bacteroides* showed slightly stronger correlations with certain energy metabolism enzymes, for example, succinate dehydrogenase and malate dehydrogenase (on the order of +0.04-0.05 pp in ρ). Conversely, *Prevotella* was relatively more correlated with tagaturonate reductase, with a correlation strength that was about 0.08 pp higher than in *Bacteroides* ($\rho \approx 0.46$ and $\rho \approx 0.38$, respectively). There were no strongly opposing (negative) correlations unique to a single genus; rather, differences were subtle shifts in the degree of the positive correlation with specific functions.

By comparing results computed within Ent1 versus Ent2 (Figure 23B), it was observed that both genera showed broadly stronger correlations with the 24 EC4 functions in Ent1 rather than in Ent2. For *Bacteroides*, the mean correlation across EC4s was 0.502 in Ent1 vs 0.478 in Ent2 (21 ECs ≥ 0.45 in Ent1 vs 18 in Ent2). For *Prevotella*, the mean was 0.523 vs 0.473 (23 ECs ≥ 0.45 in Ent1 vs 15 in Ent2). The distribution of $\Delta\rho$ (Ent1 - Ent2) was skewed positively: *Bacteroides* had 14 positive $\Delta\rho$ values (average +0.051 pp for positives and -0.013 pp for negatives), while *Prevotella* had 22 positive $\Delta\rho$ (averages of +0.057 pp and -0.020 pp). For both genera, the largest increase in Ent1 was EC4 1.1.1.58 (tagaturonate/altronate reductase: +0.151 pp for *Bacteroides* and +0.178 pp for *Prevotella*). The largest decrease for *Bacteroides* was EC4 1.2.7.3 (2-oxoglutarate synthase; -0.032pp) and for *Prevotella*, EC4 3.5.1.1 (L-asparaginase; -0.037pp) (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S9). Taking these results together, it was noticeable that Ent1 strengthened genus-function coupling relative to Ent2 (Table 7).

Table 7: Average absolute, positive and negative $\Delta\rho$ values (Ent1 - Ent2) for the two selected genera (*Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*).

Genus	Avg. $ \Delta\rho $ across 24 EC4s	Avg. positive $\Delta\rho$ (Ent1 > Ent2)	Avg. negative $\Delta\rho$ (Ent1 < Ent2)
<i>Bacteroides</i>	0.035	0.051	-0.013
<i>Prevotella</i>	0.054	0.057	-0.020

c) Functions enriched in high- and low- h^2 species

From the 15 *Bacteroides* and 57 *Prevotella* genomes, 4,413 and 5,025 unique COGs/ENOGs were initially mapped, respectively. Then, the filters for constant values and the minimum sizes for the n0 (absence) and n1 (presence) groups were applied (being defined as 3 and 6 for *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, respectively, due to their considerably different number of species). Thus, the final COGs/ENOGs numbers were 1,279 for *Bacteroides* and 1,657 for *Prevotella*. Curiously, even though more functions were mapped for *Prevotella*, only 7 functions were significantly enriched in groups with high or low h^2 for this genus, while *Bacteroides* had 122 (Figure 24A and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S10). Additionally, 53 COGs/ENOGs were removed from the *Bacteroides* dataset and 3 from *Prevotella*'s, for having "function unknown", according to the auxiliary metadata provided by the eggNOG 5.0 website⁵¹¹. Therefore, the final numbers of mapped functions that were analysed involved 31 functions enriched in the group with low h^2 and 38 for the group with high h^2 for *Bacteroides* (Figure 24B); and 4 functions enriched in the group with high h^2 for *Prevotella* (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S10). Each function enriched for *Prevotella* species belonged to a different bioprocess: carbon flux & anaerobic fermentation, horizontal gene transfer, redox balance & O₂/ROS defence, and cell cycle & morphogenesis.

Figure 24: COG/ENOG enrichment in *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species with high and low h^2 . **A)** Volcano plots showing the differential enrichment of COGs/ENOGs mapped for *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species (1,279 and 1,657, respectively), given by the PGLS regression coefficient values and the corresponding $-\log_{10} p$ -value distributions. The signal of the coefficient values indicates whether the function is associated with low or high h^2 (negative and positive values, respectively). Each point represents a COG/ENOG function, with red points being the ones that reached significant q -values after BH FDR correction ($p_{adj} < 0.10$). **B)** Number of COGs/ENOGs significantly enriched for *Bacteroides* species with high or low h^2 values per bioprocess.

Given the reasonable and balanced number of functions enriched for *Bacteroides* species with high and low h^2 , along with their different clustering patterns in bioprocesses, further observations could be made about the results for this genus. The most remarkable was the high number of enriched COGs/ENOGs involved in cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport (mostly driven by the vitamin B₁₂ biosynthesis pathway) among the group with high h^2 values (Figure 24B). This bioprocess was followed by cell cycle & morphogenesis, horizontal gene transfer, defence & antagonism and adhesion as the ones with a disproportional balance pending to the group more affected by host polygenic effects. On the other hand, redox balance & O₂/ROS defence, glycan acquisition and degradation, DNA repair & genome maintenance, and carbon flux & anaerobic fermentation stood out as bioprocesses more associated with low h^2 . These results show that for *Bacteroides* species, dealing with stronger or weaker

host control requires a distinct set of functions, suggesting an adaptive divergence of the two groups within the same community.

d) Host candidate genes associated with *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* heritability

Originally, 485 mucus/crypt-associated host genes were mapped, based on a non-exhaustive literature review (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S11). However, a few pre-selected genes did not have any SNPs mapped by the genotyping panel used in this study, resulting in a final list of 436 host genes. They were distributed into 8 different bioprocesses (crypt development & maintenance, gut motility & secretion, immunity & inflammation, metabolite recognition & processing, mucosal barrier, oxygen/ROS regulation, ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism and signal transduction), which were also subdivided into 40 categories (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S11), summing up a total of 48,382 SNPs. After the selection of the sentinel SNPs to be used for each gene/genus pair, PGLS tests were performed and those identified as having significant phylogenetic-aware associations between their additive effects on species pseudo-relative abundances and h^2 values (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S12) were used in subsequent mediation and MR analyses (Chapter 7). This test resulted in the discovery of 75 genes associated with host polygenic effects on *Bacteroides* species (distributed in 7 bioprocesses and 29 categories) and 134 linked to *Prevotella* species h^2 (distributed in 8 bioprocesses and 32 categories). It is important to reinforce two things about such results: i) that every mention to the selected host “genes” is actually referring to their chosen sentinel SNPs, not to the gene as a whole; and ii) these sentinel SNPs did not have to necessarily exert significant (BH FDR $p_{adj} < 0.10$) additive effects on the genus and species pseudo-relative abundances. What was relevant here was the strength of the association between these effects and h^2 across the species of each genus.

At first glance, when genes responsible for additive effects with significant associations with host polygenic effects were grouped according to their respective bioprocesses, the proportions of positive and negative associations mapped for *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* demonstrated very similar patterns. In general, both genera presented

a very balanced proportion of positive and negative associations, with *Bacteroides* containing 53% of positive PGLS regressions, while *Prevotella* had 55%. The comparison between bioprocesses showed that the highest difference in the proportion of positive regressions was found in the “mucosal barrier” group, with 100% of positive regressions for *Bacteroides*, and 67% for *Prevotella* (Figure 25A).

However, when the same bioprocesses were broken into more specific categories, it was possible to notice main differences. For example, while both genera had the same proportion of positives for “immunity and inflammation” (55%), the categories “inflammasome” and “cytokine signalling” revealed inverse trends, with 88% vs 33% of positives for the former and 25% vs 69% for the latter (considering *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, respectively, Figure 25B). Furthermore, nine sentinel SNPs had significant associations with both *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* h_2 values, the ones representing genes *Il2*, *Chpf2*, *Arhgap5*, *Mmp27*, *Casp14*, *Notch3*, *Pax2*, *Egln3*, and *Gng13*. However, while the former six resulted in positive β_{pgls} values for both genera, the latter three presented divergent signals (Annexe I, Supplementary Table S12).

A)

B)

Figure 25: Bar plots with the number of genes exerting significant associations between their additive effects on *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species and the corresponding species h^2 values. **A)** Counts by bioprocess. **B)** Counts by category. The bar plots were segmented according to the genes with positive associations (orange) and the genes with negative associations (blue).

6.4 Discussion, limitations and conclusion

a) Contrasts between heritable and non-heritable *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species

A central hypothesis motivating this chapter was that host polygenic effects on *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species largely reflect niche effects at epithelial-proximal habitats (i.e., mucus and crypts), such

that bacterial lineages best adapted to these habitats would exhibit higher heritability (h^2). Consequently, they would covary because host polygenic effects would operate in their common niche. The comparative results between the two genera are consistent with that view, with both being heritable with similar h^2 (~12%) and belonging to the only heritable co-abundance guild (Guild 3).

Genetic correlations reinforced the reading of a shared host-controlled niche (Table 7). Even though no REML convergence was achieved for the assessment of genetic correlation between *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, both genera were positively genetically correlated with Guild 3 and negatively correlated with β -diversity PCo1, indicating that the same aggregate host variants that favour the Ent1-like state also favour these co-abundant genera. The effect sizes were large (for example, $r_G \approx 0.97$ for *Prevotella*/Guild 3 and $r_G \approx -1.0$ for *Prevotella*/ β -diversity PCo1), suggesting extensive pleiotropy or shared causal pathways from host genotype to community structure (Table 7). This is compatible with conceptions of enterotypes as stable resource- and interaction-structured regimes rather than strict clusters, and with a guild-based organisation in which taxa co-vary because they exploit similar host-provided resources and refuges together^{70,247,248}. The fact that no convergence was observed between the two genera can be interpreted as caused by a significant collinearity between them, which, still, based on the other results, does not discard a very likely genetic correlation between them⁵¹².

However, while additive host genetic effects exceeded maternal and co-housing effects for both genera, *Bacteroides* species displayed higher maternal than co-housing effects, with the opposite pattern being seen for *Prevotella* (Figure 13). Furthermore, genome size analysis indicated larger genomes in *Bacteroides* than in *Prevotella*, but no within-genus genome-size difference between heritable and non-heritable species, collectively implying that heritability tracked niche-adapted functions rather than the genome bulk (also meaning metabolic independence). These contrasts were accompanied by marked differences in network embeddedness: heritable *Prevotella* species showed significantly higher degree and eigenvector centrality, whereas *Bacteroides* did not (Figure 13). In addition, heritable *Prevotella* species associated more strongly with higher phylogenetic α -diversity and with lower β -diversity PCo1

scores, aligning them with Ent1-type communities (Figure 13). Taken together, these observations suggest that the two genera participate in a host-structured guild, but could either: i) occupy slightly different positions within it, with *Prevotella* being more centrally connected in the co-abundance backbone and more predictive of the Ent1 state, while *Bacteroides* remains more isolated; or ii) exert different effects on the rest of the community when able to successfully occupy the mucosa.

Viewed in the light of gut biogeography, a simple spatial model accommodates these patterns. Imaging, modelling and oxygen measurements have shown that mucus and crypts are host-sculpted microhabitats: oxygen and reactive oxygen species (ROS) peak at the tissue interface and drop steeply into the lumen; crypt bottoms are diffusion-limited and stably hypoxic; and the inter-crypt surface experiences microaerobic pulses and strong immune policing^{78,118,119,124,420,513,514}. In that framework, the large, versatile genomes and surface-interaction systems seen in *Bacteroides* are classically associated with mucosal association and crypt residency, while *Prevotella*'s heritable species seem to align with traits favouring growth and survival at the mucus-lumen interface. The genus-level convergence in genetic correlation, therefore, likely reflects shared host control over the mucosal domain, while the genus-specific differences reflect micro-partitioning within that domain. Such genus-level overall regularities thus set the stage for interpreting functional signals. Because no within-genus genome-size separation by heritability was detected, the subsequent analyses focused on (i) genus-function correlations that capture shared guild metabolism and (ii) phylogenetically informed enrichment of genome-encoded functions that stratified species by h^2 , better reflected the refined “niche-securing” modules expected to be under host control.

b) A bacteria-centred view: functional correlations and enrichment

Two complementary functional perspectives were used, focusing on the functional potential of these highly heritable genera. First, correlations between genus abundances and mapped EC4 enzymatic functions reflected, to some degree, the guild-level metabolic milieu

(Figure 16 and Annexe I, Supplementary Table S6), however, this reinforced more the shared phylogenetic characteristics of both taxa (e.g., SCFAs production, Gram-negative envelope characterisation, glycan degradation) than necessarily pointed to functions revealing specific niche preferences. Nevertheless, in Ent1, the genus-function coupling strengthened for both genera (larger $|\Delta\rho|$), with a particularly pronounced and mostly positive shift for *Prevotella*, suggesting that the Ent1 state represents a better coordination of a shared metabolic program that both genera participate in. This is consistent with the genetic correlations with β -diversity PCo1, which also tended to be slightly higher for *Prevotella*, pointing to Ent1-associated values. Second, a PGLS enrichment analysis connected the presence/absence of COG/ENOG families in their species genomes to the respective h^2 values, thereby identifying the functions most associated with host-tracked lineages.

Despite more COG/ENOGs were mapped to *Prevotella* genomes overall, only four functions were significantly enriched with high h^2 within this genus, whereas 69 functions were enriched across high- and low- h^2 *Bacteroides* (after removing “unknown function” entries). For the latter, the high- h^2 subset was enriched for features characteristic of life in space-limited habitats: adhesion/encapsulation (including sialic-acid/capsule biosynthesis), contact-dependent antagonism (Type VI secretion, VgrG), defence against phages and stress, and, strikingly, multiple contiguous steps of cobamide (vitamin B₁₂) biosynthesis and transport. The low- h^2 subset instead carried a broad oxygen/redox-repair toolkit (e.g., methionine-R-sulfoxide reductase, MdaB, DNA repair modules), a Type-V autotransporter (EstA family), and cross-feeding metabolism (e.g., lactate utilisation, arginine/polyamine catabolism), matching a fluctuating, diet-fed interface. This split maps naturally onto caecal spatial ecology: dense, diffusion-limited, physiologically hypoxic crypts favour long-term attachment, capsule phase variation and contact-dependent competition, while open surfaces and the lumen reward redox buffer capacity and opportunistic cross-feeding under microaerobic pulses^{118,119,363,419,459,462}. This interpretation is aligned with direct imaging and *Bacteroides* colonisation studies: *B. fragilis*, for example, requires the CCF locus to penetrate mucus and occupy deep crypts³⁵⁸, a stable reservoir that promotes resilience after perturbation, while mucosal oxygen gradients partition communities radially from tissue to lumen⁴²⁰. The ecological logic of contact-

dependent warfare in tight spaces is supported by Bacteroidales T6SS studies *in vivo*^{463,465}, while the highly competitive “corrinoid economy” at the mucosa, underscored by its biosynthesis, is justified by the importance of B₁₂ as a cofactor for the generation of propionate during anaerobic fermentation, which is a SCFA with an important contribution to keep the homeostasis of goblet cells⁵¹⁴⁻⁵¹⁷. Notably, comparative genomics indicates that *de novo* cobamide biosynthesis is unevenly distributed across bacteria; many Bacteroidota rely on salvage and capture, while others encode partial or complete pathways. The enrichment of multiple B₁₂ steps in the high-*h*² *Bacteroides* subset therefore suggests investments in the cobamide economy, precisely where it pays off most: dense mucosal isolated microcolonies⁵¹⁹.

The *Prevotella* signal was sparser but coherent: high-*h*² species carried superoxide-reducing enzymes (desulfoferrodoxin/SOR), a TCA cycle step (succinyl-CoA synthetase), and a ribosome-assembly factor (YihI), indicating together that microaerotolerance and the capacity for growth spurts at oxygen-touched interfaces were more important than heavy investment in crypt anchoring. Superoxide reductases are canonical anaerobe defences against oxygen stress; their presence points to survival under low-level O₂/ROS such as those encountered near crypt mouths and inter-crypt mucus^{418,420,451,520}. This places high-*h*² *Prevotella* at the more-oxygenated mucus edge, while high-*h*² *Bacteroides* appear to extend deeper into hypoxic crypt recesses, suggesting the two together inhabit adjacent layers of the same host-sculpted region.

To emphasise the reasoning behind the abductive hypothesis of niche colonisation based on all evidence collected so far, the proposed four niches were described based on their combination of host control factors (Table 8) and the major enriched bacterial functions were linked to the most likely of them in Table 9.

Table 8: Summary of the main characteristics of different caecal niches. The four niches were defined based on studies using three-dimensional analyses and reviews about the general characteristics of transversal biogeography of the caecum or the proximal colon^{118,119,124}. Furthermore, the descriptions on how host control varies across these niches also considered recent models of host physiochemical gradients⁷⁸.

Host control factor	Deep crypts (Mucus-rich, epithelium-proximal)	Crypt opening / surface mucus (Mucus-rich, farther from epithelium)	Inter-crypt (Thin mucus layer, epithelium-proximal)	Lumen (No mucus, far from epithelium)
Competitor density & contact ^{457,465}	High cell density → contact-dependent systems favoured (e.g., T6SS).	High density at interface; episodic contact-dependent antagonism.	Dense, mixed communities with frequent host-driven turnover.	Diverse but more diffuse; less physical contact.
Flow / shear ⁵²¹	Lowest (protected pocket); promotes long-term attachment and stable consortia.	Moderate; periodic mixing and erosion events.	Moderate-high locally; thin layer is sensitive to motility and peristaltic shear.	Highest; frequent washout; favours fast growth.
Glycan landscape ^{355,410,427,522}	Mucin O-glycans (sialylated/fucosylated; sulphated) abundant and relatively constant; host-derived peptides	Mucin glycans abundant but more mixed with dietary residues; higher turnover.	Thin mucus; host glycans present but renewed by shear/stress.	Dietary polysaccharides dominate; fewer intact mucin glycans.
HGT opportunities ^{367,523}	Biofilm-like consortia support exchange; competence if present benefits here.	Similar to deep crypts but more transient.	Episodic exchange under stress and high density.	Less likely conjugative events.
Immune exposure ^{129,365,522}	Immune evasion required for persistence (adhesion without inflammation).	AMPs and IgA higher than lumen; barrier policing.	Highest mucosal policing (thin layer over epithelium)	Lowest direct epithelial contact; indirect IgA/complement via flow.
Oxygen / ROS ^{420,513,524}	Physiologic hypoxia; epithelial O ₂ consumption (butyrate oxidation) maintains very low O ₂ ; stable over time.	Microaerobic “interface”: intermittent O ₂ /ROS pulses from epithelium and inflammation; more variable than deep crypts.	Epithelium-adjacent and thin; strong exposure to O ₂ /ROS bursts and host antimicrobials; highest variability in the cecum mucosa.	Most anaerobic; lowest O ₂ and ROS; diffusion distance is the largest.
Phages ^{525,526}	Lower diffusivity may promote stable bacteriophage coexistence and phase-variation defences.	Intermediate; bursts during mixing.	High encounter with lytic and temperate phages arriving from lumen and attached to mucus.	High encounter rate (well-mixed).
Vitamin B12 / corrinoids ^{515,516,527}	Host-mediated stability; high-affinity capture (BtuG, specialized transporters) and biosynthesis are advantageous.	Intermediate availability and competition; mixed sources.	Competition is intense.	Dietary corrinoids pulse; competition depends on transport arrays.

Table 9: Likely niche occupation by *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species inferred from enriched bacterial functions. Because no significant enrichments were mapped for low-heritability *Prevotella*, this group was not included. Most likely niches are highlighted with a light grey background.

Niche / Bacterial group	<i>Bacteroides</i> (High heritability)	<i>Bacteroides</i> (Low heritability)	<i>Prevotella</i> (High heritability)
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<p>Deep crypts (Mucus-rich, epithelium-proximal)</p>	<p>Most likely: Capsule sialic-acid synthesis SpsE (immune camouflage, complement dampening); outer-membrane adhesin/porin BP26/OMP28 (SIMPL family) and Ca²⁺-binding RTX-related adhesin support attachment; septal ring protein DamX and multiple ribosomal proteins suggest sustained growth in a protected niche; extensive cobamide (B₁₂) biosynthesis genes indicate investment where corrinoids are limiting and competition is intense; anti-phage programs (HEPN RNases, HigB, HicB-fold nuclease) and competitor antagonism (T6SS VgrG) fit dense, contact-rich consortia typical of crypts.</p>	<p>Less likely: This set lacks the capsule/adhesion bias and instead shows broader stress-repair.</p>	<p>Possible: No capsule or T6SS signal; the set emphasizes superoxide detox (SOR-like), TCA flux and a ribosome assembly factor, which suits metabolically active but not tightly attached crypt consortia.</p>
<p>Crypt opening / surface mucus (Mucus-rich, farther from epithelium)</p>	<p>Plausible: Same adhesion set could engage the mucus surface while allowing exchange with lumen; B₁₂ synthesis still advantageous; T6SS helps hold territory at crowded interfaces.</p>	<p>Likely: Enrichment for redox/oxidative-damage control and DNA repair (MdaB, YggE-SIMPL, methionine-R-sulfoxide reductase, MutY, SbcCD, photolyase) matches a microaerobic, variable interface where epithelium-derived O₂/ROS intermittently penetrate the mucus; glycolysis/lactate-utilization modules point to cross-feeding with fermenters washing by.</p>	<p>Most likely: SOR/desulfoferrodoxin provides microaerotolerance; TCA step (succinyl-CoA synthetase) supports energy in mixed substrates; YihI (Der-activator) aids ribosome assembly during bursts of growth; a transposase spike hints at adaptive turnover at a dynamic interface. Closer to co-abundant deep-crypt <i>Bacteroides</i>.</p>
<p>Inter-crypt (Thin mucus layer, epithelium-proximal)</p>	<p>Possible: Considering subsets with strong immune evasion and T6SS; however, higher O₂/ROS variability may penalize strictly anaerobic strains lacking stress toolkits.</p>	<p>Most likely: Enriched oxidative-stress and repair systems pair with flexible carbon entry (glycolysis, lactate utilization) and Type V autotransporter EstA, a surface-active enzyme associated with motility/biofilm remodeling in fluctuating, shear-exposed environments.</p>	<p>Likely: SOR supports survival near epithelium, but absence of explicit adhesion/immune-evasion modules suggests more transient occupancy. However, there would be a certain distance between them and crypt-associated heritable <i>Bacteroides</i> from the same guild.</p>

Lumen (No mucus, far from epithelium)	Less likely: adhesion, T6SS and B ₁₂ biosynthesis invest in fixed territory more than in planktonic competition.	Plausible: Redox/repair and broad carbon entry fit a wash-out environment; lack of specialized adhesion aligns with lower heritability.	Plausible: SOR + TCA step + ribosome assembly suggest robust growth on diet- derived substrates under strict anaerobiosis; limited adhesion signal fits a luminal lifestyle; the transposase enrichment may reflect genome plasticity under fluctuating resources.
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This mapping offers a possible ecological reading: host-governed crypt architecture and mucus chemistry create a stabilising refuge that selects for *Bacteroides* lineages, while adjacent, oxygen-touched layers select for microaerotolerant *Prevotella*. The same host variants, therefore, can move both genera in concert at the community level (shared genetic correlations), even as each genus emphasises different survival modules. Furthermore, the asymmetric number of significant enrichments (many in *Bacteroides*, few in *Prevotella*) can be understood technically and biologically. First, the *Bacteroides* “host-interface” commitments arrive in operonic blocks (e.g., contiguous cobamide loci; T6SS cassettes^{523,527}), so a single ecological investment registers as multiple significant COGs. Second, among-genome variability may be lower in the *Prevotella* features under host selection, reducing contrast power even with more mapped COGs.

Placed side by side, the two functional views are complementary. EC4 correlations summarise shared community metabolism that underlies the co-abundance guild spanning both genera and reinforces how Ent1 seems to correspond to a configuration that strengthens the taxa/function correlations; COG/ENOG enrichment pinpoints the niche-securing modules that differentiate high- and low-heritability subsets within a genus. This division explains why both *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* are genetically aligned with Guild 3 and β -diversity PCo1, while only *Bacteroides* displays a rich catalogue of host-interface enrichments: the two genera share a guild-level metabolic scaffold that might be more stable in Ent1 but differ in the specific tools that translate host control into heritability.

c) A host-centred view: where does the polygenic signal sit?

After running LMM with cross-validation to select per-gene/genus sentinel SNPs and then performing PGLS to tie out-of-sample additive effects (β_a) to species h^2 , 75 genes were associated with *Bacteroides* heritability and 134 genes with *Prevotella* heritability. The PGLS slope β_{pgls} captured these cross-species associations while accounting for phylogeny in a way that if $\beta_{pgls} > 0$, species with higher heritability tend to be those for which the allele increases their relative abundances (i.e., their β_a skew positive). This supports the hypothesis that these bacterial species are successful colonisers because of the influence of host genetics. On the contrary, if $\beta_{pgls} < 0$, high- h^2 species tend to decrease with increasing allele dosage (i.e., their β_a skew negative). Still, two practical cautions must be considered: (i) the sign depends on consistent allele coding across species; flipping the effect-allele flips all β_a and β_{pgls} . (ii) β_{pgls} does not mean that the gene is up- or down-regulated; it links host genotype effects to which species (more vs less heritable) benefit or are suppressed by the additive effects of such a gene.

The analysis of the β_{pgls} values across different bioprocesses and categories revealed distinct and often contrasting host-genetic conditions favouring either *Bacteroides* or *Prevotella*. The original hypothesis that heritable species of both genera could colonise deep, well-structured crypts was not totally supported after the COG/ENOG enrichment analysis, so far restricting this niche to *Bacteroides*. However, as pointed out before, the lower identification of significantly enriched functions across *Prevotella* species limited the analysis. Therefore, the host-centred approach was included here not only with the main objective to map genetic instruments for posterior causal inference analyses (Chapter 7), but also to fulfil this kind of gap present in the bacterial-centred approach, being an essential complementary analysis.

In summary, the β_{pgls} patterns indicated that both *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* contain heritable species whose success is tightly coupled to a well-organised crypt ecosystem rather than to a generic luminal niche. Positive slopes for Wnt ligands (Wnt3a, Wnt8a, Wnt9a) in high- h^2 *Bacteroides*, with negative β_{pgls} for the Wnt

antagonist Dkk3, together with negative slopes for components of the Notch (Notch3 and Msi1), and BMP/TGF- β (Smad2, Tgfb1i1) pathways, align high- h^2 *Bacteroides* species with conditions typical of the proliferative deep crypt stem compartment^{127,435,436,528,529}. This environment continually renews the epithelium, sustains a Muc17-coated brush border^{220,356,405,410,459,530}, and maintains Cldn15-rich tight junctions at the crypt base. The same *Bacteroides* set shows strong alignment with ECM remodelling (Mmp27)^{436,444,532} and proteoglycan synthesis (polymerases and sulfotransferases), consistent with a dependency on crypt basement-membrane GAGs that shape tissue stiffness, ligand presentation, and interfacial mucus properties, reflecting niche resilience and stability^{442,443,532-534}. A positive β_{pgls} for Keap1 and selected inflammasome components (Nlrp3, Nlrp4b, Nlrp6 and Nlrp10) suggests that these lineages are most compatible with epithelia that efficiently resolve oxidative stress and deploy controlled IL-18/CASP1 programs⁴³¹. Such epithelia probably maintain not only a Muc17-coated glycocalyx, but also secrete a thick, structured mucus, with the support of Clca1 and Fut4, limiting bacterial encroachment^{410,459,536}. Curiously, high- h^2 *Bacteroides* had a positive β_{pgls} for Retnlb, a gene responsible for RELM β , a Gram-negative-focused AMP released by goblet cells at the top of crypts^{450,537}. This might reflect the enrichment of cell envelope adaptations that protect high- h^2 *Bacteroides* from AMPs, conferring them the ability to pass through this barrier and penetrate deeper into the crypt luminal space, where Gram-negative competitors will fail to do so.

In contrast, the signal of high- h^2 *Prevotella* species set points to a slightly higher position along the crypt, where strong Notch/Hes1 and Hippo cues (Notch1, Hes1 and Yap1), along with negative β_{pgls} for Wnt signalling (Wnt1, Wnt10b, Wnt9b), indicate the predominance of differentiating cells^{127,437,529}. Furthermore, the recognition of FFAR2-amplified SCFAs by enterocytes (mainly propionate and acetate), as well as chemokine-directed immune traffic (Ccr1, Ccr2, Ccr5, and Ccr7)⁵³⁸, is also compatible with the crypt opening, where bacterial anaerobic SCFA concentrations are high due to intensive fermentation, as well as immune surveillance. Interestingly, the prominent negative β_{pgls} for Zgl6 imply that the high- h^2 *Prevotella* species prosper where the lectin-mediated aggregation barrier is less exclusionary, allowing the approximation of Gram-positive bacteria⁴²⁸. This is likely linked to the fact that high- h^2 *Prevotella*

species tend to be more connected to other species, according to their degree and eigenvector centrality values (Figure 21).

In terms of synergies, high- h^2 species of both genera benefit from neuroeffectors leading to the stimulation of goblet cell secretion, which replenishes mucin in the crypts. While *Bacteroides* had positive β_{pgls} values for Myh11, Chrm2 and Tacr3, *Prevotella* had for Chrm5 and Tacr1. Furthermore, both bacterial groups appear to thrive in environments with active, regulated signalling and immune traffic; however, they do so through different mechanisms. High- h^2 *Bacteroides* are associated with a niche supported by a restrained, barrier-protective inflammatory response, while high- h^2 *Prevotella* are benefited by an active and reparative inflammatory state. By looking at this in more detail, it is possible to notice that, among *Bacteroides*, high- h^2 species tracked host genotypes that are permissive for epithelial inflammasome activity: β_{pgls} was positive for Nlrp3, Nlrp6, Nlrp10, Casp1 and Casp12, a pattern consistent with contexts that sustain goblet-cell mucus secretion and barrier protection by epithelial inflammasomes^{430,431}. At the same time, IL-18, a Caspase-1 product with context-dependent effects on barrier stability, showed a negative β_{pgls} , suggesting that these species align with inflammasome competence but with a restrained IL-18 axis. IL-18 can be protective in some settings yet barrier-disruptive when excessive, so such a “restrained IL-18 axis” alongside inflammasome competence is biologically coherent⁵³⁹. Additionally, Il20rb was also associated with negative β_{pgls} , in line with a limited IL-20 drive that can otherwise couple inflammation to epithelial remodelling⁵⁴⁰. Together with positive β_{pgls} for Ccr4/Ccr7, these results point to a niche that tolerates chemokine-guided immune traffic yet relies on epithelial inflammasome signalling to maintain a structured, mucus-fortified interface⁵³⁸.

By contrast, high- h^2 *Prevotella* species are associated with reduced IL-10 signalling (negative β_{pgls} for Il10rb), a pathway required for mucosal tolerance⁵⁴¹, but positive β_{pgls} for Ptges and Il1r12, which together favour epithelial repair and leukocyte activation and can be pro-inflammatory depending on context¹²⁹. They also showed positive β_{pgls} for Ccr2/5/7, which is consistent with enhanced immune-cell recruitment, while β_{pgls} values were negative for Il1a/b and positive for Il17a, indicating a mixed Th1/Th17-type tone rather than blunt tolerance⁵⁴². Pattern-recognition signals also differed for

high- h^2 *Prevotella* species: β_{pgls} was positive for Nod1 (a cytosolic Gram-negative muropeptide sensor), and negative for Tlr5 (a transmembrane apical flagellin sensor)^{543,544}. Taking into consideration that most bacteria associated with the mucus layer tend to be non-motile Gram-negative bacteria, such as *Prevotella* species themselves, this suggests high- h^2 *Prevotella* benefit from an environment capable of responding to competitors, likely having adaptations against Nod1-triggered inflammation. Overall, these β_{pgls} signs fit a regulated, signalling-rich niche characterised by active trafficking and repair.

On this reading, the hypothesis that high- h^2 *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species are those capable of colonising well-structured and stable crypts is consistent with the gene-level β_{pgls} signs observed here and with contemporary knowledge about gut epithelial biology. At the same time, the observed differences plausibly reconcile how both genera can share a “crypt-proximal” niche yet segregate along micro-gradients within it.

d) Linking host genes to bacterial modules

A parsimonious abductive synthesis of all results is that host polygenic variation gates access to, and stability of, epithelial-proximal refuges within crypts and the overlying mucus. Under barrier-tight, hypoxia-stabilising, immune-modulated and low-washout regimes, *Bacteroides* lineages equipped with adhesion, capsule sialylation, T6SS, anti-phage and cobamide biosynthesis apparatus present higher h^2 , compared to other species, because their abundances covary tightly with such host-determined habitat conditions across individuals. At the same time, under regimes with stronger cytokine-linked redox dynamics and microaerobic pulses at the surface, *Prevotella* lineages bearing SOR and growth-burst machinery become more host-tracked at the crypt edge, where they are more connected to a larger number of other bacteria, while still being part of the same local guild as *Bacteroides*.

The consequences of such dynamics result in the patterns commonly reported by the literature: i) the apparent *Bacteroides* vs *Prevotella*-based sample dissimilarity, when faecal samples are analysed, with *Bacteroides* tending to dominate only when the faecal samples come

from patients with highly inflammatory conditions, which are usually associated with the aggressive destabilisation of the epithelial barrier and, consequently the protected deep crypt niche⁵⁴⁵; and ii) the collaborative cross-feeding chains that result in health promotion not because of specific bacterial species, but because of the collective products they generate when in collaboration.

An example that could be constructed based on the results obtained is the potential collaboration between the host, *Prevotella*, and *Bacteroides*. By providing an adequate niche where *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* can coexist, the union of the remarkable capacity for corrinoid biosynthesis by the former and succinate production by the latter can result in an integrated stimulation of the succinate pathway, which depends on corrinoids to convert succinate to propionate and can be performed by both^{64,516,518,546,547}. Then, the same propionate can act as a carbon source for the aerobic respiration performed by the absorptive enterocytes, thereby reducing the amount of oxygen that reaches the lumen and contributing to the maintenance of an anoxic chamber for strict anaerobes without defences against oxygen, such as those adopted by *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*^{5,548}.

Luminal bacteria, mostly dominated by the Gram-positive Clostridiales (Firmicutes A), release butyrate as the main by-product of their fermentation, which can also be consumed by enterocytes⁵⁴⁹, but also has a second role as a modulator of the mucosal innate immune system, through FFAR2-associated signalling^{548,550}. This contributes to the reduction of local and even systemic inflammation levels, reducing the risks associated with inflammatory processes to host health. At the same time, it makes the caecum more tolerant to other commensals, lacking the same immune evasion apparatuses found in *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, and thus becomes another factor capable of contributing to community diversity, establishing a resilient homeostatic state. Nevertheless, to turn such claims into possible mechanisms worth testing in experimental procedures, it is essential to take a step further and identify whether these bacteria and the emerging community structures associated with them are linked by causal paths.

A last observation that cannot be left behind is the fact that while *Bacteroides* tended to reveal much more COG/ENOG functions significantly enriched in high- and low- h^2 species than *Prevotella*

(122 vs 7, respectively), the opposite trend happened when the comparison involved the number of host genes that had significant positive or negative associations with their species h^2 values (75 vs 134, respectively). A possible explanation is that, given the overall bigger genomes of *Bacteroides* compared to *Prevotella* (Figure 22B), it is possible that such differences confer greater versatility on *Bacteroides* to deal with the specific conditions imposed by the crypt niche. So, while the number of factors influencing host-control niche-structuring tends to be more influential on *Prevotella*'s heritability, the number of factors behind the capability of bacterial adaptation to the same niche conditions tends to be more favourable to *Bacteroides*, suggesting two different strategies for adapting to the same environment.

This is in accordance with a recent claim that gut community assembly is organized by a hierarchy of constraints, beginning with the host setting the “habitat filter,” mainly by controlling redox chemistry (oxygen, nitrate) and mucosal conditions along the gut; then, with the commensals sorting themselves within the niches that pass that filter based on metabolic capacities and competitive traits; and finally, with priority effects stabilizing whichever bacteria got established earlier. The key idea is that host physiology does not just passively tolerate commensal bacteria; it actively sculpts which functional guilds can exist in a given spatial niche, especially near the epithelium, by restricting or leaking electron acceptors like O_2 and NO_3^- and by shaping mucus, barrier tone, and inflammation. When host control is intact, the colon remains anaerobic and is dominated by obligate anaerobic fermenters. In contrast, loss of control (e.g., inflammation, epithelial stress) allows facultative anaerobes, such as Enterobacteriaceae, to proliferate^{551–553}. From this perspective, *Prevotella* heritability could be the result of being more tightly gated by the host-level habitat filter. By contrast, *Bacteroides*' success is less about a single, strict host-controlled gate and more about encoded metabolic versatility that lets its different species adapt to slightly different resource and chemical microgradients within the same broad anaerobic guild.

e) Limitations and safeguards

Many caveats can be highlighted about the procedures deployed in this chapter. First, functional annotation remains uneven: *Bacteroides* genetic modules are historically better characterized than *Prevotella*'s, which likely deflates enrichment counts in the latter. Second, COG/ENOG presence is a coarse proxy that does not capture phase variation, regulation, or mobile elements that are central to mucosal life in Bacteroidota; some signals will therefore be cryptic to genome-content statistics. Furthermore, the genomes used for the enrichment analysis keep being the ones mapped from the GTDB R207 database, which results in a proximal representation of the bacterial genomes likely present in the HS rats' caecal samples. Third, although cross-validation and LOCO GRMs were used to mitigate selection bias and proximal contamination, sentinel SNPs act as proxies for regulatory architecture that may lie outside annotated loci. The SNP selection adopted, which considered only SNPs located within the candidate genes, without exploring upstream and downstream windows, not only reduce the chances of capturing *cis* regulatory factors that might be of great relevance, but assume the simplistic idea that such group of SNPs likely incurs in allele dosages that represent the number of functional copies of the gene, which is not necessarily true, given intronic regions, alternative splicing, and other mechanisms that might result in deviant effects. Finally, context dependence is expected: the rat caecum's mucus and crypt architecture differs from other regions and species; nevertheless, the biophysical principles (oxygen gradients, diffusion limits, immune policing) are well established and make the observed patterns mechanistically plausible.

f) Conclusion

In summary, converging lines of evidence suggest that host polygenic effects on *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* are manifestations of host control over the crypt as a niche for commensal bacteria, being a complex, mucin-rich, epithelial-proximal habitat with a defined shape, a certain chemical composition, a renovation dynamic, and different interconnected immuno-physiological processes and gradients. The same host variants that shift the community toward Ent1 also increase both heritable genera and the corresponding co-abundance guild they belong to, which is consistent with pleiotropic gating of a shared mucosal domain. Yet,

the distinct patterns of functional enrichment and opposite host-gene signs in key categories indicate micro-partitioning of that domain, with *Bacteroides* specialising in more isolated deep crypt-stabilised microcolonies and *Prevotella* in microaerotolerant growth at the crypt surface. The key message from the bacterial gene enrichments is that adhesion, immune evasion, contact-dependent antagonism and corrinoid economy mark the species that become highly heritable under host-stabilized crypt conditions; while the key message from the host associated genes is that barrier integrity, inflammasome tone, cytokine-linked redox and ECM structure are the levers through which the host makes those conditions more or less stable, thereby modulating bacterial heritability, shedding light to the real architecture behind host polygenic effects on gut bacteria. These insights suggest a niche-centric paradigm of host-microbiome genetics and justify the mechanism-guided, polygenic strategy adopted here. The sentinel variants mapped provide the natural instruments for the causal inference undertaken next, where pleiotropy and mediation define the path from host genotypes to the mucosal niche, modulating heritable bacteria and the whole community structure, in a way that they might end influencing host phenotypes.

Methodologically, this chapter underscored the value of a polygenic, mechanistic-guided paradigm for microbiome-related complex traits, reinforcing the importance of making use of more biology-driven knowledge to interpret such multifaceted systemic dynamics, instead of simply relying on a limited statistics-driven GWAS analysis⁴¹⁹. Heritability estimates and genetic correlations were modelled in mixed-effects frameworks that absorbed relatedness and shared environment, and the hypothesis-driven candidate-genes strategy (with cross-validated sentinels and phylogeny-aware PGLS) increased interpretability relative to agnostic scans, which often lack power for small effects at the microbiome scale. This trade-off (less breadth, more mechanistic resolution) resulted in a collection of results from different fronts (e.g., bacterial-centred and host-centred) with converging patterns that reflected other phenomena already described in the literature, setting up the causal questions addressed in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 7. CAUSAL PATHS FROM HERITABLE BACTERIA TO HOST METABOLISM

7.1 Introduction

a) Metabolic diseases as an alarming public health issue

Obesity and diabetes now constitute concurrent global epidemics with profound human and economic costs. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that in 2022, 2.5 billion adults were overweight and 890 million were living with obesity (roughly 1 in 8 people) with prevalence having more than doubled since 1990; trends mirrored among children and adolescents⁵⁵⁴. Recent burden analyses indicate that deaths attributable to high BMI rose to about 3.7 million in 2021, underscoring the accelerating mortality impact of excess adiposity⁵⁵⁵. In parallel, metabolic risk from high blood sugar ranks among the top three contributors to early death and poor health worldwide. Diabetes prevalence has climbed to an estimated 589 million adults in 2024 and is projected to reach ~853 million by 2050⁵⁵⁶. In 2024, diabetes caused ~3.4 million deaths and consumed roughly US\$1.015 trillion in global health expenditure⁵⁵⁶, while the broader economic impact of overweight and obesity is projected to exceed US\$4.32 trillion annually by 2035⁵⁵⁷. From a biomedical standpoint, obesity and dysglycemia are highly polygenic with substantial pleiotropy and context dependence^{558,559}. This genetic architecture interacts with diet, activity, medications, and even microbiome exposures to shape risk and therapeutic response, making “one-size-fits-all” strategies blunt, therefore encouraging precision approaches that integrate genomics with environmental modification^{560,561}.

b) Genetic architecture of BMI and fasting glucose in HS rats

Work in HS rats has begun to resolve the polygenic architecture underlying BMI and glycaemic traits while also clarifying its limits. A landmark GWAS with 3,173 HS rats measured body weight, BMI, multiple fat pad masses, and fasting glucose across three centres

(including the two centres corresponding to the MI and NY cohorts adopted by the current study) and identified 32 independent loci; several intervals narrowed to single genes (for example, *Epha5*, *Nrg1*, *Klhl14*) and others contained strong candidates such as *Adcy3* and *Prlhr*¹¹⁵. The study also documented strong phenotypic and genetic correlations among adiposity traits and fasting glucose, with extensive pleiotropy across loci, illustrating shared genetic control of obesity and glycaemia in this model. A subsequent work that combined physiological traits with liver and adipose transcriptomes leveraged mediation analysis to move beyond loci and nominate likely causal mediators, such as *Grk5*, *Krtcap3*, *Ilrun*, and *Rfx6*, with experimental support from knockdown/knockout models for several candidates, thereby connecting variants to tissue-specific gene expression and, in turn, to adiposity and triglycerides⁵⁶². Earlier studies had already established that this outbred population was suitable for fine-mapping metabolic loci at high resolution, resulting in the refinement of QTLs for glucose tolerance, and helping to localise candidate regions within a few megabases⁵⁶³. Furthermore, it has also been reviewed that the eight HS founder backgrounds contributed to the identification of broad cardiometabolic risk variation, including glucose intolerance, insulin resistance, and BMI under controlled environments, strengthening inferences about the genetic architecture behind such diseases compared with typical human cohorts¹¹⁴. What remains missing, however, is equally clear: despite locus discovery and mediator nomination, most causal variants and mechanisms are unresolved; sex-specific and gene-by-environment effects are incompletely mapped; and cross-species translation is imperfect at the single-gene level even when broader molecular networks appear conserved between rats and humans⁵⁶⁴.

Integrating the gut microbiome into HS-rat systems genetics can provide an additional path to resolve the most persistent gaps in the genetic architecture of BMI and glycaemic traits. First, microbial taxa, genes, and metabolites can act as experimentally tractable mediators between host variants and metabolic phenotypes; joint mapping of such metabolic QTLs with microbiome QTLs, followed by statistical mediation and colocalization, can turn pleiotropic “locus hits” into mechanistic chains, something that HS designs are uniquely positioned to test under controlled environments and large sample sizes. Proof-of-concept already exists in outbred rodent resources, showing that host genotype shapes both microbiota and

metabolic readouts, enabling the nomination of mediators that can be validated by perturbation. In mice, for example, host-diet-genotype interactions reprogram microbiota and insulin-related traits with identifiable bacterial mediators, and systems-genetics studies have linked host loci (for example, at amylase and bile-acid pathways) to microbial functions and metabolic endpoints^{565,566}. Second, causality, often elusive in pure GWAS, can be established with microbiome-directed experiments that are practical in HS rats: antibiotics or gnotobiotic rederivation, reciprocal faecal microbiota transplants (FMT) between divergent HS lines, and addition or removal of candidate consortia or metabolites, all of which have repeatedly transferred insulin resistance or adiposity phenotypes across hosts in preclinical and clinical contexts. Such manipulations allow one to test whether an HS host locus exerts its effect via a microbial intermediary (loss of effect after microbiome depletion and rescue with targeted reconstitution), thereby converting statistical associations into causal mechanisms^{103,567,568}. Finally, cross-species translation improves when we compare conserved microbial functions and metabolites rather than one-to-one taxa or genes: microbial carbohydrate-utilization signatures linked to insulin resistance, the capacity of FMT to modulate human insulin sensitivity, and drug-microbiome interactions (for example, metformin's microbiome-mediated benefits) define functional modules that can be mapped in HS rats and then aligned with human cohorts, narrowing the gap between rodent loci and human mechanisms, as already suggested for mice¹³⁴.

c) Fasting glucose and the gut microbiome

Fasting plasma glucose is widely used as a practical indicator of insulin resistance because, in the basal state, hepatic glucose production should be restrained by insulin. When the liver is insulin-resistant, hepatic output remains inappropriately high, and fasting glycaemia rises. Surrogate indices derived from fasting glucose and insulin primarily reflect hepatic insulin sensitivity, providing epidemiologic scalability even if they lack the mechanistic precision of clamp methods⁵⁶⁹. In parallel, multi-omics human studies increasingly link gut microbial activity to insulin resistance: a large metagenomics and metabolomics analysis showed that insulin-resistant individuals harbour elevated faecal monosaccharides and a

gut microbial signature enriched for carbohydrate-utilisation pathways that correlate with host inflammatory signalling, suggesting a microbiome-host axis that promotes impaired insulin action⁵⁷⁰. In addition, broader population studies have reported lower microbial diversity and depletion of butyrate producers in type 2 diabetes, consistent with links between the gut ecosystem and glycaemic dysregulation, although effect sizes vary across cohorts and designs⁵⁷¹. Critically, antidiabetic drugs profoundly reshape the gut microbiome, reflecting that the failure to account for treatment can confound apparent microbe-glycaemia associations, which argues for careful adjustment or stratification in microbiome-glycaemia analyses⁵⁷².

d) BMI and the gut microbiome

The relationship between BMI and the gut microbiome is compelling but nuanced. Early reports emphasised reduced diversity and a higher F:B ratio in obesity, yet re-analyses and meta-analyses have shown that this ratio is not a reliable biomarker and that between-study heterogeneity and confounding are substantial^{573,574}. More recent pooled and harmonised analyses recovered a more consistent signal of modestly reduced α -diversity and shifts in functional pathways in obesity, while also highlighting variability across populations, diets, and technical pipelines⁵⁷⁵. Emerging multi-cohort work maps microbiome features tied to cardiometabolic health, but generalization across cohorts remains challenging and effect sizes for BMI per se are generally small relative to lifestyle factors⁵⁷⁶.

Together, these observations support the idea that obesity and fasting glucose are influenced by overlapping, pleiotropic genetic architectures in HS rats, with fasting glucose being an accessible, hepatic insulin-resistance-weighted readout that can be contextualised by gut microbial ecology, while BMI-microbiome associations exist but are modest, context-dependent, and best interpreted with attention to medications and diet.

e) Causal inference for microbiome research

While association studies have mapped thousands of links between the gut microbiome and human phenotypes, few have created a

foothold for genetics-anchored causal inference. Studies combining metagenomics with MR have reported putative causal effects of microbially derived metabolites and taxa on metabolic traits, while also showing how often naive associations fail under causal scrutiny^{15,16,389,577,578}. At the same time, meta-analyses across diseases show broad, system-level dysbiosis patterns rather than single “culprit” species, underscoring that causal signals might be also embedded in community-level emergent properties rather than individual taxa alone⁵⁷⁹. These insights motivate a strategy that tests both taxon-level and community-level mediators and treats the microbiome as an interacting system.

a) Mediation analysis using genetic instruments

Mediation analysis decomposes an exposure-outcome relationship into indirect paths through a mediator and a residual direct path. In the counterfactual framework, the product-of-coefficients approach estimates the mediated (indirect) effect as $\alpha \times \beta$, where α captures the exposure-to-mediator association and β the mediator-to-outcome effect adjusted for the exposure. Significance is then assessed for the direct (γ) and indirect paths, and if only the indirect path is considered statistically significant, the mediation is assumed to be the mechanism through which the exposure exerts effects on the outcome⁵⁸⁰. In microbiome research, mediation analysis has been typically used to investigate whether microbiome features (i.e., the relative abundances of a given bacterial taxon) mediate the effects of certain diets on host health⁵⁸¹. However, mediation analysis also provides a principled way to ask whether host variants influence metabolic phenotypes via the microbiome, while simultaneously quantifying any remaining direct genetic effect. This is attractive because it yields path-specific estimates that map onto biology and assumes the principle that the reverse path from the mediator to the genetic variant is not possible, once host genes can only be obtained through vertical transmission⁵⁸². Thus, this design serves as a way to identify indirect paths as causal paths. Nevertheless, it also has limitations, being sensitive to weak instruments (i.e., host genetic variants used as exposures with low α values). Therefore, the definition of clear rules that specifically comprehends a robust use of genetic instruments as the exposures is established by the MR approach, moving from the confirmation of mediation to the statistic validation of causal paths.

b) Mendelian randomisation

MR formalises the rules of using genetic instruments to test whether variation in a putative exposure causes differences in an outcome⁵⁸³. Valid instruments must be strongly associated with the exposure, independent of confounders, and affect the outcome only through the exposure (no horizontal pleiotropy). In practice, researchers in the field gate instruments using strength metrics, such as F-statistics and orientation checks, including the Steiger test, to ensure the instrument explains more variance in the exposure than in the outcome, as well as heterogeneity diagnostics. They also meta-analyse across folds or cohorts and prefer concordant signs between total and mediated effects^{584,585}. Thus, combining a first look using the mediation analysis, and then sift with MR aligns with best-practice guidance and purpose-built resources that emphasise instrument validation and directionality.

c) Structured equation model (SEM)

SEM estimates a network of directed dependencies simultaneously, allowing the integration of multiple mediators and outcomes and the partition of total effects into direct and indirect components within a single, coherent system. The extent to which the proposed model fits the data can be first assessed by robust ML, fitting a trimmed model that keeps only FDR-supported paths. Then, the final validated model can be re-fitted with Bayesian SEM to obtain posterior intervals and, therefore, a second distribution-sensitive check on model fit. The two engines are complementary: frequentist SEM is efficient and offers familiar fit indices for iterative pruning, while Bayesian SEM (BSEM) adds partial pooling via priors and transparent uncertainty quantification, which is especially valuable in complex microbiome systems with correlated mediators. Crucially, once causal ordering among microbial features has already been anchored by valid instruments and mediation/MR evidence, the host-gene nodes can be dropped to only interrogate the validity of an integrated view of the mediation network^{586,587}.

f) Complementary strategies to map causal paths

Overall, the results obtained so far suggest that the host genetic background simultaneously influences the relative abundances of *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, their co-abundance guild, and the whole community structure (Table 6), resulting in the two enterotypes observed (Figure 12). Furthermore, based on the combined analysis of the genes enriched in the species within these genera with high h^2 values and the host genes associated with such heritability, it was hypothesized that host polygenic effects on these bacteria are associated with certain conditions that allow them to colonise the caecal crypts, with *Bacteroides* being capable to penetrate it, while *Prevotella* occupies the region of the crypt opening (Tables 8 and 9). However, it is not clear yet how these different microbiome systemic levels interact with each other, and, most importantly, how these elements can influence host health. Thus, given the identification of host variants that can be tested as instruments for causal inference analyses, the objective of this chapter is to identify causal paths and determine the extent to which the selected microbiome features affect one another, ultimately influencing host metabolism, using BMI and fasting blood glucose levels as proof-of-concept traits. In order to structure the causal inference analysis, it was assumed that the influence chain begins with the two genera as collinear exogenous components that cause the guild, which may then join them in causal paths affecting α -diversity and β -diversity. Additionally, given the observation that β -diversity PCo1 represents the continuum between the two enterotypes (Figure 13D), with Ent1 being more phylogenetically diverse than Ent2 (Figure 14C), it was also assumed that α -diversity vary in response to β -diversity. Lastly, all these microbiome traits were assumed to have direct causal paths to both BMI and glucose (Figure 26).

Figure 26: Overall representation of the hypothesis about the multi-level causal path involving host genes, heritable *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, community-level measurements and host metabolic traits. **A)** Host polygenic effects on *Bacteroides* (blue bacterial cells) and *Prevotella* (purple bacterial cells) likely happen through multiple factors controlling the stabilisation of well-structured, dynamic, mucin-rich and immune-selective crypts. While such conditions allow adapted *Bacteroides* to penetrate the crypt mucus layer and live in the particular conditions of the crypt base, heritable *Prevotella* species likely occupy the crypt opening. **B)** Possible causal paths to be tested, from the two heritable bacterial genera to host BMI and fasting blood glucose levels, directly or indirectly. The double arrow between *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* represent possible covariance between them due to external factors. Created in BioRender.com¹³⁰.

The assessment will begin with a mediation analysis, using host variants as the exposure and the microbiome traits as mediators and intermediate outcomes, as outlined in Figure 26. Additionally, BMI and glucose will be treated only as outcomes. The second step will involve the selection of significant full mediations to unidirectional MR tests, validating the genetic variants as instruments and the direction of the causal paths. Finally, a SEM combining these paths will be designed, refined and validated.

7.2 Methods

a) Mediation analysis and instrument validation

The mediation analysis was included in the pipeline created to identify and validate sentinel SNPs associated with host polygenic effects on *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* (Figure 21), defined as HERMES-WIRE's Step 4. This was designed to leverage the cross-validation framework, using the same five folds of the testing subset as in the PGLS analysis, based on the sentinel SNPs defined in the training subset (Figure 21). However, it is important to highlight that while only the sentinel SNPs associated with h^2 values were selected for each of the two taxonomic traits (*Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*), when Guild 3, α - and β -diversity were used as mediators, all mapped sentinel SNPs were employed (Figure 21).

The causal chains were estimated using three mixed-model regressions for each gene, mediator, and outcome combination, with GENESIS, allowing for the estimation of fixed effects while accounting for relatedness and shared environment via LOCO GRMs, dam, and cage covariance matrices (utilising the same random-effect structure in every model). Specifically, for each candidate instrument G, microbial mediator M and outcome Y:

- (1) $M \sim G$: the α path;
- (2) $Y \sim G$: the total effect c ;
- (3) $Y \sim M+G$: the mediator \rightarrow outcome β path and the direct effect c' .

The indirect effect was computed as $\alpha \times \beta$ ($\alpha\beta$) with a delta-method SE, which is the classical product-of-coefficients mediation estimator, and significance was assessed with a normal approximation (Sobel-type test)⁵⁸⁸. Multiple testing was controlled by BH FDR ($p_{adj} < 0.10$) per mediator. After FDR correction, the results would be classified as: i) "Only direct effect", if c' was significant and $\alpha\beta$ not (Positive or Negative, according to the c' signal); ii) "Full mediation", if $\alpha\beta$ was significant and c' not; iii) "Partial mediation" if both c' and $\alpha\beta$ were significant with the same signal; "Partial mediation - Reverse", when they were both significant but with different signals; iv) "Pleiotropy", when α and c' were significant but $\alpha\beta$ not (Positive or Negative, according to the

signals of α and c'); and v) “No effects”, when no direct or indirect paths (c' or $\alpha\beta$) were significant.

After selecting only the paths resulting in “Full mediation” to avoid pleiotropy, three unidirectional MR tests were performed. To guard against weak instruments, the instrument strength was estimated via the first-stage F -statistic, while directionality was validated with a Steiger test heuristic, which requires the instrument to explain more variance in the mediator than in the outcome. Then, a simple Wald ratio and its SE were computed to summarise the implied causal effect of the mediator on the outcome per variant^{583,584}. Together, these criteria formed an “IV-OK” flag, which denoted the variant as a valid instrument and the causal path as having a consistent direction from the mediator to the outcome, and not the opposite.

All fold-level coefficients and SEs for α , β , c , c' , $\alpha\beta$ and Wald ratios were meta-analysed across folds by fixed-effect inverse-variance weighting to obtain cross-fit estimates, SEs and two-sided Z tests. Heterogeneity was summarised with Cochran’s Q and the I^2 statistic⁵⁸⁹. Fixed-effects meta-analysis was chosen to summarise cross-validation replicates because the folds were balanced partitions of the same cohort rather than independent studies. Nevertheless, heterogeneity metrics were retained as diagnostics of instability. For families of tests aggregated by mediator, BH FDR control was applied ($p_{adj} < 0.10$). It is essential to note that the pipeline was designed to ensure that each run corresponded to a specific microbiome trait chosen as a mediator (e.g., *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella*, Guild 3, α - and β -diversity).

The final indicators used to nominate robust, likely causal paths combined evidence from the mediation, MR and cross-fit meta stages. A sentinel-mediator-outcome triplet was considered a “Validated Causal Path” when the cross-fit Wald ratio for the mediator was significant after FDR correction, the instrument passed the IV-OK gate (first-stage $F \geq 10$, Steiger-consistent direction, significant α , and non-significant c'), and the sign of indirect and total effects was coherent across folds. These decision rules closely mirror current practice in MR when prioritising biologically credible, directionally consistent signals under realistic pleiotropy^{583,584}.

b) Structured equation modelling

SEM was run outside the main pipeline with a custom R script to assess how they would behave together under a single multivariate model (Figure 26B). Before starting to fit the proposed model, each variable used (e.g., *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella*, Guild 3, α - and β -diversity and glucose) was residualized with the same random-effects included in other tests (GRM, dams and cages) using the package sommer v4.3.7⁵⁹⁰, given that both tools used posteriorly to validate the model (lavaan v0.6-19⁵⁹¹ and blavaan v0.5-8⁵⁹²) did not allow the incorporation of GRM as a random effect. This way, the values used in the initial model were already adjusted for relatedness and shared environment. Then, the entire matrix containing this group of variables and the allele dosages of all sentinel SNPs included per run, according to the target mediator, was scaled using Z-score normalisation with R base³²⁶. After that, the following model skeleton was provided to the script workflow, considering not only validated causal paths but also the remaining ones to guarantee the full structure imagined previously (Figure 26B), however, focusing only on glucose as an outcome, given the mediation/MR results discussed further in the chapter. In addition, the fixed residual covariance between the two exogenous variables (Bact, for *Bacteroides* and Prev, for *Prevotella*) were also included:

Bact ~ ~ *Prev*

Guild ~ *Bact* + *Prev*

Beta ~ *Bact* + *Prev* + *Guild*

Alpha ~ *Bact* + *Prev* + *Guild* + *Beta*

Glucose ~ *Bact* + *Prev* + *Guild* + *Beta* + *Alpha*

The initial model was fit with lavaan using an MLR estimator and robust SEs (i.e., the standard frequentist SEM approach). All regressions were labelled so they could be trimmed interactively based on BH FDR ($p_{adj} < 0.10$), with the objective to refine and refit the model until only significant regressions and paths (direct or indirect) remained. Final fit indices were reported for the evaluation of good or bad fit: the Comparative Fit Index (CFI), the Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and the Standardised Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR). Furthermore, the code for a Mermaid⁵⁹³ diagram

representing the winning model was also generated in the end to facilitate its visual representation. As a sensitivity analysis, the final trimmed model was re-fit with blavaan using weakly informative priors: $normal(0,0.5)$. The test would then provide Bayesian confidence intervals (CIs) for regressions and paths, along with the posterior predictive p -value (PPP) fit index. Furthermore, along with the individual estimates for each regression and path, the R^2 values per mediator and outcome were also provided for both lavaan and blavaan summaries as a measure of the extent to which the model could explain the variances of these components.

7.3 Results

a) Identified causal paths

After coupling the mediation analysis with MR to validate causal paths involving the host genetic variants selected for each mediator, it became clear that a combination of effects was occurring for all mediator-outcome pairs (Figure 27). The results showed that *Bacteroides* presented fully mediated effects for all outcomes, lacking validated causal paths only for BMI, which was an outcome that was not involved in any causal path. At the same time, it was interesting to see that for the mediator-outcome pairs that presented validated causal paths for some instruments, there were always other variants that were only partially mediated or responsible for pleiotropic effects on the mediator and the outcome (Figure 27).

Figure 27: Number of variants involved in different types of effects involving a mediator and different outcomes.

Apart from these highlights, the most important outcome from this analysis was the confirmation of causal paths for almost all routes envisioned for such a systemic influence chain (Figure 26), except for those to BMI, and the paths from *Prevotella*, Guild 3, and β -diversity PCo1 to glucose. All instrument-mediator-outcome trios validated as causal paths are listed in Annexe I, Supplementary Tables S13 and S14, where the main values used for mediation analysis and unidirectional MR are also shared, respectively.

b) A unified causal model

The trimmed SEM converged cleanly and provided a very good fit to the data. In lavaan (SE robust), the scaled χ^2 was 1.20 with 3 degrees

of freedom (df) ($p = 0.753$), CFI = 1.000 and TLI = 1.005, SRMR = 0.007, and RMSEA ≈ 0.000 with a 90% CI up to 0.026. By conventional guidance, CFI/TLI ≥ 0.95 , SRMR ≤ 0.08 , and RMSEA ≤ 0.06 indicate good fit, so all indices meet or exceed recommended thresholds; moreover, because this is a very low-df path model (df = 3), the excellent SRMR/CFI/TLI are particularly informative while the already-near-zero RMSEA should be interpreted with the usual caution about RMSEA's instability at small df. These interpretations follow standard cut-offs⁵⁹⁴, together with work specifically warning that RMSEA can misbehave in small-df models⁵⁹⁵.

Bayesian validation with blavaan closely agreed with the frequentist estimates and indicated an excellent absolute fit and convergence. All key coefficients remained directionally and numerically stable, with $\hat{R} \approx 1.000$ across parameters, and the PPP was 0.551. In BSEM, PPP values near 0.5 indicate that the model can reproduce the data well (extreme values near 0 or 1 suggest misfit), so a PPP around 0.55 supports a good fit⁵⁹⁶.

The final directed structure retained the regressions: *Prevotella* \rightarrow Guild 3 ($\beta = 0.888$, $z = 48.8$), *Prevotella* \rightarrow β -diversity PCo1 (-0.333 , $z = -3.68$) and Guild 3 \rightarrow β -diversity PCo1 (-0.318 , $z = -3.70$), along with *Bacteroides* \rightarrow α -diversity (0.262, $z = 4.76$), *Prevotella* \rightarrow α -diversity (-0.311 , $z = -4.70$), and β -diversity \rightarrow α -diversity (-0.303 , $z = -5.51$). For glucose, the retained predictors were *Bacteroides* (-0.362 , $z = -6.68$), *Prevotella* ($+0.355$, $z = 6.42$) and α -diversity (-0.102 , $z = -3.04$). Residual covariances included a strong positive *Bacteroides* $\sim\sim$ *Prevotella* ($r \approx 0.80$), while the residual links of *Bacteroides* with Guild 3 or β -diversity PCo1 were small and non-significant after trimming. Variance explained (R^2) was high for Guild 3 (0.789) and moderate for β -diversity PCo1 (0.400), but low for α -diversity (0.091) and glucose (0.068), indicating that the microbial layers were well captured by the retained drivers, whereas the host metabolic outcome remained largely influenced by factors outside this model (Figure 28, Table 10, And Annexe I, Supplementary Table S15).

Figure 28: Representation of the final structured equation model, with arrows connecting two objects symbolising direct effects, while simple lines connecting two objects represent residual covariance. Light blue boxes denote microbiome traits in the genus and guild levels, light green boxes denote microbiome diversity traits, and the yellow box characterises a host phenotype. The values within grey boxes are the estimated regression coefficients in standard deviations. Created in Mermaidchart.com⁵⁹³

Table 10: Net effects in standard deviation (SD) for each output, considering the sum of direct and indirect effects from the exogenous variables *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, along with the outputs' R^2 values, representing the proportion of their variance explained by the model.

Output	R^2	Net effect (SD)	Number of paths
Guild	0.79	0.89	1
Beta	0.40	-0.62	2
Alpha	0.09	0.14	4
Glucose	0.07	-0.02	6

Total and path-decomposed effects clarified how *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* influence fasting blood glucose levels. For *Bacteroides*, the total standardised effect on glucose was -0.389 (lavaan) and -0.380 (blavaan), dominated by the direct pathway (-0.362), with a

smaller supporting indirect component via α -diversity of -0.0267 . For *Prevotella*, the total standardised effect on glucose was $+0.368$ (lavaan) and $+0.359$ (blavaan). The direct path *Prevotella* \rightarrow glucose accounted for $\sim 96\%$ of this total ($+0.355$). The remaining $\sim 3\text{-}4\%$ came from three antagonistic indirect routes that nearly cancel: a positive *Prevotella* \rightarrow α -diversity \rightarrow glucose path ($+0.0317$) reflecting the double-negative chain (*Prevotella* lowers α -diversity; α -diversity lowers glucose), offset by two small negative paths that pass through community structure before α -diversity: *Prevotella* \rightarrow β -diversity PCo1 \rightarrow α -diversity \rightarrow glucose (-0.0103) and *Prevotella* \rightarrow Guild 3 \rightarrow β -diversity PCo1 \rightarrow α -diversity \rightarrow glucose (-0.0087). This decomposition reveals that, in the current data, *Prevotella* primarily raises glucose directly, with modest countervailing community-mediated brakes, while *Bacteroides* lowers glucose both directly and, to a lesser extent, by nudging α -diversity downward.

Looking upstream, *Prevotella* almost entirely determined the Guild 3 node ($\beta = 0.888$; $R^2 = 0.789$) and exerted a strong overall pull on β -diversity PCo1 (total effect -0.615), splitting between its direct path to β -diversity PCo1 (about 54% of the total magnitude) and the Guild 3-mediated route (about 46%). Additionally, α -diversity integrated three inputs: *Bacteroides* positive, *Prevotella* negative, and β -diversity negative, yielding a modest net total effect across sources (≈ 0.137 standardised), given that opposing influences partially cancel. Together, these patterns explain why the net effect on glucose across all sources nearly cancels (≈ -0.021 when summing the contributions), even though the organism-specific totals remain sizable and opposite in sign.

7.4 Discussion, limitations and conclusion

The objective of this chapter was to move beyond association and test a directional, biologically grounded chain from host genotype to specific microbial genera, from there to community structure, and ultimately to metabolic readouts, adopting BMI and fasting blood glucose levels as proof-of-concept indicators. Across mediation, instrument-gated causal estimation, and structural equations in both frequentist and Bayesian forms, a consistent picture emerged in which *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* exert countervailing direct effects on glycaemia that are subsequently modulated, often attenuated or even sign-inverted, by community-level routes (Figure 28). The

consequence is a near-zero signed total (Total Effect SD ≈ -0.021), illustrating that what appears contradictory at the genus level is resolved once the system routes are explicit: strong, opposing direct signals can cancel after being reweighted by community structure.

This systems view helps reconcile apparent conflicting reports about *Prevotella* and metabolic control. Studies in humans and mice, for example, have implicated *Prevotella copri* in increased biosynthetic capacity for branched-chain amino acids and in the worsening of insulin resistance, while others have pointed to the same species as responsible for alleviating hyperglycaemia⁵⁹⁵⁻⁵⁹⁷. The present pattern of large direct effects that are moderated through guilds and diversity (Figure 28), provides a mechanistic bridge: the sign of the genus-level association is not universal but depends on ecological routing through the community. Where the surrounding network channels *Prevotella*'s activity into functions that raise α -diversity and stabilise the interface, benefits can be seen; where such wiring is less strong, the detrimental direct path might predominate.

While the current study focuses on demonstrating how host polygenic effects can contribute to the definition of such alternative states, it is already well-documented that diet interventions play a significant role in this kind of modulation⁶⁰⁰. A practical consequence is that if the host genetic makeup does not provide the right conditions for *Prevotella* colonisation that results in a community structure favourable to homeostatic glycaemia, this can still be counteracted through dietary interventions that can offer alternatives to a beneficial host-*Prevotella*-community wiring.

A similar systems logic can account for why *Bacteroides* emerged with an opposite direct association to glucose in this dataset (favouring glucose reduction), despite its frequent linkage to protein/fat-rich “Western” dietary patterns in observational studies, often associated with worse health conditions^{601,602}. Recent multi-omics work, reinforcing the role of microbial carbohydrate metabolism and host inflammatory tone in insulin resistance, further supports the interpretation that functional context, rather than genus labels, governs metabolic consequences⁵⁷⁰. Furthermore, the results obtained in the current research resonate the idea that, actually, because *Bacteroides* are able to colonise deep crypts and better deal with inflammation, what happens is that, even though its species

might promote glycaemia reduction, in studies involving inflamed, dysbiotic intestinal conditions where bacterial diversity is usually very low and insulin resistance takes place, they tend to be found as abundant, just for being adapted to such adversities, not because they are causing them.

The results also intersect with long-running debates on community typologies and diagnostic markers. The β -diversity axis summarised here is interpreted as an enterotype-like continuum dominated at one end by *Prevotella* (and other Bacteroidota) and by Firmicutes A at the other end. The finding that β -diversity and the functional guild transmit a share of the effect from heritable genera to glucose is consistent with consensus statements urging a balanced use of enterotype concepts: these axes are ecologically informative but must not be reified as single-cause explanations. In the same vein, the protective association of α -diversity observed here should not be overgeneralised into a universal diagnostic, since meta-analyses across diseases report that diversity reductions are inconsistent and modest outside a few conditions. The present framework clarifies why α -diversity can capture salutary community organisation in some contexts, but its metabolic meaning depends on how specific taxa, guilds, and host factors interact with it⁵⁷⁹.

It is also important to highlight that the same signs, respective to the effects exerted by a source on an outcome, were obtained in both the mediation/MR analysis and SEM. Additionally, the causal inference analysis reinforced the evidence seen in previous chapters, that *Prevotella* had a stronger link not only with the guild it belongs to, but also with α - and β -diversity than *Bacteroides*. These results sustained the fact that both genera and their guild were associated with negative β -diversity PCo1 values, meaning more proximity to Ent1-type communities at the same time that this composition reflects a higher phylogenetic α -diversity (Figure 28). Along with that, causal inference added a new layer to the understanding of such dynamics, revealing that not only these genera were genetically correlated with the guild and β -diversity (Table 7), meaning that the same host polygenic effects lead them to the same direction, but once they are favoured by such genetic makeup they are also capable to affect the community themselves, with an emphasis on the role of heritable *Prevotella*, which might exert stronger effects most likely due to their higher centrality in the bacterial network (Figure 22C).

An important conceptual addition is that instrument-defined causal paths for a given mediator \rightarrow outcome pair should be viewed as members of a larger family of paths. In a polygenic setting with correlated exposures (e.g., *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella*, and community traits), some variants will deliver “clean” mediation through the intended bacteria, while others will exert parallel or off-target effects (partial mediation or horizontal pleiotropy). The broader MR literature makes it clear that horizontal pleiotropy is common, motivating multivariable MR to separate direct effects of correlated exposures and the use of sensitivity estimators when instrument counts permit⁶⁰³. The recent findings therefore fit the expectation that both processes are happening concurrently: heritable bacteria shape higher-level community traits and glucose, while host variants also influence glucose via routes that bypass (or only partially traverse) the microbial mediator (Figure 27).

It is also notable that a robust causal signal was found for fasting glucose but not for BMI. This divergence is plausible on both biological and empirical grounds. Fasting glucose and insulin sensitivity can shift over short time scales through microbial metabolites (SCFAs, bile acids, branched-chain amino acids flux) and mucosal immunometabolism signalling, often without concurrent weight change; multiple trials and meta-analyses show improvement in insulin sensitivity or glycaemia after microbiome-targeted or diet fibre interventions with little or no immediate effect on body weight. By contrast, BMI is a slowly varying, highly polygenic trait whose variance is dominated by long-term energy balance, environment, and thousands of small-effect loci¹¹⁵. In that landscape, genus-level microbiome instruments may be too weak or too diffuse to detect BMI changes significantly in typical cohorts, even when glucose regulation does respond. This “fast glucose vs slow BMI” asymmetry is observed across lean-donor FMT trials that enhance insulin sensitivity without weight loss, along with fibre-responsive glycaemic improvements that precede weight change, and large-scale genetic studies confirming the extreme polygenicity of BMI^{115,567,600}.

Nevertheless, there are notable strengths and limitations that bound interpretation. By embracing a triangulation mindset, with the implementation of instruments to orient mediation and validating a

system of paths using SEM in both robust frequentist and Bayesian forms, the approach adopted tackles several common threats to inference simultaneously. It is essential to emphasise, though, that instrument validity remains the primary constraint on causal interpretation. Although instruments were stringently gated, microbiome-adjacent instruments are inherently susceptible to horizontal pleiotropy because the same host variant can influence multiple, correlated microbial and host processes^{510,603}. In settings with multiple related exposures (e.g., *Bacteroides*, *Prevotella*, guilds), it is recommended to estimate the direct effects conditional on the others. However, conditional instrument strength can degrade substantially relative to univariable strength, making it difficult to adopt multivariable MR⁶⁰³. When instrument numbers are small, these sensitivity tools may be underpowered, so residual pleiotropy cannot be totally ruled out.

Model specification also warrants caution. SEM fit indices were excellent, but RMSEA is known to be unstable at very small df, and the primary reliance should therefore be on CFI/TLI and SRMR in such models. Moreover, any specified path model risks omitting plausible edges; the finding that large absolute effects on glucose compress to a near-zero total underscores how modest misspecification could reweight cancellation among paths. These concerns argue for replication with alternative, but biologically plausible graphs, and for complementary Bayesian model comparisons when practical⁵⁹⁴. Furthermore, the fact that the model kept paths that were not identified as causal paths by the MR assessment, such as the direct effect of *Prevotella* on glucose levels, raises the hypothesis that non-mapped instruments might be behind it or even that the persistence of a possible non-causal path after trimming is an artificial result of the combination of the other paths included.

In conclusion, a system-level causal model was assembled, assuming that host genetic influences were propagated through heritable bacterial genera into the community structure and then to host fasting blood glucose levels. Opposite-signed direct effects of *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* were documented, and it was shown that guild-level and diversity-mediated paths frequently reduced or inverted these direct signals, reconciling contradictory findings in the literature and explaining why *Prevotella* can both “help” or “harm” depending on

host genetics and ecological context. The work advances microbiome causal inference by combining instrument-gated mediation with structural equations and by explicitly modelling community-level mediation, thereby moving the field beyond one-bacterium narratives and diversity-only heuristics. The overarching message for translational efforts is that interventions and diagnostics should be designed with community routing and host context in mind, acknowledging that durable metabolic effects will emerge from coordinated shifts in taxa, functions, and diversity rather than from any single lever.

CHAPTER 8. FINAL REMARKS

8.1 Summary and general discussion

The work undertaken across Chapters 3-7 assembled a coherent, mechanism-guided account of how host polygenic variation channels gut ecological structure toward a limited set of stable bacterial community configurations, with downstream consequences for host metabolism. A “polygenic-first” strategy was adopted rather than a “locus-first” scan, leveraging shallow-shotgun metagenomics, function-aware profiling, and LMMs to prioritise traits with significant host aggregate genetic effects. This design improved power and interpretability over amplicon-only or single-edge analyses (i.e., purely taxonomic or purely gene-centric) and enabled a system-level causal model in which host variants act primarily by modulating the crypt niche, thereby altering the abundance of keystone bacteria and the routing of community-level mediation to glycaemic levels. The resulting overall picture integrates and extends prior evidence that shallow-shotgun sequencing can recover species- and function-level structure with acceptable accuracy and reproducibility, at far lower cost than deep metagenomes, while providing marked advantages over 16S for taxonomic resolution and sparsity, which is pivotal for Quantitative Genetics and causal path modelling, when large cohorts must be profiled efficiently⁴¹.

Based on an experimental design that focused on HS rats kept under similar controlled laboratory conditions, with siblings never sharing the same cage, the collection of their caeca for microbiome analysis aimed to test a set of linked hypotheses, in order to ultimately run causal inference analyses using genetic instruments that would hardly emerge from agnostic GWAS, and non-conventional microbiome traits as mediators (i.e., guilds and diversity measurements). The hypotheses were: i) Multi-cohort datasets of HS rats are not limited by population structure; ii) Shallow shotgun data can reveal associations between different microbiome traits (e.g., bacterial taxa, EC4 functions, co-abundance guilds, α - and β -diversity); iii) Shallow shotgun data can yield better heritability values and detect more heritable taxa than 16S; iv) Heritable microbiome traits can also be detected among bacterial functions, guilds and diversity values; v) Associated multi-level microbiome traits are genetically correlated;

vi) Species with high heritability values within the same genus are enriched with functions that point out to the adaptations required to live in a highly host-controlled niche; vii) The additive effects of sentinel SNPs from a group of hypothesis-driven candidate genes can be associated with host polygenic effects across species of the same genus; viii) The same sentinel SNPs can be used as instruments in causal inference analyses involving multi-level microbiome traits and host phenotypes linked to metabolic health (e.g., BMI and fasting blood glucose levels).

In Chapter 3, it was demonstrated that the two HS cohorts pooled here lacked cohort-specific population structure, supporting joint heritability analyses and alleviating concerns about stratification artefacts in the genetic random-effects terms. This conclusion followed MANOVA/PERMANOVA over GRM principal components and Tracy-Widom screening of significant axes, with non-significant cohort effects supporting pooling for subsequent steps. In Chapter 4, two optimised Nextflow pipelines were described, as part of the HERMES-WIRE suite composed of four chained steps, each with its own pipeline, to perform the activities designed for this project in a reproducible way. These first two pipelines were developed to process shallow shotgun reads into taxonomic and function-centric count tables, define co-abundance guilds, diversity measures, network structures and enterotypes, harmonise inputs across cohorts, control compositionality, and fit REML LMMs for polygenic signals. The approach emphasised containerised, version-controlled, and parameterised execution to favour reproducibility on HPC. Furthermore, they focused on maximising the mapping ratio after aligning short reads to a broad reference bacterial and archaeal genome catalogue (GTDB R207^{44,45}), while reducing the loss of reads during filtering steps. The integrated pipelines also replicated the best solutions adopted by currently used tools^{157,180,212,283,284,290} to compensate for the limitations imposed by shallow sequencing, which resulted in a comprehensive characterisation of the HS rat caecal microbiome beyond simple taxonomic and functional profiling, integrating them with co-abundance guilds, networks, enterotypes, α - and β -diversity. This provided connected fragments of evidence about the existence of multi-level functional wiring. In Chapter 5, it was observed that significant host aggregate genetic effects tended to be very influenced by phylogenetic relationships, being concentrated in *Bacteroides* and

Prevotella species, with Guild 3 (where most *Bacteroides* and all *Prevotella* species were grouped) and β -diversity PCo1 also being heritable. In Chapter 6, genome-resolved enrichment uncovered that *Bacteroides* species with high h^2 values carried functions consisting mostly of vitamin biosynthesis, cell envelope flexibility, adhesion and defence, whereas *Prevotella* species with higher heritability were enriched with functions such as ROS detoxification, horizontal gene transfer and the anaerobic production of succinate. These patterns motivated a list of host candidate genes tied to barrier integrity, epithelial hypoxia, and immune tone for instrument-gated causal analyses. After selecting for each genus a sentinel-SNP per gene, following a cross-validation approach, the additive effects of such variants on the species pseudo-relative abundances were associated with their respective h^2 values, revealing genes that likely integrate the host polygenic effects on these bacteria. In Chapter 7, a three-step causal program (instrument-screened mediation and a trimmed SEM validated in both robust frequentist and Bayesian forms) was used to assemble a host \rightarrow keystone genera \rightarrow community \rightarrow metabolism chain. Opposite-signed direct paths from *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* to glucose were observed; however, community-level mediation via guilds and diversity often attenuated or inverted these direct signals. The model detected consistent mediation of fasting glucose, but not of BMI, aligning with prior human intervention and prediction studies, in which glycaemic outcomes modulation by microbiome composition can be detected in cross-sectional studies without revealing commensurate changes in body mass.

Placed in the current conceptual frame that points out the priority of host control over diet and priority effects in setting the conditions for gut habitat filters⁵⁵¹, these results suggest the existence of a crypt-scale host genetic constrain that not only modulates the colonisation and maintenance of caecal *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*, but also affects their influence in the host-microbiome ecosystem. Many studies in spatial gut ecology have already established that the gut is not a homogeneous tube; instead, each intestinal crypt constitutes a distinct microhabitat with its own oxygen tension, epithelial metabolic state, mucin and extracellular matrix (ECM) glycan chemistry, immune tone, and tightly associated microbial consortia³⁶⁵. These crypt consortia are not considered passive passengers. They have been correlated with local inflammation and epithelial metabolic programming and, crucially, they sit at the

earliest interface between host physiology and the microbial production of metabolites important to host health^{70,354,365}. In the HS rats examined here, specific host loci linked to epithelial oxygen handling (e.g., *Hif1a*, *Epas1*), epithelial barrier/tolerance and junctional programs (e.g., *Notch2*, *Tjp1*), and nutrient/hormonal sensing (e.g., *Ffar2*) were associated with the heritability of *Prevotella* and *Bacteroides* species. This is consistent with the idea that the host genome engineers crypt conditions, such as hypoxia profiles, mucin/ECM glycan availability, and local tolerance versus reactivity, acting as selective filters that shape which bacteria can successfully colonise and persist^{32,365,604}.

Ecologically the *Prevotella/Bacteroides*-dominated guild (Guild 3) did not act alone in a local scale. Its abundance was associated with global β -diversity structure, essentially behaving like a keystone module that helps organise which other taxa can persist. This observation resonates strongly with large human metagenomic efforts, arguing that a surprisingly small number of “core” or “keystone” taxa and functions explain a disproportionate share of inter-individual metabolic variations⁶⁰⁵, a phenomenon that has been also detected in studies with ruminants^{88,92}. The HS rat data parallel that logic: instead of relying on vague cluster labels, a concrete, functionally defined guild anchored in a plausible spatial niche (the crypt mucus) was specified.

This perspective also upgrades how the very own concept of “enterotypes” are interpreted. The field has been shifting from viewing enterotypes as fuzzy stool-based clusters to treating them as deterministic alternative stable states, self-reinforcing configurations shaped by substrate supply, redox conditions, immune tone, and the presence/absence of keystone degraders. Once a host-microbiome system falls into one basin of attraction, it tends to remain there until a sufficiently strong perturbation (antibiotics, diet shift, inflammation) flips it to another^{245,363}. In HS rats, two such basins were observed along β -diversity PCo1: one state in which *Prevotella* dominates, α -diversity is high, and the F:B ratio is reduced; and another in which *Prevotella* collapses, and α -diversity drops, having higher Firmicutes A dominance, a pattern observed by other studies with humans and pigs^{91,239}. In addition, network analysis and guild-function correlations indicated that the “*Prevotella*-rich” state (Ent1) displayed a more modular species network with guilds aligned to

specific functional niches, whereas the “*Prevotella*-poor” state (Ent2) displayed a less modular network and weaker coupling between guild structure and functional signatures usually associated with the colonisation of the mucosa^{118,119,363,418–420,451,459,462,519,520}. This organisation is consistent with the phylo-niche theory, in which ecological slots emerge as phylogenetically structured, functionally cohesive modules³⁵⁰. Furthermore, the two detected enterotypes were seamlessly distributed in the β -diversity PCo1 landscape, with a *Prevotella*-rich and a *Prevotella*-poor poles, remaining a useful coarse descriptor when treated as an ecological gradient rather than as rigid clusters, and becoming the link between the idea of enterotypes and other microbiome features^{226,234,236}. Additionally, the keystone-taxa framework and community-level mediation were consonant with the current ecological theory, which posits that a small subset of highly connected intestinal taxa can steer community structure and function, a phenomenon detected in studies with ruminants, for example^{88,92}.

A crucial point brought by the current research as a novelty to this paradigm was the idea that the basin occupied by gut bacterial communities can be partly explained by host genetics. Host alleles were not merely tweaking individual species but biasing the entire gut ecosystem toward one of two quasi-stable, crypt-anchored regimes. This aligns with recent work in pigs and rabbits, in which microbiomes have been decomposed into reproducible “guilds” or “enterosignatures” that were partially heritable, and also predicted growth, feed efficiency, stress physiology, and broader metabolic traits^{221,384,587}. In other words, the study with HS rats contributed to the idea that the same ecological logic that applies to heritable, niche-anchored microbial guilds associated with host performance traits appears to generalise across mammals. This aligns with current expectations for more translationable mechanistic descriptions of host-microbiome interactions^{50,419,606–608}, by consolidating the systems biology-driven hologenomics paradigm¹⁰ through coupling a deeper understanding of the host polygenic architecture³⁸³ and commensal ecosystemic networks⁷⁴.

Then, the current study closed the link between host genetics, microbiome composition, and host physiology by placing gut bacterial ecology on a clear causal path toward fasting glucose (but less clearly toward BMI). Human cohort studies have often reported

that microbiome composition correlates with cardiometabolic health across age, ancestry, and lifestyle contexts, sometimes even after controlling for basic anthropometrics^{239,250}. The conceptual leap advanced here is that a mechanistic link is now proposed: host alleles sculpt crypt microhabitats that favour keystone bacteria organised in a phylogenetic-coherent co-abundance cluster, and the multi-layer combination of their isolated genera and common guild, along with the community as a whole, which is strongly affected by them, feed back on host fasting blood glucose control. Sometimes, these layers can sum their effects, however, they can also lead to opposite directions, partially cancelling each other. This means, that looking to them separately might not be the suitable strategy for precision health management.

It is important to highlight, that by consisting of an observational study, where the detected patterns generate hypotheses that can be statistically tested, but not yet in an experimental set, all conclusions and developments of this thesis are based on the elaboration of a final parsimonious abductive theoretical framework aiming to explain the amount of evidence collected in order to formulate the experimental design set that succeeds such investigation. Therefore, this thesis does not intend to claim the real existence of the proposed mechanisms, but rather to suggest explanations that can leverage the information provided by heritability tests to predict possible candidate genes for use as instruments in causal inference analysis. With that purpose, it then offers some reasoning for more structured and targeted experiments.

As much important than that, this work also makes methodological advances that push the field forward. It employed shallow shotgun metagenomic sequencing as an alternative strategy to detect host polygenic effects in a cost-effective way, highlighting the details that must be accounted to improve success and comparing results with the current most adopted method, the 16S marker-gene sequencing. The results obtained proved that shallow-shotgun based protocols are sufficient to capture the major taxonomic and functional patterns of crypt-niche communities, while enabling affordable cohort sizes needed for such genetic analysis.

8.2 Limitations

Despite the clear limitations surrounding the use of shallow shotgun compositional data and broad reference catalogues, other aspects of this research must be reinforced to facilitate an understanding of the conditions in which the results were obtained and the potential risks associated with their interpretation.

First, causality was established statistically rather than experimentally. All analyses were performed on observational and cross-sectional data. The current clinical and translational consensus is clear that association is not enough; robust causality in microbiome-host metabolism links should ultimately be demonstrated using longitudinal human cohorts, controlled colonisation of gnotobiotic hosts, and mechanistic testing in organoids or gut-on-chip systems that reproduce crypt-like gradients of oxygen, mucus, and immune pressure^{7,50,608}. Because such manipulative steps have not yet been carried out here, strict causality cannot be claimed.

Second, the crypt localisation of keystone heritable bacteria was inferred indirectly. Direct spatial profiling, such as laser microdissection of crypt biofilms, spatial metagenomics, or in situ multi-omics of single crypt units, has not yet been performed in the HS rats to study the caecal microbiome. Instead, the argument that the *Prevotella/Bacteroides* guild (Guild 3) was crypt-anchored relied on bacterial functional enrichments and known features of crypt ecology. However, three-dimensional imaging and spatial multi-omics in mice have already shown that individual crypts can host distinct microbial consortia tightly linked to that crypt's epithelial metabolism, immune tone, and local inflammatory state^{124,411}. Without equivalent spatial measurements in HS rat tissue, it cannot be excluded that the “crypt guild” signal detected here partly reflects tightly adherent mucus communities immediately adjacent to, but not physically embedded within, the crypt surface, or near-crypt biofilms that are functionally similar but anatomically offset, limiting anatomical precision.

Third, the host phenotypes considered were relatively coarse metabolic readouts (fasting glucose and body-composition proxies) rather than a full systemic panel including insulin sensitivity, lipid metabolism, stress hormones, and inflammatory cytokines. Human cardiometabolic studies spanning diet, lifestyle, psychosocial stress,

and genotypes continue to detect robust microbiome-metabolism associations across the life course^{239,250}. It remains unknown whether the HS rat crypt guild identified here modulates insulin resistance, chronic low-grade inflammation, stress-axis hormones, or barrier-derived cytokine tone, all of which are increasingly implicated in metabolic disease in humans^{11,239,576}. This is particularly important because mucus-foraging commensals, including some *Bacteroides* lineages, have been reported to flip into pathogenic or pro-inflammatory behaviour under conditions of barrier erosion, excessive glycan foraging, or deep crypt penetration. Such events can amplify inflammation and have even been linked to tumorigenesis in extreme cases^{354,601,609}. Without direct measurements of barrier integrity, inflammatory tone, or neoplastic risk, it is not yet possible to say whether the same crypt-stabilised guild that appears metabolically beneficial in one genetic/immune background could become deleterious in another.

Fourth, although this thesis argues for the host genotype as an ecological engineer, causal identification in Chapter 7 depended on the validity and strength of the instruments derived from specific candidate genes. Horizontal pleiotropy is a structural risk in microbiome-adjacent MR, and conditional instrument strength can degrade in multivariable mediation settings when exposures (e.g. *Prevotella* and *Bacteroides*) are correlated. These are known challenges in causal inference frameworks applied to complex, compositional microbial data⁶⁰³. Similarly, the trimmed SEM achieved excellent global fit indices, however, certain indices (e.g. RMSEA at very low degrees of freedom) are known to behave erratically and therefore should not be over-interpreted in isolation. Replication under alternative but biologically plausible cohort structures remains essential.

Finally, external generalisation must be applied cautiously. All microbiome samples were collected from rat caecal content, and despite the discussed parallels with mammalian mucosal guilds reported in mice, pigs, rabbits, and humans, niche architecture, diet, life history, and immunological tone differ across hosts^{123,126,341,366,406,587}. Furthermore, cohort differences (e.g. age) and unmeasured covariates could also contribute to residual confounding despite harmonisation and random-effect absorption, a

generic challenge in all multi-cohort microbiome genetics studies^{134,610}.

Nevertheless, taken together, these limitations do not undermine the central conceptual model built from the collective results of this research: that host genetics can act as an ecological engineer of cryptic niches, favouring specific keystone guilds whose activities, in turn, propagate to community structure and metabolic phenotypes. They do, however, require that the strongest claims here be interpreted as mechanistic hypotheses that remain to be demonstrated via direct perturbation, spatial validation, and broader phenotyping, rather than as already proven cause-and-effect chains. That said, a recommendation for future developments inspired by the results and discussions of the current work would benefit from not taking what was built and discovered here as a literal object of discussions about how translational or not it can be in humans. Instead, the main objective of a study like this is to discuss how detected patterns can point to mechanisms and how such mechanisms should then be thought in a translatable way. Not necessarily, *Prevotella* species should now become the target for the development of microbiome-based treatments, for example. However, the fact that key species capable of influencing the whole community, which leads to non-conventional results in host metabolic traits, are restrained by the genetic potential of the host in offering a proper niche is itself an idea that should be translated to microbiome investigation in other hosts.

8.3 Conclusions

In conclusion, this study demonstrated the potential of shallow shotgun sequencing in enhancing the detection of host genetic effects on the gut microbiome, highlighting its advantage of better resolving bacterial species and generating less sparse taxonomic profiles compared to 16S. With an optimised pipeline for shallow shotgun data processing, the gut microbiome of two cohorts of HS rats was defined in terms of taxonomy, functionality, ecological guilds, enterotypes, networks and diversity, and this data revealed that aggregate host genetic effects were stronger among *Prevotella* and *Bacteroides* species, with a possible important influence of the niche they occupy as a co-abundant guild. Then, a refined framework has been proposed in which host polygenic variation modulates a mucus-rich crypt niche, thereby changing the relative fitness of *Bacteroides*

and *Prevotella*. Those shifts propagate through guild-level and diversity-mediated paths to influence fasting blood glucose, while BMI remains comparatively insensitive at this resolution. The synthesis moves beyond one-taxon narratives by demonstrating that community routing can amplify, mask, or invert genus-level direct effects, thus reconciling conflicting reports on *Prevotella* across studies^{271,408,409,468,478,598,600,601} and offering a principled basis for ecology-aware precision interventions.

8.4 Outlook

The next phase should move from statistical to experimental causality. Trials with germ-free or antibiotic-cleared SPF HS rats with contrasting genotypes for the specific instruments mapped by this study should be planned, so they can be colonised with a defined consortium that varies in *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species, containing or not in their genomes the functions predicted to be linked with crypt occupation. Then, spatial imaging (e.g., FISH/HiPR-FISH⁶¹¹) and meta-omics (e.g., metagenomics, metatranscriptomics and metabolomics) can be used to confirm crypt-proximal localisation and performance of different combinations of host-bacteria containing genotypes with predicted complementary functions in terms of niche building and adaptation, respectively.

Furthermore, parallel experiments can introduce the same consortia into rat-derived intestinal organoids and gut-on-chip systems that recreate crypt-like oxygen and mucus gradients⁶¹². This could make it possible to ask mechanistic questions directly: is glycaemic modulation driven by crypt colonisation per se, by mucin/ECM glycan foraging, by local oxygen management, by immune tolerance signalling, or by downstream cross-feeding cascades? Engineered perturbations to epithelial oxygen handling and barrier programs (for example, intestinal epithelial HIF and Notch axis manipulations) could test whether host levers recapitulate the enterotype shifts and the predicted directionality of fasting blood glucose causal paths.

Still in the metagenomics field, further improvements can also be made to complement and validate previous observations. Long-read and deep-shotgun sequencing in matched samples can capture strain-level PUL architecture and mobile elements to refine the functional

mediation map (including the corrinoid and antagonism systems enriched in high- h^2 *Bacteroides* species). Additionally, quantitative microbiome profiling can calibrate absolute abundances to reduce compositional artefacts. Replication of the trimmed SEM in independent HS cohorts and in human faecal datasets can be also pursued, accompanied by alternative causal graphs and Bayes model comparison to check the stability of community-level routes.

More importantly, the conclusions of this research have a profound impact in the field of translational clinical studies focusing on the gut microbiome management. The results obtained reinforce the idea that the host genetic control of the gut habitats might be the primary responsible of the chain of events that lead to community assembly, acting as a first filter that constrains the gradients landscape, affecting how gut niches will be “tuned” by diet sources and regime, and then how these influence bacteria-bacteria interactions (e.g., cooperation and competition)⁵⁵¹. As precision medicine initiatives begin to consider the microbiome as a potential game-changer in the prevention and treatment of chronic diseases⁶¹³, the type of host-microbiota interaction mapped in this work can inform new kinds of interventions.

In that sense, by considering the crypt as the main niche for the colonisation of keystone species, while its genetic control by the host is the top-tier factor in the microbiota assembly hierarchy, interventions such as prebiotics, probiotics, and FMT cannot be considered efficient microbiome-targeted medical procedures themselves^{551–553}, and may also incur the risk of turning potential beneficial commensals into pathogens when not properly managed in combination with the treatment of the crypt environment. Thus, the combination of non-invasive genetic tests and the measurement of physiological/biochemical markers capable of revealing, together, genetically based preconditions affecting crypt homeostasis becomes an essential step to be incorporated in such protocols. For example, many crypt-associated genes identified in the current research were linked to *Bacteroides* and/or *Prevotella* h^2 values (i.e., being likely part of host polygenic effects on them), such as those involved in TGF- β /SMAD, BMP, Wnt/LRP6, or ECM remodelling via MMPs. Imbalances associated with these systems are already treated by clinicians, even though they are not necessarily intentionally applied to treat the crypt niche in patients.

First, when TGF- β /SMAD3 signalling is chronically overactivated in fibroblasts, for example, a pathological fibrosis (i.e., an excess of extracellular matrix, tissue stiffening, and crypt architectural distortion) occurs. In humans, this is most clinically obvious in idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, with two oral antifibrotic drugs already prescribed to fight it: pirfenidone⁶¹⁴ and nintedanib⁶¹⁵. Second, the BMP-family genes mapped in the current study (e.g., Bmp4/5, Bmpr1b, Grem1) are also targets for current treatments. While pathologic “too much BMP” is suppressed pharmacologically with palovarotene⁶¹⁶, “not enough BMP” is compensated with recombinant BMP-2 to promote differentiation and matrix deposition⁶¹⁷. Third, hyperactivation of Wnt/ β -catenin/LRP5/6 signalling drives unchecked growth (classic in colorectal cancer and adenoma), whereas insufficient Wnt signalling causes failure of tissue renewal or bone formation. Clinically, romosozumab is a Wnt-pathway-modifying antibody in bone disease that boosts Wnt/LRP5/6 signalling, doing to bone what Lrp6/Wnt3a/Wnt10b does to intestinal stem cells conceptually: it turns up the Wnt tone in a stem-cell niche to favour anabolic rebuilding⁶¹⁸. Fourth, matrix metalloproteinases (e.g., Mmp8, Mmp10, Mmp13, Mmp16, Mmp20, Mmp21, Mmp24, Mmp27) remodel extracellular matrix and basement membrane. When their activity is excessive and unregulated in human tissues, there is a collagen breakdown, loss of attachment, and chronic inflammatory remodelling. Curiously, the subantimicrobial-dose of doxycycline is currently prescribed as an adjunct to scaling/root planning for adult periodontitis⁶¹⁹. At this low dose, doxycycline is not used for its antibiotic effect; it inhibits MMPs such as MMP-8 and MMP-9, which are key drivers of connective tissue and alveolar bone destruction in periodontal disease. If crypt stability depends on balanced ECM remodelling by epithelial and stromal cells, then the MMP cluster mapped by the current study is situated on a pathway where “too much protease” is already clinically recognised as pathogenic and has already been pharmacologically controlled in humans. Together, these examples demonstrate that some of the signalling pathways linked to the study’s crypt homeostasis gene set are already targeted by treatments for conditions that become pathological elsewhere in the body. Furthermore, many other drugs, such as the anti-inflammatory infliximab and other anti-TNF- α antibodies (e.g., adalimumab, certolizumab pegol), are already standard treatments for moderate to

severe ulcerative colitis and Crohn's disease, promoting overall mucosal healing and epithelial renewal after long-term disturbances⁶²⁰. Similarly, teduglutide, a long-acting analogue of glucagon-like peptide 2, stimulates crypt stem and progenitor cells to proliferate, inhibits epithelial apoptosis, increases mucosal surface area, tightens barrier integrity, and slows transit, so more nutrients can be absorbed by the gut⁶²¹.

Therefore, integrating a patient's polygenic risk profile with their gut microbiome composition to predict disease risk or treatment response, and then tailoring a combination of pharmaceutical-microbiota-targeted therapies accordingly, can ensure proper microbial colonisation and prevent potential commensals from becoming pathogens. By considering host genetics and its possible association with an Ent2-type gut community, possible treatments could also involve the recommendation of more aggressive, individualised diets that support the growth of beneficial strains in a more competitive environment, assuming that this kind of enterotype is the result of a genetically-driven, less-protected crypt niche for keystone bacteria. Thus, refining the clinical ability to modulate the gut microbiota in harmony with the host's genetic makeup, new biomedical advancements might edge closer to a future of truly personalised medicine and nutrition where metabolic health can be maintained or restored. The current work presented in this thesis is a stepping stone toward that future, providing a robust conceptual blueprint for how it can be achieved.

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ANNEXES

This section contains all supplementary material referenced in Chapters 3-7.

1) Annexe I: Supplementary Tables

Supplementary Table S1: Detailed description of the costs involved in sequencing 1,000 samples with: **A)** 16S-amplicon sequencing; **B)** shallow shotgun sequencing (targeting 1 million pairs of reads); and **C)** deep shotgun sequencing (targeting 20 million pairs of reads). These costs were estimated on 03/06/2025 by the Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG) Genomics Unit, considering the services offered by the CRG Core Facilities Programme.

Method	Service	Unit of measure	Cost per unit	N° of units	Total cost
A) 16S rRNA amplicon	Sample Quality Control (Microbiome)	Plate	€ 269.10	10	€ 2,691.00
	Library Preparation Microbiome	Plate	€ 1,100.10	10	€ 11,001.00
	MiSeq (600 cycles, v3)	Run	€ 1,569.56	5	€ 7,847.80
Total (no IVA)					€ 21,539.80

Method	Service	Unit of measure	Cost per unit	N° of units	Total cost
B) Shallow shotgun sequencing (1mi pairs of reads)	DNA Quantification (96-well plate)	Plate	€ 164.02	10	€ 1,640.20
	DNA Concentration Normalization (96-well plate)	Plate	€ 90.40	10	€ 904.00
	Library Preparation gDNA-Tn5 (96-well plate)	Plate	€ 2,383.15	10	€ 23,831.50
	NovaSeq 6000 (300 cycles, S2)	Millions of reads	€ 3.29	960	€ 3,158.40
Total (no IVA)					€ 29,534.10

Method	Service	Unit of measure	Cost per unit	N° of units	Total cost
C) Deep shotgun sequencing (20mi pairs of reads)	DNA Quantification (96-well plate)	Plate	€ 164.02	10	€ 1,640.20
	DNA Concentration Normalization (96-well plate)	Plate	€ 90.40	10	€ 904.00
	Library Preparation gDNA-Tn5 (96-well plate)	Plate	€ 2,383.15	10	€ 23,831.50
	NovaSeq 6000 (300 cycles, S4)	Millions of reads	€ 1.98	19200	€ 38,016.00
Total (no IVA)					€ 64,391.70

Supplementary Table S2: Tissue / Environment group vocabulary for the classification of the isolation sources of the mapped genomes after removing the ones with <0.01% of average relative abundance. When there was no information available, the isolation source was classified as “Undefined”.

Final classification	Sub-category	Keywords
Gut	Gut	caecal, caecum, caecal content, cecal, cecal content, cecum, colon, colonic, coprolite, digestive, duodenum, faecal, faeces, fecal, feces, gastrointestinal, gizzard, gut, hindgut, ileum, intestinal, intestine, jejunum, lumen, luminal, midgut, mucosa, rectal, rectum, rumen, ruminal, stool
Non-gut	Oral cavity	Salivary gland, buccal, dental, mouth, oral, plaque, saliva, salivary, subgingival, supragingival, tongue
Non-gut	Respiratory tract	airway, bronchus, lung, nares, nasal, nose, pharyngeal, respiratory, sputum, throat, trachea
Non-gut	Urogenital tract	bladder, cervix, egg, eggs, semen, urine, urogenital, uterus, vagina, vaginal
Non-gut	Skin / cutaneous	cutaneous, dermis, epidermis, pore, sebaceous, skin
Non-gut	Other organs	hepatopancreas
Environment	Environment	aquaculture, basin, environment, forest, freshwater, lake, marine, mat, mud, petroleum, pond, river, sediment, sludge, soil, swab, water
Food	Food / feed	beef, cheese, chicken, comminuted, feed, ferment, fibre, food, kimchi, kombucha, milk, salami, sausage, shrimp, silage, turkey, wine, yogurt
Plant	Plant-associated	endophyte, leaf, phyllosphere, plant, rhizosphere, root, seed, stem

Supplementary Table S3: Host group vocabulary for the classification of the isolation sources of the mapped genomes after removing the ones with <0.01% of average relative abundance. When there was no information available, the isolation source was classified as “Undefined”.

Host group	Keywords
Mouse	mice, mouse, muridae, murinae, murine, mus, mus musculus
Rat	rat, rats, rattus, rattus norvegicus
Other rodents	apodemus, castor, cavia, chinchilla, cricetus, gerbil, guinea pig, hamster, marmot, mesocricetus, myodes, rodent, squirrel, vole, wood mouse, yellow-necked mouse

Human	h. sapiens, homo, homo sapiens, human, patient
Other mammals	Myotragus, baboon, bison, boar, bos, bovine, camel, canis, capra, cat, cattle, cervus, cow, deer, dog, equus, felis, goat, horse, koala, macaca, oryctolagus, ovis, phascolarctos, pig, rabbit, ruminant, sheep, sus, vombatus, water buffalo, wombat, yak
Other animals	amphibian, anas, aves, bird, chicken, danio, duck, fish, frog, gallus, gasterosteus, lizard, oreochromis, papio, penaeus, pigeon, pigeons, reptile, salmo, serpentes, shrimp, snake, tachysurus, tilapia, trout, xenopus, zebrafish

Supplementary Table S4: ANOVA tests performed for the comparison of three different α -diversity measures between samples grouped according to four covariates. The tests were performed for both functional and taxonomic profiles, before and after the removal of fixed effects (termed here as different steps).

Step	Profiling method	Covariate	Measure	<i>p</i> -value	<i>R</i> ²
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Batch	Rao's quadratic index	1.27E-08	0.06
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Batch	Richness	5.02E-02	0.02
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Batch	Shannon index	1.14E-07	0.06
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Enterotype	Rao's quadratic index	7.80E-01	0.00
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Enterotype	Richness	2.34E-02	0.01
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Enterotype	Shannon index	1.59E-04	0.02
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Sex	Rao's quadratic index	2.02E-01	0.00
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Sex	Richness	3.04E-01	0.00
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Sex	Shannon index	4.11E-02	0.00
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Study	Rao's quadratic index	2.06E-14	0.07
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Study	Richness	2.20E-02	0.01
With fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Study	Shannon index	1.98E-14	0.07
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Batch	Rao's quadratic index	7.00E-11	0.08
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Batch	Richness	2.87E-03	0.03
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Batch	Shannon index	2.46E-11	0.08
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Enterotype	Rao's quadratic index	7.67E-06	0.02
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Enterotype	Richness	3.94E-03	0.01
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Enterotype	Shannon index	1.78E-02	0.01
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Sex	Rao's quadratic index	1.22E-03	0.01
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Sex	Richness	6.47E-01	0.00
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Sex	Shannon index	2.64E-03	0.01
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Study	Rao's quadratic index	6.94E-45	0.21
With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Study	Richness	1.63E-03	0.01

With fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Study	Shannon index	3.45E-42	0.19
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Batch	Rao's quadratic index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Batch	Richness	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Batch	Shannon index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Enterotype	Rao's quadratic index	9.84E-01	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Enterotype	Richness	1.53E-02	0.01
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Enterotype	Shannon index	1.95E-05	0.02
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Sex	Rao's quadratic index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Sex	Richness	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Sex	Shannon index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Study	Rao's quadratic index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Study	Richness	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Functional (EC4)	Study	Shannon index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Batch	Rao's quadratic index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Batch	Richness	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Batch	Shannon index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Enterotype	Rao's quadratic index	3.66E-06	0.02
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Enterotype	Richness	2.95E-03	0.01
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Enterotype	Shannon index	2.88E-02	0.01
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Sex	Rao's quadratic index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Sex	Richness	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Sex	Shannon index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Study	Rao's quadratic index	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Study	Richness	1.00E+00	0.00
Without fixed effects	Taxonomic (Species)	Study	Shannon index	1.00E+00	0.00

Supplementary Table S5: System of colour identification of nodes belonging to each species co-abundance guild in the global network (Figure 15A).

Guild	Hex code	Approximate colour name
0	#3FD7AA	teal / medium aquamarine
1	#CB1110	crimson red
10	#A48743	dark khaki / mustard
11	#A9C13E	yellow
2	#BAF172	lime green

3	#3CD22F	bright leaf green
4	#80FDA6	spring-mint green
5	#6DD4ED	sky blue
6	#729CED	cornflower blue
7	#DC1470	deep pink / magenta
8	#FD80F3	light violet
9	#535BC0	indigo
noise	#8A5CBF	medium purple

Supplementary Table S6: EC4 functions selected based on thresholds for their correlations with species guilds across all 858 samples (Pearson correlation $p_{adj} < 0.05$ and $\rho > |0.40|$).

Bioprocess	Category (Pathway)	EC4 Number	Name (Key Function)
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Amino acid (histidine) degradation	2.1.2.5	Glutamate formimidoyltransferase (FTCD) - histidine catabolism
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Amino acid (histidine) degradation	4.2.1.49	Urocanate hydratase (urocanase) - histidine catabolism
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Amino acid catabolism (asparagine)	3.5.1.1	L-Asparaginase - asparagine \rightarrow aspartate + NH_3
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Methionine salvage & quorum signal (AI-2)	3.2.2.9	S-adenosylhomocysteine/5'-methylthioadenosine nucleosidase
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Polyamine & acid resistance	4.1.1.19	Arginine decarboxylase (SpeA) - produces agmatine + CO_2
Aromatic compound metabolism	Anaerobic aromatic (benzoyl-CoA) degradation	4.2.1.100	Cyclohexa-1,5-dienecarbonyl-CoA hydratase - hydrates benzoyl-CoA intermediate
Carbohydrate metabolism	Carbohydrate degradation	3.2.1.1	α -Amylase - endo-1,4- α -glucanase (starch/glycogen)
Carbohydrate metabolism	Central carbon (glycolysis)	1.2.1.12	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase (GAPDH) - glycolysis
Carbohydrate metabolism	Central carbon (PPP)	3.1.1.31	6-Phosphogluconolactonase - pentose phosphate shunt
Carbohydrate storage	Storage carbohydrate biosynthesis	2.4.1.11	Glycogen (starch) synthase - UDP-glucose: glucan transferase
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Cell envelope (Gram+ S-layer glycan)	2.7.1.168	<i>D</i> -Glycero- α - <i>D</i> -manno-heptose-7-phosphate kinase - S-layer glycan heptose pathway
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Inositol phosphate metabolism	2.7.1.158	<i>Myo</i> -Inositol pentakisphosphate 2-kinase - $\text{IP}_5 \rightarrow \text{IP}_6$ (phytic acid pathway)

Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	LPS core heptose biosynthesis	5.1.3.20	ADP- <i>glycero-manno</i> -heptose 6-epimerase (HidD)
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	LPS core heptose biosynthesis	5.3.1.28	Sedoheptulose-7-P isomerase (GmhA) - heptose biosynthesis
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	LPS inner core biosynthesis	2.5.1.55 (Formerly EC44.1.2.16)	3-Deoxy-8-phosphoactulonate synthase (KDO synthase) - forms KDO sugar
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Phospholipid biosynthesis	2.7.8.8	Phosphatidylserine synthase (CDP-DAG:serine transferase)
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Phospholipid turnover (membrane)	2.7.1.107	1,2-Diacylglycerol kinase (ATP) - DAG → phosphatidate
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Polyamine biosynthesis, biofilm	4.1.1.96	Carboxynorspermidine decarboxylase - produces norspermidine
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Polyol metabolism (inositol biosynthesis)	5.5.1.4	L-myo-Inositol-1-phosphate synthase (MIPS) - cyclizes G6P
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Protein N-glycosylation (Dolichol pathway)	2.4.1.83	Dolichyl-phosphate β- <i>D</i> -mannosyltransferase (Dol-P-Man synthase)
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Sugar nucleotide (fucose) biosynthesis	1.1.1.271	GDP- <i>L</i> -fucose synthase - makes GDP-fucose for glycan assembly
Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis	Ubiquinone (coenzyme Q) biosynthesis	2.5.1.39	4-Hydroxybenzoate polyprenyltransferase (UbiA) - prenylates p-HB
Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis	Vitamin B ₆ (pyridoxal-P) pathway	2.6.99.2	Pyridoxine 5'-phosphate synthase (PdxJ)
Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis	Vitamin K ₂ (menaquinone) pathway	4.1.3.36	1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoyl-CoA synthase (MenB) - <i>o</i> -succinylbenzoyl-CoA → DHNA
Membrane transport	Energy metabolism (ion pumps, etc.)	3.6.1.3 (Deleted - now classified under EC45.6 and EC47)	"ATPase" (Adenosinetriphosphatase) - generic ATP hydrolysis
Nucleotide biosynthesis	Nucleotide <i>de novo</i> synthesis	2.1.1.45	Thymidylate synthase (Tyms) - dUMP → dTMP (DNA synthesis)
Nucleotide metabolism	Nucleotide modification (tRNA)	6.3.4.20	7-Cyano-7-deazaguanine synthase (QueC) - queuosine tRNA base synthesis
Nucleotide metabolism	dNTP pool regulator	3.1.5.1	<i>d</i> GTP triphosphatase (dGTPase) - hydrolyzes dGTP
Redox balance	Anaerobic respiration (nitrate → nitrite)	1.9.6.1	Nitrate reductase (cytochrome <i>c</i> , NapA) - periplasmic nitrate → nitrite
Redox balance	Anaerobic respiration (nitrite → NH ₄ ⁺)	1.7.2.2	Nitrite reductase (cytochrome <i>c</i> , ammonia-forming, NrfA)
Redox balance	TCA cycle (anaerobic variant)	1.2.7.3	2-Oxoglutarate synthase (KGOR) - ferredoxin-dependent <i>a</i> -KG oxidoreductase
SCFA & organic acids metabolism	Organic acid metabolism (oxalate)	4.1.1.8	Oxalyl-CoA decarboxylase (Oxc) - oxalate fermentation
SCFA & organic acids metabolism	Short-chain fatty acid metabolism (propionate)	5.4.99.2	Methylmalonyl-CoA mutase - propionate pathway (B ₁₂ - dependent)

Supplementary Table S7: EC4 functions with the greatest increase and decrease based on $\Delta\rho$ values (Ent1 - Ent2) for individual guilds.

Guild	EC4 with greatest increase ($\Delta\rho>0$)	$\Delta\rho$	EC4 with greatest decrease ($\Delta\rho<0$)	$\Delta\rho$
0	2.1.2.5	0.163	2.7.1.168	-0.039
1	2.7.1.158	0.101	3.2.1.1	-0.114
2	3.6.1.3	0.121	5.4.99.2	-0.143
3	3.1.5.1	0.205	4.2.1.100	-0.102
4	5.1.3.20	0.151	4.2.1.100	-0.097
5	2.4.1.83	0.105	3.6.1.3	-0.248
6	4.2.1.100	0.207	2.1.2.5	-0.273
7	3.2.1.1	0.137	4.2.1.100	-0.126
8	3.6.1.3	0.131	2.4.1.83	-0.072
9	2.1.2.5	0.217	4.2.1.100	-0.030
10	4.1.1.8	0.264	4.2.1.100	-0.107
11	4.1.1.8	0.26	4.2.1.100	-0.138

Supplementary Table S8: EC4 functions selected based on thresholds for their correlations with genera *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* across all 858 samples (Pearson correlation $p_{adj} < 0.05$ and $\rho > |0.45|$).

Bioprocess	Category (Pathway)	EC4 Number	Name (Key Function)
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Asparagine utilization (nitrogen salvage)	3.5.1.1	Asparaginase (L-asparagine amidohydrolase)
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Histidine degradation (ureidoglycolate pathway)	4.2.1.49	Urocanate hydratase (imidazolonepropionate hydrolase)
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Histidine degradation / One-carbon folate cycle	2.1.2.5	Glutamate formimidoyltransferase (formiminoglutamate transferase)
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Polyamine biosynthesis (Arginine \rightarrow Agmatine)	4.1.1.19	Arginine decarboxylase
Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Tryptophan degradation (indole production)	4.1.99.1	Tryptophanase (tryptophan indole-lyase)
Carbohydrate metabolism	Pectin degradation (plant cell wall)	3.1.1.11	Pectinesterase (pectin methylesterase)
Carbohydrate metabolism	Uronic acid metabolism (hexuronate pathway)	1.1.1.58	Tagaturonate reductase (altronate oxidoreductase)
Carbohydrate storage	Glycogen biosynthesis (storage polysaccharide)	2.4.1.11	Glycogen [starch] synthase (UDP-glucose glycogen transferase)

Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Inositol biosynthesis (polyol pathway)	5.5.1.4	1D-myo-Inositol-3-phosphate synthase
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Lipid A biosynthesis (LPS endotoxin)	2.3.1.129	UDP-N-acetylglucosamine O-acyltransferase (LpxA)
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Lipid A biosynthesis (LPS endotoxin)	3.5.1.108	UDP-3-O-acyl-N-acetylglucosamine deacetylase (LpxC)
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Lipopolysaccharide core (KDO) synthesis	2.5.1.55	3-Deoxy-8-phosphooctulonate synthase (KDO-8-P synthase)
Cell envelope & biofilm biosynthesis	Protein N-glycosylation (dolichol pathway)	2.4.1.83	Dolichyl-phosphate β -D-mannosyltransferase (DPM synthase)
Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis	NAD ⁺ cofactor (de novo pathway)	2.4.2.19	Nicotinate-nucleotide diphosphorylase (quinolinate PR transferase)
Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis	Vitamin B ₂ (riboflavin) pathway	2.5.1.9	Riboflavin synthase
Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis	Vitamin B ₆ (pyridoxal-P) pathway	1.1.1.290	4-Phosphoerythronate dehydrogenase (PdxB)
Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis	Vitamin K2 (menaquinone) pathway	4.1.3.36	1,4-Dihydroxy-2-naphthoyl-CoA synthase (MenB, naphthoate synthase)
Redox balance	Electron transport chain (NDH-2)	1.6.5.11	NADH dehydrogenase (quinone)
Redox balance	Reductive TCA (anaerobic 2-oxoglutarate)	1.2.7.3	2-Oxoglutarate synthase (ferredoxin oxidoreductase)
Redox balance	TCA cycle (malate-oxaloacetate step)	1.1.1.37	Malate dehydrogenase (NAD-dependent)
Redox balance	TCA cycle & electron transport (Complex II)	1.3.5.1	Succinate dehydrogenase (quinone)
SCFA & organic acids metabolism	Malonate metabolism (fatty acid turnover)	4.1.1.9	Malonyl-CoA decarboxylase
SCFA & organic acids metabolism	Propionate metabolism (odd-chain FA pathway)	5.4.99.2	Methylmalonyl-CoA mutase (succinyl-CoA synthase)
SCFA & organic acids metabolism	Propionate metabolism (stereoisomer conversion)	5.1.99.1	Methylmalonyl-CoA epimerase (racemase)

Supplementary Table S9: EC4 functions with the greatest increase and decrease based on $\Delta\rho$ values (Ent1 - Ent2) for *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella*.

Genus	EC4 with greatest increase ($\Delta\rho>0$)	$\Delta\rho$	EC4 with greatest decrease ($\Delta\rho<0$)	$\Delta\rho$
<i>Bacteroides</i>	1.1.1.58 (Tagaturonate/altronate reductase)	0.151	1.2.7.3 (2-oxoglutarate:ferredoxin oxidoreductase)	- 0.032
<i>Prevotella</i>	1.1.1.58 (Tagaturonate/altronate reductase)	0.178	3.5.1.1 (<i>L</i> -asparaginase)	- 0.037

Supplementary Table S10: Functions (COGs/ENOGs) with significant enrichment in the genomes *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species grouped according to h^2 values (high or low).

Genus	Function	Bioprocess	Category	Official Name	Group
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2859	Adhesion	Outer membrane porin/adhesion (BP26/OMP28)	Outer membrane channel-forming protein BP26/OMP28, SIMPL family	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2931	Adhesion	RTX toxin/adhesion (Ca ²⁺ -binding)	Ca ²⁺ -binding protein, RTX toxin-related	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG5571	Adhesion	Type V secretion (autotransporter EstA)	Secreted esterase EstA, contains T5SS autotransporter beta-barrel domain	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0686	Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Alanine metabolism (alanine dehydrogenase)	Alanine dehydrogenase (includes sporulation protein SpoVN)	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1247	Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Amino-acid N-acylation (MnaT)	L-amino acid N-acyltransferase MnaT	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0010	Amino acid & polyamine metabolism	Polyamine/arginine catabolism (urea cycle branch)	Arginase/agmatinase family enzyme	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1830	Carbon flux & anaerobic fermentation	Glycolysis (fructose-bisphosphate aldolase)	Fructose-bisphosphate aldolase class Ia, DhnA family	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1139	Carbon flux & anaerobic fermentation	Lactate utilization (LutB)	L-lactate utilization protein LutB, contains a ferredoxin-type domain	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1556	Carbon flux & anaerobic fermentation	Lactate utilization (LutC)	L-lactate utilization protein LutC, contains LUD domain	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1929	Carbon flux & anaerobic fermentation	Non-phosphorylated Entner-Doudoroff (glycerate kinase)	Glycerate kinase	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0756	Cell cycle & morphogenesis	dUTPase (uracil prevention; thymidylate support)	dUTP pyrophosphatase (dUTPase)	High Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0256	Cell cycle & morphogenesis	Ribosomal protein L18 (50S)	Ribosomal protein L18	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0198	Cell cycle & morphogenesis	Ribosomal protein L24 (50S)	Ribosomal protein L24	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0267	Cell cycle & morphogenesis	Ribosomal protein L33 (50S)	Ribosomal protein L33	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0828	Cell cycle & morphogenesis	Ribosomal protein S21 (30S)	Ribosomal protein S21	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3266	Cell cycle & morphogenesis	Septal ring/cell division (SPOR-associated DamX)	Cell division protein DamX, binds to the septal ring, contains C-terminal SPOR domain	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0449	Cell envelope biogenesis & integrity	Peptidoglycan precursor synthesis (GlmS)	Glucosamine 6-phosphate synthetase, contains amidotransferase and phosphosugar isomerase domains	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4953	Cell envelope biogenesis & integrity	Peptidoglycan remodeling (PbpC carboxypeptidase /PBP)	Membrane carboxypeptidase /penicillin-binding protein PbpC	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3883	Cell envelope biogenesis & integrity	PG hydrolase regulator (CwIO N-terminal coiled-coil)	Uncharacterized N-terminal coiled-coil domain of peptidoglycan hydrolase CwIO	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2089	Cell envelope biogenesis & integrity	Sialic acid/capsule biosynthesis (SpsE)	Sialic acid synthase SpsE, contains C-terminal SAF domain	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2091	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Carrier protein activation (phosphopantetheinyl transferase)	Phosphopantetheinyl transferase	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2087	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (AdoCbiK/AdoCbi-P guanylyltransferase)	Adenosyl cobinamide kinase/adenosyl cobinamide phosphate guanylyltransferase	High Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2073	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (Cobalt-precorrin 5A hydrolase)	Cobalt-precorrin 5A hydrolase	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1903	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (Cobalt-precorrin-5B methyltransferase)	Cobalt-precorrin-5B methyltransferase	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1270	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (CobD/CbiB)	Cobalamin biosynthesis protein CobD/CbiB	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0368	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (CobS)	Cobalamin synthase CobS (adenosylcobinamide-GDP ribazoletransferase)	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1797	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (Cobyric acid a,c-diamide synthase)	Cobyric acid a,c-diamide synthase	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2038	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (NaMN:DMB phosphoribosyltransferase)	NaMN:DMB phosphoribosyltransferase	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2243	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (Precorrin-2 methylase)	Precorrin-2 methylase	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1010	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (Precorrin-3B methylase)	Precorrin-3B methylase	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2241	Cofactor & vitamin biosynthesis/transport	Vitamin B12 biosynthesis (Precorrin-6Y C5,15-methylase CbiE)	Precorrin-6Y C5,15-methylase subunit CbiE	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1401	Defence & antagonism	Anti-virus defence	5-methylcytosine-specific restriction endonuclease McrBC, GTP-binding regulatory subunit McrB	Low Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1895	Defence & antagonism	Anti-virus defence	HEPN domain protein, predicted toxin of MNT-HEPN system	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4680	Defence & antagonism	Anti-virus defence	mRNA-degrading endonuclease (mRNA interferase) HigB, toxic component of the HigAB toxin-antitoxin module	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1700	Defence & antagonism	Anti-virus defence	Predicted anti-virus defence system component AQ645, contains DUF2357 and PD-(D/E)xK nuclease domains	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4226	Defence & antagonism	Anti-virus defence	Predicted nuclease of the RNase H fold, HicB family	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1944	Defence & antagonism	Competitors	Peptide backbone phosphorylating domain YcaO, involved in protein thioamidation and methylthiolation	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3501	Defence & antagonism	Competitors	Type VI secretion system spike component VgrG,	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1194	DNA repair & genome maintenance	Base-excision repair (MutY adenine glycosylase)	Adenine-specific DNA glycosylase, acts on AG and A-oxoG pairs	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1533	DNA repair & genome maintenance	DNA photoreactivation (photolyase)	DNA thymine dimer repair photolyase	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0419	DNA repair & genome maintenance	DNA repair complex SbcCD (ATPase)	DNA repair exonuclease SbcCD ATPase subunit	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0420	DNA repair & genome maintenance	DNA repair complex SbcCD (nuclease)	DNA repair exonuclease SbcCD nuclease subunit	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0817	DNA repair & genome maintenance	Holliday junction resolvosome (RuvC)	Holliday junction resolvosome RuvABC endonuclease subunit RuvC	High Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG5297	Glycan acquisition & degradation	Cellulose breakdown (cellulase/cellobiase)	Cellulase/cellobiase CelA1	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4632	Glycan acquisition & degradation	Glycan remodeling (phosphorylated glycans; UCE)	Sugar-P-sugar glycosidase (uncovering enzyme, UCE), NAGPA superfamily	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3509	Glycan acquisition & degradation	Hemicellulose deacetylation (acetyl xylan esterase)	Acetyl xylan esterase AxeA and related esterases, LpqC family	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3661	Glycan acquisition & degradation	Hemicellulose debranching (alpha-glucuronidase)	Alpha-glucuronidase	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4833	Glycan acquisition & degradation	Mannan degradation (GH76 alpha-1,6-mannase)	Predicted alpha-1,6-mannanase, GH76 family	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4806	Glycan acquisition & degradation	Rhamnose catabolism (L-rhamnose isomerase)	L-rhamnose isomerase	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2333	Horizontal gene transfer	DNA uptake (ComEC; natural competence)	DNA uptake channel protein ComEC C-terminal domain, metallo-beta-lactamase superfamily	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3628	Horizontal gene transfer	Phage baseplate assembly protein W	Phage baseplate assembly protein W	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG5283	Horizontal gene transfer	Phage-related tail protein	Phage-related tail protein	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3668	Horizontal gene transfer	Plasmid stabilization protein ParE (toxin)	Plasmid stabilization system protein ParE	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4387	Horizontal gene transfer	Prophage structural protein (Mu-like gp36)	Mu-like prophage protein gp36	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1357	Horizontal gene transfer	Type IVB secretion/DNA transfer (DotG/IcmE)	Type IVB secretion/DNA transfer system protein DotG/IcmE, contains pentapeptide repeats	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG4474	Horizontal gene transfer	Uncharacterized SPBe2 prophage-derived protein YoqJ	Uncharacterized SPBe2 prophage-derived protein YoqJ	Low Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3292	Inorganic ion transport	Periplasmic ligand-binding sensor domain	Periplasmic ligand-binding sensor domain	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0704	Inorganic ion transport	Phosphate homeostasis regulator PhoU	Phosphate uptake regulator PhoU	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0519	Nucleotide metabolism	Purine biosynthesis (GMP synthase)	GMP synthase, PP-ATPase domain/subunit	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2968	Redox balance & O ₂ /ROS defence	Envelope/oxidative stress protein YggE (SIMPL)	Oxidative stress-related protein YggE, contains kinase-interacting SIMPL domain	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG2249	Redox balance & O ₂ /ROS defence	NADPH-quinone reductase (redox control; MdaB)	Putative NADPH-quinone reductase (modulator of drug activity B)	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1956	Redox balance & O ₂ /ROS defence	Protein repair (methionine-R-sulfoxide reductase; GAF-related)	GAF domain-containing protein, putative methionine-R-sulfoxide reductase	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0639	Stress response & detoxification	Alarmon metabolism (Ap4A hydrolase/PP2A-like)	Diadenosine tetraphosphatase ApaH/serine/threonine protein phosphatase, PP2A family	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG0076	Stress response & detoxification	Amino-acid decarboxylation (acid resistance; PLP-dependent)	Glutamate or tyrosine decarboxylase or a related PLP-dependent protein	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1854	Stress response & detoxification	Autoinducer-2 biosynthesis (LuxS)	S-ribosylhomocysteine lyase LuxS, autoinducer biosynthesis	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1076	Stress response & detoxification	Chaperone (DnaJ)	DnaJ domain-containing protein	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3832	Stress response & detoxification	Lipid/ligand-binding (START/SRPBC C domain YndB)	Chalcone/flavone-binding protein YndB, AHS A1/START/SRPBCC domain	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1825	Stress response & detoxification	Ribosomal protein L25 (50S; Ctc)	Ribosomal protein L25 (general stress protein Ctc)	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG1725	Stress response & detoxification	Transcriptional regulator (GntR family)	DNA-binding transcriptional regulator YhcF, GntR family	High Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG5519	Unknown function	General function prediction only (Cch-like helicase ATPase)	Predicted ATPase domain of Cch-like helicases, DUF927 family	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	COG3618	Unknown function	Predicted metal-dependent hydrolase (TIM-barrel)	Predicted metal-dependent hydrolase, TIM-barrel fold	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	295IV	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2EUVB	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	28KZ4	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DKZS	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DYW3	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2E9E6	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DR57	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	28JT8	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	29FUY	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	29FVJ	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2CBAS	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DMKQ	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2EU8H	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2BTXK	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DF51	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2EXMV	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2EQ0K	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2C5EY	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2CB57	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DRVS	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2A58H	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	28KJP	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	28YC2	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2A805	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2BUU6	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2AV4S	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2BTEY	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	29ZV8	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2A32N	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2A8JD	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DH2N	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	High Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	28JXB	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	290SF	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2A26Q	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2CF7P	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2CIJU	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2AGHM	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2E2AU	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2A7B7	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2AU7E	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2C2Y8	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2CAZP	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DNN4	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DRT8	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2EG2H	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2EYRH	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability

<i>Bacteroides</i>	2FJH4	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DVVT	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2DFY1	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	28PCZ	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
<i>Bacteroides</i>	2BFKU	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability
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<i>Prevotella</i>	COG0045	Carbon flux & anaerobic fermentation	TCA cycle	Succinyl-CoA synthetase, beta subunit	High Heritability
<i>Prevotella</i>	COG2963	Horizontal gene transfer	Transposase InsE and inactivated derivatives	Transposase InsE and inactivated derivatives	High Heritability
<i>Prevotella</i>	COG2033	Redox balance & O ₂ /ROS defence	Superoxide reduction (desulfoferrodoxin/SORL)	Desulfoferrodoxin, superoxide reductase-like (SORL) domain	High Heritability
<i>Prevotella</i>	COG3078	Cell cycle & morphogenesis	Ribosome assembly factor Yih1 (Der GTPase activator)	Ribosome assembly protein Yih1, activator of Der GTPase	High Heritability
<i>Prevotella</i>	COG4747	Unknown function	General function prediction only (ACT domain)	ACT domain-containing protein	High Heritability
<i>Prevotella</i>	COG1808	Unknown function	Uncharacterized membrane protein (DUF389)	Uncharacterized membrane protein AF0785, contains DUF389 domain	High Heritability
<i>Prevotella</i>	2BVJA	Unknown function	Unknown function	Unknown function	Low Heritability

Supplementary Table S11: Rat genes selected for the discovery of variants associated with *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* heritability. All genes were classified according to the bioprocess they correspond to, with their location in the rat genome (mRatBN7.2), the number of SNPs mapped for each of these genes and the reference that supports their bioprocess classification. The symbol “*” tags the genes often referred to in the literature as associated with such bioprocess, while other variants of the same gene were included after consulting the Rat Gene Database^{497,498}.

Bioprocess	Category	Gene	Chromosome	Start	End	Mapped SNPs	Reference
Crypt development and maintenance	Autophagy	Wdfy1	9	81034852	81092823	41	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Autophagy	Wdfy2	15	37083842	37209559	191	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Autophagy	Wdfy3*	14	7578245	7810491	576	127,383
Crypt development and maintenance	Autophagy	Wdfy4	16	8221853	8450494	539	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp1	15	45551603	45595862	34	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp2*	3	120812660	120822579	14	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp3	14	10712489	10737153	152	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp4*	15	19618538	19633494	36	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp5*	8	76517164	76639925	377	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp6	17	26318121	26469691	383	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp7*	3	161639915	161716938	119	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmp8b	5	135386058	135411337	68	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmpr1a	16	9736390	9829825	168	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmpr1b	2	230538252	230871077	478	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Bmpr2	9	61192718	61307280	64	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Grem1*	3	100512317	100524001	13	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Grem2	13	86778543	86871509	260	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Nog	10	74128712	74130339	0	127
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad1	19	28513130	28573665	109	622,623

Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad2	18	69849884	69918926	55	622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad3	8	64126829	64236960	27	622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad4	18	67243742	67274438	20	622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad5	17	7862332	7891678	32	622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad6	8	64450114	64519673	10	622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad7*	18	68988429	69016774	58	622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Smad9	2	138956326	139006315	70	622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb1	1	81196532	81212848	0	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb1i1	1	182828553	182835465	25	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb1i	17	7955603	7984903	107	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb1*	5	61653773	61710777	128	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb2*	8	115794537	115883615	0	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb3	14	2489397	2665383	572	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb3l	12	2600874	2604211	3	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	BMP/TGF- β pathway	Tgfb3l1	9	45320975	45371329	345	27,622,623
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn1	11	74421569	74436728	21	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn10	15	95862785	95954526	209	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn11	2	112207745	112221050	51	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn12	4	28522659	28533647	42	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn14	11	33232281	33329440	467	127,439

Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn15	12	19698167	19708419	28	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn16	11	74290298	74309588	60	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn17	11	27827454	27828630	0	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn18	8	100246499	100265797	29	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn19	5	132862939	132870364	14	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn20	1	44133769	44134428	1	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn22	16	44422344	44423370	1	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn23	16	56413677	56415401	1	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn24	16	44424810	44425472	2	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn25	8	49391930	49392664	0	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn3	12	21708538	21710010	1	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn4	12	21751638	21753436	3	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn5	11	82212822	82214248	0	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn6	10	12710302	12713987	10	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn7*	10	54689684	54692177	4	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn8	11	27875857	27878106	0	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldn9	10	12714137	12715568	2	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldnd1	11	41883120	41889471	7	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Cldnd2	1	93848533	93851693	6	127,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Ocln	2	31657217	31707466	185	127

Crypt development and maintenance	Cell adhesion	Tjp1	1	118849838	119094492	192	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Alpi	9	87773411	87776877	9	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Hes1	11	70705763	70708176	2	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Klf4	5	70278843	70283751	0	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Nkx6_1	14	7969756	7976689	18	127,383
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Nkx6_2	1	194380149	194383533	5	127,383
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Nkx6_3	16	68868404	68873617	23	127,383
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax1	3	134792330	134801637	41	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax2	1	243616509	243697454	71	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax3	9	79567455	79664042	52	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax4*	4	57058453	57065995	2	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax5	5	58763334	58945719	346	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax6*	3	92128772	92157022	1	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax7	5	151996368	152098023	131	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax8	3	7185721	7242363	70	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Pax9	6	74186749	74203508	34	624
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell differentiation	Shroom3	14	15099415	15396832	1439	21
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell proliferation	Ect2	2	109975813	110037911	47	436
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell proliferation	Egf	2	218219408	218302359	204	625
Crypt development and maintenance	Cell proliferation	Pdgfra	14	33005838	33054347	47	127

Crypt development and maintenance	Cell proliferation	Tgfa	4	118618043	118700897	368	625
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Adamts20	7	125396227	125528020	749	383,534
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Krt20	10	84384790	84394125	25	626
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Krt7	7	132528881	132545052	53	626
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp1	8	4658588	4679099	17	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp10	8	4689840	4697748	19	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp11	20	12730846	12739629	6	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp12	8	4581785	4591687	4	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp13	8	4497960	4508239	32	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp14	15	27887795	27897020	2	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp15	19	9663449	9684943	21	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp16	5	31312280	31556276	700	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp17*	12	27074398	27099317	25	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp19	7	1221229	1229555	7	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp2	19	14154657	14182870	43	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp20	8	4789415	4830035	143	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp21	1	188480186	188485855	7	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp23	5	166239643	166242734	2	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp24	3	144279096	144323572	174	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp25	10	12661297	12676119	29	21,533,627

Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp27	8	4745887	4755806	13	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp28	10	68241138	68264866	6	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp3	8	4640397	4653963	5	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp8	8	4724009	4733864	4	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Mmp9	3	153684158	153692118	15	21,533,627
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Postn	2	138527714	138559098	1	628
Crypt development and maintenance	ECM remodelling	Smoc2	1	55262472	55391804	382	436
Crypt development and maintenance	Epithelial cytoskeleton & junctions	Myh10	10	53393901	53525174	185	436,629
Crypt development and maintenance	Epithelial cytoskeleton & junctions	Myh14	1	95096266	95158861	54	436,629
Crypt development and maintenance	Epithelial cytoskeleton & junctions	Myh9	7	109343718	109424457	68	436,629
Crypt development and maintenance	Hedgehog pathway	Shh	4	6954017	6963170	6	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Hedgehog pathway	Smo	4	58343626	58373823	27	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Hippo pathway	Stk3	7	66053209	66323292	434	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Hippo pathway	Stk4	3	152745958	152827747	141	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Hippo pathway	Wwtr1	2	141651159	141766919	158	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Hippo pathway	Yap1	8	5095705	5166808	105	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Neuronal development	Prdm12	3	14928651	14943341	49	630
Crypt development and maintenance	Neuronal development	Prdm15	11	37164608	37225172	0	630
Crypt development and maintenance	Neuronal development	Prdm16	5	164879864	165203986	0	630
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Atoh1	4	93912068	93914163	4	127

Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Foxp1	4	131559599	132155092	0	631
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Foxp2	4	43133827	43712442	0	631
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Foxp4	9	13058506	13115406	90	631
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Msi1	12	41158301	41251134	172	436,439
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Notch1*	3	9277955	9323531	61	439,631
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Notch2*	2	185610594	185744088	191	439,631
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Notch3	7	11132984	11184025	177	439,631
Crypt development and maintenance	Notch pathway	Notch4	20	4160362	4184466	172	439,631
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Asc12	1	198148999	198151406	4	436
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Axin2	10	93893830	93927042	57	436,629
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Dkk1	1	228381521	228385202	15	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Dkk2	2	220568338	220660225	112	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Dkk3*	1	166237969	166281271	37	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Dkk4	16	69403215	69406580	1	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Dkk11	1	95694010	95699259	0	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Lgr5	7	51087059	51221882	206	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Lrp6	4	167269856	167400364	85	632
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Olfm4	15	55385100	55429687	105	127,436
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Rspo1	5	137251629	137273273	0	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Rspo2	7	74096378	74239398	220	127

Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Rspo3	1	28283914	28368661	0	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Rspo4	3	140357256	140391780	0	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Sfrp1*	16	68575763	68614180	83	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Sfrp2	2	169089517	169097064	25	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Sfrp4	17	45278867	45330806	0	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Sfrp5	1	241006762	241011224	6	127
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt1	7	129938604	129942651	3	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt10a	9	76349931	76362400	20	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt10b	7	129922088	129927892	3	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt11	1	153134503	153154294	36	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt16	4	50820968	50831380	12	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt2	4	46328408	46374673	92	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt2b	2	192454226	192468599	0	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt3	10	88680198	88724170	114	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt3a	10	44034174	44078366	18	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt4	5	149513573	149535415	0	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt5a	16	3697032	3718230	60	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt5b	4	152609566	152733790	187	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt6	9	76329882	76343523	20	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt7a	4	123863108	123908981	105	127,528,529

Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt7b	7	116634817	116679459	57	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt8a	18	26137690	26143283	3	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt8b	1	243354145	243376000	10	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt9a	10	44094140	44121134	17	127,528,529
Crypt development and maintenance	Wnt pathway	Wnt9b	10	88635330	88657035	85	127,528,529
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	B3galt6	5	166584202	166586338	8	535,633
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	B3gat3	1	205817374	205823928	1	535,633
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	B4gal7	17	9018514	9027591	9	535,633
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chpf	9	76963178	76967878	1	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chpf2	4	10578470	10585940	4	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chst11	7	20524535	20743008	689	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chst13	4	122824022	122837940	0	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chst14	3	105916481	105918538	2	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chst3	20	28114386	28152046	70	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chsy1	1	119689626	119750711	214	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Chsy3	18	52644356	52901257	857	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Csgalnact1	16	20995210	21330586	1124	535

ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Csgalnact2	4	151271774	151308856	100	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	CSPG core protein	Cspg4	8	57264962	57300010	78	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	CSPG core protein	Cspg4b	2	44939807	45008284	116	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Dse	20	26118194	26196889	79	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Extl3	15	39294033	39384086	214	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Slc35b2	9	15438594	15442227	2	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Slc35b3	17	25846590	25873115	0	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Slc35d1	5	117928628	117981289	0	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Slc35d2	17	987899	1019747	0	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Xylt1	1	171643925	171929774	632	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG biosynthesis	Xylt2	10	79605910	79619482	13	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	GAG turnover	Arsb	2	25002210	25162675	390	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	Glycoconjugate (non-GAG) biosynthesis	B3gat1	8	25087123	25114692	64	535,633
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	Glycoconjugate (non-GAG) biosynthesis	B3gat2	9	26167174	26250153	0	535,633
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	Glycoconjugate (non-GAG) biosynthesis	Chst8	1	87294144	87435900	405	535
ECM proteoglycan biosynthesis & metabolism	Glycoconjugate (non-GAG) biosynthesis	Chst9	18	6576391	6851078	209	535

Gut motility and secretion	Motility - Smooth muscle contraction	Actg2	4	116021832	116046475	114	436,629
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Chrm1	1	205567226	205583001	18	383,634
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Chrm2	4	65015408	65149104	513	383,634
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Chrm3*	17	60005137	60467250	1492	383,634
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Chrm4	3	77893425	77901166	3	383,634
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Chrm5	3	99284846	99337252	113	383,634
Gut motility and secretion	Motility - Smooth muscle contraction	Des	9	76850979	76858695	3	436,629
Gut motility and secretion	Motility - Smooth muscle contraction	Diaph3	15	62543375	63013060	0	436,629
Gut motility and secretion	Motility - Smooth muscle contraction	Myh11	10	743364	838459	132	436,629
Gut motility and secretion	Motility - Smooth muscle contraction	My19	3	145281943	145288333	4	436,629
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Tacr1	4	114920844	115089733	852	383
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Tacr2	20	30208907	30223446	99	383
Gut motility and secretion	ENS signalling	Tacr3	2	223266536	223363791	294	383
Immunity and inflammation	Chemokine receptor	Ccr3	8	123586100	123634178	103	538
Immunity and inflammation	Chemokine receptor	Ccr4	8	114176291	114182033	2	538
Immunity and inflammation	Chemokine receptor	Ccr5	8	123752423	123757538	3	538
Immunity and inflammation	Chemokine receptor	Ccr6*	1	52474477	52508301	50	538
Immunity and inflammation	Chemokine receptor	Ccr7	10	84098193	84108309	17	538
Immunity and inflammation	Chemokine receptor	Ccr8	8	119826332	119828292	6	538
Immunity and inflammation	Chemokine receptor	Ccr9*	8	123396157	123410199	1	538
Immunity and inflammation	Complement factor	C3	9	2087437	2114366	45	537
Immunity and inflammation	Complement factor	Cd40	3	153790372	153805279	32	537
Immunity and inflammation	Complement factor	Cdc42	5	149555069	149593239	0	537
Immunity and inflammation	Complement factor	Cfd	7	9813148	9814871	3	537
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il11ra1	5	56931824	56941408	17	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il12rb1	16	18620228	18633207	9	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il12rb2	4	96426396	96515251	103	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il17ra	4	153667534	153690174	13	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il17rc	4	146618321	146631444	13	27,32,127,129,365,541,635

Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il17re	4	146604547	146618206	29	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il18r1	9	42727416	42760971	88	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il18rap	9	42768112	42800964	80	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il1m	3	7111567	7127451	19	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il1r1	9	42504917	42580958	152	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il1r2	9	42384280	42424726	114	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il1rap	11	74062999	74199530	296	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il1r1*	9	42661694	42727266	211	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il1r2*	9	42591658	42639351	109	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il20ra	1	14424215	14494226	0	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il20rb	8	100979085	101010829	65	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il21r	1	180168028	180195690	51	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il22ra1	5	147961496	147986296	53	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il22ra2	1	14353736	14377844	0	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il23a	7	721809	723923	4	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il23r*	4	96580568	96672540	202	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il27ra1	19	24109963	24121977	14	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il2ra	17	66849974	66898665	5	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il2rb	7	110033341	110048054	50	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il31ra	2	44118748	44189943	51	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il36m	3	7044419	7051016	3	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il3ra	12	16318081	16323781	0	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il4r	1	180115061	180139981	42	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il5ra	17	66802300	66831973	0	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il6r*	2	175289157	175347719	50	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il7r*	2	58452393	58477757	63	27.32.127.129.365.541.635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine receptor	Il9r	10	15431706	15444144	76	27.32.127.129.365.541.635

Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Foxo3	20	45672995	45764561	48	129,541
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Gata3	17	68643760	68666000	52	129,541
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il12b	10	28888832	28903802	58	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il13	10	37790130	37792687	0	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il15	19	25640025	25706818	123	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il17a	9	23144402	23147889	4	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il18	8	50904630	50932887	36	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il18bp	1	156372923	156374963	2	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il19	13	42397715	42411637	18	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il1a*	3	116526601	116537055	33	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il1b*	3	116577005	116583386	5	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il1f10	3	7072511	7075439	6	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il2	2	120004862	120009566	8	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il20	13	42380981	42384625	3	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il21	2	120117105	120127012	4	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il22*	7	53801206	53805673	0	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il24	13	42353089	42358487	22	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il25	15	28408766	28412157	4	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il27	1	181173108	181178720	16	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il3	10	38405716	38408066	37	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il31	12	33095108	33105026	15	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il33*	1	227701964	227736374	128	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il34	19	38714990	38782749	155	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il4*	10	37771203	37776750	0	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il5	10	37874342	37877213	0	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il6	4	5214602	5219178	1	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il7	2	94235219	94280075	67	27,32,127,129,365,541,635

Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Il9	17	8111772	8114895	3	27,32,127,129,365,541,635
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Myd88	8	119074439	119078508	6	129,541
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Stat1	9	49419561	49459969	49	129,541
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Stat2	7	702565	718349	21	129,541
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnf	20	3622011	3624629	33	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf10	2	110199835	110227239	39	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf11	15	53673850	53705325	102	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf12	10	54403870	54413213	6	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf13	10	54400054	54403723	3	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf13b	16	79462406	79492888	46	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf14	9	2068295	2073128	14	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf15	5	77134885	77156171	44	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf18	13	73833478	73907249	166	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf4	13	73723329	73746809	1	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf8	5	77250942	77277364	73	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Cytokine signalling	Tnfsf9	9	1944017	1946351	0	129,541,636
Immunity and inflammation	Hormonal modulation of regulatory T-cells	Ptges	3	14177892	14189236	18	637
Immunity and inflammation	Hormonal modulation of regulatory T-cells	Ptges2*	3	15690501	15697688	9	637
Immunity and inflammation	Hormonal modulation of regulatory T-cells	Ptges3	7	490698	507759	26	637
Immunity and inflammation	Hormonal modulation of regulatory T-cells	Ptgr1*	5	73784000	73802624	120	637
Immunity and inflammation	Hormonal modulation of regulatory T-cells	Ptgr2	6	103931367	103963113	69	637
Immunity and inflammation	Hormonal modulation of regulatory T-cells	Ptgr3	18	77454435	77463785	7	637
Immunity and inflammation	Immunoglobulin	Aicda	4	155774132	155783972	20	638
Immunity and inflammation	Immunoglobulin	Fcgbp	1	83374979	83413082	32	639
Immunity and inflammation	Immunoglobulin	Jchain	14	19538927	19547023	12	640

Immunity and inflammation	Immunoglobulin	Pigr	13	42298905	42326877	21	639
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Casp1	8	2587812	2597403	26	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Casp12	8	2642296	2669549	60	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Casp14	7	10929759	10932591	1	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Casp16	10	12586009	12592023	12	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Casp2	4	71149632	71167388	18	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp10	1	162922806	162930363	43	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp12	1	65932610	65969873	59	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp14	1	161069141	161089158	5	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp1a	10	55778560	55833639	208	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp1b	10	55838381	55904374	342	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp2	1	69515505	69554689	72	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp3*	10	44326770	44353814	62	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp4	1	68089321	68132429	96	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp4a	1	66171037	66258045	167	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp4a1	7	13464475	13489185	68	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp4b	1	70426021	70457919	39	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp4f	1	66273079	66294331	34	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp5	1	67778037	67810941	49	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp6*	1	196004854	196011615	20	641
Immunity and inflammation	Inflammasome	Nlrp9	1	68291180	68341512	140	641
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-A1	20	4905309	4914593	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-A2	20	4870939	4910183	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-A3	20	4847518	4851344	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Ba	20	4575134	4579727	281	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Bb	20	4596558	4602201	266	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE1	20	3555779	3559487	6	27,129,635,642,643

Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE10	20	3377284	3380301	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE11	20	3355393	3358520	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE12	20	3338907	3342547	3	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE13	20	3314830	3318106	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE14	20	3296654	3300795	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE15	20	3275575	3279074	3	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE16	20	3257109	3260747	1	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE2	20	3538452	3541841	1	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE3	20	3516647	3520938	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE4	20	3431509	3504535	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE5	20	3403418	3479476	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE6	20	3460979	3461929	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-CE7	20	3434205	3437152	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Da	20	4513464	4518457	7	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Db1	20	4548664	4558237	551	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Db2	20	4520723	4539724	191	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Dma	20	4707028	4710432	21	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-DMb	20	4693102	4700340	70	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Doa	20	4753587	4756590	20	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-DOb	20	4619418	4625627	107	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-Ha	20	4760631	4770662	75	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M1-2	20	1909506	1913423	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M1-4	20	1891365	1893585	4	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M1-5	20	1858608	1860708	1	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M2	20	978918	981510	15	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M3-1	20	1323976	1328126	7	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M4	20	1552072	1555823	5	27,129,635,642,643

Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M5	20	1546496	1548948	4	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M6-1	20	1566220	1569151	7	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-M6-2	20	1583267	1587099	7	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-N2	20	2641157	2645439	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-N3	20	2659132	2665536	4	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-O1	20	2655116	2657520	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-O111	20	2624073	2658023	2	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-S2	20	2650233	2651654	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-S3	20	2670654	2675411	10	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-T18	20	2605261	2608909	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-T24-1	20	2761495	2774871	32	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-T24-2	20	2734415	2738899	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-T24-3	20	2718210	2730604	0	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	MHC	RT1-T24-4	20	2684515	2747878	142	27,129,635,642,643
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (cytosolic)	Nod1*	4	84060871	84111668	524	21,32,129,635,644
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (cytosolic)	Nod2*	19	18382369	18422817	37	21,32,129,635,644
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (cytosolic)	Ripk1*	17	30839639	30871824	203	645
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (cytosolic)	Ripk2*	5	29630806	29662804	70	645
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (cytosolic)	Ripk3	15	29283153	29292107	0	645
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (cytosolic)	Ripk4	11	37122555	37144799	0	645
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr1	14	43384127	43396765	14	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr10	14	43400843	43414056	52	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr11	15	23545408	23549849	0	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr12	5	140961166	140964171	1	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr2*	2	169200620	169206819	11	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr3	16	46821980	46837900	103	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr4*	5	80145867	80159501	22	21,27,129,383,644,646

Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr5*	13	94634778	94658992	37	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr6	14	43362164	43374500	15	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pathogen recognition (transmembrane)	Tlr9	8	106864680	106868796	12	21,27,129,383,644,646
Immunity and inflammation	Pro-inflammatory response	Irak1bp1	8	83731512	83748289	56	129,383
Immunity and inflammation	Pro-inflammatory response	Irak2	4	146786004	146842615	143	129,383
Immunity and inflammation	Pro-inflammatory response	Irak3	7	55653949	55714371	2	129,383
Immunity and inflammation	Pro-inflammatory response	Irak4*	7	125682502	125708294	93	129,383
Immunity and inflammation	Pro-inflammatory response	Mapk10*	14	6497662	6790109	1457	129,383
Metabolite Recognition & Processing	SCFA signalling	Ffar1	1	86111368	86112272	0	550
Metabolite Recognition & Processing	SCFA signalling	Ffar2*	1	86072184	86075033	5	550
Metabolite Recognition & Processing	SCFA signalling	Ffar3*	1	86104920	86106849	0	550
Metabolite Recognition & Processing	SCFA signalling	Ffar4	1	235873576	235891597	61	550
Mucosal barrier	Mucin packaging and secretion	Cds1	14	7820328	7882943	122	427
Mucosal barrier	Mucin packaging and secretion	Cds2	3	119514963	119553555	0	427
Mucosal barrier	Mucin packaging and secretion	C1ca1	2	233938677	233964369	126	427
Mucosal barrier	Mucin posttranslational modification	St6galnac1*	10	101972656	101983053	5	427,633,647
Mucosal barrier	Mucin posttranslational modification	St6galnac2*	10	101910220	101928412	13	427,633,647
Mucosal barrier	Mucus stabilization	Tff1*	20	9235736	9239597	26	427,648
Mucosal barrier	Mucus stabilization	Tff2*	20	9215750	9219619	13	427,648
Mucosal barrier	Mucus stabilization	Tff3*	20	9193259	9197969	8	427,648
Mucosal barrier	Mucus stabilization	Zg16	1	181657722	181660079	6	427
Mucosal barrier	Mucus stabilization	Zg16b	10	12970888	12984170	43	427
Mucosal barrier	Polyamine metabolism	Amd1	20	43695783	43711476	40	427
Mucosal barrier	Polyamine metabolism	Azin1	7	69654773	69681578	0	427
Mucosal barrier	Polyamine metabolism	Azin2	5	141281310	141310415	25	427
Mucosal barrier	Polyamine metabolism	Odc1	6	40329831	40336444	5	427
Mucosal barrier	Polyamine metabolism	Paox	1	194919655	194928498	9	427
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut1	1	96086934	96090352	0	427,633
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut10	16	60868761	60958762	160	427,633
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut11	15	3598768	3602328	2	427,633

Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut2*	1	96119549	96139567	0	427,633
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut4	8	11586721	11590682	5	427,633
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut7	3	8237687	8242273	4	427,633
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut8	6	95949246	96176677	740	427,633
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Fut9	5	39351815	39565256	719	427,633
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Muc19	7	123017896	123139053	235	427
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Muc2*	1	196799494	196831740	187	427
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Muc20	11	67987816	68001496	0	427
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Muc5ac	1	196864336	196896475	208	427
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Muc5b	1	196916861	196948830	31	427
Mucosal barrier	Secreted/Gel-forming Mucins	Muc6	1	196726678	196764842	21	427
Mucosal barrier	Transmembrane (Cell Surface) Mucin	Muc1*	2	174635989	174640738	3	427
Mucosal barrier	Transmembrane (Cell Surface) Mucin	Muc13	11	66957208	66980264	203	427
Mucosal barrier	Transmembrane (Cell Surface) Mucin	Muc15	3	97294728	97308641	0	427
Mucosal barrier	Transmembrane (Cell Surface) Mucin	Muc17	12	19527251	19536924	76	427
Mucosal barrier	Transmembrane (Cell Surface) Mucin	Muc3a	12	19450679	19454753	12	427
Mucosal barrier	Transmembrane (Cell Surface) Mucin	Muc4	11	68008245	68053242	85	427
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Antioxidant response	Keap1	8	19768375	19777862	2	649
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Hypoxia regulation	Epas1	6	7790236	7871717	180	524,650
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Hypoxia regulation	Hif1a*	6	92624059	92669262	48	524,651
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Hypoxia regulation	Hif3a	1	77718110	77750448	42	524,650
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Hypoxia regulation	Idh1	9	66534146	66563703	86	513
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Hypoxia regulation	Vhl	4	146772483	146779376	27	651
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdha*	1	28935965	28960936	0	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdhaf1	1	85576207	85577156	1	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdhaf2	1	207139070	207167830	9	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdhaf3	4	35100533	35160740	180	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdhaf4	9	26408332	26416478	0	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdhb	5	153264906	153285570	31	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdhc	13	83544652	83565560	3	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Mitochondrial function	Sdhd	8	50944702	50954298	8	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Oxygen sensing	Egln1	19	52867900	52907308	98	652
Oxygen/ROS regulation	Oxygen sensing	Egln2	1	82451554	82459809	3	513

Oxygen/ROS regulation	Oxygen sensing	Egln3	6	71650297	71675766	48	513
Oxygen/ROS regulation	ROS production	Duox2	3	109223809	109247023	29	653
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng10*	5	73856124	73863017	20	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng11	4	32023003	32028443	21	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng12*	4	96011118	96134767	116	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng13	10	14741179	14743083	5	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng14	19	23089638	23090140	0	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng2	15	4316038	4416918	139	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng3	1	205731837	205733603	3	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng4	17	86448708	86497560	33	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng5	2	235394680	235403177	0	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng7	7	8697458	8761239	95	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gng8	1	77564512	77568371	2	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Gpr84	7	134443904	134446173	0	383,654
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Mchr1	7	112761554	112764746	2	383
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Nmur1	9	87033231	87038070	10	383
Signal transduction	G protein signalling	Nmur2	10	40166223	40182078	20	383
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap1	3	77621377	77643400	22	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap10	19	30448572	30710315	792	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap12	17	51588810	51702417	188	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap15	3	27989368	28592722	1149	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap17	1	177807579	177897027	83	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap18	1	18403531	18637306	320	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap19	1	240571554	240617361	50	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap20	8	52074472	52155739	263	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap21	17	83348673	83472202	106	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap22	16	8473806	8631552	513	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap23	10	82437578	82496846	28	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap24	14	6800624	7183877	1938	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap25	4	119896844	119974982	0	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap26	18	30835806	31237945	457	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap27	10	88280470	88313225	87	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap28	9	107832584	107998030	243	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap29	2	210060036	210132572	71	383,655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap30	13	83822290	83843634	20	383,655

Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap31	11	62038635	62151564	236	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap32	8	30421269	30681653	373	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap33	1	85776112	85789767	7	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap35	1	77202436	77319298	112	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap39	7	108446280	108538875	0	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap40	3	147165781	147206552	229	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap42	8	6154759	6384497	946	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap44	10	49655583	49822876	254	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap45	7	9674873	9690286	23	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap5	6	69975904	70039299	51	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap8	7	115842223	115902094	106	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Arhgap9	7	63148573	63157025	0	383.655
Signal transduction	Rho regulation	Rac1	12	11037028	11057251	28	655

Supplementary Table S12: Identification of every sentinel SNP identified as being associated with host polygenic effects on *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species (chromosome and position, based on the mRatBN7.2 reference genome). The regression coefficients (β_{pgls} values) and the respective p -values and p_{adj} (BH FDR) are also displayed.

Genus	Gene	Chromosome	Position (mRatBN7.2)	β_{pgls}	p -value	p_{adj}
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpi	9	87773898	-0.93858947	7.32116E-05	0.000179368
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Arhgap22	16	8566780	0.35729369	1.4312E-28	4.89271E-28
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Arhgap28	9	107832761	-1.57747985	1.1102E-33	6.52799E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Arhgap5	6	69976513	0.67398666	0.02747439	0.0545775
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Casp1	8	2592079	1.09161645	7.23908E-05	0.000179368
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Casp12	8	2643151	1.09161645	7.23908E-05	0.000179368
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Casp14	7	10932475	-0.1713999	1.0233E-19	3.00849E-19
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Casp16	10	12586328	0.26953344	0.004799397	0.01039584
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Ccr4	8	114180568	1.74562811	3.0253E-36	7.41198E-35
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Ccr7	10	84098868	1.41064522	1.8855E-36	6.544E-35
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Cfd	7	9813583	0.90524611	2.23123E-30	8.86463E-30
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Chpf	9	76964669	-0.44799613	1.9585E-07	5.14107E-07
<i>Bacteroides</i>	ChpI2	4	10581944	1.38462029	1.32876E-33	7.51263E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Chrm1	1	205572021	0.41869187	0.04516057	0.08851471
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Chrm2	4	65033892	0.88581415	4.84341E-29	1.69519E-28

<i>Bacteroides</i>	Chst14	3	105916553	-0.50272333	0.02331467	0.04694871
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Clea1	2	233949179	0.60628912	0.005408914	0.01152334
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Cldn15	12	19698519	2.71179583	1.52936E-36	6.544E-35
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Cldn23	16	56415192	-1.99610167	6.98437E-36	1.14474E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Cldn3	12	21709676	-0.64010436	3.15957E-35	3.31755E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Cldn4	12	21752452	-0.64010436	3.15957E-35	3.31755E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Cldn6	10	12710588	0.02883914	0.001267322	0.002957084
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Des	9	76852597	-0.44799613	1.9585E-07	5.14107E-07
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Dkk3	1	166238314	-2.54535851	8.68179E-36	1.27622E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Ect2	2	109977410	-0.54770588	0.01078491	0.02232931
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Egln3	6	71655363	-0.47864718	0.001632555	0.003692086
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Fut4	8	11587726	1.31084765	2.17148E-34	1.8777E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Gng13	10	14742101	1.1060745	1.02582E-32	5.02651E-32
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Gng7	7	8698207	1.36090106	1.46609E-31	6.33866E-31
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II18	8	50907195	-1.80881378	2.22585E-36	6.544E-35
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II19	13	42397915	-0.66868793	5.12088E-11	1.39402E-10
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II2	2	120006075	0.22605912	1.71351E-12	4.84395E-12
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II20	13	42381359	-0.66868793	5.12088E-11	1.39402E-10
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II20rb	8	100979085	-0.04128283	2.99549E-05	7.7252E-05
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II23a	7	721848	-0.12634367	0.004044097	0.009007308
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II27	1	181173884	-0.47921066	5.70611E-27	1.82347E-26
<i>Bacteroides</i>	II3	10	38407958	1.17830201	6.39454E-33	3.24137E-32
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Irak1bp1	8	83733778	-1.46140574	7.00861E-36	1.14474E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Irak2	4	146817559	1.31768743	9.9548E-35	9.28805E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Kcap1	8	19771593	0.34212108	9.76E-30	3.67877E-29
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Mchr1	7	112763972	-1.77599399	1.01094E-34	9.28805E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Mmp21	1	188484026	-0.28177937	0.00480896	0.01039584
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Mmp27	8	4747888	2.42803423	1.85589E-42	2.72816E-40
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Msi1	12	41158443	-2.17812436	1.62967E-35	2.17783E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Muc17	12	19532922	2.0501951	6.02502E-36	1.14474E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Myh11	10	760772	0.74741935	1.46885E-27	4.79824E-27
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Nkx6_3	16	68869172	-0.4997869	2.48652E-29	8.91508E-29
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Nlrp10	1	162925475	0.42490814	2.14928E-30	8.77621E-30
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Nlrp3	10	44345612	0.65117207	0.01390312	0.02838553
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Nlrp4b	1	70430854	0.44040516	1.53071E-24	4.6878E-24

<i>Bacteroides</i>	Nlrp6	1	196005864	0.81356771	0.001366477	0.003138626
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Notch3	7	11136201	-0.1713999	1.0233E-19	3.00849E-19
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Olfm4	15	55398761	1.41316597	2.10419E-32	9.97791E-32
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Pax2	1	243650818	-0.29358426	9.14852E-15	2.63693E-14
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Pax5	5	58945553	-0.77543662	6.76393E-32	3.01302E-31
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Ptges3	7	491659	1.37563581	3.38057E-33	1.7748E-32
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Retnlb	11	51984087	0.5659906	1.72137E-28	5.75094E-28
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Ripk1	17	30859520	-1.36550111	9.9785E-34	6.11183E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	RT1-Bb	20	4598711	-1.82869197	8.559E-34	5.47032E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	RT1-CE15	20	3276109	-0.68809377	0.001220741	0.002894336
<i>Bacteroides</i>	RT1-M1-4	20	1892446	1.66496341	6.2019E-34	4.144E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	RT1-M1-5	20	1859217	1.66496341	6.2019E-34	4.144E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	RT1-M3-1	20	1326684	-0.68159702	4.16651E-32	1.91399E-31
<i>Bacteroides</i>	RT1-S3	20	2670748	1.66496341	6.2019E-34	4.144E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Sdhc	13	83547561	-0.44829963	8.52414E-27	2.66606E-26
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Smad2	18	69857621	0.84662607	6.32522E-30	2.44686E-29
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Tacr3	2	223310461	1.78892052	2.91926E-35	3.31755E-34
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Tgfb1i1	1	182829382	1.07677545	9.07539E-31	3.81166E-30
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Tgfb1	17	7957732	1.30224446	2.77934E-33	1.5132E-32
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Tlr12	5	140963149	-0.18373024	0.000392642	0.000946204
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Tnfsf10	2	110200786	-0.54770588	0.01078491	0.02232931
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Tnfsf13b	16	79463795	-2.33713991	4.48418E-34	3.49505E-33
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Wnt3a	10	44036852	0.74486208	1.04137E-29	3.82705E-29
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Wnt8a	18	26139205	2.30568884	1.35034E-37	9.92498E-36
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Wnt9a	10	44104924	-1.16613799	4.51741E-34	3.49505E-33
<i>Prevotella</i>	Aicda	4	155774527	-0.50181302	7.21733E-30	3.05258E-29
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap15	3	28058265	-0.17873708	5.25784E-37	2.4664E-36
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap18	1	18628240	0.29441701	5.21415E-19	1.92179E-18
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap21	17	83387641	-0.43272065	0.000876828	0.002075427
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap23	10	82443367	0.07042519	6.43111E-73	5.02796E-72
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap26	18	30881599	0.05905958	4.45617E-10	1.36868E-09
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap27	10	88280558	0.14653798	6.68515E-08	1.93794E-07
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap30	13	83823703	0.49471437	2.6076E-48	1.37298E-47
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap35	1	77204078	0.2096541	1.25171E-09	3.79931E-09
<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap42	8	6180206	0.13364581	1.7795E-76	1.48101E-75

<i>Prevotella</i>	Arhgap5	6	69976513	0.10962462	2.38353E-43	1.16028E-42
<i>Prevotella</i>	Azin2	5	141281556	0.43776013	9.2715E-121	1.7086E-119
<i>Prevotella</i>	B3galt6	5	166584328	-0.04893301	2.55849E-27	1.06466E-26
<i>Prevotella</i>	B4galt7	17	9021064	-0.20539309	1.55334E-06	4.3561E-06
<i>Prevotella</i>	Bmp4	15	19619101	-0.38681464	0.003381528	0.007586385
<i>Prevotella</i>	Bmp5	8	76521513	0.52597589	1.42813E-05	3.91975E-05
<i>Prevotella</i>	Bmpr1b	2	230538816	-0.27978142	0.03533984	0.07236254
<i>Prevotella</i>	C3	9	2093883	0.39629292	1.9076E-14	6.56213E-14
<i>Prevotella</i>	Casp1	8	2589537	0.54121011	8.85809E-35	4.00945E-34
<i>Prevotella</i>	Casp12	8	2642357	0.54121011	8.85809E-35	4.00945E-34
<i>Prevotella</i>	Casp14	7	10932475	-0.26893929	0.04329929	0.08463042
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ccr1	8	123560691	0.10144535	0.00081808	0.001954301
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ccr10	10	86109400	-0.17856004	9.93158E-07	2.81577E-06
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ccr2	8	123735050	0.61932859	2.7428E-138	7.8628E-137
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ccr5	8	123752622	0.61932859	2.7428E-138	7.8628E-137
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ccr7	10	84098278	0.12868496	1.955E-112	2.5219E-111
<i>Prevotella</i>	Chpf2	4	10581944	0.11014377	0.000484466	0.001225413
<i>Prevotella</i>	Chrm5	3	99285082	0.25370757	1.66539E-18	5.96763E-18
<i>Prevotella</i>	Cldn12	4	28523327	0.07269087	0.006195636	0.01354639
<i>Prevotella</i>	Cldn14	11	33305765	0.25757752	1.57437E-08	4.61575E-08
<i>Prevotella</i>	Cldn24	16	44424905	0.3279794	1.02657E-19	3.83849E-19
<i>Prevotella</i>	Cldn6	10	12710711	-0.50282829	1.952E-143	8.3935E-142
<i>Prevotella</i>	Cldn9	10	12714232	-0.50282829	1.952E-143	8.3935E-142
<i>Prevotella</i>	Cldnd2	1	93850386	-0.33978563	4.1317E-171	3.5533E-169
<i>Prevotella</i>	Cspg4	8	57265100	-0.36152969	4.2322E-54	2.42646E-53
<i>Prevotella</i>	Defa3	16	70533999	-0.06197675	2.07565E-80	1.78506E-79
<i>Prevotella</i>	Dkk2	2	220568463	-0.32973342	1.5556E-111	1.9112E-110
<i>Prevotella</i>	Egln2	1	82454402	-0.52233977	4.7299E-140	1.7433E-138
<i>Prevotella</i>	Egln3	6	71655363	0.28209913	3.75022E-47	1.89717E-46
<i>Prevotella</i>	Extl3	15	39294111	0.29840083	8.73165E-47	4.33224E-46
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ffar2	1	86072420	0.31324312	3.63622E-50	1.99605E-49
<i>Prevotella</i>	Fut7	3	8238557	0.40908621	0.001738966	0.004041922
<i>Prevotella</i>	Gata3	17	68644251	-0.06569135	0.000786314	0.001895972
<i>Prevotella</i>	Gngl1	4	32024054	-0.38387544	2.95835E-22	1.15645E-21
<i>Prevotella</i>	Gngl3	10	14742101	-0.42404905	1.7242E-111	2.022E-110

<i>Prevotella</i>	Gng7	7	8744671	-0.17531635	2.34266E-30	1.00734E-29
<i>Prevotella</i>	Gng8	1	77566197	0.2058957	3.08928E-10	9.60282E-10
<i>Prevotella</i>	Grem1	3	100513165	-0.29617143	7.8307E-124	1.6836E-122
<i>Prevotella</i>	Hes1	11	70707527	1.03155555	5.6509E-179	7.2897E-177
<i>Prevotella</i>	II10rb	11	30647292	-0.44151664	1.94038E-68	1.43034E-67
<i>Prevotella</i>	II17a	9	23145375	0.14235272	2.41033E-05	6.47777E-05
<i>Prevotella</i>	II1a	3	116527341	-0.18620909	0.000474035	0.001210901
<i>Prevotella</i>	II1b	3	116577391	-0.18756224	0.000114172	0.000303674
<i>Prevotella</i>	II1f10	3	7072917	0.46298882	0.000338077	0.000872238
<i>Prevotella</i>	II1r11	9	42661747	-0.23435774	1.2261E-133	3.1633E-132
<i>Prevotella</i>	II1r12	9	42630244	0.44422028	1.40107E-97	1.4459E-96
<i>Prevotella</i>	II2	2	120006075	0.26732253	5.9233E-20	2.24737E-19
<i>Prevotella</i>	II21	2	120121183	-0.23708213	2.60448E-18	9.20487E-18
<i>Prevotella</i>	II21r	1	180171089	0.31902098	1.52719E-73	1.2313E-72
<i>Prevotella</i>	II22ra1	5	147976662	-0.06813268	0.000541698	0.001356873
<i>Prevotella</i>	II23r	4	96612551	-0.22359627	2.4918E-119	4.2858E-118
<i>Prevotella</i>	II24	13	42354399	0.09135626	0.02405484	0.05027912
<i>Prevotella</i>	II25	15	28411181	0.02930201	4.8804E-12	1.61429E-11
<i>Prevotella</i>	II2ra	17	66888955	0.24054434	2.16785E-57	1.27115E-56
<i>Prevotella</i>	II2rb	7	110033474	-0.27246632	4.05383E-64	2.75233E-63
<i>Prevotella</i>	II34	19	38716794	0.32200185	9.93231E-49	5.33862E-48
<i>Prevotella</i>	II36rn	3	7045216	0.46298882	0.000338077	0.000872238
<i>Prevotella</i>	II9r	10	15435519	0.16801276	6.38993E-11	2.01049E-10
<i>Prevotella</i>	Krt7	7	132530291	-0.29519407	7.24868E-52	4.06557E-51
<i>Prevotella</i>	Lrp6	4	167360819	0.53879206	2.5603E-126	6.0051E-125
<i>Prevotella</i>	Mmp10	8	4690879	0.26720119	0.04100274	0.08075348
<i>Prevotella</i>	Mmp13	8	4498781	0.26720119	0.04100274	0.08075348
<i>Prevotella</i>	Mmp16	5	31340552	-0.60107662	7.76725E-48	4.0079E-47
<i>Prevotella</i>	Mmp20	8	4791600	0.26720119	0.04100274	0.08075348
<i>Prevotella</i>	Mmp24	3	144306402	-0.19544828	2.80849E-88	2.78689E-87
<i>Prevotella</i>	Mmp27	8	4747888	0.32682032	1.3446E-112	1.8259E-111
<i>Prevotella</i>	Mmp8	8	4728993	0.26720119	0.04100274	0.08075348
<i>Prevotella</i>	Muc17	12	19527287	-0.20832599	0.002296739	0.005197884
<i>Prevotella</i>	Muc4	11	68021955	0.46360691	2.66079E-27	1.08966E-26
<i>Prevotella</i>	Myh14	1	95130750	0.21185191	1.06177E-12	3.55763E-12

<i>Prevotella</i>	Myh9	7	109357517	-0.54868651	2.9614E-118	4.7752E-117
<i>Prevotella</i>	Nkx6_2	1	194381687	0.24466986	1.45019E-18	5.26972E-18
<i>Prevotella</i>	Nkx6_3	16	68873165	0.07289131	0.001111833	0.002607753
<i>Prevotella</i>	Nlrp14	1	161071375	-0.30053745	0.02416516	0.05027912
<i>Prevotella</i>	Nlrp2	1	69516303	-0.19317259	0.02405392	0.05027912
<i>Prevotella</i>	Nlrp9	1	68316967	-0.34043107	1.00072E-11	3.22733E-11
<i>Prevotella</i>	Nod1	4	84063591	0.06605267	2.50223E-67	1.74797E-66
<i>Prevotella</i>	Notch1	3	9308879	0.55101509	1.24725E-05	3.46011E-05
<i>Prevotella</i>	Notch3	7	11136201	-0.27339884	0.04005925	0.08075348
<i>Prevotella</i>	Notch4	20	4174600	-0.32449138	1.59402E-63	9.79183E-63
<i>Prevotella</i>	Odc1	6	40333608	0.01439736	2.10072E-05	5.70512E-05
<i>Prevotella</i>	Pax2	1	243650818	0.01951047	1.49308E-80	1.32833E-79
<i>Prevotella</i>	Pax5	5	58945497	-0.29093243	0.02349351	0.05009359
<i>Prevotella</i>	Pax6	3	92131167	-0.47907504	1.65915E-68	1.259E-67
<i>Prevotella</i>	Pax8	3	7186164	0.45228682	6.17152E-09	1.85146E-08
<i>Prevotella</i>	Pax9	6	74190200	0.37664153	1.3248E-99	1.42417E-98
<i>Prevotella</i>	Postn	2	138558241	-0.25267307	0.000722442	0.001792212
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ptges	3	14178946	0.49105757	0.00013595	0.000357908
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ptgr3	18	77456133	0.26079322	0.04998381	0.09657399
<i>Prevotella</i>	Ripk2	5	29632769	-0.05131442	0.02704342	0.05581762
<i>Prevotella</i>	RT1-Ba	20	4576395	-0.30194618	5.1152E-64	3.29931E-63
<i>Prevotella</i>	RT1-Db2	20	4530443	-0.30194618	5.1152E-64	3.29931E-63
<i>Prevotella</i>	RT1-Dma	20	4710091	0.07296019	0.001967786	0.004492821
<i>Prevotella</i>	RT1-DMb	20	4695551	-0.28062931	2.50678E-67	1.74797E-66
<i>Prevotella</i>	RT1-Ha	20	4760942	0.07296019	0.001967786	0.004492821
<i>Prevotella</i>	RT1-M2	20	980517	-0.18939296	4.45285E-11	1.41832E-10
<i>Prevotella</i>	RT1-T24-4	20	2732997	0.42791256	2.90957E-23	1.17292E-22
<i>Prevotella</i>	Sfrp2	2	169090742	0.29722363	5.198E-113	7.4505E-112
<i>Prevotella</i>	Shroom3	14	15268973	0.09641512	1.04021E-82	9.5848E-82
<i>Prevotella</i>	Slc35b2	9	15441794	0.10247172	1.4466E-143	8.3935E-142
<i>Prevotella</i>	Smad3	8	64143785	-0.47314428	2.1389E-121	4.2449E-120
<i>Prevotella</i>	Smad5	17	7866107	0.30259921	6.36871E-22	2.45243E-21
<i>Prevotella</i>	Smad6	8	64450715	-0.17220157	1.51568E-07	4.34495E-07
<i>Prevotella</i>	Smad7	18	68998814	0.21771791	8.37266E-09	2.48293E-08
<i>Prevotella</i>	Smad9	2	138956395	0.0280576	0.05015858	0.09657399

<i>Prevotella</i>	Stk4	3	152746002	-0.47433677	9.79753E-86	9.36209E-85
<i>Prevotella</i>	Tacr1	4	114920882	0.33271084	5.807E-197	1.4982E-194
<i>Prevotella</i>	Tgfb3l	12	2603979	0.20325386	8.25857E-63	4.95514E-62
<i>Prevotella</i>	Tlr5	13	94635290	-0.3418931	5.52881E-23	2.19451E-22
<i>Prevotella</i>	Tnfsf14	9	2068718	0.35420747	0.006100492	0.01345237
<i>Prevotella</i>	Tnfsf18	13	73835439	0.09748117	0.000755008	0.00183766
<i>Prevotella</i>	Tnfsf4	13	73743992	0.09748117	0.000755008	0.00183766
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wdfy1	9	81035193	-0.22065511	4.44244E-18	1.54885E-17
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wdfy2	15	37148974	-0.58592852	9.91704E-39	4.73814E-38
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wnt1	7	129938960	-0.32722242	0.008113401	0.0175904
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wnt10b	7	129922761	-0.34455042	0.00497211	0.01105866
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wnt11	1	153153922	0.17961385	7.37509E-12	2.40857E-11
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wnt16	4	50822079	-0.1956173	5.76446E-14	1.95688E-13
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wnt5b	4	152733653	-0.54436482	3.18675E-33	1.41755E-32
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wnt7a	4	123867738	0.22646179	1.28311E-63	8.07421E-63
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wnt9b	10	88636118	-0.47818911	1.63676E-32	7.15735E-32
<i>Prevotella</i>	Wwtr1	2	141670457	-0.3428243	0.00940386	0.0202183
<i>Prevotella</i>	Yap1	8	5098926	0.257416	1.9757E-113	2.9984E-112
<i>Prevotella</i>	Zg16	1	181658381	-0.30045229	5.1872E-102	5.8187E-101

Supplementary Table S13: Main values evaluated for mediation analysis of all gene-mediator-outcome trios validated as causal paths. The values represent the final meta values obtained from the five folds used for cross-validation.

Mediator	Outcome	Gene	Indirect effect	<i>q</i> -value (Indirect effect)	Direct effect	<i>q</i> -value (Direct effect)
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	Il21r	-0.016	6.45E-02	-0.075	2.11E-01
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	Mmp23	0.014	2.01E-02	0.018	7.20E-01
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	RT1-M5	0.010	6.69E-02	0.017	7.23E-01
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	Tff3	0.011	9.94E-03	0.040	1.97E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il20	-0.010	1.34E-02	-0.016	7.38E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il23a	0.008	8.90E-02	0.029	5.84E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Msi1	-0.010	1.34E-02	-0.016	7.38E-01

<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	RT1-S3	-0.011	1.97E-02	-0.074	1.17E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Wnt8a	-0.005	8.90E-02	-0.052	1.65E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Retnlb	0.496	8.42E-04	0.206	5.87E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	RT1-S3	-0.484	3.81E-08	-0.253	1.91E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Chst14	-0.011	1.78E-02	-0.030	5.17E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Il20	-0.016	1.72E-04	-0.031	4.09E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Msi1	-0.016	1.72E-04	-0.031	4.09E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Nkx6_3	-0.017	2.93E-02	-0.075	2.18E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Retnlb	0.019	1.05E-02	0.090	1.60E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Guild 3	Il23a	-0.067	1.39E-03	-0.027	3.08E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Guild 3	Nkx6_3	0.101	3.88E-04	-0.007	8.91E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Ccr4	0.018	2.93E-02	0.011	9.47E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Cd40	-0.010	2.93E-02	-0.042	3.05E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Mmp1	0.022	1.76E-02	0.016	8.76E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Mmp12	0.014	3.56E-02	0.068	3.05E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Mmp3	0.015	3.09E-02	0.064	3.22E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Myd88	0.018	8.05E-02	0.011	9.51E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Prdm12	0.010	8.42E-02	0.059	3.84E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Sdhc	-0.011	6.26E-02	-0.044	5.87E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Smad3	0.007	8.23E-02	0.034	5.19E-01
Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Wdfy2	0.009	9.13E-02	0.004	9.61E-01

Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Arhgap44	0.017	1.50E-03	-0.006	9.32E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Casp1	-0.017	2.27E-02	-0.025	7.19E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Cldn14	-0.026	2.57E-02	-0.124	1.12E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Duox2	-0.021	1.81E-02	-0.028	7.36E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Idh1	0.015	8.77E-03	0.016	7.48E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Il11	-0.013	2.27E-02	-0.008	8.89E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Il9	-0.015	3.56E-03	-0.011	8.59E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Krt7	-0.020	4.72E-03	-0.031	6.73E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Myh10	0.019	2.74E-02	0.001	9.98E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Nlrp2	0.020	2.01E-03	0.028	5.83E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Nlrp4	-0.014	2.11E-02	-0.008	9.06E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Nlrp4a	-0.019	2.74E-02	-0.064	2.51E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Pax1	-0.023	3.01E-02	-0.058	5.19E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Stat1	0.015	8.77E-03	0.016	7.48E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Wdfy1	-0.025	4.72E-03	-0.030	7.26E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Wnt1	-0.020	2.06E-03	-0.013	8.78E-01
Guild 3	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Arhgap44	0.404	4.54E-05	0.112	5.01E-01
Guild 3	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Casp1	-0.396	6.54E-03	-0.255	1.94E-01
Guild 3	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Il27	-0.633	1.13E-05	0.027	9.43E-01
Guild 3	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Myh10	0.447	6.29E-03	0.053	8.78E-01
Guild 3	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Pax1	-0.554	6.73E-03	-0.137	7.18E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Aicda	-0.025	1.08E-03	-0.022	7.53E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il1f10	-0.019	2.27E-04	-0.019	7.05E-01

<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il24	-0.018	1.02E-02	-0.043	3.78E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Notch1	-0.025	6.69E-03	0.009	9.74E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Pax8	-0.019	1.60E-02	-0.019	8.49E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Yap1	-0.020	7.84E-03	-0.022	7.72E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Aicda	-0.492	4.33E-05	0.152	4.86E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Ccr7	0.590	1.76E-05	0.092	7.55E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Cldn6	-0.427	2.87E-03	0.227	2.97E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Cldn9	-0.427	2.87E-03	0.227	2.97E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Il24	-0.348	4.00E-03	-0.214	2.37E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Notch1	-0.475	1.85E-03	-0.181	5.00E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Diversity (PCo1)	Yap1	-0.389	3.32E-03	-0.246	2.18E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Aicda	0.102	3.60E-05	0.012	5.47E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Cldn6	0.089	2.71E-03	-0.018	3.89E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Cldn9	0.089	2.71E-03	-0.018	3.89E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Egln2	0.069	1.66E-03	0.007	7.19E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Gng8	0.070	1.66E-03	0.007	7.12E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Il24	0.073	3.82E-03	0.004	8.86E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Nod1	0.096	1.66E-03	-0.005	8.86E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Notch1	0.100	1.66E-03	0.007	8.05E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Notch3	0.068	5.37E-04	0.006	7.19E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Ptges	0.076	1.24E-03	0.005	8.05E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Wnt16	0.099	1.66E-03	-0.004	9.18E-01

Supplementary Table S14: Main values evaluated for the unidirectional Mendelian Randomisation analysis of all gene-mediator-outcome trios validated as causal paths. The values represent the final meta values obtained from the five folds used for cross-validation.

Mediator	Outcome	Gene	alpha	q-value (alpha)	c (total)	q-value (c)	IV theta	q-value (IV theta)
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	Il21r	0.123	1.13E-02	-0.088	1.41E-01	-0.716	9.90E-01
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	Mmp23	-0.105	1.79E-03	0.031	5.32E-01	-0.292	9.90E-01
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	RT1-M5	-0.080	2.58E-02	0.028	5.46E-01	-0.350	9.90E-01
Alpha Diversity	Glucose	Tff3	-0.084	1.28E-03	0.049	1.06E-01	-0.581	9.90E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il20	0.152	1.83E-09	-0.025	5.04E-01	-0.165	8.99E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il23a	-0.115	1.35E-03	0.037	4.79E-01	-0.324	8.99E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Msi1	0.153	1.83E-09	-0.025	5.04E-01	-0.164	8.99E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	RT1-S3	0.174	2.27E-08	-0.085	6.92E-02	-0.491	6.92E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Alpha Diversity	Wnt8a	0.080	5.69E-03	-0.056	1.63E-01	-0.706	7.50E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Retnlb	-0.178	7.63E-04	0.677	3.00E-02	-3.798	2.03E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	RT1-S3	0.174	2.27E-08	-0.763	2.82E-05	-4.390	5.58E-03
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Chst14	0.112	7.45E-04	-0.042	3.24E-01	-0.374	6.84E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Il20	0.152	1.83E-09	-0.046	1.62E-01	-0.305	5.00E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Msi1	0.153	1.83E-09	-0.047	1.62E-01	-0.306	5.00E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Nkx6_3	0.172	3.56E-04	-0.093	1.14E-01	-0.544	4.86E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Glucose	Retnlb	-0.178	7.63E-04	0.108	9.64E-02	-0.604	4.86E-01
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Guild 3	Il23a	-0.115	1.35E-03	-0.096	8.26E-04	0.835	7.37E-02
<i>Bacteroides</i>	Guild 3	Nkx6_3	0.172	3.56E-04	0.095	1.43E-02	0.553	1.55E-01
Beta Div. (PCoI)	Alpha Diversity	Ccr4	-1.278	2.52E-05	0.029	7.79E-01	-0.022	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCoI)	Alpha Diversity	Cd40	0.696	6.24E-05	-0.054	1.69E-01	-0.078	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCoI)	Alpha Diversity	Mmp1	-1.507	8.62E-11	0.036	6.19E-01	-0.024	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCoI)	Alpha Diversity	Mmp12	-0.979	5.90E-04	0.081	2.10E-01	-0.083	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCoI)	Alpha Diversity	Mmp3	-1.093	9.87E-05	0.079	2.26E-01	-0.073	1.00E+00

Beta Div. (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Myd88	-1.278	1.25E-03	0.029	8.31E-01	-0.022	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Prdm12	-0.716	1.31E-02	0.071	2.80E-01	-0.100	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Sdhe	0.800	5.09E-03	-0.055	4.50E-01	-0.068	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Smad3	-0.519	1.06E-02	0.043	3.80E-01	-0.083	1.00E+00
Beta Div. (PCo1)	Alpha Diversity	Wdfy2	-0.635	5.13E-03	0.013	8.61E-01	-0.020	1.00E+00
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Arhgap44	-0.095	3.88E-05	0.012	7.96E-01	-0.128	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Casp1	0.093	6.17E-03	-0.042	4.84E-01	-0.458	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Cldn14	0.146	7.37E-03	-0.152	3.66E-02	-1.043	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Duox2	0.118	1.12E-03	-0.049	4.84E-01	-0.415	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Idh1	-0.082	2.19E-03	0.030	4.84E-01	-0.367	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Il11	0.074	8.54E-03	-0.023	5.96E-01	-0.313	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Il9	0.082	5.04E-04	-0.025	5.81E-01	-0.308	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Krt7	0.113	6.03E-04	-0.053	4.04E-01	-0.468	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Myh10	-0.104	5.75E-03	0.019	7.98E-01	-0.183	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Nlrp2	-0.113	4.69E-05	0.049	2.63E-01	-0.436	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Nlrp4	0.075	7.30E-03	-0.023	6.13E-01	-0.300	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Nlrp4a	0.108	4.94E-03	-0.084	1.10E-01	-0.781	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Pax1	0.130	6.17E-03	-0.085	2.74E-01	-0.658	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Stat1	-0.082	2.19E-03	0.030	4.84E-01	-0.367	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Wdfy1	0.136	5.46E-04	-0.058	4.36E-01	-0.427	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Alpha Diversity	Wnt1	0.108	1.58E-04	-0.033	5.67E-01	-0.307	9.99E-01
Guild 3	Beta Div. (PCo1)	Arhgap44	-0.095	3.88E-05	0.510	1.85E-03	-5.393	1.11E-01

Guild 3	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Casp1	0.093	6.17E-03	-0.632	8.44E-03	-6.818	2.83E-01
Guild 3	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Il27	0.148	7.99E-06	-0.601	2.08E-02	-4.066	2.09E-01
Guild 3	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Myh10	-0.104	5.75E-03	0.504	9.17E-02	-4.829	5.18E-01
Guild 3	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Pax1	0.130	6.17E-03	-0.677	6.26E-02	-5.226	5.00E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Aicda	0.117	3.48E-05	-0.049	3.47E-01	-0.419	9.81E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il1f10	0.089	1.03E-05	-0.039	2.55E-01	-0.440	9.71E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Il24	0.083	3.79E-03	-0.060	1.68E-01	-0.721	9.71E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Notch1	0.114	1.63E-03	-0.016	8.67E-01	-0.140	9.96E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Pax8	0.089	4.54E-03	-0.039	5.33E-01	-0.440	9.96E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Alpha Diversity	Yap1	0.093	3.21E-03	-0.042	4.68E-01	-0.456	9.96E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Aicda	0.117	3.48E-05	-0.325	1.63E-01	-2.777	5.68E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Ccr7	-0.141	1.44E-05	0.704	6.46E-03	-4.986	1.42E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Cldn6	0.102	2.68E-03	-0.208	4.46E-01	-2.044	8.02E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Cldn9	0.102	2.68E-03	-0.208	4.46E-01	-2.044	8.02E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Il24	0.083	3.79E-03	-0.554	1.35E-02	-6.647	2.59E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Notch1	0.114	1.63E-03	-0.641	2.02E-02	-5.628	2.59E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Beta Div. (PCoI)	Yap1	0.093	3.21E-03	-0.632	8.91E-03	-6.795	2.59E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Aicda	0.117	3.48E-05	0.115	7.22E-05	0.978	3.48E-02
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Cldn6	0.102	2.68E-03	0.072	4.64E-02	0.708	2.31E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Cldn9	0.102	2.68E-03	0.072	4.64E-02	0.708	2.31E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Egln2	0.079	1.63E-03	0.075	4.68E-03	0.947	1.08E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Gng8	0.080	1.63E-03	0.076	4.07E-03	0.954	1.07E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Il24	0.083	3.79E-03	0.080	8.00E-03	0.964	1.44E-01

<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Nod1	0.110	1.63E-03	0.091	1.22E-02	0.826	1.33E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Notch1	0.114	1.63E-03	0.105	3.66E-03	0.923	1.07E-01
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Notch3	0.078	5.30E-04	0.075	5.05E-04	0.962	8.57E-02
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Ptges	0.087	1.22E-03	0.079	2.61E-03	0.915	8.57E-02
<i>Prevotella</i>	Guild 3	Wnt16	0.113	1.63E-03	0.095	8.00E-03	0.840	1.13E-01

Supplementary Table S15: Final direct and indirect paths per source/output defined for the structured equation model and their estimated effects in standard deviations.

Output	Source	Path	Type	Effect (SD)
Guild	Prev	Prev -> Guild	Direct	0.89
Beta	Guild	Guild -> Beta	Direct	-0.32
Beta	Prev	Prev -> Beta	Direct	-0.33
Beta	Prev	Prev -> Guild -> Beta	Indirect	-0.28
Alpha	Bact	Bact -> Alpha	Direct	0.26
Alpha	Beta	Beta -> Alpha	Direct	-0.30
Alpha	Guild	Guild -> Beta -> Alpha	Indirect	0.10
Alpha	Prev	Prev -> Alpha	Direct	-0.31
Alpha	Prev	Prev -> Beta -> Alpha	Indirect	0.10
Alpha	Prev	Prev -> Guild -> Beta -> Alpha	Indirect	0.09
Glucose	Alpha	Alpha -> Glucose	Direct	-0.10
Glucose	Bact	Bact -> Glucose	Direct	-0.36
Glucose	Bact	Bact -> Alpha -> Glucose	Indirect	-0.03
Glucose	Beta	Beta -> Alpha -> Glucose	Indirect	0.03
Glucose	Guild	Guild -> Beta -> Alpha -> Glucose	Indirect	-0.01
Glucose	Prev	Prev -> Glucose	Direct	0.36
Glucose	Prev	Prev -> Alpha -> Glucose	Indirect	0.03
Glucose	Prev	Prev -> Beta -> Alpha -> Glucose	Indirect	-0.01
Glucose	Prev	Prev -> Guild -> Beta -> Alpha -> Glucose	Indirect	-0.01

2) Annexe II: Supplementary Codes

Supplementary Code S1: Parameters used by HERMES-WIRE's Step 1 (files params.yaml and tool_opt.tsv).

```
# Parameters for HERMES-WIRE
## STEP 1: Data preprocessing and profiling

### Modules
module_preprocessing: "YES"
module_taxonomic_mapping: "YES"
module_functional_mapping: "YES"

### Tool options
tool_opt: "./tool_opt.tsv"

### Pre-processing
preprocessing_file_raw_reads: "./dataset_raw/*_R{1,2}_001.fastq.gz"
preprocessing_file_adapters: "./input/Adapters_Qiita.fa"
preprocessing_file_host_genome: "./input/indexes/mRatBN7.2.fna"

### Non-host reads (If you don't select Module Pre-processing)
file_non_host_reads: "./dataset_non_host/*_{1,2}.fq.gz"

### Taxonomic
taxonomic_file_microbiome_index: "./input/indexes/gtdb_index.fmi"
taxonomic_file_genome_sizes: "./input/catalogue_stats.csv"
taxonomic_parameter_normalization_by_genome_size: "YES"

### Functional
functional_file_ref_catalogue: ""
functional_file_index: "./input/indexes/prromenade/bactvirus2020*"
functional_file_ec: "./input/indexes/prromenade/taxid_name.txt"

### Output folder
output_folder: "./Output/"
```

```
# Tool options file

trimming trimmomatic "ILLUMINAACLIP:./Adaptors_Qiita.fa:2:30:10:2:keepBothReads LEADING:3 TRAILING:3
SLIDINGWINDOW:4:15 MINLEN:36"
remove_host samtools "-f 12 -F 256"
alignment_microbiome kaiju ""
alignment_microbiome humann3 "--verbose --evalue 0.01 --bypass-prescreen"
report multiqc "-c config.yaml"
```

Supplementary Code S2: Parameters used by the HERMES-WIRE's Step 2 (file params.yaml), considering only the analysis of shallow shotgun-based profiles (no harmonisation with 16S data). The comments after some parameters show the other options used to run the same pipeline for other targets.

```
# Parameters for HERMES-WIRE
## STEP 2: Matrix processing and analyses

### Modules
module_analysis: "Pooled"
module_profile: "Taxonomic" ## Or "Functional"
module_comparisons: "NO"
module_matrix_processing: "YES"
module_cluster: "YES"
module_network: "YES"
module_enterotype: "YES"
```

```

module_alpha_diversity: "YES"
module_beta_diversity: "YES"
module_heritability: "YES"

### Profile: Taxonomic
taxonomic_file_taxonomy: "./input/taxonomy_GTDB207.txt"
taxonomic_file_phylotree: "./input/phylotree_GTDB207.tree"
taxonomic_parameter_ranks: "Phylum,Class,Order,Family,Genus,Species" ### Order from the highest to the lowest

### Profile: Functional
functional_parameter_ranks: "EC1,EC2,EC3,EC4" ### Order from the highest to the lowest
functional_tax_sample_filter: "YES"
functional_tax_defined_samples_and_enterotypes: "./input_func/tax_defined.csv"

### Module: Comparisons - Harmonization for comparisons with another dataset (i.e. 16S data)
harmonization_file_secondary_counts_table: "./input/out_table_16S_taxonomic.biom"
harmonization_file_secondary_taxonomy: "./input/taxonomy_Greengenes2.txt"
harmonization_parameter_secondary_min_initial_depth: 0
harmonization_parameter_secondary_min_final_depth: 6000
harmonization_parameter_methods: "Shallow,16S" ### Keep the target method used for the analyses as the first.
harmonization_parameter_taxa_harmonization: "NO"
harmonization_parameter_hybrid_matrix: "NO"
harmonization_parameter_hybrid_matrix_proportion_of_main: 1

### Module: Matrix processing
processing_file_counts_table: "./input/norm_matrix.txt"
processing_file_remove_ids: "./input/remove_ids_Shallow.txt"
processing_file_metadata: "./input/metadata_Shallow.txt"
processing_file_library: "./input/statistics.txt"
processing_file_covariates: "./input/covariates_Shallow.txt"
processing_file_cov_types: "./input/covariates_classification.txt"
processing_parameter_sample_identifier: "host_subject_id"
processing_parameter_host_identifier: "RFID"
processing_parameter_min_initial_depth: 0
processing_parameter_min_abundance: 0.0001 ## And 0 for ECs
processing_parameter_min_final_depth: 30000 ## And 0 for ECs
processing_parameter_min_prevalence: 0.5
processing_parameter_sample_material: "Caecal" ### Required for host genetic analyses and comparisons between two
methods (i.e. Shallow vs 16S)
processing_parameter_method: "Shallow"

### Modules: Alpha and Beta Diversity
diversity_parameter_type: "TD,PD"
diversity_parameter_alpha_hill_number: "0,1,2"
diversity_parameter_alpha_nboot: 50
diversity_parameter_alpha_conf: 0.95

### Module: Clusters
cluster_parameter_number_of_neighbors: 30
cluster_parameter_minimum_distance: 0.05
cluster_parameter_number_of_components: 20
cluster_parameter_metric_umap: "cosine"
cluster_parameter_metric_hdb: "euclidean"
cluster_parameter_minimum_cluster_size: 15
cluster_parameter_minimum_samples: 10
cluster_parameter_epsilon: 0.01
cluster_parameter_target_DBCV: 0.5
cluster_parameter_target_ARI: 0.6
cluster_parameter_taxa_harmonization: "NO"

### Module: Enterotypes
enterotypes_parameter_rank_name: "Genus"
enterotypes_parameter_kmax: 5
enterotypes_parameter_nstart: 25

### Module: Network
network_parameter_measure: "bicolor"
network_parameter_outliers: "0.05"
network_parameter_threshold: "0.25"
network_parameter_alpha: "0.05"
network_parameter_cluster_method: "cluster_walktrap"
network_parameter_hub_definition: "betweenness,eigenvector"

### Module: Heritability
genetic_file_h5: "./input/P50_Rn7_pruned.h5" ### If you don't select module "Matrix processing"

```

```

genetic_file_gen_info: "/input/P50_rats_Rn7.h5"
genetic_parameter_effects_null: "cageEffect,maternalEffect" ### cageEffect and/or maternalEffect"
genetic_parameter_effects_full: "DGE" ### DGE for "Direct genetic effects"
heritability_file_prev: "/input/filtered_prev.RData" ### If you don't select module "Matrix processing"
heritability_file_catalogue_stats: "/input/catalogue_stats.csv"
heritability_parameter_kinship: "P50_Rn7_pruned"
heritability_parameter_significance_fdr: 0.10
heritability_parameter_significance_bonferroni: 0.05

### Output folder
output_folder: "/Output_Tax"

```

Supplementary Code S3: Parameters used by the HERMES-WIRE's Step 2 with the harmonisation of samples and/or taxa between shallow shotgun and 16S-based profiles (file params.yaml). Here, the shallow shotgun counts table is being adopted as the main one as an example. For the analyses taking the 16S counts table as the primary source, the information would be inverted in the options for Module Comparisons and Module Matrix Processing. The comments after some parameters show the other options used to run the same pipeline for other targets.

```

# Parameters for HERMES-WIRE
## STEP 2: Profile matrix processing and analyses

### Modules
module_analysis: "Pooled"
module_profile: "Taxonomic"
module_comparisons: "YES"
module_matrix_processing: "YES"
module_cluster: "NO"
module_network: "NO"
module_enterotype: "NO"
module_alpha_diversity: "NO"
module_beta_diversity: "NO"
module_heritability: "YES"
module_gwas: "NO"

### Profile: Taxonomic
taxonomic_file_taxonomy: "/input/taxonomy_GTDB207.txt"
taxonomic_file_phylotree: "/input/phyloree_GTDB207.tree"
taxonomic_parameter_ranks: "Phylum,Class,Order,Family,Genus,Species" ### Order from the highest to the lowest

### Profile: Functional
functional_parameter_ranks: "EC1,EC2,EC3,EC4"
functional_tax_sample_filter: "YES"
functional_tax_defined_samples_and_enterotypes: "/input_func/tax_defined.csv"

### Module: Comparisons - Harmonization for comparisons with another dataset (i.e. 16S data)
harmonization_file_secondary_counts_table: "/input/out_table_16S_taxonomic.biom"
harmonization_file_secondary_taxonomy: "/input/taxonomy_Greengenes2.txt"
harmonization_parameter_secondary_min_initial_depth: 0
harmonization_parameter_secondary_min_final_depth: 6000
harmonization_parameter_methods: "Shallow,16S" ### Keep the target method used for the analyses as the first.
harmonization_parameter_taxa_harmonization: "YES"
harmonization_parameter_hybrid_matrix: "NO"
harmonization_parameter_hybrid_matrix_proportion_of_main: 1

### Module: Matrix processing
processing_file_counts_table: "/input/norm_matrix.txt"
processing_file_remove_ids: "/input/remove_ids_Shallow.txt"
processing_file_metadata: "/input/metadata_Shallow.txt"
processing_file_library: "/input/statistics.txt"
processing_file_covariates: "/input/covariates_Shallow.txt"
processing_file_cov_types: "/input/covariates_classification.txt"
processing_parameter_sample_identifier: "RFID"
processing_parameter_host_identifier: "RFID"
processing_parameter_min_initial_depth: 0
processing_parameter_min_abundance: 0.0001

```

```

processing_parameter_min_final_depth: 30000
processing_parameter_min_prevalence: 0.5
processing_parameter_sample_material: "Cecal" ### Required for host genetic analyses and comparisons between two
methods (i.e. Shallow vs 16S)
processing_parameter_method: "Shallow"

### Modules: Alpha and Beta Diversity
diversity_parameter_type: "TD,PD"
diversity_parameter_alpha_hill_number: "0,1,2"
diversity_parameter_alpha_nboot: 50
diversity_parameter_alpha_conf: 0.95

### Module: Clusters
cluster_parameter_number_of_neighbors: 30
cluster_parameter_minimum_distance: 0.05
cluster_parameter_number_of_components: 20
cluster_parameter_metric_umap: "cosine"
cluster_parameter_metric_hdb: "euclidean"
cluster_parameter_minimum_cluster_size: 15
cluster_parameter_minimum_samples: 10
cluster_parameter_epsilon: 0.01
cluster_parameter_target_DBCV: 0.5
cluster_parameter_target_ARI: 0.6
cluster_parameter_taxa_harmonization: "NO"

### Module: Enterotypes
enterotypes_parameter_rank_name: "Genus"
enterotypes_parameter_kmax: 5
enterotypes_parameter_nstart: 25

### Module: Network
network_parameter_measure: "bicolor"
network_parameter_outliers: "0.05"
network_parameter_threshold: "0.25"
network_parameter_alpha: "0.05"
network_parameter_cluster_method: "cluster_walktrap"
network_parameter_hub_definition: "betweenness,eigenvector"

### Modules: Overall Host Genetic Effects Analyses
genetic_file_h5: "./Output_Shallow/Matrix_Processing/P50_Rn7_pruned.h5"
genetic_file_gen_info: "./input/P50_rats_Rn7.h5"
genetic_parameter_effects_null: "cageEffect,maternalEffect" ### cageEffect and/or maternalEffect"
genetic_parameter_effects_full: "DGE" ### DGE for "Direct genetic effects and IGE for indirect genetic effects"

### Module: Heritability
heritability_file_prev: "./Output_Shallow/Matrix_Processing/filtered_prev.RData"
heritability_file_catalogue_stats: "./input/catalogue_stats.csv"
heritability_parameter_kinship: "P50_Rn7_pruned"
heritability_parameter_significance_fdr: 0.10
heritability_parameter_significance_bonferroni: 0.05

### Module: GWAS
gwas_file_residuals: "./Output_Shallow/Matrix_Processing/filtered_clr_counts.RData"
gwas_parameter_dosage_field: "direct_unpruned_Rn7"
gwas_parameter_kinship_loco: "P50_Rn7_pruned"
gwas_parameter_significance_logp: 5.8
gwas_parameter_min_logp: 4

### Output folder
output_folder: "./Output_Shallow_Full_Harm/"

```

Supplementary Code S4: Parameters used for the analyses involving a hypothesis-driven selection of host candidate genes for the selection of sentinel SNPs (one per gene/trait), a PGLS association between the effect sizes of genus-based sentinel SNPs, additive effects and h^2 values per species, mediation analysis, univariate and multivariate MR (file `params.yaml`). The comments after some parameters show the other options used to run the same pipeline for other targets. Most input files

come from HERMES-WIRE's Step 2.

```
# ===== Input files =====
h5_path: "./hermes-wire/step2/input/P50_rats_Rn7_cp.h5"
genes_xlsx: "./input/putative_genes_final.xlsx"
metadata_tsv: "./hermes-wire/step2/input/metadata_Shallow.txt"

# genetics / random effects
grm_rdata: "./hermes-wire/step2/input/grm.RData"
resid_rda: "./hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Matrix_Processing/residuals_qned_counts.RData"
beta_rda: "./hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Diversity/residuals_qned_counts_beta.RData"
alpha_rda: "./users/abaud/fmorillo/NextFlow/hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Diversity/residuals_qned_counts_alpha.RData"
clusters_rda: "./hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Cluster_Analyses/residuals_qned_counts_clusters.RData"
med_glucose_rdata: "./input/pchotypes_residuals.RData"
herit_rdata: "./hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Heritability/heritability.RData"

# taxonomy / phylogeny (used in Phase 7 PGLS)
taxonomic_file_taxonomy: "./hermes-wire/step2/input/taxonomy_GTDB207.txt"
taxonomic_file_phylotree: "./hermes-wire/step2/input/phylotree_GTDB207.tree"
taxonomic_parameter_ranks: "Phylum,Class,Order,Family,Genus,Species"

# ===== Outputs =====
outdir: "./results"

# ===== Executables =====
gcta_exec: "gcta64"
plink_exec: "plink"

# ===== Trait selection =====
trait: "Taxa" # Taxa, Guild, Beta, Alpha
genera: ["Bacteroides"] # "Prevotella", "PD_q2" (for Alpha), "PD_PC1" (for Beta) or "3" (for Guild)
genus_trait_prefix: "g_" # "cluster_" (for Guild), "alpha_" (for Alpha), "beta_" (for Beta)
species_trait_prefix: "s_" # "cluster_" (for Guild), "alpha_" (for Alpha), "beta_" (for Beta)

# ===== Variant QC thresholds (assoc/set tests) =====
maf_min: 0.02
miss_max: 0.10
mac_min: 5
hwe_p_min: 1.0e-6
hwe_maf_min: 0.05

# ===== Reproducibility =====
seed: 17

# ===== Gene windows (bp) for candidate mapping =====
candidate_window_up: 0
candidate_window_down: 0

# ===== Set tests (GENESIS::assocTestAggregate) =====
set_test: "SKATO"
var_block: 500

# ===== ACAT combine species -> genus =====
acat_weight: "h2"
acat_p_floor: 1.0e-15
q_gene: 0.10

# ===== Crossfit sentinel picking =====
kfolds: 5
crossfit_seed: 17

# ===== Sentinels for correlations =====
sentinel_ld_r2: 0.10
sentinel_ld_kb: 250
sentinel_p1: 1.0
sentinel_p2: 1.0
min_species: 6

# ===== Mediation analysis =====
mediation_enable: true
med_bh_q: 0.10
med_gate_from_pgl_s_q: 0.10
med_method: "genesis"
```

```

med_boot: false
med_boot_sims: 0

med_glucose_column: "Glucose"
med_bmi_column: "BMI"
med_beta_trait_name: "beta_PD_PC1"
med_alpha_trait_name: "alpha_PD_q2"
med_guild_trait_name: "cluster_3"
outcomes: "guild,alpha,beta,bmi,glucose"

# ===== MR toggles (used by simple IVW step) =====
mr_enable: true
mr_fdr_level: 0.10
mr_mode: "crossfit"
mr_ld_prune: true
mr_ld_kb: 250
mr_ld_r2: 0.10
mr_fstat_min: 10.0
mr_do_steiger: true
mr_bh_q: 0.10

# ===== Genetic correlation / BLUP =====
rg_enable: true
rg_partition: true
he_enable: true
cvblup_enable: false
blup_enable: true
cvblup_align_enable: true
geta_threads: 4

rg_traits: ["beta_PD_PC1","alpha_PD_q2","cluster_3","Glucose","BMI"]
rg_pairs:
"genus~beta_PD_PC1,genus~alpha_PD_q2,genus~cluster_3,genus~other_genus,genus~Glucose,genus~BMI"

# ===== Containers =====
container_bioconductor: "docker://morillofe/microbiome_genome_bioconductor:step4_v4"
container_plink: "docker://quay.io/biocontainers/plink:1.90b6.21--h779adbc_1"
container_geta: "docker://morillofe/microbiome_genome_geta:step4_v1"
container_python: "docker://morillofe/python-ps:3.11-slim"
container_genesis: "docker://morillofe/genesis-nf:bioc3.18-ext.v2"

```

Supplementary Code S5: Parameters used by the R workflow (script sem_feedforward.R) to refine and validate the structured equation model.

```

COHORT="/input/genesis_final_label_ids.txt"
MED_BAC="/input/results_bac/phase9_mediation/mediation_sig_iv.tsv"
MED_PREV="/input/results_prev/phase9_mediation/mediation_sig_iv.tsv"
PUTATIVE="/input/putative_genes_final.xlsx"
GDS="/input/genotypes_candidates.gds"

RESID_RDA="/hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Matrix_Processing/residuals_qned_counts.RData"
BETA_RDA="/hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Diversity/residuals_qned_counts_beta.RData"
ALPHA_RDA="/hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Diversity/residuals_qned_counts_alpha.RData"
CLUSTERS_RDA="/hermes-wire/step2/Output_Tax_Mat_Net/Cluster_Analyses/residuals_qned_counts_clusters.RData"
PHEN_RDA="/input/phenotypes_residuals.RData"
GRM_RDA="/hermes-wire/step2/input/grm.RData"
META="/hermes-wire/step2/input/metadata_Shallow.txt"

OUTDIR="/results"

# ---- optional custom model control ----
# Provide EITHER MODEL_FILE or MODEL_TEXT (leave both empty to use the feed-forward builder)
MODEL_FILE="/input/my_model.lav"
MODEL_TEXT=""
# Only knob for inclusion/exclusion:
# Empty -> use all variables available in data
# Non-empty -> intersect with available ones
COMPONENTS="Bact, Prev, Guild, Beta, Alpha, Glucose" # e.g. "Bact, Prev, Guild, Beta, Alpha, Glucose, BMI"

# ---- run ----
run -u stdbuf -oL -eL Rscript --vanilla sem_feedforward.R \
--cohort "${COHORT}" \

```

```

--med_bac_tsv "${MED_BAC}" \
--med_prev_tsv "${MED_PREV}" \
--putative_genes_xlsx "${PUTATIVE}" \
--selected_genes_rdata "${GDS}" \
--resid_rda "${RESID_RDA}" \
--beta_rda "${BETA_RDA}" \
--alpha_rda "${ALPHA_RDA}" \
--clusters_rda "${CLUSTERS_RDA}" \
--phen_rda "${PHEN_RDA}" \
--grm_rda "${GRM_RDA}" \
--metadata "${META}" \
--meta_rfid_col RFID \
--meta_dam_col dam \
--meta_cage_col cage \
--bac_name_g Bacteroides \
--prev_name_g Prevotella \
--guild_name cluster_3 \
--beta_trait beta_PD_PC1 \
--alpha_trait alpha_PD_q2 \
--glucose_col Glucose \
--bmi_col BMI \
--drop_genes FALSE \
--iv_gold_tier FALSE \
--missing_mode fiml \
--drop_corr_threshold 0.99 \
--qr_drop TRUE \
--jitter_sd 0.0 \
--print_mmer_summary TRUE \
--fdr_level 0.10 \
--mi_threshold 10.0 \
--max_iter 10 \
--model_file "${MODEL_FILE}" \
--model_text "${MODEL_TEXT}" \
--components "${COMPONENTS}" \
--outdir "${OUTDIR}"

```


3) Annexe III: Supplementary Figures

Supplementary Figure S1: Distribution of the species mapped with Kaiju/GTDB and Woltka/WoL according to the type of the corresponding isolation source (only when identifiable). All comparisons involve the same 858 samples after filtering out species with low relative abundances (<0.01%).

Supplementary Figure S2: Stacked bar plots containing the relative abundances of bacterial phyla (left) and EC1 protein domains (right) per fixed effect, after all feature and sample filtering steps. **A)** Stacked bar plots per sex (F=Female, M=Male). **B)** Stacked bar plots per sequencing batch. **C)** Stacked bar plots per cohort (or study), including the MI and NY cohorts.

Supplementary Figure S3: Stacked bar plots containing the relative abundances of bacterial species guilds. **A)** Stacked bar plot per sex (F=Female, M=Male). **B)** Stacked bar plot per sequencing batch. **C)** Stacked bar plot per cohort (or study), including the MI and NY cohorts.

A)

B)

Supplementary Figure S4: Comparisons between the species-based enterotypes. **A)** Mean relative abundance (%) of all guilds per enterotype. **B)** Mean relative abundance (%) of the top 20 most abundant EC4 functions per enterotype.

Supplementary Figure S5: PCoA plots for EC4-based between-sample multivariate distances (β -diversity) before and after the removal of fixed effects from the data (left and right charts, respectively). Each pair of plots identifies the samples according to different characteristics: **A)** PCoA plots with samples separated by animal sex (F = Female and M = Male), with females represented by dark green points and males by light green points. **B)** PCoA plots with samples separated by sequencing batch with multiple

colours. **C)** PCoA plots with samples separated by the cohort the sample came from (MI or NY). **D)** PCoA plots with samples separated by the enterotypes detected in the current study (Enterotype 1 as dark red points and Enterotype 2 as orange points). Note that before fitting the known biological and experimental covariates, identifying the samples according to cohort would result in a clear separation based on the first PCo axis. PERMANOVA p -values are highlighted in small boxes within the plots (Approximate discrete Monte-Carlo p -values for 999 permutations: top-right side of each plot).

Supplementary Figure S6: Comparison of the first principal coordinate of β -diversity values (PCo1) between samples belonging to Enterotype 1 and Enterotype 2. The p -value was calculated using a Wilcoxon rank-sum test.

Cluster: 2

Cluster: 3

Cluster: 4

Cluster: 5

Cluster: 6

Cluster: 7

Cluster: 8

Cluster: 9

Cluster: 10

Cluster: 11

Supplementary Figure S7: Graphical representation of the sub-networks of species co-abundance guilds (here referred as “cluster”) across all 858 samples. Every circle characterises a node (species) and the lines connecting them symbolise their edges. Green edges denote positive correlations, while red edges represent negative correlations. Furthermore, edge lengths vary according to the edge weight, approximating nodes when the weight is greater. Edges were only included when correlations were higher than 10%. Node sizes are defined by their eigenvector centrality values, and the nodes of each guild received the same colours, allowing the identification of the guilds in the full network plot (Figure 15A). The colour system adopted is detailed on Annexe I, Supplementary Table S5.

Supplementary Figure S8: Graphical representation of the sub-networks of EC4 modules across all 858 samples. Every circle characterises a node (EC4 functions) and the lines connecting them symbolise their edges. Green edges denote positive correlations, while red edges represent negative correlations. Furthermore, edge lengths vary according to the edge weight, approximating nodes when the weight is greater. Edges were only included when correlations were higher than 10%. Node sizes are defined by their eigenvector centrality values, and the nodes of each module received the same colours, allowing the identification of the modules in the full network plot (Figure 15B).

A)

B)

Supplementary Figure S9: Graphical representation of the species **(A)** and the EC4 **(B)** networks per enterotype (Ent1 on the left side and Ent2 on the right side). Every circle characterises a node (species or EC4 function) and the lines connecting them symbolise their edges. Green edges denote positive correlations, while red edges represent negative correlations. Furthermore, edge lengths vary according to the edge weight, approximating nodes when the weight is greater. Edges were only included when correlations were higher than 10%. Node sizes are defined by their eigenvector centrality values, and while the node colours in the taxonomic network correspond to the co-abundance guild to which the node belongs (according to the UMAP-HDBSCAN analysis), the node colours in the functional network represent the network modules assigned to them by NetCoMi. The plots for the sub-networks corresponding to each species guild and EC4 modules are presented in Annexe III, Supplementary Figures S7 and S8, which use the same colours as in **(A)** and **(B)**, respectively.

Method: 16S

Supplementary Figure S10: Rarefaction curve of the asymptotic number of species per sample depth (total number of reads) after the removal of low-abundance ASVs. The vertical red line indicates the threshold chosen to filter out too shallow samples.

A)

B)

C)

Supplementary Figure S11: Comparisons between 16S- and shallow shotgun-based taxonomic profiles. **A)** Venn diagrams of family, order, class and phylum mapped by shallow shotgun and 16S sequencing. **B)** Density of samples according to their proportion of zeroes (sparsity), comparing values obtained by 16S and shallow shotgun-based of family, order, class and phylum profiles. The boxplots on the top right illustrate the significant differences in the proportion of zeroes between the two methods (Wilcoxon rank-sum test). **C)** Spearman correlation between the \log_{10} (geometric mean counts) of shared families, orders, classes and phyla between both methods (purple dots with a diagonal purple line). Taxa mapped only by shallow shotgun data are represented by green vertical dots, and the ones mapped only by 16S data are represented by red horizontal dots.

Supplementary Figure S12: Pairwise comparison of h^2 values between common taxa mapped by both sequencing methods (considering all ranks, from species to phylum). The p -value on the top of the boxes was defined with the Wilcoxon rank-sum test and shows significantly higher h^2 values for the shallow shotgun-based profile. Light blue lines represent h^2 values

that were higher in the shallow shotgun profile, while light red lines represent h^2 values that were higher in the 16S profile.

Supplementary Figure S13: Density of samples according to their proportion of zeroes (sparsity), comparing values obtained by shallow shotgun-based species (or OGU) and EC4 profiles. The boxplots on the top right illustrate the significant differences in the proportion of zeroes between the two methods (Wilcoxon rank-sum test).

Supplementary Figure S14: Comparisons of random effects on pseudo-relative abundances of *Bacteroides* and *Prevotella* species. All p -values were defined with the Wilcoxon rank-sum test. **A)** Heritability values (or host additive effects). **B)** Maternal effects. **C)** Cohousing effects.